

An Empirical Analysis of Monetary Policy Communication in Nigeria

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Statement of Originality

I hereby declare that this thesis is my own work and to the best of my knowledge contains no material(s) previously published or written by another person, or substantial proportions of materials which have been accepted for the award of any other degree or diploma at UWS or any other educational institution.

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Abstract

The thesis examines the monetary policy communication of the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) between 2001 and 2018 by: (a) probing the clarity of the Monetary Policy Communiqués; (b) measuring communication and ascertaining the transmission effects; (c) scrutinizing the intensity of fiscal policy communication; and (d) gauging the public's knowledge of monetary policy.

The Flesch Kincaid and Gunning Fog readability tools were used to measure clarity, while the multiple regression, Impulse Response Function and Variance Decomposition techniques were applied to test how clarity responded to changes in macro variables in the period. The main findings are: (a) The number of paragraphs, sentences, and words of the communiqués increased in the period, suggesting improved transparency by the CBN; (b) The high Flesch Kincaid and Gunning Fog scores signifies that the communiqués were complex, buttressing the findings of Tumala and Omotosho (2019) that CBN's statements have become more difficult.

To measure CBN's communication and the transmission effects, two indicators were developed - the *Monetary Policy Stance* (MPS) that codes the tightening (+1), hold (0) and loosening (-1) postures as widely applied in the literature; and the *Monetary Policy Communication on Inflation* (MPCI) that reflects statements on inflation in line with the ECB KOF approach. The empirical scrutiny followed Neuenkirch (2013) that included the KOF Communicator in a transmission mechanism study for the ECB. Also, CBN's study on monetary policy transmission in 2010 provided guide in terms of the estimated equations, which were modified with the MPS and MPCI.

The findings from the graphic analysis of the MPS showed that the CBN tightened its stance in 26 or 37% of the communiqués while it was 11 or 16% for easing and 33 or 47% for the neutral posture. The average MPCI of 0.135 indicates that the CBN communicated more about upside risk to inflation, while the relationship between voting to raise policy rate and the MPCI is positive but weak, suggesting that the CBN also used other tools to manage inflation in the period.

A juxtaposition of the movement between MPCI and policy rate showed a paradox as the upside risk sentiments to inflation coincided with falling or flattening policy rate in most parts of the period reviewed. The likely reasons are: (a) Given the multiple objectives and policy instruments, the CBN sometimes alter other tools instead of raising the policy rate; (b) CBN probably saw inflationary threats as temporary in those periods and decided to be neutral on policy; (c) The

policy rate is the most visible tool to politicians who see raising rates as undermining their preference for growth, making the CBN to sometimes adjust other tools instead of the policy rate. By means of the ARDL/Bounds testing for cointegration and the Error Correction Model, the key results from the empirical scrutiny of the effect of communication on the transmission process are: (a) The Error Correction Terms (ECTs) are negative and significant in all the models, implying long-run causality; (b) The ECTs are below 20% in all the models, indicating slow speed of adjustment in models with or without communication. This suggests that communication did not improve transmission of monetary policy between 2001 and 2018. Given that communication is aimed at managing expectations, the inference is that the result underpins that of CBN's 2010 analysis which found weak existence of policy transmission through the expectations channel; (c) The models with MPCPI that focus on inflation performed relatively better than the ones with MPS that reflects the multiple objectives and tools; (e) The short-run causality results reinforce the importance that the CBN attaches to monetary targeting as money supply granger-causes GDP and inflation. Also, the CBN's tightening, neutral and easing postures as captured by the MPS is important for short-run macroeconomic management given that the MPS granger-causes GDP.

To analyze the intensity of CBN's communication about fiscal policy, a template was designed and used to develop a *Fiscal Policy Communication Indicator* (FPCI) after the method of Allard *et al.* (2013). The multiple regression was used to estimate how macro-fiscal variables affected communication about fiscal policy, while controlling for other effects, also in line with Allard *et al.* (2013). The estimations were however complemented with the Impulse Response and Variance Decomposition methods that are widely utilized in the central bank communication literature.

The results are as follows: (a) A total of 409 statements and 20,193 words or 11.8% of total word count of all the communiqués were used to discuss fiscal policy; (b) CBN communicated more positively about fiscal policy when the oil-price based fiscal rule was introduced. The formation of the Sovereign Wealth Fund resulted in more normative statements as the posture changed from commendation to advisory; (c) Fiscal deficit and inflation have significant effects on the FPCI while effect of public debt and money supply are insignificant; (d) The variance decomposition results showed that 77% of the Forecast Error Variance in the FPCI is due to own effect, meaning that the explanatory variables did not significantly influence the variance in the FPCI; (e) FPCI is

granger-caused by fiscal deficit, public debt and money supply, while it is not granger-caused by inflation. The combined effect of all the indicators showed that they all granger caused FPCI.

To examine the public's knowledge of monetary policy, the questionnaire by Cruijsen *et al.* (2015) was modified and used for data gathering while the logistic regression method was used for the analysis. The results are: (a) Knowledge of monetary policy is not affected by gender; (b) Age is vital as older respondents are more conversant about monetary policy; (c) Educational qualification does not increase the chance of being well-informed about monetary policy; (d) Real sector respondents tend to be more familiar compared with those in other sectors; (e) Respondents with desire to be well-informed are more knowledgeable about monetary policy; (f) Work experience increases the likelihood of being familiar about monetary policy; (g) Higher income earners are well-informed about monetary policy; (h) Users of Newspapers, CBN's website, Radio and Television tend to be more aware about monetary policy; (i) Using current information, past information or both, does not impact the likelihood of being conversant about monetary policy.

Overall, the study concludes that:

- a) CBN's communication of monetary policy through the policy communiqué is complex.
- b) The transmission mechanism of monetary policy was not enhanced by communication in the review period.
- c) The discussions about fiscal policy have expectedly increased over the years, with the CBN's positive communication increasing in periods of strategic fiscal policy initiatives.
- d) The public's knowledge of monetary policy is enhanced by age, income and the media reporting through Newspapers, Television and Radio.

The study recommends as follows:

- a) To improve clarity, CBN should devise means of explicitly conveying its multiple objectives and tools and also simplify its vocabularies and choice of words.
- b) The transmission process can also be enhanced if clarity improves with simplification of vocabularies and choice of words. This will reduce the mixed signals to the public.
- c) Commending government when certain actions are taken and advising them to take firm measures in some instances will improve monetary-fiscal bond.
- d) The press briefing channel of communication should be strengthened because it is effective in helping the media to convey the policy messages clearly to the public.

Dedication

To the Glory of God

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List of Abbreviations

ADF	Augmented Dickey-Fuller
AIC	Akaike Information Criterion
ARDL	Autoregressive Distributed Lag
ARCH	Autoregressive Conditional Heteroscedasticity
ASI	All Share Index
BDC	Bureau D' Change
BOE	Bank of England
BOJ	Bank of Japan
CBN	Central Bank of Nigeria
CBRT	Central Bank of the Republic of Turkey
CRR	Cash Reserve Ratio
CUSUM	Cumulative Sum
CSUMQ	Cumulative Sum of Squares
DMO	Debt Management Office
DSGE	Dynamic Stochastic General
ECA	Excess Crude Account
ECB	European Central Bank
ECM	Error Correction Model
ECT	Error Correction Term
EGARCH	Exponential Generalized Autoregressive Conditional Heteroskedastic
FAVAR	factor augmented vector autoregression
FED	United States Federal Reserve Bank
FEV	Forecast Error Variance
FLAC	Fiscal Liquidity Assessment Committee
FMF	Federal Ministry of Finance
FOMC	Federal Open Market Committee
FPCI	Fiscal Policy Communication Indicator
FRA	Fiscal Responsibility Act
FX	Foreign Exchange

GARCH	Generalized Autoregressive Conditional Heteroskedasticity
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
IBR	Interbank Interest Rate
IMF	International Monetary Fund
IRF	Impulse Response Function
LAG	Liquidity Assessment Group
LDA	Latent Dirichlet Allocation
MPC	Monetary Policy Committee
MPCI	Monetary Policy Communication on Inflation
MPIC	Monetary Policy Implementation Committee
MPR	Monetary Policy Rate
MRR	Minimum Rediscount Rate
MPS	Monetary Policy Stance
MPTC	Monetary Policy Technical Committee
NSIA	Nigeria Sovereign Investment Authority
OLS	Ordinary Least Squares
OMO	Open Market Operation
PBC	Peoples' Bank of China
RIBR	Real Interbank Interest Rate
SVM	Support Vector Machines
SWF	Sovereign Wealth Fund
VAR	Vector Autocorrelation
VECM	Vector Error Correction Model
VD	Variance Decomposition

CHAPTER ONE: Introduction

'Central Bank Communication is a significant and influential central bank's tool'
- *Blinder et. al. (2008, pp. 911)*

1.1 Background

Communication is a crucial element of every human endeavor, including the interaction among economic agents and government institutions like central banks. Globally, central banks are one of the most important and strategic organizations in any country's economic architecture. Their mandates are mainly to guarantee price stability and, in some instances, support the policies of their governments. Hence, the way and manner that central banks communicate their monetary policy activities is very essential.

Before the late 2000s, central banks were largely secretive, and the obscure posture was hinged on the belief that they should say as little as possible and be very brief even in the tiny information that they provide (Blinder *et. al.*, 2008). This vagueness has however given way for improved interaction with the public as most central banks are now transparent and are providing more verbal information and written documents. Tobias *et. al.* (2018) posited that central banks are no longer cryptic as they often communicate their macroeconomic conditions, policy frameworks, objectives, forecasts on inflation and output and motivations for policy decisions. This paradigm shift is traced largely to the following factors:

- a) *Problem of Information Asymmetry*: Su, *et. al.* (2020) suggested that communication by central banks reduce asymmetric information by signaling the banks' policy preferences and economic outlook. This is because information asymmetry impairs economic progress as the inability of economic agents to have access to information weakens their decision-making and results in sub-optimal choices. Communication hence reduces the problem of information asymmetry between the central bank and the public, thereby enhancing the management of expectations.
- b) *Independence of Central Banks*: If an independent central bank communicates its economic outlook and policy stances more transparently, the stakeholders are less likely surprised by the monetary policy decisions which causes smooth movements in asset prices and reduces the likelihood of financial distress (Pescatori, 2018). The independence of a central bank thus enhances the monetary process as indicated in the International Monetary Fund (IMF) 2019 staff proposal shown in figure 1.1. The suggested framework is that policy requires autonomy

which also requires transparency and so strengthens accountability. This proposal differs from the 1999 framework which, as shown in figure 1.2 emphasizes that autonomy, transparency, and accountability improve the credibility, reputation, and prestige of central banks. In addition, Heenan *et. al.* (2006) pointed out that the era of central bank independence came with the implementation of inflation targeting as a nominal anchor for monetary policy. The objectives and workability needed to be understood by the public and the central banks that adopted the framework communicated more on the matter.

Figure 1. 1: Policy, Autonomy, Transparency, and Accountability

Source: IMF Staff Proposal to Update the Monetary and Financial Policies Transparency Code, 2019

Figure 1. 2: Central Bank Autonomy, Transparency and Accountability

Source: IMF Fact Sheet on Code of Good Practices on Transparency in Monetary and Financial Policies, 1999

- c) *Macroeconomic Stabilization*: The growing significance of central bank communication is also due to the use of monetary policy as a means of stabilizing the economy. Communication as explained by Eusepi and Preston (2010) also contributes to macroeconomic stability because it complements financial liberalization and deepening initiatives.
- d) *Global financial and economic crisis*: Central banks play active roles during global financial and economic crises, thereby increasing their communication with the public. Vayid (2013) posited that due to the worldwide financial crisis of 2008/9, most central banks kept monetary policy rates very low and also engaged in unconventional measures which required more and effective communications. The effect of the Covid-19 pandemic since 2019 has also seen central banks stimulating economies and communicating the measures to the public.

While central bank communication is now an essential part of the monetary policy process, what central banks talk about and reasons for such discourse are explained in table 1.1. They largely communicate about their objectives, policy decisions, economic outlook and also forward guidance in the form of what they are likely to do if certain conditions hold.

But how do central banks communicate? Majority of them take decisions by committees, indicating a consensus among members. Blinder, *et. al.* (2001) distinguished between individualistic and collegial committees. In the individualistic case, the range of opinions is clear to the public while in the collegial case, a similar multiplicity of opinions, if announced, could weaken clarity and consensus, thereby creating discordance among the committee members.

Table 1. 1: Areas Covered by Central Bank Communication

Goals and Objectives	Policy Decisions	Economic Outlook	Forward Guidance
Central banks have clearly legally defined mandates - <i>Ensuring price stability and/or supporting growth.</i>	The policy decisions and justifications are usually announced after meetings.	The outlook for the economy is provided periodically.	Provision of forward guidance is gaining traction.
Communication about objectives and strategy is thus used to publicise the mandates.	The announcements create news and reduce noise.	How to forecast and communicate key indicators like inflation remains debatable	Explicit (direct signals) and Implicit (indirect signals) forward guidance is often provided.
	News creation and noise reduction eliminates guessing on the part of the public, thereby raising the signal-to-noise ratio	Communication of future inflation is a priority for central banks that target inflation.	Publication of forecast indicators (quantitative guidance) is also provided by some central banks

Source: Blinder *et. al.* (2008)

1.2 Motivation and significance

Given the growing import of central bank communication both in the academic and policy domain, the motivating reasons and significance of this study are as follows:

- a) The need to contribute to the increasing research on the subject matter from a developing economy viewpoint given that most inquiries, as noted by García-Herrero *et al.* (2013) is dominated by studies on developed economies. While some inquiries have provided evidence from emerging markets perspectives, studies are still scanty from developing angles. This thesis thus focuses on providing evidence for Nigeria in addition to the growing research as shown in the works of Na'allah (2012), Omotosho (2019) and Tumala and Omotosho (2019). The rationale for focusing on Nigeria is that it is a major oil producing nation, the 13th largest producer of crude oil globally in 2019¹, the 26th largest economy with nominal Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of \$448 billion in 2019² and the 7th most populated country with an estimated population of 170 million.³ Central bank communication in such an economy will create news and signals sent will be of importance to economic actors, both locally and internationally.
- b) Blinder *et al.* (2008) highlighted three key gaps in the central bank communication literature as follows: (1) limited evidence on publication of projected policy rate; (2) the debate on what constitutes optimal communication; and (3) the need for research on central bank communication and the public instead of focusing only on the financial sector. Years after the review, inquiries have not fully addressed these gaps. Particularly, studies have continued to treat the financial sector as synonymous with the public, and only a handful have deviated from this, (for example, Carvalho and Nechio, 2014; and Carin van der Crujisen *et al.*, 2015). This study is motivated to contribute to this aspect of the literature by exploring the extent to which the public understand monetary policy in Nigeria.
- c) This study is significant because on the one hand, it adds to the literature on central bank communication from a developing economy perspective, while on the other hand it provides insightful policy implications that both policymakers and the public can make inferences from. Specifically, the research objectives and the associated questions were formulated in ways and manners that the outcomes will be of practical relevance.

¹ United States Energy Information Administration

² <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NY.GDP.MKTP.CD>, Cited January 15, 2021

³ World Bank Development Indicators 2017 and CIA World Fact Book

1.3 Problem statement

Institutions play important roles in economic development and central banks are mostly looked upon to contribute to such progress. Because economic agents make savings, investment and consumption decisions based on limited resources, information from the central bank is considered crucial when such choices are made. While the major area of debate remains what constitutes optimal communication, the consensus is that talks by central banks help in managing expectations and enhance policy predictability. The following points are however vital for this study:

- a) Given the limited inquiries from developing economies, (the review by Blinder *et. al.*, 2008 did not cite any study from developing economies and inquiries till date have seen only a handful of research from these countries) there is need to examine the subject matter from a developing economy viewpoint where the problem of information asymmetry is prevalent.
- b) Because of the multiplicity of monetary policy objectives and instruments for a central bank like that of Nigeria, there is need to examine if evidence from Nigeria reinforces the predominant views such as communication enhancing the transmission of monetary policy.
- c) When compared with central banks in developed economies, those in developing economies face more fiscal policy related challenges, especially in oil-exporting countries like Nigeria. For example, the procyclical and countercyclical fiscal policy measures often associated with the boom-and-bust cycle of the oil market, sometimes results in short-run macroeconomic instability which the central bank are expected to manage using their policy tools.
- d) The literature remains problematic on the aspect of central bank communication and the public's understanding of monetary policy objectives and instruments because of limited empirical evidence. This study contributes to the literature from this perspective.
- e) Another challenge in the literature is the dominance of volatility analysis despite the rise in policy-oriented studies. The thesis provides policy intuitions to the subject matter since communication is now key for monetary policy.

Overall, this study provides empirical evidence on the highlighted problems by evaluating monetary policy communication in Nigeria. Based on the review of the literature, the study focuses on the clarity of communication, effect of communication on the transmission process, study of fiscal policy discussions as well as the public's knowledge of monetary policy.

1.4 Research objectives and questions

The objectives of the study and associated research questions are as follows:

- a) **Objective 1:** Examine the clarity of monetary policy communication by the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN). The accompanying questions are:
 - i. How clear is the CBN in its communication of monetary policy?
 - ii. How sensitive is the clarity to changes in key macroeconomic indicators?
- b) **Objective 2:** Measure CBN's monetary policy communication by developing two indicators, the *Monetary Policy Stance* (MPS) that reflects the multiple objectives and instruments and the *Monetary Policy Communication on Inflation* (MPCI) which captures the statements on inflation. The two indicators are used to inspect the role of communication in the monetary policy transmission process. The corresponding questions are:
 - i. What was the pattern of CBN's tightening, loosening and neutral stance and how did the bank communicate about *Upside, Downside or Neutral* position on inflation?
 - ii. To what extent does communication enhance monetary policy transmission in Nigeria?
- c) **Objective 3:** Quantify the intensity of CBN's communication about fiscal policy by developing a *Fiscal Policy Communication Indicator* (FPCI). The associated questions are:
 - i. How strongly does the CBN communicate about fiscal policy?
 - ii. To what degree is this intensity influenced by developments in the broader economy?
- d) **Objective 4:** Investigate the extent to which the public in Nigeria understand the monetary policy objectives and instruments of the CBN. The key questions are:
 - i. What are the determinants of monetary policy knowledge in Nigeria?
 - ii. What is the major source(s) of getting information on about monetary policy?
 - iii. To what extent do the sources influence knowledge of monetary policy?

1.5 Organisation

The study is organized as follows: Chapter two reviews the literatures and chapter three discuss monetary and fiscal policy frameworks in Nigeria. Chapter four attempts to answer the questions on clarity while chapter five quantifies communication and ascertains its transmission effects. In chapter six, the intensity of fiscal policy communication is studied, and chapter seven examines the public's knowledge of monetary policy. Chapter eight summarises and concludes the study.

CHAPTER TWO: Theoretical and Empirical Literature Review

'The more you know about your topic, the more effectively you can tackle your own research problems' – Anonymous

2.1 Introduction

This section conducts a systematic review of theoretical and empirical studies on central bank transparency and communication. Figure 2.1 shows the proportion of materials reviewed, with 8% of the theoretical papers published in peer-reviewed journals, 11% theoretical Working Papers, 19% empirical papers issued in peer-reviewed periodicals, 37% as Working Papers, while 11% were Discussion Papers. In addition, 14% of the empirical materials were presented in platforms such as Seminars, Conferences, Staff Reports of central banks and Postgraduate Theses.

Figure 2. 1: Proportion of Research Studies Reviewed by Type of Publication

Source: Author's Plot

The pattern of the review followed the thematic and chronological style, and the rationale is to learn how investigations on central bank communication have evolved over the years. In terms of focus, the theoretical papers explain the desirability or otherwise of transparency and the implications for public welfare and clarifies if communication by central banks should be more or less. The empirical studies focus on the predictability of policy, clarity of policy, the intensity of fiscal policy communication and the public's understanding of monetary policy.

2.2 Theoretical literature review

Transparent central banks are known to communicate their policy objectives, decisions, and the reasons for their choices to the public as clearly as possible. The information provided are used by the public, in addition to privately acquired news, when making consumption, savings and investment decisions.

The relationship between central bank transparency and public welfare has been explored theoretically, with one strand of the literature supporting the postulation that transparency enhances welfare, while another suggests otherwise. Since communication is a prerequisite for transparency, it presupposes that studies that argue that transparency enhances welfare support more communication. On the contrary, studies that argue that transparency does not improve welfare contend that more communication may not be necessary. The ensuing sub-sections review some theoretical studies that explore the link between transparency and public welfare.

2.2.1 Transparency enhances public welfare.

One of the influential studies that claim that central bank transparency is welfare-enhancing is Geraats (2001). It posits that transparency requires the central bank, as depicted in figure 2.2, to ensure that politics, economic, procedural, policy and operational activities are clearly articulated if its policy outcomes are to align with objectives. If transparency agrees to revealing of central bank predictions of inflation and output forecasts, and central bank's status, measured by the public's inflation expectations, plays a salient role, then markets will rely less on signals from less transparent central banks because they devote less in reputation which leads to higher inflation. The public will thus prefer transparency because central bank's preferences are revealed.

Figure 2. 2: A conceptual framework for transparency

Source: Geraat (2001)

Lindner (2007) also stressed central bank forecast and applied the global game framework to study the welfare effects of different communication strategies. The study started on the premise that the basic model focusses on a constraint θ that signifies the vital state of the economy.

Economic agents see θ as significant because it benefits their decision-making and the sole representative agent k gains by aligning activities with other agents. It was further assumed that agents consider two features according to the same loss function as follows:

$$L = (1 - r) \int (q_k - \theta)^2 dk + \frac{r}{2} \iint (q_k - q_m)^2 dm dk$$

(with $0 \leq r \leq 1$). The interests of all agents are alike and used to investigate the welfare effects of different information structures. Overall, the results advocated that communication is superior to secrecy as it helps agents apply private information and rely less on common knowledge.

The herd behaviour model was used by Svensson (2006) to review an earlier study by Morris and Shin (2002) which argued that transparency does not improve welfare and found that more public signals enhance welfare because transparent communication can activate herd behaviour by using the central bank prediction as a coordination tool. The study concluded that Morris and Shin (2002) actually supports the hypothesis that transparency improves welfare and not otherwise. Corroborating this view, Morris *et al.* (2006) posited that the findings of Svensson (2006) are an important contribution to the debate on the welfare effects of public information. Noting that Morris and Shin (2002) had shown that the provision of more precise public information can be detrimental to welfare, they concluded that on the evidence of the insight provided by Svensson (2006) that Morris and Shin (2002) is essentially pro-transparency.

Baeriswyl (2007) also used Morris and Shin (2002) as reference, noting that the study considered communication as the sole task of a central bank and ignored the fact that communication goes with policy action. While accounting for the actions of a central bank and evaluating whether public disclosure is beneficial, the study showed that transparency is beneficial when a central bank's information is accurate as it reduces distortions linked with badly suited policies.

Using the imperfect common knowledge model, the optimal communication strategy of a central bank was examined by Geraats (2007) and the findings showed that the optimal strategy is to provide clarity about inflation and output targets and supply shocks, thereby supporting public decision making which improves welfare. Similarly, Roca (2010) used the imperfect common knowledge idea in a model of price-setting in a monopolistic competition. The study found that the useful effects of reduced imperfect common knowledge owing to a more precise common signal by the central bank compensates the potential rise in aggregate volatility.

Another approach to investigating the relationship between transparency and welfare is the New Keynesian framework. Jensen (2002) suggested that within a forward-looking model, some intermediate degree of transparency may be optimal, arguing that in a New Keynesian model it is easier for the public to distill the intentions of the central bank. Thus, inflation expectations by the public and inflation become more responsive to the central bank's monetary policy. Likewise, Westelius (2009) submitted that in a New Keynesian framework, transparency about the central bank's targets could reduce the volatility of inflation and output gap and enhance public welfare. Similarly, Tang and Yu (2011) focused on the role of central bank communication in shaping inflation dynamics in a New-Keynesian framework and started on the premise that imperfect information complicates the private sector's learning about the policy response function. The study showed that a clear central bank communication, which facilitates agents' understanding of policy reasoning, results in less volatility in inflation and interest rate and is positive for welfare.

2.2.2 Transparency does not enhance public welfare.

The second strand of studies that examine the nexus between central bank transparency and welfare are those that argue that welfare is not enhanced because expectations are not always properly managed through central bank communication.

Using a model where the central bank has private information about upcoming shocks, Cukierman (2001) demonstrated that advance communication by the central bank reduces social welfare because of the inability to manage expectations. This view was supported by Amato and Shin (2003) who applied a model where agents have diverse private information and suggested that in a normal macro-model, public information has uneven result on agents' choices, and so can reduce the information value of economic outcomes. Similarly, Cukierman (2008) contended that it is not possible for a central bank to be transparent about everything due to limited information about the economy. Communication hence cannot always improve public decision-making and transparency will not always lead to enhancement in welfare.

Some studies have in the context of a New Keynesian framework argued that communication of information, especially uncertain information like inflation forecasts, may be harmful. Eijffinger *et. al.* (2004) examined the disclosure of future shocks in the New-Keynesian framework and concluded that such revelations impair the balance of inflation and output and consequently impacts negatively on public welfare. Likewise, Fukač (2006) applied a New Keynesian

framework with adaptive learning and found that stabilizing an economy with heterogeneous expectations is a complex task for the central bank when compared with an economy with homogeneous expectations.

An earlier study by Morris and Shin (2002) used a model where individuals have heterogeneous private information and uncertain public information to show that the social value of public information is not welfare-enhancing. This is because when agents have access to varied private information, the availability of more precise public information damages welfare. Similarly, Morris and Shin (2007) applied a model in which public information is endogenous and found that it might be harmful because it crowds out private information.

Demertzis and Hoerberichts (2007) introduced costs to the Morris and Shin (2002) framework and showed that more transparency is not always needed because more public information lessens the motivations for the private sector to get own information. Likewise, James and Lawler (2011) modified Morris and Shin (2002) framework by identifying that central bank affect the economy indirectly through communication and directly through their policy actions. The results strengthened Morris and Shin's 2002 conclusions that public revelation of the central bank's information is sometimes undesirable.

Dale *et al.* (2008) also referred to Morris and Shin (2002) and started on the premise that the revelation of some information like the inflation target is supportive as it enhances private sector expectations. However, the communication of uncertain information like inflation forecasts might be harmful as agents may attach too much emphasis on it. The study thus showed that most information communicated is noisy or imperfect. Trabelsi (2010) also used Morris and Shin (2002) as a reference and examined fragmentation as an engine for limiting the publicity degree of information and found results supporting Morris and Shin (2002) that public welfare is impaired.

Bennani (2014) provided an extension of Morris and Shin's (2002) model by considering an interpretation bias of the public signal sent by central banks. The study showed that such a bias is detrimental and should be considered when central banks implement their communication policy. Studying the social value of public information in an environment without common knowledge, Gizatulina (2012) argued that the adverse effect of public announcement noted by Morris and Shin

(2002) may be magnified if agents doubt whether others take the public signal too literally and are too inattentive to their private signals.

In summary, evidence from theoretical studies on the link between central bank transparency and public welfare showed mixed results. However, majority of the studies investigating the subject matter are empirical, with focus on how central bank communication, a precondition for transparency, enhances the predictability of monetary policy. The next section provides a review of selected empirical studies, highlighting the methodologies and findings.

2.3 Empirical literature review

The central aim of communication is to boost the public's ability to predict monetary policy choices. Achieving this goal means that expectations are properly managed, and this will in turn have positive effects on overall economic outcomes. This section reviews some studies (segregated into those for the FED, ECB and BOE, followed by evidence from other central banks and cross-country studies) that have examined the communication of monetary policy communication.

2.3.1 The FED, ECB and BOE

The FED

The United States (US) Federal Reserve Bank (FED) started communicating more with the public in 1994 when the Federal Open Market Committee (FOMC) began releasing statements disseminating moves in the overnight funds rate. Since then, empirical inquiries have continued to explore how the FED's communication is aiding the public's anticipation of policy decisions.

Demiralp (2001) defined the anticipation effect of policy as interest rate adjustments that take place prior to a policy announcement. Using theoretical and empirical analysis, the study showed that trading desks do not act immediately after the FOMC meeting as they already adjust their positions in line with their prediction of the likely policy outcome. Similarly, Rafferty and Tomljanovich (2002) examined whether the FED's change to more transparency enhanced or deteriorated the prediction of policy. Applying the Vector Autoregressive (VAR) technique to forecast interest rates, they presented that the forecasting error reduced for interest rates on U.S. bonds of most maturity lengths, and that the expectations theory achieved better at the low end of the yield curve.

Making use of the events study approach, Kohn, and Sack (2003) posited that announcements by the FOMC and congressional testimony by Greenspan significantly affect market interest rates, indicating that markets anticipate that central bank communication bears vital information. Similarly, Gurkaynak *et al.* (2005) scrutinized the effects of policy on bond yields and stock prices and found that monetary policy activities and announcements have crucial but opposing effects on asset prices, with statements having a much greater impact on predictability of longer-term yields.

Ehrmann and Fratzscher (2007) tested for the effects of the correctness of public and private signals on the efficiency of the FED communication. They used a measure of the short-term predictability of central bank decisions and a measure of medium-term predictability to measure efficiency. The results established that exact signals from the bank enhanced the predictability of outcomes, while dispersed signals deteriorated predictability. Equally, Middeldorp (2011) analyzed the predictability before and after the FED's reforms in the 1990s and the results suggested that the reforms and guidance provided since 2003 improved predictability, while the publication of the FOMC's policy bias in 1999 had no measurable impact. The results further showed that speeches and testimonies lower short-term forecasting errors.

Using macro-economic and communication indicators and estimating an ordered probit model of a Taylor rule type, Hayo and Neuenkirch (2012) studied if FED's communications helped predict rate decisions. The findings showed that communication significantly described target rate decisions and improved explanatory power in and out of sample. Also, speeches by members of the Board of Governors and regional presidents have a statistically significant and equal-sized effect, whereas the less-frequent policy reports and congressional hearings are insignificant.

Rosa and Verga (2005) scrutinized the effects of FED's verdicts and announcements on U.S. stock and volatility indices by means of a high-frequency event-study analysis. The results disclosed that the surprise component of policy actions and communication have statistically significant and economically relevant effects on equity indices, with statements having a greater explanatory power of the reaction of stock prices to monetary policy. The study also established that equity indices tend to incorporate FOMC monetary surprises within 40 min from the statement release.

Jubinski and Tomljanovich (2013) analyzed if FOMC minutes matter to markets by probing the 2006 to 2007 time period. Using intraday data and volatility models, the study showed that equity returns are unaffected by the minute releases. Focusing on various dimensions of FED

communication and using daily and intraday data, Kliesen *et al.* (2019) showed that communication is associated with changes in prices of financial market instruments such as treasury securities and equity prices. However, this effect varies by type of communication, by type of instrument, and by who is doing the speaking.

The ECB

The predictability of the ECB monetary policy decisions has also been investigated, with Jansen and de Haan (2003) probing the reaction of the level and volatility of the exchange rates to statements of ECB officials. Using daily data for the period January 4, 1999 to May 17, 2002 and applying an Exponential Generalized Autoregressive Conditional Heteroskedastic (EGARCH) specification, the findings showed that ECB statements have a larger effect on volatility than on the level of the exchange rate. Hagen and Bernoth (2004) analysed the change of ECB decisions on Euribor futures and found that expectations were well-anchored and policy predictability enhanced. Similarly, Jansen and Jakob de Haan (2005) examined the euro-dollar exchange rate by concentrating on effects of verbal statements and found that it had small effects.

Jansen and De Haan (2006) used an ordered probit model based on the Taylor rule to evaluate statements by ECB officials as well as macroeconomic variables. Their findings indicated that the models precisely forecast verdicts to leave interest rates unmoved. The informational content of the monthly introductory statements of the ECB president was scrutinized by Ullrich (2007) and used to analyse the predictability of ECB monetary policy. The results disclosed that the contents can help predict policy decisions. Conrad and Lamla (2007) used the AR-FIGARCH specification to explore the impact of the ECB's statements on the level and volatility of the EUR-US dollar exchange rate. Using high-frequency data, they found that surprise interest rate changes explained the movements in the exchange rate immediately after press release.

Applying a Taylor-rule-type reaction function and using survey data on expectations about the future interest rate, inflation, and output, Schmidt and Nautz (2012) studied how experts observed the interest rate policy of the ECB. They showed that specialists have analytically misperceived the ECB's interest rate rule while the insight regarding inflation has become more accurate.

Bennania *et al.* (2019) used a dataset of the intermeeting verbal communication among members of the ECB's Governing Council between 2008 and 2014 and constructed a measure of

communication assessing its inclination towards easing, tightening, or maintaining the monetary policy stance. They found that this measure provided useful additional information about future policy decisions, after controlling for market-based interest rate expectations and lagged decisions. Also, the results suggested that communication shortly before meetings, related to unconventional measures and/or by the ECB President, explain the future ECB rate changes well.

Comparison of FED and ECB

Some studies have compared the predictability of policy for the FED and the ECB, with Brière (2006) relating the communication strategies of the two banks and their effect on financial markets. Using interest rates options to compute daily probability distributions of market expectations and examining how they are altered by both central banks' statements; the results showed that Greenspan's speeches have a stronger influence on rate levels predictability and market uncertainty than those of Duisenberg.

Andersson (2007) studied the anticipation of the FED and the ECB policy decisions by examining bond and stock market volatility reactions to the decisions of the two institutions between April 1999 to May 2006. By means of intraday data and Generalized Autoregressive Conditional Heteroskedasticity (GARCH) approach, the findings showed a robust surge in intraday *volatility or less predictability* when decisions are publicised, but more noticeable for the US.

Rosa and Verga (2008) examined the impact of monetary policy decisions and central banks' announcements on American and European yield curves over the sample period January 1999 to June 2006. The results showed that on meeting days, financial agents can predict policy decisions because both ECB and FED move market rates using either monetary policy or news shocks. However, the FED can move the long end more effectively than the ECB, while the FED can also move European interest rates of all maturities than the ECB to moving American rates.

The BOE

Having looked at the FED and ECB, it is also important to review some studies for the Bank of England (BOE). Lildholdt and Vila (2004) investigated if the ability to predict future policy rate in the United Kingdom changed in the period 1975-2003. Using a simple term structure model, the study showed that predictability improved over the sample period, mostly after introducing inflation targeting in 1992. Likewise, Reeves and Sawicki (2005) explored how UK financial

markets react to BOE communication. Combining Ordinary Least Square (OLS) and GARCH techniques, they found that publication of minutes and Inflation Report affect near-term interest rate predictability while speeches and parliamentary committee hearings have less impact.

El-Shagi and Jung (2015) studied whether the minutes of the BOE offered markets with extra information about future monetary policy. Applying an ordered probit model and the Vuong test for model selection, the results showed that the BOE's minutes aided markets in establishing their expectations on future monetary policy decisions.

Bholat *et. al.* (2018) in a joint BOE and Behavioural Insights Team study tested the efficiency of different methods to central bank communications. They applied an online experiment with a representative sample of the UK population and measured how changes to the BOE's summary of Inflation Report impact understanding and belief in the policy messages. They found that the Visual Summary of the Inflation Report improved knowledge of its main messages in a statistically significant way compared to the traditional executive summary. In addition, they found that public understanding and trust can be better by making the Visual Summary more relatable to people's lives. They concluded that their results shed light on how central banks can improve communication with the public at a time when trust in public institutions has fallen, while the responsibilities delegated to central banks have increased.

2.3.2 Studies on other Central Banks

Muller and Zelmer (1999) scrutinized whether transparency improved financial markets' knowledge and predictability of monetary policy in *Canada*. Using the GARCH model and intraday day data, they found that transparency helped participants anticipate monetary policy actions. Similarly, Coppel and Connolly (2003) studied the changes in monetary policy for Canada and whether financial markets responded to communication. The results showed that interest rate volatility at the short end fell, implying that predictability improved. Likewise, Hayo and Neuenkirch (2012) examined how Bank of Canada communications and the media reporting affect bond and stock market returns. The results indicated that communication have a comparatively greater effect on the bond market, while media attention is more applicable for the stock market.

Focusing on Hungary, Gabriel, and Pinter (2006) assessed how the *Central Bank of Hungary's* communication moves asset prices. The study concluded that the bank is more effective in

signaling policy contraction than easing, and with the rise of time horizon the written communication increases in importance and dominates unwritten statements. The effectiveness of the communication of *Norges Bank* was carried out by Holmsen *et al.* (2008) by exploring the monetary policy intentions of the bank using volatility models. The results showed evidence of improved predictability on interest rate decisions days. Demiralp *et al.* (2011) measured the efficiency of communication of the *Central Bank of Turkey* using the Autoregressive Conditional Hazard model and the findings suggested that using statements to predict future policy was supported by the adoption of full-fledged inflation targeting regime.

Helder and Ivando (2014) examined the effect of *Bank of Brazil's* communication on volatility of the interest rates before and after publication of communication, and the period without publication (purdah period). The results showed that communication influences expectations and predictability of changes in the interest rates and in the expected direction. Also, communication was found to be more effective and predictable before meetings and publication of the respective minutes.

Concentrating on Nigeria, Umar (2012) assessed the impact of central bank communication on stock prices from 2007 to 2011 by employing the EGARCH model. The study found that communication had significant impact on stock prices and also reduced volatility in the stock market. Concentrating on the exchange rate effect, Na'allah (2012) analyzed the effect of communication signals on daily changes in the Naira per US dollar exchange rate for the period 2007-2011. Using the EGARCH model, the paper showed that communication (oral interventions) had significant and contemporaneous effect on daily exchange rates because it reduced exchange rate volatility whereas actual interventions tend to raise volatility.

The standard deviation approach to volatility was applied by Ekor *et al.* (2015) in their study of the impact of central bank communication in *Nigeria*. They classified speeches and presentations of three central bank governors as indicated in table 2.1, into monetary policy related, economy related and '*Others*'. They noted that the classification is important because financial markets tend to gauge monetary policy sentiment from monetary policy related speeches and presentations. Thus, measuring money market volatility during the periods of the three governors, the findings, as indicated in figure 2.3 showed that volatility was lowest in the period of Chukwuma Soludo whose speeches and presentations on monetary policy were 11 out of 47, that is 23% of his total deliveries, higher than 19% for Joseph Sanusi and none for Lamido Sanusi.

Table 2. 1: Classification of speeches by Governors of Central Bank of Nigeria

Governor	Total speeches/ presentations	Speeches related to monetary policy	Speeches related to economy	Others
Joseph Sanusi	81	15	29	37
Chukwuma Soludo	47	11	35	1
Lamido Sanusi	16	0	15	1

Source: Ekor, *et. al.* (2015)

Figure 2. 3: Volatility of Nigerian Inter-bank Offered Rate under different CBN Governors

Source: Ekor, *et. al.* (2015)

Focusing on *Australia*, McCredie *et.al.* (2014) examined the differential effect of policy statements and minutes on the interest rate futures market. The study started on the premise that the policy announcements are not followed quickly by full summaries that clarify the decision process. Using volatility models, the results showed that both policy announcements and explanatory minutes have a significant effect on the implied yield and volatility of interest rate futures contracts. When the differential impact of the announcements was examined using the full sample, no statistically significant difference was found. However, when the sample was divided based on stable periods and the global financial crisis, a differential impact was evident.

The consequence of the *Czech National Bank's* communication, macroeconomic news and interest rate differential on exchange rate volatility was the focus of Horváth and Fišer (2009). Using the GARCH model, they illustrated that communication had a soothing effect on exchange rate volatility. In addition, the timing of the announcement matters as markets reacted more to communication before policy meetings. Similarly, Horvath and Karas (2013) analyzed the effect of the Czech National Bank's communication on the level and volatility of short-term and long-term interest rates. Applying the GARCH and EGARCH frameworks, and using daily data between 2007 and 2012, the result showed that markets predicted policy based on communication.

The *Reserve Bank of India* was the emphasis of Goyal and Arora (2010) that scrutinized the effectiveness of the bank's communication using the ARCH and GARCH models and found that exchange rate volatility reduced, and predictability improved with communication. Concentrating on the *Bank of Chile*, Pescatori (2018) examined the bank's communication and found that the policy actions are predictable, and the impacts of policy rates surprises are not robust.

Several studies have investigated the communication by *the Peoples' Bank of China* (PBC) and its implications. Garcia-Herrero and Girardin (2013) explored the effectiveness of PBC's communication using the hawkish-dovish classification to test the impact of communication on repo-market volatility and trading volume. The findings showed that money markets listen and also understands the tone of monetary policy. Also focusing on the money markets, Su *et.al.* (2020) constructed three communication indexes and used them in an empirical analysis of which the results indicated that the PBC communication had a significant effect on the country's money market, with informal communication more effective than formal communication.

SHU and Ng (2010) applied the narrative approach to examine the policy of the PBC using the Monetary Policy Report, a quarterly executive report of monetary policy and also constructed a time series of the policy stance index (tight, neutral or ease). The study concluded that the index was useful as it predicted China's monetary policy. The narrative approach was also used by SUN (2013) in exploring the impact of the PBC communication on the macroeconomy, including GDP, inflation, and industrial output. The study found that the PBC uses many policy instruments and none of them can be described as its principal tool while the operational procedures vary over time and the reaction function can hardly be described with a time-invariant equation.

The effect of the PBC's communication on financial markets was evaluated by McMahon *et. al.* (2019) using four categories of communication and calculating market reaction using the daily absolute changes in interest rates for money and bond markets, as well as equity market prices. The results showed that communication is helpful, and that greater transparency and independence would further improve the PBC's effectiveness, including through forward guidance.

2.3.3 Evidence from cross country studies

Connolly and Kohler (2004) focused on a panel of six countries in which macroeconomic news, overseas news, monetary policy surprises and central bank communication were considered. Using

the EGARCH model, they found that interest rate expectations respond to macroeconomic and policy news, but the response to macro news was larger, especially by including foreign news.

Rozkrut *et al.* (2008) investigated whether it pays for the central banks of Czech Republic, Hungary, and Poland to be talkative by coding their statements as follows:

$HI_t^{BE}=\{$	+1 inclination of tightening monetary policy
	-1 inclination of easing monetary policy
$HI_t^{S}=\{$	+1 improved economic outlook
	-1 weaker economic outlook
$HI_t^{M}=\{$	+1 indication of undervalued exchange rate
	-1 indication of overvalued exchange rate
$HI_t^{E}=\{$	+1 statement criticizing fiscal situation
	-1 statement favoring fiscal situation

The study found that communication in the three countries influenced behaviour of financial markets. The result, though, varied because the communication strategies are not uniform.

Égert and Kočenda (2014) also focused on the Czech Republic, Hungary and Poland and employed a two-stage empirical strategy to analyze the impact of macroeconomic news and communication on the exchange rates. They assessed the nominal equilibrium exchange rate before employing a GARCH model to estimate the effects of the news and communication along with the exchange rate misalignment. The findings suggested that currencies react to macroeconomic news while reaction of the currencies to verbal interventions becomes important only during crisis period.

The IMF in its 2018 Regional Economic Outlook for Latin America analyzed the *Credibility, Communication and Monetary Policy Procyclicality in Latin American countries* and found that stronger transparency frameworks and communication strategies are associated with more predictable policy decisions and a better anchoring of inflation expectations in Latin America.

Ekkehard and Merola (2018) developed an automated text-mining routine using the Bank of International Settlements collection of speeches and used the indicators to compare goals and strategies of the FED, ECB, BOE and the Reserve Bank of Australia between 1990 and 2016. The findings revealed that communication complements or substitutes for monetary policy; and for periods in which communication is more efficient in managing expectations, central banks may have less need for reliance on the traditional policy rate.

2.3.4 Cross-border effects of central bank communication

Arora and Cerisola (2001) studied how country risk, using sovereign bond spreads as a proxy, is affected by FED's statements, country-specific basics, and conditions in global capital markets. It showed that while country-specific essentials are vital, the posture and likelihood of FED's policy are also important for stabilizing capital flows and capital market conditions in emerging markets. Alper (2006) also explored the importance of FED's policy surprises in explaining activities in emerging markets' sovereign spreads. The outcome was that it was the unanticipated component, and not the anticipated component of FED's policy that is significant in predicting the movements in emerging markets' sovereign bond spreads.

Similarly, Uribe and Yue (2006) investigated if FED's rates affected emerging countries through their effect on country spreads. Combining empirical and theoretical elements, the results showed that FED's interest rate shocks described about 20 percent of movements in aggregate activity in emerging market economies. Focusing on equity markets, Wongswan and Hausman (2006) examined FED's surprises on foreign equity indexes, short- and long-term interest rates, and exchange rates in 49 countries. Using two proxies for monetary policy surprises, they showed that different asset classes respond to different components of the FED's surprises.

Ehrmann and Fratzscher (2009) analyzed the effects of FED's policy shocks to global equity markets and the macroeconomic determinants of the underlying transmission process. They showed that there is a substantial cross-country heterogeneity in reactions across 50 equity markets worldwide. In the same vein, Wongswan (2009) evaluated FED's policy on 15 foreign equity indexes in Asia, Europe, and Latin America. Using high-frequency data, the study showed a big and substantial reaction of foreign equity indexes to FOMC's surprises at short time horizons. Likewise, Hayo *et al.* (2012) examined the actions of FED by employing a GARCH model and found that the FED's policy greatly influences emerging equity market returns.

Focusing on trading volumes of exchange rate, Fischer and Ranaldo (2011) examined if global currency volume increased on FOMC days. Using the data set from the Continuous Linked Settlement Bank which captures more than half of the global trading volume in foreign exchange (FX) markets, the results showed that FX trading volume increased about 5% in the spot and the spot-next market following FOMC deliberations.

2.4 Summary

This chapter reviewed the theoretical and empirical studies on central bank communication. The theoretical studies focused on whether transparency enhances public welfare while the empirical ones were on how communication boosts the predictability of monetary policy. Though the theoretical outcomes were largely mixed, the empirical examinations largely support the postulation that communication enhances predictability of policy.

Evidence from the review of studies for the FED, ECB, BOE, other central banks, as well as cross country studies and those that examined the cross-border effects of policy announcements, indicate that communication reduces volatility, meaning that it improves the predictability of monetary policy.

Overall, the assessment of the literature offered the background for reviewing the specific areas of central bank communication that are applicable for this study. These are the clarity of communication, measuring communication and its effects, as well as investigating the public's understanding of monetary policy. However, before delving into these definite areas and the empirical analyses, the ensuing chapter provides further context to the study by discussing monetary and fiscal policy frameworks in Nigeria.

CHAPTER THREE: Synopsis of Monetary and Fiscal Policies in Nigeria

'A central bank's monetary policy strategy and its communication is shaped by its statutory mandate and expectations about the central banks' role in the economy'

– Orphanides (2019:pp.4)

3.1 Introduction

This section gives context to the study by providing an overview of monetary and fiscal frameworks in Nigeria. It particularly describes the monetary policy objectives and instruments of the CBN, the policy formulation process, the strategies for communicating objectives, decisions, and economic outlook, and finally how monetary policy is conducted. In addition, the relationship between the CBN and Government is explained based on provisions of the CBN Act 2007.

With respect to the fiscal angle, while the Government implements different policy measures to stimulate aggregate demand and reduce unemployment, the key fiscal policy issues of interest for this study are the oil-price based fiscal rule, the formation of the Excess Crude Account (ECA) and the setting up of the Sovereign Wealth Fund (SWF), all of which impacted the intensity with which the CBN communicated about fiscal policy in the periods they were introduced.

3.2 Overview of monetary policy in Nigeria

The CBN is statutorily accountable for the handling of monetary policy in Nigeria and the main legal instrument guiding its operations is the CBN Act 2007. Before the passing of the Act, the lawful tools that controlled the activities of the bank at different times were the CBN Act 1991, the CBN Amendment Act 1993, the CBN Amendment Act 1997, the CBN Amendment No. 2 Act 1998 and the CBN Amendment Act 1999.

The CBN was before the 2007 Act under the control of the Federal Ministry of Finance (FMF) and the period was characterized by less than transparent events as monetary policy decisions were largely based on the views and sentiments expressed by the Governor. The operational independence of the bank was also lacking because of the regulations by the Minister of Finance. However, following emerging global trends that favored monetary policy transparency and independence, the CBN Act 2007 was passed, clearly stating the mandates, operational autonomy, and the conduct of monetary policy in Nigeria.

3.2.1 Monetary policy objectives, instruments, and formulation

The CBN has multiple monetary policy objectives as provided in Section 2 of the CBN Act 2007 and shown in figure 3.1.

Figure 3. 1: Mandates of the Central Bank of Nigeria

Source: Author's Design from CBN Act, 2007

The multiple objectives also imply that the CBN uses multiple policy instruments as depicted in figure 3.2:

Figure 3. 2: Instruments of Monetary Policy in Nigeria

Source: Author's Design

Hosny and Sullivan (2018) identified the implications of multiple monetary policy objectives and instruments in Nigeria as follows:

- a) Multiple objectives and instruments give rise to the policy tools pulling in different directions, thereby making monetary policy stance difficult and unclear to the public.
- b) It obscures the design and implementation of monetary policy as the transmission mechanism is weak in Nigeria. The CBN's de facto mandate may be different from its de jure and could give rise to contradictory market signals. For example, the MPR is the key tool for managing inflation in the short-term but the CBN sometimes uses other instruments like the OMO and CRR to tighten policy while leaving the MPR unchanged.
- c) The MPR is the nominal anchor and it is meant to signal the CBN's policy posture and transmit changes in policy to market rates. Its aim is to stabilize and align short-term market rates to lessen liquidity risks and assist banks with their pricing policies. With stable short-term rates, changes in the policy rate are more likely to be quickly reflected in changes in banks' deposit and lending rates thereby aiding monetary transmission. By setting aside the MPR due to multiplicity of tools and objectives, the banking system's pricing behaviour is impaired.

The institutional framework for formulating monetary policy is illustrated in figure 3.3.

Figure 3. 3: Institutional Framework for Monetary Policy Formulation

Source: Author's Design from *CBN's Monetary Policy at a Glance, 2017*

- a) **Monetary Policy Committee:** Section 12(1) of the CBN Act 2007 states that for the CBN to enable the accomplishment of the goal of price stability and to support the economic policy of the Federal Government, there shall be a committee known as the Monetary Policy Committee (MPC), with the responsibility for formulating of monetary and credit policy. The Committee comprises 12 members i.e., the Governor, the four (4) Deputy Governors, two (2) members of the Board of Directors, three (3) members appointed by the President and two (2) members appointed by the Governor. The proceedings of the Committee as provided in the Second Schedule of the CBN Act 2007 are shown in figure 3.4:

Figure 3. 4: Schedule of the Monetary Policy Committee

Source: Author's Design from CBN Act 2007

- b) **Monetary Policy Technical Committee (MPTC):** The MPTC is the technical arm of the MPC. It was established in 2005 and is headed by the Deputy Governor (Economic Policy). Its primary function is to prepare economic analyses for the MPC, by synthesizing inputs received from departments like Research, Statistics, Banking and Payments System, Banking Supervision, Financial Policy and Regulation, Reserve Management, Financial Markets and Trade & Exchange Departments, with Monetary Policy as the secretariat.
- c) **Monetary Policy Implementation Committee (MPIC):** The MPIC is responsible for executing the monetary decisions of the CBN. It meets weekly and advises the Governor on the optimal way of ensuring that the set target on broad money supply is achieved. Precisely,

the Committee is authorized to ascertain the daily injection/withdrawal of liquidity, suggests plan(s) that will reduce the liquidity gap and identify the specific instrument to be used.

- d) **Fiscal Liquidity Assessment Committee (FLAC):** The FLAC gives a forum for interaction between the monetary and fiscal authorities. Its key tasks include: (a) providing information on the operations of the Treasury to the LAG for forecasting the level of liquidity in the economy; (b) providing policy advice on fiscal issues; and (c) generating a robust database on the operations of the Treasury that have implications on domestic liquidity.
- e) **Liquidity Assessment Group (LAG):** The LAG serves as a complement to the FLAC. The main activity of the Group is to evaluate everyday liquidity requirements and ascertain the most suitable policy action vital to correct deviations from pre-stated liquidity goals.

3.2.2 Monetary policy framework

Monetary policy framework states the approach that the central bank adopts in achieving its policy objectives. The traditional frameworks are the Exchange Rate Targeting, Monetary Targeting, Interest Rate Targeting, Inflation Targeting and Nominal GDP Targeting. Figure 3.5 depicts that Nigeria adopted the Exchange Rate Targeting framework between 1959 and 1973 while Monetary Targeting has been the preferred approach since 1973, with the Direct Monetary Control applied between 1973 and 1993 and the Indirect Monetary Control in operation since 1993.

Figure 3. 5: Phases of Monetary Policy Framework in Nigeria

Source: Author's Design from Ezema (2009)

Figure 3.6 indicates that the approach for realizing the monetary targeting is to have an *Operating Target*, with the Overnight Interest Rate as the variable of interest, while the MPR is the Operating Instrument. The operating target using the overnight interest rate is used to influence the *Intermediate Targets* which include the Reserve Money, Broad Money, Exchange Rate and Term Interest Rates, while the *Ultimate Target* is the Inflation Rate. Table 3.1 shows that between 1991 and 2019, CBN’s broad money supply and inflation targets were higher than actuals eight times.

Figure 3. 6: Monetary Targeting Framework

Source: <https://www.cbn.gov.ng/Out/2017/CCD/MONETARY%20POLICY%20AT%20A%20GLANCE.pdf>, Cited Jan 5, 2021

Table 3. 1: Broad Money Supply and Inflation Targets and Actuals

	Broad Money Supply (%)			Inflation (%)		
	Target	Actual	Deviation	Target	Actual	Deviation
1991	19.80	27.43	7.63	13.00	23.0	9.96
1992	26.80	47.53	20.73	5.00	48.8	43.80
1993	18.00	53.76	35.76	25.00	61.3	36.26
1994	14.80	34.50	19.70	na	76.8	#VALUE!
1995	10.10	19.41	9.31	15.00	51.6	36.59
1996	16.80	16.18	-0.62	30.00	14.3	-15.69
1997	15.00	16.04	1.04	15.00	10.2	-4.79
1998	15.60	22.32	6.72	9.00	11.9	2.91
1999	10.00	33.12	23.12	9.0	0.2	-8.78
2000	14.60	48.07	33.47	9.00	14.50	5.50
2001	12.20	27.00	14.80	7.00	16.50	9.50
2002	15.30	21.55	6.25	9.30	12.20	2.90
2003	15.00	24.11	9.11	9.00	23.80	14.80
2004	16.00	14.02	-1.98	10.00	10.00	0.00
2005	15.00	24.35	9.35	10.00	11.60	1.60
2006	27.00	43.09	16.09	9.00	8.50	-0.50
2007	24.10	44.24	20.14	9.00	6.60	-2.40
2008	35.00	57.78	22.78	9.00	15.10	6.10
2009	20.80	17.21	-3.59	8.20	12.00	3.80
2010	29.30	6.91	-22.39	11.20	11.80	0.60
2011	13.80	15.43	1.63	12.00	10.30	-1.70
2012	24.60	16.37	-8.23	9.50	12.00	2.50
2013	15.20	1.29	-13.91	9.90	8.00	-1.90
2014	14.52	20.43	5.91	7.50	8.00	0.50
2015	15.24	6.06	-9.18	8.00	9.60	1.60
2016	10.98	17.78	6.80	11.90	18.60	6.70
2017	10.29	2.33	-7.96	10.71	15.40	4.69
2018	10.48	12.13	1.65	13.00	11.40	-1.60
2019	12.99	7.64	-5.35	11.74	11.98	0.24

Source: CBN Annual Statistical Bulletin, 2019

In terms of the process for determining the optimal monetary target, Ezewa (2009) suggested that the CBN begins by designing a short-term monetary programme approved by monetary policy committee using the quantity theory of money illustration depicted in equation 1:

$$MV = P\dot{Y} \quad (1)$$

Where:

M = money stock / supply

V = velocity of money (the number of times a unit of currency changes hands)

P = Price of basket of goods transacted

\dot{Y} = the size of basket of goods transacted in a given period.

The main assumptions are that V and Y are constant, in the short term.

While the quantity of money which is determined by outside forces is the key influencer of economic activities, the optimum liquidity level and aggregate net credit to the economy are computed using the CBN balance sheet and solving the following equation:

$$M2 = NDC + NFA + OAN \quad (2)$$

Where:

M2 = Broad Money Supply

NDC = Net Domestic Credit

NFA = Net Foreign Assets

OAN = Other Assets Net

Taking the first difference of equation 2 as follows:

$$\Delta M2 = \Delta NDC + \Delta NFA + \Delta OAN \quad (3)$$

And breaking NDC into public and private as follows:

$$\Delta NDC = \Delta NDCg + \Delta NDCp \quad (4)$$

Where:

NDCg = Net Domestic Credit to the government sector, and

NDCp = Net Domestic Credit to the private sector

Then the new equation is:

$$\Delta M2 = \Delta NDCg + \Delta NDCp + \Delta NFA + \Delta OAN \quad (5)$$

Under the monetary targeting framework in an indirect approach, the liquidity level that is consistent with macro-objectives is determined using the Base Money (BM) as the operating target, M2 as the intermediate target while inflation is the ultimate target. Conventionally, Base Money is made up of currency with the non-bank public, (C) and reserves of DMBs, (R), while:

$$R = CRR + OR \quad (6)$$

Where:

CRR = Cash Reserve Requirement

OR = Other reserves, i.e., C + DMBs deposits at CBN

The main sources of base money are the Net Central Bank Claim on Government (NCBCg), Net Foreign Assets of the Central Bank (NFACB) and Other Assets Net of the Central Bank (OACB).

The balance sheet identity of the Central Bank can thus be written as:

$$NCBCg + NFACB + OACB = C + R = BM \quad (7)$$

The process of money creation derives from banks expanding money supply by a multiple of reserves. To influence money supply, OMO is applied among other instruments:

$$M2 = C + D \quad (8)$$

$$BM = C + R \quad (9)$$

$$M2/BM = K = (1+c)/(c+r); 0 < r, c < 1 \quad (10)$$

$$M2 = KBM = [(1+c)/(c+r) BM] \quad (11)$$

Where:

k = multiplier

R = DMBs' Reserve with the Central Bank

C = Currency outside banks

c = currency/deposit ratio

r = reserve/deposit ratio

Finally, money supply (M2) can be estimated from equation (11) from an assumed Base Money (BM) and the multiplier (k) through change in bank reserve (R) and currency outside bank (C). Although the currency/deposit ratio (c) is a function of the cash preferences of the economic agents, it may be sensitive to interest rate movements. Bank reserves/deposit ratio (r) may be influenced by reserve requirements and the multiplier (k) can be influenced in the desired direction.

3.2.3 Monetary policy communication strategy

Monetary policy communication is the process of providing info about monetary policy framework and decisions to the public. The CBN's main channels of communication are through press conference, issuance of monetary policy communiqués, press releases, circulars, and guidelines.

Ekor *et.al.* (2013) explained the communication strategies of the CBN as shown in Table 3.2. During the monetary policy committee meetings, the CBN governor who is also the chairman speaks last after other members have presented their views and this follows the pattern of the BOE and ECB. The CBN, like the three comparator central banks, provides press release after interest rate decisions have been made. This usually takes the form of a '*Monetary Policy Communiqué*'.

Table 3. 2: Communications Strategy of the CBN and Other Central Banks

Strategy	FED	BOE	ECB	CBN
Modus operandi during Meeting	Chairman speaks first	Chairman speaks last.	Chairman speaks last.	Chairman speaks last
Press release after interest rate decision	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Press conference & question/answer	No	No	Yes	Yes
Minutes of meeting	Yes	Yes	No	Yes
Video of meeting	Yes	Yes	No	No
Publish information on voting pattern	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Additional sources of information	Yes	Yes	No	Yes
Publish Governor's speeches/presentations	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Publish members speeches/presentations	Yes	Yes	Yes	No

Source: Ekor *et. al.* (2013)

In line with the ECB strategy, the CBN holds a press conference after its meeting and this also involves a question-and-answer session to explain the rationale for its decisions. Such clarifications are disseminated by the invited media practitioners who take on the duty of providing the public with further insight into why certain decisions were taken by the CBN. Also, following the ECB, BOE and FED strategies, the CBN since 2011 has been providing information on the voting pattern of committee members. The bank offers extra information beyond those provided through the press conference and releases, for example, through briefing to the parliament.

The CBN publishes the speeches and presentations of the governor on its website but does not provide such information for other members of the committee. Although the committee members give speeches and presentations at different fora, their non-publication on the CBN website makes the members less noticeable to the public.

3.2.4 Relationship between the CBN and Government

The relationship between the CBN and the Government is guided by provisions of the CBN Act 2007. Specifically, and as indicated in figure 3.7, Section 36 of the CBN Act 2007 highlights the services that the Bank should render to the Government.

Figure 3. 7: Services of the CBN to the Federal Government

Source: Author’s Design from CBN Act 2007

With respect to providing advances to the Government, figure 3.8 explains that Section 38(1) states that the CBN may grant temporary advances in respect of deficiency of budget revenue at such rate of interest as it may determine. Also, Section 38(2) indicates that the total amount of the advances outstanding shall not at any time exceed five percent of the previous year’s actual revenue of the Government, while Section 38(3)(a)(b) explains the repayment modalities.

Figure 3. 8: Advances of the CBN to the Federal Government

Source: Author's Design from CBN Act 2007

In terms of funding of government’s fiscal deficit, table 3.3 shows that over 80% of the proposed fiscal deficits between 2018 and 2020 were to be financed from borrowing from non-bank public.

Table 3. 3: Nigeria’s Proposed Fiscal Deficit and Borrowing Plan

	2018	2019	2020
Fiscal Deficit (N' trillion)	1.95	1.92	4.98
New Borrowing (N' trillion)	1.64	1.61	4.19
New Borrowing % of Fiscal Deficit	84.10	83.85	84.14

Source: Budget Office of the Federation - Medium-Term Expenditure Framework – Various Editions

The breakdown of the financing items in table 3.4 shows that while proceeds from privatization, non-oil asset sales, multilateral and bilateral project tied loans, and borrowing from special accounts, are part of the funding sources, the bulk of the amount comes from borrowings from the domestic bond market and foreign sources. The Debt Management Office (DMO) is responsible for borrowing and debt management activities in Nigeria and its board is indicated in figure 3.9.

Table 3. 4: Breakdown of Fiscal Deficit Financing Items (Naira)

	2018	2019	2020
1 Sale of Govt Properties	0.00	0.00	0.00
2 Privatization Proceeds	306,000,000,000	210,000,000,000	126,041,863,844
3 Non-oil Asset Sales	5,000,000,000	0.00	0.00
4 Multilateral/Bilateral Project tied loans	0.00	92,836,081,493	387,298,800,000
5 Borrowing from Special Accounts	0.00	0.00	263,630,000,000
6 New Borrowings	1,643,464,992,872	1,605,638,968,248	4,198,572,722,984
• Domestic	n/a	802,819,484,124	2,213,892,722,984
• Foreign	n/a	802,819,484,124	1,984,680,000,000

Source: Budget Office of the Federation - Medium-Term Expenditure Framework – Various Editions

Figure 3. 9: DMO Supervisory Board

Source: Author’s Design from DMO Annual Report, 2018

However, because projected revenues often fall short of expectations, and borrowing plans sometimes delayed by technicalities of the process, the government depend on the CBN for advances to fund its deficit. Figure 3.10 shows that the claim on government by the monetary authorities stood at N7.03 trillion in 2019, while the percentage change in the disbursements was relatively constant for most of the period. The frequency of the advances by the CBN to the federal government is not time bound but depends on the needs and exigencies of the times.

Figure 3. 10: Monetary Authorities Claim on the Federal Government 2016 - 2019

Source: CBN Statistical Bulletin Q4 2019

There are sometimes concerns, even by members of the Monetary Policy Committee, about CBN's advances to the government. For example, Professor Adedoyin Salami, a member of the Committee expressed doubts in the Policy Communiqué of July 2017, pages 38 - 39, as follows:⁴

'Monetary data shows a sharp rise in the extent of CBN financing of the government deficit.

Highlights of CBN financing of the Federal Government since Dec. 2016 are as follows:

- a) *CBN's claims on Federal Government (FG) at N814bn is twentyfold higher while the claims of Commercial Banks rose marginally by 0.4% to N4.6 trillion.*
- b) *30.0 per cent increase to N454bn in CBN's purchase of government T-Bills.*
- c) *5 percent increase in FG Overdrafts to N2.8 trillion; and*
- d) *Rise in the 'mirror account' from N3 billion in 2016 to N1.5 trillion in April 2017.*

He concluded that *'It is clear that the CBN has provided 'piggy bank' services to the Federal Government'.*

4

<https://www.cbn.gov.ng/Out/2017/MPD/Central%20Bank%20of%20Nigeria%20Communique%20No.%2014%20of%20the%20Monetary%20Policy%20Committee%20Meeting%20of%20July%2024%20and%2025.%202017.%20with%20Personal%20Statement%20of%20Members.pdf>, Cited February 27, 2021

3.3 Some key fiscal policy events – Oil-price based fiscal rule, ECA and SWF.

Several key fiscal policy developments have happened in Nigeria since the end of military regime in 1999. Among them are the introduction of the oil-price based fiscal rule in 2003 which automatically led to the creation of the Excess Crude Account (ECA) and subsequently the Sovereign Wealth Fund (SWF). These events are particularly important because of their direct and indirect implications for the conduct of monetary policy.

The oil-price based fiscal rule was aimed at basing government's expenditure on a prudent oil price benchmark and revenues that accumulate above the reference prices were saved. Adoption of the rule ensured that expenditures were de-linked from oil revenue earnings, thereby limiting the transmission of external shocks into the economy. The enactment of the Fiscal Responsibility Act (FRA) 2007 which empowers the Federal Government to prudently manage the nation's resources and ensure long-term macro-economic stability provided the legal framework for the oil-price based fiscal rule. Section 35(1) of the Act stipulates that '*Where the reference commodity price rises above the predetermined level, the resulting excess proceeds shall be saved...*'.

Okonjo-Iweala (2014) noted that the adoption of the rule reduced the macroeconomic volatility and increased government's savings while the ECA was beneficial in the following ways:

- a) It ensured that Nigeria was able to withstand the negative impact of the 2008/9 global economic and financial crises when oil prices crashed from \$147 per barrel to less than \$40 per barrel, within a 4-month period.
- b) During periods of revenue shortfall arising from oil production disruptions due to domestic pipelines vandalism and oil theft, the ECA was used to augment revenue allocations to the three tiers of government.
- c) The 2005 debt relief from the Paris Club wiped off about 60 percent (\$18 billion) from Nigeria's national debt and \$6 billion was utilized from the ECA to buyback the rest of the debt at 25 cents on the dollar, after paying off accumulated interest arrears.

In terms of operation of the ECA, the account belongs to the three tiers of Government (Federal, State and Local Governments). Thus, any draw-down from it is done in consultation with representatives the States and Federal Government and such withdrawals occur only when there are shortfalls in revenues. In such cases, discussions are held among all State Commissioners of

Finance and the Federal Government to agree on the amount of revenue augmentation which would be needed from the ECA. An application is then made to the President for approval; and following his endorsement payments are made to the respective tiers of government.

In line with global best practices, especially for oil producing nations, the Nigerian government used the ECA as a basis for setting up the SWF in 2011. The Nigeria Sovereign Investment Authority (NSIA) was then established by an Act of Parliament, the (NSIA) (Establishment, etc.) Act, 2011. According to Okonjo-Iweala (2014), there are two main reasons why commodity exporting countries create SWF:

- a) First, because commodity prices are volatile, they generate fluctuations in resource revenues which are transmitted into the economy through the national budgets. If natural resource revenues are a substantial share of government revenues, the external volatility can result in significant fluctuations in public expenditures. This leads to a pro-cyclical fiscal policy where government spending on projects increases during the boom times, and crashes when resource revenues collapse. The fluctuations in expenditures result in macroeconomic volatility, which creates uncertainty for businesses, and reduces economic growth.
- b) Second, because natural resources are depleting assets, some resource revenues must be preserved for future generations. In other words, these resources will be exhausted at some point in the future. Responsible policymakers should therefore aim at saving some part of these resources so that future generations can also benefit from them.

The core capital of Nigeria's SWF stood at \$1.5 billion as at December 2019⁵. The funds are allocated as follows: 20% in Stabilization Fund (the funds here are in liquid assets); 40% in Infrastructure Fund; and 40% in Future Generations fund. According to the NSIA Act, only the Stabilization Fund is available for drawdown and the disbursement process is as follows:

- a) The determination of drawdown is made by the Minister of Finance depending on the needs of the Federation, including catering for emergencies arising from human and natural disasters.
- b) Upon request from the Minister of Finance, the NSIA executes a drawdown request with its asset managers, who then execute the trades and make the funds available.

⁵ <https://nsia.com.ng/~nsia/sites/default/files/downloads/NSIA%20Annual%20Report%202019.pdf>, Cited January 16, 2021

3.4 Summary

The chapter offered a brief synopsis of monetary and fiscal frameworks in Nigeria with a view to providing a background setting for the ensuing empirical analyses. From the monetary perspective, the mandates, instruments, and framework for the conduct of monetary policy were highlighted, while the communication strategy of the CBN was also discussed. Likewise, the central bank's approach for setting monetary policy was described while the relationship with Government was explained based on provisions of the CBN Act 2007.

The fiscal policy aspect focused mainly on three key events that influenced the CBN's conduct of monetary policy in the periods they were carried out.

- First, the introduction of the oil-price based fiscal rule in 2003 helped curb the effect of external negative shocks on oil prices on the domestic economy.
- Second, the creation of the ECA which automatically happened when the oil-price based rule was introduced provided the necessary fiscal buffers during periods of low oil prices.
- Third, the establishment of the SWF with an initial capital of \$1bn in 2011 provided the platform for setting aside funds for Infrastructure, Stabilization, and the Future Generation.

All the above issues were instrumental in the way and manner the CBN communicated about fiscal policy in those periods.

Having provided the monetary and fiscal context, the ensuing empirical chapters attempt to answer the different research questions under the four objectives of the study.

CHAPTER FOUR: Examining Clarity of Monetary Policy Communication

'Monetary policy communication is never easy: one must find the right vocabulary to communicate to a wide audience the notion and content that are not immediately intuitive but highly relevant for the lives of many people' – Praet (2014)⁶

4.1 Introduction

The importance of clarity in monetary policy communication is captured by Blinder *et. al.* (2008) who submit that it has a higher signal-to-noise ratio and provides useful information to the public. It is therefore a prerequisite for predictability and efficient transmission of policy outcomes.

The main channel through which the CBN communicates its policy decisions is the Monetary Policy Communiqué issued at the end of the committee meetings. To ascertain clarity, this study thus concentrates on the policy communiqués because written communication has been found to have greater impact than oral communication and speeches (Blinder *et.al.*, 2008).

Apart from the writing style, choice of words and vocabularies used, the ease with which the public will understand CBN's communiqué will also depend largely on the complexity of the message that the bank is trying to get across. This will be affected by the multiple objectives as provided in Section 2 of the CBN Act 2007 as follows: (1) ensuring monetary and price stability (2) issuing legal tender currency (3) maintaining external reserves to preserve the value of the domestic currency (4) promote a sound financial system and (5) act as banker to the Government.

The tools that are used to achieve the objectives are the MPR, OMO, CRR, etc. Clarity will invariably be contingent on the content of the communiqué as the CBN tries to explain its many objectives and how the different policy instruments are used to achieve them.

Consequently, the key questions that this chapter aim to address are as follows:

- a) How clear is CBN's communiqués and to what extent did the clarity vary over the years?
- b) How sensitive is the clarity of the communiqués to changes in key macroeconomic variables?

The rest of the chapter sheds light on the literature on clarity of central bank communication, data and methodology, the empirical techniques for analyzing the nexus between clarity and changes in key macroeconomic indicators, while the last part discusses the results and policy implications.

⁶ <https://www.ecb.europa.eu/press/key/date/2014/html/sp140312.en.html>, Cited February 27, 2021.

4.2 Literature review on clarity of central bank communication

The dominant focus of the literature on central bank communication dwells on its impact on the financial markets, with most studies focusing on how agents can predict policy changes. One key factor that enhances the predictability of policy is the clarity of communication. Blinder *et al.* (2008) posits that when communication is clear, it means the various tools applied are well organized and that the message is not affected by contradictions. They explain three scenarios of clarity as follows:

- a) Clarity with no shocks where the central bank constantly talks about economic events and its policy responses with no substantial surprises occurring, and the public appropriately foresees the ultimate policy outcome.
- b) Clarity with shocks where the central bank provides a reliable clarification of issues but unexpected shock(s) push inflation significantly above or below the prediction, and the public is surprised by the inflation outcome. However, the public knows the central bank is reliable but the deviation of inflation from the target is brief and triggered by unexpected shocks.
- c) Confusion occurs when communication is unpredictable and results in public mix-up. Clarity of communication is thus important for understanding and predicting monetary policy.

To examine clarity, text mining tools have been employed to scrutinize written reports by central banks. For studies on the FED, Romer and Romer (2004) used text analysis to extract a narrative-based examination of the impact of monetary policy shocks. Bailey and Schonhardt-Bailey (2008) also used text scrutiny to study FED records, focusing on opinions and rhetorics applied by policymakers. Fligstein *et al.* (2014) applied the text mining tool of Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) to FED minutes from 2000 to 2007, while Hansen *et al.*, (2018) also used the LDA to develop measures of communication patterns at the meeting-section-speaker level.

Cannon (2015) studied FED's records from 1977 to 2009 by gauging the tone of debates, exploring the differences across speakers, and probing how the tone of the debates relates to economic activity. The results showed that the tone varied by speaker, and that Bank Presidents contributed to the debates in significantly diverse ways compare to Governors or staff members. Meade and Acosta (2015) used computational linguistics to examine how the content of FED's post-meeting statement changed from May 1999 when the Committee started announcing statements

consistently through December 2014. They found that the semantic content of the statements from one meeting to the next is less similar and more variable than would appear at first glance.

With respect to studies for the ECB, Heinemann and Ullrich (2006) assessed the clarity of the content of the ECB monthly press conferences, and based on a counting of certain signal words, they constructed a wording indicator reflecting the “hawkishness” of monetary rhetoric. For the creation, they developed an objective algorithm signifying a learning process of ECB observers. They then integrated the indicator into a standard Taylor type ordered probit model for the clarification of the interest rate. They found that the wording indicator improves the model’s fit when added to the normal explanatory variables.

Buliř *et al.* (2008) found that during 1999–2007, the ECB’s communication was clear in about 95 percent of cases and that the clarity improved in 2003–2007 compared to 1999–2002. Specifically, they posited that it is valuable to read the ECB’s bulletins and look for news both on individual inflation factors (demand, supply, and external) and on the general forecast risk as such information improves clarity.

Starting on the premise that clarity and consistency are required for communication to be effective, Jansen and Jakob de Haan (2010) applied the Wordscores methodology which requires that the reference texts of the ECB President’s introductory statements by the President are coded. They suggested that if central bankers too frequently change their language, it will be hard for observers to deduce the message they are trying to send. Therefore, they assessed the internal consistency of ECB communication by looking at the similarities in the vocabulary over the years. Also, noting that as conditions change, communication strategy is certain to change and from this viewpoint, too much emphasis on consistency may mean too much rigor with communication. Overall, they examined whether ECB communications have been consistent, and changes in language have augmented the understanding of monetary policy. They found that clarity and consistency improved the predictability of policy by financial markets.

Likewise, Amaya and Filbien (2015) examined the similarity of ECB’s communication, using learning models and data collected for 172 introductory monthly statements. They found that similarity of the speeches has been growing and has helped stock markets learn from ECB monetary policy and facilitate the mining of forward-looking evidence by investors.

Apart from studies on the FED and the ECB, investigations have also been conducted to ascertain the clarity and consistency of communication by other central banks. Kawamura *et al.* (2019) studied the Bank of Japan's Monthly Report and its features in relation to the business cycles. The results showed that unclear languages tend to appear often with adverse expressions, and the inclination is more noticeable in recessions. This according to the authors suggested that the central bank communicates tactically by obscuring the reports when their private information is unfavorable, thereby impairing clarity of the Bank's communication in such periods.

Bulíř and Šmídková (2008) started on the premise that the Czech National Bank has a reputable record in terms of its actions and the equivalent inflation outturns. Thus, using a simple forward-looking policy rule, they found that its main communication tools provided clear messages in about three out of every four observations in our 2001–2005 sample. Focusing on the Reserve Bank of South Africa, Reid, and Plessis (2009) assessed the degree of clarity since the introduction of inflation targeting by constructing a numerical index that was used to reflect the information of the bank's communications, especially the monetary policy statements. They found that the clarity and consistency of the bank improved the predictability of policy.

As part of a broader analysis of the Bank of Indonesia's monetary policy communication, Calixte *et al.* (2020) used the Flesch-Kincaid and Gunning Fog readability techniques to estimate the clarity of the bank's written communication. The results showed that the Flesch Kincaid scores were higher than the recommended good business writing score of less than 10. The Gunning Fog index suggested that the bank's statements were written in long sentences using complicated languages as the scores were above 12, signifying that the texts are too difficult to comprehend.

Cross country inquiries have also been conducted to ascertain the clarity and consistency of communication by a panel of central banks. Fracasso *et al.* (2003) described the Inflation Reports by 19 inflation-targeting central banks by relying on questionnaire completed by independent evaluators. After conducting statistical tests, the study concluded that the quality of the writing style negatively correlates with policy surprises, suggesting that clarity reduces uncertainty.

Similarly, Bulíř *et al.* (2008) evaluated inflation reports for six countries, using a simple forward-looking policy rule. The results showed that the reports provided a consistent message in five out of the six observations. Bulíř *et al.* (2012) also examined whether the clarity of communication about inflation changes with the economic environment. They used the Flesch-Kincaid readability

index and content analysis for inflation outlook by seven central banks between 1997 and 2010 and found no strong indications that central banks were less clear in explaining their policies when faced with higher uncertainty or a less favorable inflation outlook. The global financial crisis, however, did have a negative impact on clarity of central bank communication.

Likewise, Bulir *et al.* (2014) measured the clarity of inflation reports by four central banks using the Flesch-Kincaid readability tool before and during the global financial crisis and found an association of clarity and reduced market volatility. Longer sentences and complicated words with many syllables were found to reduce the clarity of messages.

Emphasizing the period of the financial crisis and using data from five countries, Siklos (2013) examined whether the language used by central banks has changed. Applying DICTION, a software program for text analysis, the study found a greater focus on financial stability and more attention for uncertainty concerning the economic outlook. Born *et al.* (2011) also emphasized the financial crisis and found that financial stability reports are clear and had significant effect on stock market returns and reduced volatility. They however found that speeches and interviews had little effect on market returns and do not generate a volatility reduction during calm times.

Grimaldi (2011) focused on the ECB and used quantitative methods to measure the clarity about financial stress. The results showed that clarity improved how communication is designed and understood. Also, Knütter *et al.* (2013) analysed the effects of communication on financial stability, noting that information asymmetries and uncertainties led central banks to attach importance to communication policy as a monetary policy instrument. The results support the view that clarity of written reports move asset prices.

Tumala and Omotosho (2019) constructed a corpus based on 87 policy communiques with a total word count of 123, 353 for the Central Bank of Nigeria. After processing the textual data into a form suitable for analysis, they examined the readability, sentiments, and topics of the policy documents. Amongst other results, they found that the word and sentence structures of the policy communiques have become more complex, thereby reducing its readability. On the contrary however, Omotosho (2019) amongst other results, used the Coleman and Liao (1975) readability index to show that the word and sentence structures of the press releases of the Bank of Ghana have become less complex, indicating increased readability.

Given that clarity of monetary policy communication is important for predicting policy outcomes and enhancing the transmission mechanism of policy, the ensuing sub-section explains how the clarity of CBN's policy communiqués is measured and the extent to which it was affected by changes in key macroeconomic variables.

4.3 Methodology

4.3.1 Data and content analysis of communiqués

The CBN started publishing its policy communiqués in 2001 and a total of 113 downloadable communiqués were obtained from the bank's website for the period Q2 2001 to Q4 2018. A template as shown in table 1 of Appendix 1 was designed and used to extract information from the communiqués. The first column provides details such as the date of the meeting, the communiqués number, date of release, the person responsible for the issuance, date of publication and the governor of the bank.

To determine clarity of the communiqués, the study applied the Flesch-Kincaid readability tool used by Bulíř *et al.* (2012) and Bulíř *et al.* (2014) as well as the Gunning Fog Index by Calixte *et al.* (2020). The Flesch-Kincaid uses features of texts, such as the number of words, sentences, and syllables and it is calculated as follows:

$$0.39*(\# \text{ words} / \# \text{ sentences}) + 11.8*(\# \text{ syllables} / \# \text{ words}) - 15.59 \quad (1)$$

The insight from the Flesch-Kincaid is that many words per sentence or many syllables per word decreases readability. If someone must process a document with long words or sentences, it will be harder to understand the message, and so would need more years of education. The Flesch-Kincaid is thus considered an intuitive way to evaluate variation in clarity. The predominant rule is that written documents should aim for a Flesch-Kincaid grade level of less than 10.

The Gunning Fog Index estimates the years of formal education desirable to comprehend a passage of text on the first reading. The principle is that short sentences written in plain English receive a better score than longer sentences written in complex language. A score of 7 or 8 is said to be ideal, and anything higher than 12 is too complex to read. The index is calculated as follows:

$$0.4 \left[\left(\frac{\text{words}}{\text{sentences}} \right) + 100 \left(\frac{\text{complex words}}{\text{words}} \right) \right] \quad (2)$$

Tables 2, 3 and 4 in Appendix 1 show examples of the populated templates using communiqués *No. 1*, the first published, *No. 68* issued when the CBN changed its policy rate from the Minimum Rediscount Rate (MRR) to the Monetary Policy Rate (MPR) and *No. 121* was the last for 2018.

A scrutiny of the communiqués shows that the number of paragraphs as depicted in figure 4.1 has increased since the first was issued in 2001, the highest being 98, lowest 5 and average 35 between 2001 and 2018. Figure 4.2 indicates that the number of sentences also increased in line with the number of paragraphs, with the highest of 181, lowest 13 and average 75. The number of words per communique displayed in figure 4.3 specifies that it also increased in line with the number of paragraphs and sentences, with the highest word count of 3,172, the lowest 304 and average of 1,516 in the period under review.

In terms of clarity, figures 4.4 and 4.5 show that the communiqués issued by the CBN between 2001 and 2018 were on average difficult to understand. This is because the Flesch Kincaid and Gunning Fog scores averaged 12.85 and 13.84 respectively, higher than the benchmark 10 for clarity. These findings contrast Bulíř *et al.* (2008) and Jansen and Jakob de Haan (2010) that found that the ECB's communication to be clear. Likewise, the results differ from Bulíř and Šmídková (2008) that found that the Czech National Bank provided clear messages in about three out of every four observations. It also differs from Omotosho (2019) that amongst other results found that press releases of the Bank of Ghana have become less complex. The outcomes are however similar to Mathur and Sengupta (2019) that found that the Reserve Bank of India's written communication is linguistically complex and Tumala and Omotosho (2019) and Calixte *et. al.* (2020) that found that written statements by the CBN and the Bank of Indonesia are complex.

The clarity of CBN's communiqués likewise depend on how the bank is able to articulate its multiple objectives and the several instruments used to achieve them. This could be challenging as Hosny and Sullivan (2018) argued that CBN's explanations of its multiple objectives and instruments often send mixed signals to the markets. A similar view was expressed by SUN (2013) who argued that the Peoples' Bank of China uses many policy instruments and none of them can be defined as its principal tool while the operational procedures vary over time and the reaction function can hardly be described with a time-invariant equation.

Figure 4. 1: Number of Paragraphs in the Communiqués

Source: Author's Plot

Figure 4. 2: Number of Sentences in the Communiqués

Source: Author's Plot

Figure 4. 3: Number of Words in the Communiqués

Source: Author's Plot

Figure 4. 4: Flesch Kincaid Grade Level Scores

Source: Author's Plot

Figure 4. 5: Gunning Fog Index Scores

Source: Author's Plot

4.3.2 Estimation techniques

In line with Bulíř *et al.* (2012) and Bulíř *et al.* (2014) this study used the Flesch Kincaid score as a clarity indicator and examined whether its variation is related to changes in key macro variables.

Multiple OLS Regression

Following Mathur and Sengupta (2019) which among other estimations, used the multiple regression to measure the relationship between readability and length of Reserve Bank of India reports, this study evaluates the effect of macro variables on the clarity of CBN's communiqués.

The estimated equation is as follows:

$$FK_t = \alpha + \beta \Delta ASI_t + \delta \Delta CRD_t + \lambda \Delta DEF_t + Q \Delta INF_t + U_t \quad (1)$$

Where:

- FK = Flesch-Kincaid score
- ΔASI = Change in the All-Share Index
- ΔCRD = Change in total credit to the economy
- ΔDEF = Deficit/GDP Ratio
- ΔINF = Change in the rate of headline inflation
- β, δ, λ and Q = Estimated parameters
- U_t = Captures all other effects apart from those of the listed explanatory variables

The rationale for using the change in the explanatory variables is to enable us to capture the dynamic effects of developments in the economy. Equation 1 thus explains that the clarity of the communiqués is contingent on changes in the macroeconomy as they concern the stock market, credit, fiscal policy issues captured by the deficit/gdp ratio and the inflation rate.

Put differently, the idea behind the regression analysis is to estimate how changes in the explanatory variables cause the clarity indicator to change. It does not ascertain the extent to which discussions about specific issues relating to the stock market, inflation, credit, and deficit are altered. The basis for not emphasizing how discussions is altered is because this will require the use of automated or text mining approach by means of dedicated computerized methods which are not applied in this study.⁷

⁷ Tumala and Omotosho (2019) provided such evidence for Nigeria using the text mining technique.

VAR Impulse Response Function and Variance Decomposition

The Impulse Response Function (IRF) and Variance Decomposition (VD) techniques of the VAR model are also applied to establish how clarity responds to shocks to the key macroeconomic variables. Studies such as Lucca and Trebbi (2009), Neuenkirch (2011) and Siklos (2019) applied the VAR tool in exploring the central bank communication subject matter. While the IRF is used to trace out the response of clarity to shocks to the macro-variables, the VD describes determinants of the variation in clarity in the short and long run. A key benefit of the VAR model is that all variables in the system are presumed to be endogenous.

4.4 Results

Multiple OLS Regression

The first task in an empirical investigation with time series data is to test for unit root and the essence is to ensure that estimated parameters are valid and not spurious. Table 4.1 shows that all the variables are stationary at level, implying that they do not have unit roots and are I(0) variables.

Table 4. 1: Unit Root Test

	Test Critical Values			ADF Test Statistic	Prob.	Order of Integration
	1% Level	5% Level	10% Level			
FK	-3.5285	-2.9041	-2.5895	-4.6493	0.0003	I (0)
ASI	-3.5332	-2.9062	-2.5906	-3.3077	0.0184	I (0)
CRD	-3.5348	-2.9069	-2.5910	-4.2960	0.0010	I (0)
INF	-3.5300	-2.9048	-2.5899	-3.5477	0.0095	I (0)
DEF	-3.5285	-2.9041	-2.5895	-3.4925	0.0111	I (0)

Source: Author's Estimates

The multiple regression results depicted in table 4.2 are summarized as follows:

- a) The explanatory variables as indicated by the R-square explain approximately 29% of the variation in clarity.
- b) The joint influence of the explanatory variables on clarity is significant as shown in the F-statistics and the corresponding p-values.
- c) The residual diagnostic tests are as follows:
 - i. The serial correlation and heteroskedasticity tests are shown in table 4.3 and indicate that the assumptions that observations of the error term should be uncorrelated with each other and that error terms should be constant were not violated.

- ii. Figures 4.6 indicate that the residuals in the equation are normally distributed.
 - iii. The CUSUM stability plot shown in figure 4.7 indicate that the model is stable.
- d) The effect of credit is significantly positive.
- i. Credit issues are very sensitive because of the intermediary role of the commercial banks who grant these credits based on guidelines by the CBN.
 - ii. Systemic challenges, unprofessional and sharp practices, and defaults by creditors sometimes impair the credit portfolio of banks and results in non-performing loans.
 - iii. CBN addresses credit issues from both monetary and regulatory aspects. While regulation is set out in the banking supervision framework, monetary policy instruments are deployed in order to control the quantity of credit in the economy.
 - iv. Empirical studies have explored the issue of credit in the economy, with Ogechi and Ikpesu (2017) examining the determinants of non-performing loans in Nigeria and found that the main causes are lending rate, money supply and unemployment rate. Similarly, Atoi (2018) found that lending rate is a driver of non-performing loans using a restricted dynamic Generalized Method of Moments method to study the stability of Nigerian banks.
- e) The effect of fiscal deficit is also significantly positive.
- i. The challenge of fiscal dominance has receded in Nigeria with measures such as the oil-price based fiscal rule introduced in 2003, the ensuing the ECA, as well as the SWF, all of which led to increased positive statements about fiscal policy by the CBN.
 - ii. The reduced fiscal dominance has been empirical examined, with Sanusi and Akinlo (2016) using the structural VAR technique to show that shock to fiscal deficits does not stimulate response from the growth of monetary base between 1986-2013. They also found that there exists no causality running from fiscal deficits to growth of monetary base and thus concluded that there is no evidence of fiscal dominance in Nigeria during the study period.
 - iii. Afolabi and Atolagbe (2018) also found no evidence of fiscal dominance in Nigeria between 1986 and 2016 using the Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) and cointegration methods. They showed that deficit, debt, and money supply have no significant influence on the average price level.

- f) The impact of stock market is negative but insignificant.
- i. The negative result aligns with Mathur and Sengupta (2019) that found that the less readable statements for the Reserve Bank of India are associated with stock market developments like trading volumes and volatility.
 - ii. Speculations and manipulations associated with stock market activities and the resultant volatility affect analysts, including the CBN's view of the market. This has been shown empirically to negatively affect the economy. Akinmade *et. al.* (2020) analyzed the effect of stock market manipulation on the Nigerian economy by employing a broad data set of 186 actual manipulation cases indicted by the Nigerian Security and Exchange Commission between 2002 and 2016. They applied the market microstructure analysis, event study method and the Error Correction Model to evaluate the economic effects and found that manipulation distorts market efficiency, resulting in genuine traders exiting the market, thereby creating negative consequences for the broader economy.
- g) The impact of inflation is also negative but insignificant.
- i. While the inflation objective is predominant, the need to discuss other objectives as well as explain the usage of the instruments mixes up the message being sent to the public.
 - ii. For example, while the MPR is the main instrument for managing inflation in the short run, the CBN sometimes uses other instruments like OMO and CRR without adjusting the MPR and this according to Hosny and Sullivan (2018) obscures monetary policy.

Table 4. 2: Multiple Regression Result

Dependent Variable: FK				
	Coefficient	Standard Error	t-Statistic	p-value
C	3.7864	0.0260	145.2731	0.0000
CRD	0.1218	0.0578	2.1067	0.0391
DEF	0.0628	0.0134	4.6638	0.0000
ASI	-0.0234	0.0932	-0.2514	0.8023
INF	-0.0302	0.0606	-0.4985	0.6198
R-squared	0.2849	Mean dependent var	3.6903	
Adjusted R-squared	0.2403	S.D. dependent var	0.1336	
S.E. of regression	0.1164	Akaike info criterion	-1.3926	
Sum squared resid	0.8681	Schwarz criterion	-1.2307	
Log likelihood	53.0460	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-1.3284	
F-statistic	6.3774	Durbin-Watson stat	1.1387	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.0002			

Table 4. 3: Residual Diagnostic Test Results

Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test			
F-statistic	2.0262	Prob. F (2,62)	0.0765
Obs*R-squared	11.9568	Prob. Chi-Square (2)	0.0629
Heteroskedasticity Test: Harvey			
F-statistic	1.1326	Prob. F (4,64)	0.3491
Obs*R-squared	4.5616	Prob. Chi-Square (4)	0.3353
Scaled explained SS	4.1928	Prob. Chi-Square (4)	0.3805

Figure 4. 6: Normality of Residual Plot

Figure 4. 7: CUSUM Model Stability Plot

IRF and VD

The results of the IRF show that the response of the Flesch Kincaid to shocks to the explanatory variables was not significant, as such they were not reported. However, the variance decomposition outcomes are depicted in table 4.4 and indicate that the variations in the clarity indicator is mainly due to own effects. Specifically, the Forecast Error Variance (FEV) in the clarity indicator is on average 89% due to its own-effect despite the gradual increase in the effect of the explanatory variables in the long-run. The implication is that the explanatory variables do not explain much of the variation in clarity.

Table 4. 4: Variance Decomposition Results

Period	S.E.	FK	ASI	CRD	INF	DEF
1	0.1021	100.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
2	0.1148	95.9575	0.3332	0.0585	2.5551	1.0954
3	0.1180	92.5116	0.5405	1.4163	3.2202	2.3111
4	0.1199	89.6704	0.6746	2.8431	3.9005	2.9112
5	0.1212	87.6508	1.3673	3.1452	4.5406	3.2958
6	0.1223	86.1501	2.2058	3.1345	5.1486	3.3608
7	0.1229	85.5063	2.7294	3.1340	5.2775	3.3526
8	0.1231	85.2376	2.8856	3.2262	5.3082	3.3421
9	0.1233	85.0374	2.9184	3.3594	5.3505	3.3340
10	0.1234	84.8939	2.9293	3.4313	5.4158	3.3294
Average	0.1191	89.2616	1.6584	2.3749	4.0717	2.6332

Cholesky Ordering: FK ASI CRD INF DEF

Source: Author's Estimates

4.5 Summary

The chapter examined the clarity of the monetary policy communiqués issued by the CBN between 2001 and 2018. The key questions asked were: (1) How clear are the communiqués and to what extent did clarity vary over the years? (2) How sensitive is the clarity of the communiqués to key macroeconomic variables? The Flesch Kincaid was used to measure clarity while the multiple regression technique was applied in line with Mathur and Sengupta (2019) and complemented with the IRF and VD techniques of the VAR model.

The findings indicate that the number of paragraphs, sentences and words of the communiqués have increased over time. Also, the clarity results showed that the communiqués are difficult to understand as the Flesch Kincaid and Gunning Fog Index scores are higher than 10. The findings contrast Bulíř *et al.* (2008) and Jansen and Jakob de Haan (2010) that found the ECB's

communication to be clear; Bulíř and Šmídková (2008) that showed that the Czech National Bank provided clear messages in about three out of every four observations; and Omotosho (2019) that found that the press releases of the Bank of Ghana on monetary policy have become clearer in recent times. The outcomes are however similar to those of Mathur and Sengupta (2019), Tumala and Omotosho (2019) and Calixte *et. al.* (2020) that found that the statements of the Reserve Bank of India, the Central Bank of Nigeria and the Bank of Indonesia have become more complex due to the word and sentence structures.

The multiple regression results showed that the explanatory variables described about 29% of the variation in the Flesch Kincaid. Their joint influence is significant given the F-statistics and the associated p-values. The residual diagnostic showed that the model did not violate the serial correlation and heteroskedasticity assumptions, while the residuals are normally distributed, and CUSUM stability plot indicate that the models are stable.

The regression results showed that the effects of credit and fiscal deficit on clarity are positive and significant as credit issues are very sensitive while the challenge of fiscal dominance has receded in Nigeria. The impact of stock market and inflation are however insignificantly negative. The IRF indicated that the response of clarity to shocks to the explanatory variables was not significant while the variance decomposition outcomes specified that the FEV in clarity is largely due to own effect. This implies that the explanatory variables did not explain much of the variation in the clarity indicator.

In conclusion, the results suggest that the monetary policy communiqués issued by the CBN between 2001 and 2018 were difficult to comprehend. The challenge of explaining the multiple objectives and the instruments used to achieve them is probably the major reason why the communiqués are hard to comprehend.

CHAPTER FIVE: Measuring Communication and the Transmission Effects

'The reason for focusing on communication is that macroeconomic management is affected by longer-term interest rates, equity values and exchange rate – Yellen (2012)

5.1 Introduction

The growing research on central bank communication has seen aspects of the empirical inquiries finding means of measuring statements by central banks. The two main methods of doing this are the automated and heuristic approaches. While the latter gauges statements based on guidelines and researcher's interpretations, the former uses dedicated computer programmes and software. The heuristic method, though time consuming, enables the investigator to adapt the indicator to the set-out goals and also detects conditions that a machine cannot notice. Automated methods are however objective and quick but need text structures to stay similar over time.

The objective of this chapter is to quantify the communication of the CBN using the heuristic approach to develop two indicators: First, a measure that captures the bank's overall *Monetary Policy Stance* (MPS) based on signals to tighten, loosen, or hold. This takes into consideration the use of the several policy instruments to achieve the multiple objectives listed in Section 2 of the CBN Act 2007. Second, because of the primacy of the price stability objective, a *Monetary Policy Communication on Inflation* (MPCI) is developed. The goal is to ascertain the *Upside, Downside or Neutral* inflation statements of the CBN in the review period.

Following Neuenkirch (2013) that added the KOF MPC Communicator alongside the usual indicators in a study for the ECB, the *MPS* and *MPCI* are used to augment the traditional variables in assessing the effect of communication in the transmission process for Nigeria. This deviates from most studies where only the traditional indicators are used to evaluate transmission of policy. For example, the research unit of CBN in 2010 applied Structural VAR and Dynamic Stochastic General Equilibrium models while Obafemi and Ifere (2015) used Factor-Augmented VAR to examine the dominant channel of transmission without checking the impact of communication.

The rest of the chapter sheds light on the literature and methodology for measuring central bank communication, including the forward-looking inflation statements. The techniques for estimating the effect of communication in the monetary policy transmission process are presented and the results and policy implications discussed.

5.2 Literature on measurement of central bank communication

The approach for revising some studies that quantified communication by central banks is to first discuss those that applied the heuristic method and then the ones that used the automatic approach. A sequential pattern of review is used in order to determine the level of investigative progress in the area of quantifying central bank communication.

5.2.1 Studies that follow the heuristic method.

One of the influential heuristic ideas for quantifying central bank statements is the Swiss Economic Institute's KOF Monetary Policy Communicator developed in 2007. It covers the forward-looking information reports about risks to price stability in the ECB president's introductory statements. Conrad and Lamla (2010) used the KOF Monetary Policy Communicator to demonstrate that the EUR/USD exchange rate responds to ECB communication. Sturm and De Haan (2011) also found the KOF indicator useful in predicting ECB's next policy decision.

Neuenkirch (2013) likewise applied the KOF indicator as an additional variable for exploring the role of communication in the ECB monetary policy transmission process. The study used the VAR method and estimated a baseline five-variable model without communication that includes industrial production index, the harmonized index of consumer prices inflation rate, the monetary aggregate M3, the MRR and the 12-month-ahead expected inflation rate. When the baseline model was modified with the KOF indicator, the study found that communication has an effect on inflation expectations and exerts a clear role in the spread of monetary policy to output.

The heuristic approach by Rozkrut (2008) for measuring the communication of the National Bank of Poland was to evaluate selected texts on four dimensions using judgement and assigned binary value for each dimension. Farka (2011) also applied judgement to separate statements into "informative" and "uninformative" groups with informative statements delivering important information which were not previously anticipated.

Focusing on Nigeria, Ibrahim and Sanusi (2012) measured the signals contained in the policy communiqués by creating a 3-way dummy variable of 1, 0 and -1. They studied the content of each document to code the nature of the signals concerning the future path of monetary policy. Whenever the impression obtained from the communiqué suggests that the bank expects tighter future policy or that inflation is still a threat or any information that suggests future tightening,

they assigned 1 to the dummy variable. Using the same criteria, when a communiqué suggests future easing, they assigned -1, and 0 where it suggests hold and they found that the signals are instrumental to reducing market volatility.

Farka and Fleissig (2013) created an indicator variable that considered the information content of policy statements of the FOMC and found that evolution of the language of its statements does matter to market participants and, in particular, the ‘forward-looking’ language adopted in mid-2003. Carvalho *et al.* (2013) analyzed how the Central Bank of Brazil communication affects the term structure of future interest rates. Using principal components analysis, they constructed a measure of the minutes content that replicates optimism about economic conditions and found that policy maker communication has an effective impact on market expectations.

Lehtimäki and Palmu (2019) classified statements into “dovish”, “hawkish” and “neutral” positions according to the stance of the monetary policymakers in the news. Classification of the key message in a story is done by using +1 for a hawkish monetary policy stance, 0 for neutral view and -1 for a dovish posture. While the hawkish stance connotes interest rate increase, the dovish is for cut in rate and the neutral classification referred to appropriate monetary policy level or that there are no monetary policy changes expected.

5.2.2 Studies that follow the automated approach.

The study by Lucca and Trebbi (2009) is one of the early inquiries that applied automated method to quantify the communication by a central bank. They applied a computerized approach to assess FED’s statements starting in 1999 on the hawkish – dovish axis. Using intra-day financial quotes, they showed that short-term yields respond to changes in policy rates around policy announcements, whereas longer-dated Treasuries mainly react to changes in policy communication. Furthermore, they found that changes in the content of the statements led policy decisions by more than a year in univariate interest rate forecasting and VAR models.

Apel and Grimaldi (2012) measured the tone and sentiment of the statements of the Swedish central bank using a computerized content analysis that converts the information in the statements to a measurable quantity and found that the measure is useful in forecasting policy rates. Chague *et al.* (2015) also used algorithm that classified words from the Central Bank of Brazil into programmed semantic themes and then evaluated a time-series factor related to the bank’s

optimism. The results showed that long-term interest rates are sensitive to optimism factor when the bank is more optimistic, long-term interest rates fall. Carvalho *et al.* (2014) likewise quantified reports by the Central Bank of Brazil using Google search inquiries to measure the degree to which each statement is perceived to be related with more "hawkish" or "dovish" language. They found that changes in the statements have significant effects on yields at short-to-medium maturities.

The hawkish-dovish indicator method was similarly adopted by Tobback *et. al.* (2017) to measure the 'hawkishness' or 'dovishness' of the media's observation of the ECB's tone during its press conference. They compared two methods to compute the indicator: semantic orientation and Support Vector Machines (SVM) text classification which provides steady and precise dimensions of awareness. They also demonstrated the possible use of the indicator with numerous applications: performing a relationship analysis with a set of interest rates using the LDA to detect the main topics in the news and estimating a set of Taylor rules. The findings provided suggestion in favour of using an advanced text mining classification model.

Picault and Renault (2017) developed a field-specific dictionary to quantify the posture of the ECB and proposed the use of term-weighting and contiguous sequence of words (n-grams) to capture communication. The results showed that measuring ECB communication using the field-specific weighted lexicon clarifies future ECB decisions in an augmented Taylor rule. Similarly, Young *et al.* (2018) used the contiguous sequences of words (n-grams) in addition to a field-specific Korean dictionary to enumerate the statements of the Bank of Korea and found that the text-based indicators explain current and future policy decisions when considering an augmented Taylor rule.

Eyup and Odabaş (2016) offered a semantic check of statements for FED, ECB, and the Central Bank of the Republic of Turkey (CBRT) to detect the change in tone with movements toward transparency. They studied the statements in the pre-crisis years of 2002 to 2015 using *Diction 7 software* and showed that optimistic tone of FED reduced whereas certainty tone increased. For the ECB and CBRT, they found no significant tone difference in certainty, optimism, and realism over time. But, for CBRT's last two statements, there was a significant rise of optimistic tone.

Siklos (2019) also used the *Diction 7 software* to analyze 60 years of FED minutes using the VAR method. The results showed differences in the language across various FED Chairs since the

1950s. A statistically significant connection was found between the statements and real GDP and changes in the fed funds rate. No significant links were found between the minutes and inflation.

Bennani and Neuenkirch (2014) employed a computerized text *linguistic approach* to create an indicator that measured the tone of 1,618 speeches by ECB members between 1999M1-2014M4. Their findings are as follows: First, inflation and growth prospects have a positive and significant effect on the hawkishness of a speech. Second, country-specific conditions matter for speeches inside the central banker's country but not for those made abroad. Third, differences in preferences are the main source of differences in speeches before the financial crisis, while differing national conditions are the key factor in the second part of the sample.

Hansen and McMahon (2016) explored how the multi-dimensional aspects of information by the FOMC affect market and real economic variables. Using tools from *computational linguistics*, they measured the news released by the FOMC and the guidance about future monetary policy. Employing the measures within a FAVAR framework, they found that surprises to forward guidance are more vital than the FOMC communication of current economic conditions in terms of their impact on market and real variables.

Filbien *et. al.* (2016) explored whether the sentiment by the ECB and FOMC officials affect the term structure of short-term interest rate expectations. They proceeded in three steps. First, they measured sentiment using *computational linguistics*. Second, they identified exogenous shocks to the quantitative measures using an augmented narrative approach. Third, they estimated the effect on private agents' views about future short-term interest rates using an event-study method and an ARCH model. The results showed that sentiment surprises increase private interest rate expectations at maturities around 1 and 2 years and the effect is non-linear, depending on the features of the sentiment signal conveyed to the public and on the state of the economy.

Hansen *et. al.* (2018) also used *computational linguistics algorithms* and a natural experiment in the FOMC in 1993 to explore how transparency affect monetary policy makers' deliberations and the results showed that large changes in communication patterns after transparency. Similarly, Hubert and Labondance (2019) explored whether tone conveyed in FOMC reports contain valuable news. They quantified tone using *computational linguistics algorithms* and identified

exogenous shocks to tone orthogonal to the state of the economy. Using the ARCH model and a high-frequency method, they showed that positive tone helps predict future policy decisions.

Ekkehard and Merola (2018) developed an automated text-mining routine using the Bank of International Settlements collection of speeches given by central bank senior executives. The indicators were used to compare goals and strategies of the FED, ECB, BOE, and the Reserve Bank of Australia from the late 1990s up to 2016. The results presented that communication complements and substitutes for monetary policy because in the periods in which communication is more effective, central banks may have less need for dependence on the traditional policy rate.

Armeliu *et. al.* (2018) used text analysis and a new dataset to measure the sentiment of communications in 23 countries over the 2002-2017 period. The main outcomes were: First, using directed networks, comovement in sentiment across central banks is not reducible to trade or financial flow exposure. Second, geographic distance is a robust and economically significant determinant of comovement in central bank sentiment, while shared language and colonial ties are economically significant, but less robust. Third, sentiment shocks generate cross-country spillovers in sentiment, policy rates, and macroeconomic variables. Overall, the results showed that communication contains systematic biases that could lead to suboptimal policy outcomes.

Mathur and Sengupta (2019) likewise developed measures of *linguistics* and quantitatively analysed statements of the Reserve Bank of India (RBI) from 1998 to 2017. They found that while communication is linguistically complex on average, the length of statements has gone down, and readability has improved significantly in the recent years. Applying the OLS regression model, they found that lengthier and less readable statements are related to both higher trading volumes and higher returns volatility in the equity markets, though the effects are not persistent.

Tumala and Omotosho (2019) employed text-mining techniques to analyse the communication strategy of the Central Bank of Nigeria during the period 2004-2019 by constructing a corpus based on 87 policy communiques with a total of 123, 353 words. They examined the readability, sentiments, and topics of the policy documents and amongst other results, found that the word and sentence structures of the communiques have become more complex, thus reducing its readability.

Having reviewed studies that quantified communication by central banks using the heuristic and automated methods, the ensuing subsection explains the approach for measuring CBN's communication in this study and its effect in the transmission of monetary policy in Nigeria.

5.3 Methodology, Estimations and Results

5.3.1 Measuring CBN's Communication

Two communication indicators were measured from CBN's monetary policy communiqués issued between Q3 2001 and Q4 2018. First is the *Monetary Policy Stance* (MPS) which considers CBN's multiple objectives and the corresponding policy instruments. Second is the *Monetary Policy Communication on Inflation* (MPCI) which reflects the primacy of the price stability objective.

Developing the MPS followed the conventional method used by Ehrmann and Fratzscher (2007), Jansen and De Haan (2009) and Lehtimäki and Palmu (2019) where statements or policy actions are coded based on inclinations to tighten, hold, or loosen. The decisions to raise interest rates are coded +1, to hold rate 0 and to cut rate -1. Appendix 2 shows for each communiqué, the decisions, reasons, interpretations (tightening, hold or loosening) and the associated coding of +1, 0, and -1.

A review of the monetary policy decisions by the CBN between 2001 and 2018 as shown in figure 5.1 indicates that the bank tightened its stance in 26 or 37% of the communiqués using a combination of the policy rate, OMO sales, CRR and sometimes foreign exchange interventions and withdrawal of public sector funds from commercial banks when government institutions were still allowed to deposit with them. The easing stance was observed in 11 or 16% of the communiqués while it maintained a neutral stance in 33 or 47% as depicted in figure 5.1.

Figure 5. 1: CBN's Monetary Policy Stance 2001 - 2018

Source: Author's Plot

The MPCI was measured using the approach of the Swiss Economic Institute’s KOF Monetary Policy Communicator which ‘*translates the ECB president’s statements concerning risks to price stability as made during the monthly press conference into an index. By aggregating forward-looking statements on price stability, the KOF Monetary Policy Communicator contains information about the future path of ECB monetary policy*’, (KOF MPC, 2007).⁸

It is based on a coding of each introductory statement where analysts read the text sentence by sentence and each sentence contains one or more statements, which are then coded. The data which underlies the indicator is obtained from all sections of the statement but only statements that refer to risks for future price stability are selected for construction of the KOF Monetary Policy Communicator. The coding is aggregated by taking balances of the statements that reveal upside risks to price stability and statements that reveal that the ECB sees downside risks to price stability, relative to all statements about price stability (including neutral) and this is stated as follows:

$$\text{KOF MPC} = \frac{\text{Statements that reveal upside risk} - \text{Statements that reveal downside risk}}{\text{Total statements about price stability (including neutrals)}}$$

The values of the KOF Communicator are restricted to the range of minus one to plus one, the larger a positive (negative) value, the stronger the ECB communicated about upside (downside) risks for price stability. The sequence for the construction is depicted in figure 5.2 as follows:

Figure 5. 2: Swiss Economic Institute’s KOF Framework

Source: Author’s Design from KOF Framework, 2007

⁸ <https://kof.ethz.ch/en/forecasts-and-indicators/indicators/kof-monetary-policy-communicator.html>, Cited Aug 10, 2018

Table 5.1 shows the template designed to classify and code inflation comments in each of the CBN's policy communiqués. Sentences were extracted according to the subject matter in each paragraph and then entered in Panel A. Any comment(s) on inflation is/are highlighted and entered as 'Yes' in Panels B, C and D as follows:

- a) If any statement in Panel A is about upside risk to inflation, that is the CBN projects that inflation may rise, 'Yes' is reflected in Panel B and 'No' in Panels C and D.
- b) If any statement in Panel A is about downside risk to inflation, that is the CBN projects that inflation may decline, 'Yes' is reflected in Panel C and 'No' in Panels B and D.
- c) If any statement in Panel A is about a neutral position, that is the CBN reports what happened as far as inflation is concerned, then 'Yes' is reflected in Panel D and 'No' in Panels B and C.
- d) The statements are summarized in Panel E where the *MPCI* is calculated by taking the balance between upside and downside risks statements and then divided by the total number of statements about inflation, including the neutral statements.
- e) The calculated *MPCI* ranges between -1 and 1, with a higher positive (negative) value indicating that the CBN sees upside (downside) risks for price stability.

Tables 1 – 3 in Appendix 3 show how the *MPCI* was estimated from each communiqué. Table 1 demonstrate that in *Communique No. 1*, two upside risk and one neutral statement were made and no statements on downside risk. The estimated *MPCI* of 0.667 means that the CBN communicated more about upside risk to inflation. Table 2 shows that in *Communique No. 68*, one upside risk, two downside risk and one neutral statement were made, resulting in an estimated *MPCI* of -0.250, implying that the CBN communicated about downside risks to inflation. Table 3 illustrates that in *Communique No. 121*, the CBN's position concerning risks to inflation was neutral as it made one upside risk, one downside risk and two neutral statements, resulting in an estimated *MPCI* of 0.

Table 4 in Appendix 3 and figure 5.3 below provide all the upside, downside, and neutral statements on inflation for all the communiqués and the average *MPCI* of 0.135 meant that overall, the CBN communicated more about upside risk to inflation between 2001 and 2018.

The voting pattern of the members of CBN's monetary policy committee and the *MPCI* is shown in table 5.2. There is a positive, though weak correlation, between voting to increase the policy rate and the *MPCI*. This may be attributed to the fact that the CBN also use other policy tools like the OMO and CRR to manage liquidity and consequently inflation in the short-term.

Figure 5.4 shows the graphical illustration between the *MPCI* and CBN policy rate while figure 5.5 depicts the KOF Monetary Policy Communicator and the ECB refinancing rate. It is seen that the upside risk to inflation sentiments expressed by the ECB coincide with increases in the refinancing rates. Paradoxically, the upside risk sentiments coincide with decreasing or flattening policy rate for most periods for Nigeria.

The following reasons could be attributed for the Nigerian contradiction:

- a) Given the multiple monetary policy objectives and many instruments used to achieve them, the CBN sometimes alter the other tools like the OMO and CRR, etc. to manage inflation in the short-term instead of raising the policy rate. Thus, in the periods where the policy rates were unchanged when the CBN expressed upside risk to inflation sentiments, the other instruments may have been adjusted to tighten liquidity. The positive but weak correlation between the *MPCI* and the policy rate shown in table 5.2 underpins this view.
- b) It could be that the CBN saw inflationary threats as temporary in those periods that it expressed upside risk to inflation sentiments and decided to remain neutral on policy on those occasions.
- c) The CBN implicitly targets inflation at between 6-9%. Thus, in some periods where upside risk to inflation sentiments were expressed, the bank may have decided to remain neutral if it sees inflation not crossing its upper target limit of 9%.
- d) The policy rate is the most visible monetary policy tool to the politicians who see raising rates as undermining their preference for economic growth. As such, for some of the periods that the CBN expressed upside risk to inflation sentiments, it may have, for political reasons, adjusted other policy instruments like the OMO and CRR instead of raising the policy rate.

Table 5. 1: Template for Quantifying Monetary Policy Communication on Inflation by the CBN

	A: Sentence	B: Does the highlighted statement(s) in the sentence reveal upside risks to price stability?	C: Does the highlighted statement(s) in the sentence reveal downside risks to price stability?	D: Does the highlighted statement(s) in the sentence reveal neutral position on price stability?
1				
2				
3				
4				
5				
	Total Number of Statements on Upside, Downside and Neutral Position	0	0	0
E: Summary				
1	Total number of statements that reveal upside risks to price stability		$=(C9 - C10)/C13$, that is total number of statements that reveal upside risks to price stability minus total number of statements that reveal downside risks to price stability, divided by total number of statements about price stability, including neutral	
2	Total number of statements that reveal downside risks to price stability			
3	Total number of statements that reveal neutral position on price stability			
4	Total number of statements about price stability (A + B)			
5	Total number of statements about price stability (including neutral) (A + B + C)			
	MPC	#DIV/0!		

Source: Author

Table 5. 2: Correlation btw the Monetary Policy Communication on Inflation and Committee’s Voting Pattern

	MPCI	Vote to Increase MPR	Vote to Reduce MPR	Vote to Hold MPR
MPCI	1.000			
Vote to Increase MPR	0.305	1.000		
Vote to Reduce MPR	-0.089	-0.213	1.000	
Vote to Hold MPR	-0.165	-0.848	-0.182	1.000

Note: MPR = Monetary Policy Rate; MPCI = Monetary Policy Communication on Inflation

Figure 5. 3: Estimated MPCI for each Monetary Policy Communiqué, 2001 - 2018

Source: Author's Plot

Figure 5. 4: CBN's Policy Rate and the Estimated MPC

Source: Author's Plot

Figure 5. 5: ECB's Refinancing Rate and KOF MPC

Source: ECB KOF MPC Framework, 2007

5.3.2 Models, Variables and Estimation Techniques

The estimated models

The research department of the CBN in a 2010 study examined the different channels of monetary policy transmission with the goal of determining the channel with the highest speed of transmission. The investigation, like most studies on monetary policy transmission for Nigeria, did not consider the role of communication and its impact. This study modified the CBN equations with the *MPS* and *MPCI* as indicated in table 5.3 in line with Neuenkirch (2013) who combined the KOF Monetary Policy Communicator in a VAR framework to ascertain the impact of communication in the monetary policy transmission for the ECB.

A baseline model was estimated and then augmented with the *MPS* and *MPCI* separately in order to see the effect of the overall policy stance on one hand, and that of the communication about inflation on the other. In the interest rate channel, six equations were estimated as follows: first, the nominal interest rate equation without communication, with *MPS* and then with *MPCI*. Second, the real interest rate equation without communication, then with *MPS* and with *MPCI*.

In the credit channel three equations were assessed, that without communication, with *MPS* and then with *MPCI*. For the exchange rate channel, six equations were measured: first, the official exchange rate without communication, then with *MPS* and with *MPCI*. Second, following Hosny and Sullivan (2018), the BDC rate was applied in an exchange rate equation without communication, then with *MPS* and with *MPCI*. In the asset channel, three equations were estimated; the equation without communication, followed by that with *MPS* and then with *MPCI*.

Overall, the rationale for estimating the equations without communication and the ones with communication, that is with *MPS* and *MPCI* separately, is to identify whether communication enhances the transmission mechanism process. Also, the justification for using the *MPS* and *MPCI* separately is to ascertain whether the transmission process is better improved by the general policy stance of tightening, hold or easing which takes into consideration the multiple objectives and instruments, or by communication about only inflation.

Table 5. 3: Estimated Monetary Policy Transmission Models

	Model	Equation
1	Baseline model	$X_t = (GDP_t, INF_t, MS_t)$
2	Augmented baseline with communication	
	• With MPS	$X_t = (GDP_t, INF_t, MS_t, MPS_t)$
	• With MPCl	$X_t = (GDP_t, INF_t, MS_t, MPCl_t)$
3	Interest Rate Channel	
	• Nominal Interest Rate without communication	$X_t = (GDP_t, INF_t, MS_t, IBR_t, MPR_t)$
	• Nominal Interest Rate with MPS	$X_t = (GDP_t, INF_t, MS_t, IBR_t, MPR_t, MPS_t)$
	• Nominal Interest Rate with MPCl	$X_t = (GDP_t, INF_t, MS_t, IBR_t, MPR_t, MPCl_t)$
	• Real Interest Rate without communication	$X_t = (GDP_t, INF_t, MS_t, RIBR_t, MPR_t)$
	• Real Interest Rate with MPS	$X_t = (GDP_t, INF_t, MS_t, RIBR_t, MPR_t, MPS_t)$
	• Real Interest Rate with MPCl	$X_t = (GDP_t, INF_t, MS_t, RIBR_t, MPR_t, MPCl_t)$
4	Credit Channel	
	• Without communication	$X_t = (GDP_t, INF_t, MS_t, CRD_t)$
	• With MPS	$X_t = (GDP_t, INF_t, MS_t, CRD_t, MPS_t)$
	• With MPCl	$X_t = (GDP_t, INF_t, MS_t, CRD_t, MPCl_t)$
5	Exchange Rate Channel	
	• Official Exchange Rate without communication	$X_t = (GDP_t, INF_t, MS_t, EXC_t)$
	• Official Exchange Rate with MPS	$X_t = (GDP_t, INF_t, MS_t, EXC_t, MPS_t)$
	• Official Exchange Rate with MPCl	$X_t = (GDP_t, INF_t, MS_t, EXC_t, MPCl_t)$
	• BDC Exchange Rate without communication	$X_t = (GDP_t, INF_t, MS_t, BDC_t)$
	• BDC Exchange Rate with MPS	$X_t = (GDP_t, INF_t, MS_t, BDC_t, MPS_t)$
	• BDC Exchange Rate with MPCl	$X_t = (GDP_t, INF_t, MS_t, BDC_t, MPCl_t)$
6	Asset Channel	
	• Without communication	$X_t = (GDP_t, INF_t, MS_t, ASI_t)$
	• With MPS	$X_t = (GDP_t, INF_t, MS_t, ASI_t, MPS_t)$
	• With MPCl	$X_t = (GDP_t, INF_t, MS_t, ASI_t, MPCl_t)$

Source: CBN 2010 Equations with modifications by Author

Variables description and sources

Table 5.4 describes the variables, their sources, and the justifications for including them in the equations. The following points are to be noted:

- a) Apart from the *MPS* and *MPCl*, all the other variables enter the equations in their log form. The reason for not taking the log of the *MPS* and *MPCl* is because they contain negative figures and log is only taken for positive integers.
- b) All the variables, apart from the *MPS* and *MPCl* were obtained from the CBN 2018 Statistical Bulletin. Getting data from limited sources improves reliability of data.
- c) The CBN 2018 Statistical Bulletin had some data in quarterly format and some as annual data. Because the *MPS* and *MPCl* are in quarterly format, the variables extracted in the annual form were calibrated into quarterly figures using E-views.

Table 5. 4: Variables and Definitions

Variable	Description	Source	Rationale
GDP	Gross Domestic Product at Current Basic Prices (₦ Bn)	CBN 2018 Statistical Bulletin	Provides the size of the economy
INF	Inflation (%)	CBN 2018 Statistical Bulletin	Price stability is the key mandate of the CBN.
MS	Money Supply (M2) Aggregates (₦ Bn)	CBN 2018 Statistical Bulletin	One of the most important variables in the monetary policy process.
MPR	Monetary Policy Rate (%)	CBN 2018 Statistical Bulletin	The nominal anchor that provides a gauge of how the official rate influences the system
IBR	Interbank Interest Rate (%)	CBN 2018 Statistical Bulletin	The rate at which the banks engage in money market transactions.
RIBR	Real Interbank Interest Rate (%)	Author's Calculation	Interbank Interest Rate adjusted for Inflation
CRD	Total Credit to the economy (₦ Bn)	CBN Website on 06-01-2019	Credit creation/contraction affects economic activities
EXC	Official Exchange Rate (₦/\$)	CBN Website on 06-01-2019	Nigeria gets the bulk of her revenues from export of crude oil
BDC	Unofficial exchange rate obtained on the street and licensed Bureau D' Changes (₦/\$)	CBN 2018 Statistical Bulletin	Due to restrictions to the official window, the unofficial window provides alternative access to FX
ASI	All Share Index	CBN 2018 Statistical Bulletin	Stock market provides avenue for medium-to long-term funds
MPS	Monetary Policy Stance	Developed by Author	Communication now an important tool in monetary policy
MPCI	Monetary Policy Communication on Inflation	Developed by Author	

*Apart from the MPS and the MPCI, the other indicators were calibrated into quarterly figures.

Estimation techniques

The process for choosing the estimation methods is depicted in figure 5.6 and explained as follows:

- a) If unit root test shows that all the variables are stationary at level, that is they are I (0) series, then the OLS and basic VAR methods can be used.
- b) If unit root is present, that is they are I (1) or I (2) series, the appropriate techniques are the Johansen and VECM and ARDL/Bounds Testing models.
- c) If there is no evidence of cointegration, the basic VAR is estimated. However, if there is sign of cointegration, the ECM can be estimated, and direction of causality ascertained.
- d) If there are I (0) and I (1) variables, the suitable method for cointegration is ARDL/Bounds testing, from which the ECM is estimated, and direction of causality established.

Figure 5. 6: Framework for Selecting Estimation Techniques

Source: Shrestha and Bhatta (2018)

Figure 5.7 shows that some of the variables exhibit stationarity and the others display some form of trend and cycles. While these charts provide an insight, the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test is used to ascertain the true unit root properties of the variables. Table 5.5 illustrates the test results and three of the variables are I (0) the others are I (1).

Figure 5. 7: Variables at their Original Levels

Table 5. 5: Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test

	Test Critical Values			ADF Statistic	Prob.	Order of Integration*
	1% Level	5% Level	10% Level			
GDP	-3.5332	-2.9062	-2.5906	1.2315	0.9981	I (1)
INF	-3.5348	-2.9069	-2.5910	-2.3197	0.1690	I (1)
MS	-3.5300	-2.9048	-2.5899	-1.4291	0.9990	I (1)
MPR	-3.5300	-2.9048	-2.5899	-2.6623	0.0859	I (1)
IBR	-3.5300	-2.9048	-2.5899	-1.5461	0.5497	I (1)
RIBR	-3.5348	-2.9069	-2.5910	-1.5422	0.5061	I (1)
CRD	-3.5300	-2.9048	-2.5899	0.6008	0.9888	I (1)
EXC	-3.5300	-2.9048	-2.5899	-0.1162	0.9648	I (1)
BDC	-3.5300	-2.9048	-2.5899	-0.5527	0.8734	I (1)
ASI	-3.5332	-2.9062	-2.5906	-3.3077	0.0184	I (0)
MPS	-3.5285	-2.9042	-2.5896	-5.7077	0.0000	I (0)
MPCI	-3.5300	-2.9048	-2.5899	-4.6514	0.0003	I (0)

Source: Author’s Calculations

*The I (1) variables became I (0) after the first differencing.

• *Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL)/Bounds Testing and Error Correction Model*

Given that the ADF test showed that the variables are I (0) and I (1), it implies that the Johansen method cannot be used to test for cointegration. Rather, the ARDL/Bounds testing method due to Pesaran *et al.* (2001) is applied. The basic ARDL regression model is of the form:

$$y_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 y_{t-1} + \dots + \beta_k y_{t-p} + \alpha_0 x_t + \alpha_1 x_{t-1} + \alpha_2 x_{t-2} + \dots + \alpha_q x_{t-q} + \varepsilon_t \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Where ε_t is a random disturbance term and assumed to be "well-behaved".

The process for estimating the ARDL/Bounds testing model is explained in figure 5.8 below:

Figure 5. 8: Steps for Estimating the ARDL/Bounds Testing Model

Source: Author’s Design

Equation 1 shows that the basic ARDL model is categorised by having lags of the dependent variable, as well as lags and current value of other variables as the regressors. Suppose there are three variables in the model, a dependent variable, y , and two other explanatory variables, x_1 and x_2 , then generally, there will be $(k + 1)$ variables - a dependent variable, and k other variables.

A *conventional* ECM is of the form:

$$\Delta y_t = \beta_0 + \sum \beta_i \Delta y_{t-i} + \sum \gamma_j \Delta x_{1t-j} + \sum \delta_k \Delta x_{2t-k} + \phi z_{t-1} + e_t \quad (2)$$

where z , the "error-correction term" is the residual from the long-run cointegrating regression:

$$y_t = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 x_{1t} + \alpha_2 x_{2t} + v_t \quad (3)$$

ADF test is used to check for no I(2) series before the model is formulated as follows:

$$\Delta y_t = \beta_0 + \sum \beta_i \Delta y_{t-i} + \sum \gamma_j \Delta x_{1t-j} + \sum \delta_k \Delta x_{2t-k} + \theta_0 y_{t-1} + \theta_1 x_{1t-1} + \theta_2 x_{2t-1} + e_t \quad (4)$$

Equation 4 is a normal ECM, but the modification is that the ECT z_{t-1} is replaced with the terms y_{t-1} , x_{1t-1} , and x_{2t-1} . From (3), the lagged residuals series would be $z_{t-1} = (y_{t-1} - \alpha_0 - \alpha_1 x_{1t-1} - \alpha_2 x_{2t-1})$, where the a 's are the OLS estimates of the α 's. Equation (4) thus includes the same lagged levels as in a regular ECM, but this time the coefficients are not restricted. The appropriate lags are select for p , q_1 , and q_2 using the information criteria AIC, SBIC and HQ.

A crucial assumption in the ARDL / Bounds Testing method is that the errors of equation (4) must be serially independent. Also, since the model is autoregressive, there is need to ascertain the stability as Pesaran (1997) contended that it is vital to establish the constancy of the long-run multipliers by testing for the stability of parameters. The generally used tests are the cumulative sum (CUSUM) and the cumulative sum of squares (CUSUMQ).

Performing the bounds test from equation 4 requires that an "*F-test*" of the hypothesis - $H_0: \theta_0 = \theta_1 = \theta_2 = 0$; against the alternative that H_0 is not true is carried out. As in traditional cointegration testing, what is being tested is the long-run equilibrium relationship among the variables. A rejection of the null hypothesis H_0 implies that there exists long-run relationship.

Pesaran *et al.* (2001) supplied bounds on the critical values for the asymptotic distribution of the F-statistic and they give lower and upper bounds on the critical values. The lower bound assumes that all the variables are I (0) and the upper bound assumes that all the variables are I (1) and the truth may be somewhere in between the two extremes.

The decision rules are as follows:

- a) If the computed *F-statistic* falls below the lower bound, we conclude that the variables are I (0), so no cointegration is possible.
- b) If the *F-statistic* exceeds the upper bound, we conclude that we have cointegration.
- c) If the *F-statistic* falls between the bounds, the test is inconclusive.

If the bounds test leads to the conclusion of cointegration, then the long-run equilibrium relationship can be estimated among the variables:

$$y_t = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 X_{1t} + \alpha_2 X_{2t} + v_t \quad (5)$$

as well as the usual ECM:

$$\Delta y_t = \beta_0 + \sum \beta_i \Delta y_{t-i} + \sum \gamma_j \Delta x_{1t-j} + \sum \delta_k \Delta x_{2t-k} + \phi z_{t-1} + e_t \quad (6)$$

where $z_{t-1} = (y_{t-1} - \alpha_0 - \alpha_1 X_{1t-1} - \alpha_2 X_{2t-1})$, and the α 's are the OLS estimates of the α 's in (5).

The long-run effects can then be extracted from the unrestricted ECM.

Overall, the advantages of the ARDL/Bounds testing approach to cointegration over the traditional Johansen and Engle-Granger methods are as follows:

- a) It provides better results for small sample data set.
- b) The unrestricted ECM takes satisfactory lags that captures the data generating process in a general-to-specific framework of specification.
- c) It avoids the classification of variables as I (1) and I (0) by developing bands of critical values which identifies the variables as being stationary or non-stationary processes.
- d) Provides an alternative test for examining a long-run relationship regardless of whether the underlying variables are purely I (0) or I (1).
- e) While the traditional cointegration methods may suffer from endogeneity, the ARDL/Bounds testing method distinguishes between dependent and explanatory variables and the estimates are unbiased and efficient since they avoid the problems that may arise in the presence serial correlation and endogeneity.

- *Granger-Causality*

The ARDL/Bounds testing provides information on whether there is cointegration among the variables. If cointegration exists, then causality is present in at least one direction, and for this

purpose, this study applies the Granger causality to establish the direction of causality. For example, should our communication variable *MPCI* granger-causes *Inflation*, it means that the past values of *MPCI* contains evidence that helps forecast *Inflation*.

The Granger causality test augmented by ECT allows testing for short-run causality through the lagged differenced explanatory variables and for long-run causality through the lagged ECM_{t-1} term. A statistically significant ECM_{t-1} term implies long-run causality running from all the explanatory variables to the dependent variable.

- *Diagnostics tests*

The robustness of the results is carried out by conducting different diagnostic tests. It is important to note that the mostly conducted diagnostic tests are *lag structure*, *coefficient diagnostics* and *residual diagnostics*. However, residual tests are the most important because regression models attempt to minimize errors (or residuals). The error terms must be white noise (independently and identically distributed, i.i.d.) and residual diagnostics examine whether they are i.i.d. The stability test scrutinizes whether the parameters are stable across various sub-samples of the data.

5.3.3 Discussion of results

The ARDL/Bounds Testing for Cointegration

The detailed results of the estimated models are presented in Parts A-F in Appendix 4 while the synopses are shown in this sub-section. The summary of the outcomes for the ARDL/Bounds testing for cointegration are depicted in table 5.6. The selected models were estimated using lag lengths indicated by the lowest AIC.

Applying the *Nayaran 2005 critical values*, the bounds testing outcomes specify that there is evidence of cointegration in all the models as the *F-statistics* are higher than the upper bound limits at 5% critical values, except for two equations, *Real Interest Rate with MPC* and *Asset Channel with MPS*, at 10% critical value.

Table 5. 6: ARDL/Bounds Testing Cointegration Test Results

	Model	Lag Length for Est.	k	n	F-Statistic
1	Baseline model	3	2	70	9.278
2	Augmented baseline				
	• With MPS	3	3	70	5.609
	• With MPCl	3	3	70	6.440
3	Interest Rate Channel				
	• Nominal Interest Rate without MPS and MPCl	4	4	70	5.562
	• Nominal Interest Rate with MPS	3	5	70	5.285
	• Nominal Interest Rate with MPCl	4	5	70	5.269
	• Real Interest Rate without MPS and MPCl	3	4	70	5.164
	• Real Interest Rate with MPS	3	5	70	7.049
	• Real Interest Rate with MPCl*	3	5	70	3.866
4	Credit Channel				
	• Without MPC and MPCl	3	3	70	9.409
	• With MPS	3	4	70	6.508
	• With MPCl	3	4	70	6.908
5	Exchange Rate Channel				
	• Official Exchange Rate without MPS and MPCl	3	3	70	7.722
	• Official Exchange Rate with MPS	4	4		6.179
	• Official Exchange Rate with MPCl	3	4	70	5.926
	• BDC Exchange Rate without MPS and MPCl	4	3	70	6.678
	• BDC Exchange Rate with MPS	4	4	70	5.549
	• BDC Exchange Rate with MPCl	3	4	70	5.347
6	Asset Channel				
	• Without MPS and MPCl	4	3	70	4.932
	• With MPS*	4	4	70	3.793
	• With MPCl	3	4	70	4.557
	Nayaran 2005 Critical Values	Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
K=2	1%	5.487	6.880		
	5%	3.947	5.020		
	10%	3.250	4.237		
K=3	1%	4.635	6.055		
	5%	3.370	4.545		
	10%	2.818	3.880		
K=4	1%	4.098	5.570		
	5%	3.022	4.256		
	10%	2.552	3.648		
K=5	1%	3.747	5.285		
	5%	2.788	4.073		
	10%	2.363	3.510		

Source: Author's Computations

* *F-statistics* are higher than the upper bound limits at 10% Narayan 2005 critical values.

Error Correction and Long-run Causality

Having established that cointegration exist in the equations, the Error Correction Models (ECMs) were estimated and used to determine the speed of adjustments and the long-run and short-run causality. The summary of the results as shown in table 5.7 indicates that the coefficients of the Error Correction Terms (ECTs) are negative and significant, implying long-run causality.

The low values of the ECTs however indicate that the speed of adjustment is very slow in all the models, both without and with communication. This suggests that communication did not improve the transmission of monetary policy in Nigeria in the period reviewed. Given that the fundamental goal of central bank communication is to manage expectations, the inference is that the results reinforce the findings of CBN's research department in 2010 that found weak existence of monetary policy transmission through the inflation expectations channel.

Although the speed of adjustment is very slow in all the models, those with MPCCI that focus on inflation communication performed relatively better than the ones with MPS that consider the tightening, neutral and loosening stance based on the multiple objectives and tools. This supports the view by Hosny and Sullivan (2018) that the transmission of monetary policy in Nigeria is weak because of the multiple objectives and instruments that send conflicting signals to the markets.

Specifically, the results presented in table 5.7 are summarized as follows:

a) Baseline and Augmented Baseline Models

- i. The baseline model reverts to equilibrium at a pace of about 11.3%.
- ii. The augmented baseline model with MPCCI reverts at approximately 11.4% and that with MPS at a relatively slower pace of 10.2%.
- iii. The implication is that communication with MPS weakens the transmission process as CBN tightens or eases with multiple tools that send mixed signals to the markets.

b) Credit Channel

- i. The model without communication reverts to equilibrium at about 11.8%.
- ii. The model with MPCCI also reverts at about 11.8% but that with MPS at 10.9%.
- iii. The suggestion is that while communication did not enhance transmission in the credit channel when MPCCI is considered, it was impaired with MPS, suggesting again that CBN's tightening or easing postures with multiple instruments send mixed signals.

c) Exchange Rate Channel

- i. The model with official exchange rate without communication reverts at around 11.2%, that with MPCCI also at 11.2% and that with MPS at 9.3%.
- ii. The model with the BDC exchange rate without communication reverts at 10.8%, that with MPCCI at 11.3% and that with MPS at 9.8%.
- iii. The results imply that communication slightly improved transmission in the exchange rate channel with BDC rate when MPCCI is used but weakened with MPS. This again indicates that transmission is relatively weaker when CBN's tightening and easing stance are considered compared to specific communication about inflation.

d) Asset Channel

- i. The model without communication reverts at 9.7%
- ii. The model with MPCCI returns at 12.9% and with MPS at a slower pace of 9.3%.
- iii. The inference is that communication with MPCCI improved transmission slightly in the asset channel while with MPS it weakened transmission.

e) Interest Rate Channel

- i. The model with nominal interest rate without communication reverts at 8.4%, that with MPCCI also at 8.4% and with MPS at 9.4%.
- ii. The model with real interest rate without communication returns at 9.3%, that MPCCI at 9.5% and with MPS at 9.3%
- iii. The effect is that communication with MPS marginally improved transmission in the interest rate channel when nominal rate is considered and almost neutral with real rate.

Table 5. 7: Error Correction and Long-run Causality

	Model	ECT	Std. Error	t-statistic	Prob.
1	Baseline model	-0.1132	0.0245	-4.6082	0.0000
2	Augmented baseline				
	• With MPS	-0.1023	0.0276	-3.7016	0.0005
	• With MPCCI	-0.1138	0.0254	-4.4705	0.0000
3	Credit Channel				
	• Without communication	-0.1184	0.0250	-4.7391	0.0000
	• With MPS	-0.1092	0.0287	-3.8047	0.0004
	• With MPCCI	-0.1182	0.0260	-4.5467	0.0000
4	Exchange Rate Channel				
	• Official Exchange Rate without communication	-0.1121	0.0254	-4.4118	0.0001
	• Official Exchange Rate with MPS	-0.0926	0.0366	-2.5306	0.0151
	• Official Exchange Rate with MPCCI	-0.1122	0.0266	-4.2179	0.0001

	• BDC Exchange Rate without communication	-0.1079	0.0332	-3.2428	0.0022
	• BDC Exchange Rate with MPS	-0.0981	0.0371	-2.6399	0.0115
	• BDC Exchange Rate with MPCl	-0.1134	0.0280	-4.0516	0.0002
5	Asset Channel				
	• Without communication	-0.0968	0.0331	-2.9226	0.0053
	• With MPS	-0.0932	0.0389	-2.3938	0.0211
	• With MPCl	-0.1287	0.0308	-4.1726	0.0001
6	Interest Rate Channel				
	• Nominal Interest Rate without communication	-0.0838	0.0432	-1.9386	0.0591
	• Nominal Interest Rate with MPS	-0.0942	0.0314	-2.9950	0.0044
	• Nominal Interest Rate with MPCl	-0.0842	0.0471	-1.7849	0.0820
	• Real Interest Rate without communication	-0.0926	0.0319	-2.8991	0.0060
	• Real Interest Rate with MPS	-0.0925	0.0334	-2.7621	0.0089
	• Real Interest Rate with MPCl	-0.0949	0.0327	-2.8939	0.0063

Source: Author's Estimates

A further breakdown of the results as shown in table 5.8 indicates that:

- In the models without communication, the speed of adjustment is relatively faster in the credit channel, followed by the exchange rate model with official rate, while the interest rate channel with the nominal rate reverts slowest to equilibrium. This mirrors slightly CBN 2010 that found the credit and exchange rate channels to be the dominant channels of transmission in Nigeria.
- In the models with MPS, the credit channel also reverts relatively fastest to equilibrium followed by the augmented baseline model, the exchange rate model with the BDC exchange rate, while in the model with real interest rate reverts slowest to equilibrium.
- In the models with MPCl, the asset channel returns relatively faster to equilibrium, followed by the credit channel, the augmented baseline model, while the interest rate model with the nominal rate returns most sluggishly to equilibrium.

Table 5.8: Ranking of Models without Communication and with Communication

Models without Communication		Models with MPS		Models with MPCl	
Model	ECT	Model	ECT	Model	ECT
Credit	-0.1185	Credit	-0.1092	Asset	-0.1287
Official Exc. Rate	-0.1121	Augmented baseline	-0.1023	Credit	-0.1182
BDC Exc. Rate	-0.1079	BDC Exc. Rate	-0.0981	Augmented baseline	-0.1138
Asset	-0.0968	Nominal Interest Rate	-0.0942	BDC Exc. Rate	-0.1134
Real Interest Rate	-0.0926	Asset	-0.0932	Official Exc. Rate	-0.1122
Nominal Interest Rate	-0.0838	Official Exc. Rate	-0.0926	Real Interest Rate	-0.0949
		Real Interest Rate	-0.0925	Nominal Interest Rate	-0.0842

Source: Author's Estimates

The ranking of all the models with the communication indicators, MPS and MPCl, is shown in table 5.9. The effect of communication is highest in the asset channel with MPCl, followed by the credit channel with MPCl and then the augmented model with MPCl. The exchange rate channel with the BDC rate and MPCl, and that with the official rate with MPCl are next.

Table 5. 9: Ranking of Models with Communication

		ECT	P-value
1	Asset with MPCl	-0.1287	0.0001
2	Credit with MPCl	-0.1182	0.0000
3	Augmented with MPCl	-0.1138	0.0000
4	BDC Exchange Rate with MPCl	-0.1134	0.0002
5	Official Exchange Rate with MPCl	-0.1122	0.0001
6	Credit with MPS	-0.1092	0.0004
7	Augmented baseline with MPS	-0.1023	0.0005
8	BDC Exchange Rate with MPS	-0.0981	0.0115
9	Real Interest Rate with MPCl	-0.0949	0.0063
10	Nominal Interest Rate with MPS	-0.0942	0.0044
11	Asset with MPS	-0.0932	0.0211
12	Official Exchange Rate with MPS	-0.0926	0.0151
13	Real Interest Rate with MPS	-0.0925	0.0089
14	Nominal Interest Rate with MPCl	-0.0842	0.0820

Source: Author's Estimates

Given that the top models are those with MPCl, it suggests that communication about inflation have relatively higher effects on the transmission of monetary policy when compared with the overall communication about the different policy objectives of the CBN. The findings thus strengthen the hypothesis that because the CBN deals with multiple objectives and uses different policy instruments to achieve them, communicating the policy stance by way of tightening or easing, often results in mixed signals that impair the transmission of policy. However, because of the primacy of the inflation objective, communication about inflation as reflected in the MPCl is less confusing, hence its comparatively better effect on the transmission process.

Short-run Causality

The results of the short-run causality in table 5.10 are summarized as follows:

- a) MS granger-causes GDP and Inflation; there is bi-directional causality between MPCl and inflation; and MPS granger-causes GDP.

- b) In the credit channel, CRD granger-causes GDP; INF granger-causes CRD; and CRD granger-causes MS.
- c) In the asset channel, MPS granger-causes ASI.
- d) Interest Rate Channel - bidirectional causality between GDP and RIBR; MPR and MS granger-cause GDP; MS and MPC I granger-cause RIBR and MPR granger-cause MPS.

Overall, the short-run causality results underpin the importance that the CBN attaches to monetary targeting given that money supply granger-causes GDP and inflation. Also, the CBN’s tightening and easing postures as captured in the MPS is important for short-run macroeconomic management given that the MPS granger-causes GDP.

Table 5. 10: Short-run Granger Causality

Baseline	Augmented Baseline	Interest Rate Channel	Credit Channel	Exchange Rate Channel	Asset Channel
Money Supply Granger-Causes GDP					
Money Supply Granger-Causes Inflation					
	MPCI Granger-causes INF				
	INF Granger-causes MPC I				
	MPS Granger-Causes GDP				
		GDP Granger-Causes IBR	CRD Granger-Causes GDP		MPS Granger-Causes ASI
		MPR Granger-Causes GDP	INF Granger-Causes CRD		
		MS Granger-Causes IBR	CRD Granger-Causes MS		
		RIBR Granger-Causes GDP			
		GDP Granger-Causes RIBR			
		MS Granger-Causes RIBR			
		MPR Granger-Causes MPS			
		MPCI Granger-Causes RIBR			

Source: Based on Author’s Computations

Diagnostic tests

Residual diagnostic tests were conducted to ascertain the validity of the results in the different models. Table 5.11 shows that none of the models violated the serial correlation assumption while the CUSUM lines as indicated in the different figures in Appendix 4 show that the models are stable as the lines are in between the 5% significance lines.

Table 5. 11: Residual Diagnostic Tests

<i>Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test</i>			
		F-statistic	Prob.
1	Baseline model	0.1295	0.8788
2	Augmented baseline		
	• With MPS	0.3040	0.7392
	• With MPCl	0.1229	0.8845
3	Interest Rate Channel		
	• Nominal Interest Rate without communication	1.7058	0.1942
	• Nominal Interest Rate with MPS	0.9427	0.3973
	• Nominal Interest Rate with MPCl	1.2662	0.2938
	• Real Interest Rate without MPC and MPCl	2.0709	0.1401
	• Real Interest Rate with MPS	1.8569	0.1712
	• Real Interest Rate with MPCl	1.8625	0.1703
4	Credit Channel		
	• Without communication	0.3717	0.6914
	• With MPS	0.7187	0.4926
	• With MPCl	0.2561	0.7751
5	Exchange Rate Channel		
	• Official Exchange Rate without communication	0.0374	0.9632
	• Official Exchange Rate with MPS	0.2115	0.8102
	• Official Exchange Rate with MPCl	0.0014	0.9986
	• BDC Exchange Rate without communication	0.4361	0.6492
	• BDC Exchange Rate with MPS	0.1263	0.8816
	• BDC Exchange Rate with MPCl	0.0288	0.9716
6	Asset Channel		
	• Without communication	0.0820	0.9214
	• With MPS	0.0299	0.9705
	• With MPCl	0.0824	0.9210

Source: Based on Author's Computations

5.4. Summary

The chapter quantified the communication of the CBN using the heuristic approach to design two indicators, the MPS and MPCl. While the MPS, which takes into consideration the multiple objectives and instruments of the CBN was developed in line with the conventional method of coding tightening (+1), hold (0) and loosening (-1) postures used by Ehrmann and Fratzscher (2007), Jansen and De Haan (2009) and Lehtimäki and Palmu (2019), the MPCl is mainly about

communication of upside, downside and neutral risks to inflation based on the approach of the ECB KOF Monetary Policy Communicator.

The empirical analysis followed Neuenkirch (2013) that estimated the monetary policy transmission of the ECB by adding the ECB KOF Communicator to the traditional variables in a VAR framework. Also, the study by CBN's research department in 2010 on monetary policy transmission in Nigeria provided guide in terms of the equations estimated, which were augmented with the MPS and MPCPI. The goal is to ascertain the effect of communication, whether in the form of MPS or MPCPI, on the transmission mechanism in Nigeria. Another study that provided direction for estimation is Hosny and Sullivan (2018) where the BDC exchange rate was incorporated in an exchange rate equation and result compared with the equation with the official exchange rate.

The estimations were carried out using the ARDL/Bounds testing approach to cointegration and the ECMs where the coefficients showed the speed of adjustment to equilibrium as well as long-run and short-run causality. The rationale for applying the ARDL/Bounds testing method is because the ADF test for unit root showed that the variables were a mixture of I(0) and I(1). This automatically invalids the use of the conventional Johansen test for cointegration.

The estimated equations were: (1) a baseline model; (2) an augmented baseline model with MPS and MPCPI separately; (3) six equations in the interest rate channel - first, the nominal interest rate equation without communication, with MPS and then with MPCPI. Second, the real interest rate equation without communication, with MPS and with MPCPI; (4) three equations in the credit channel - that without communication, with MPS and then with MPCPI; (5) six equations for the exchange rate channel - first, the official exchange rate without communication, with MPS and then with MPCPI. Second, the BDC exchange rate equation without communication, with MPS and with MPCPI; (6) three equations in the asset channel - the equation without communication, followed by that with MPS and then with MPCPI.

The findings from the descriptive analysis of the MPS showed that the CBN between 2001 and 2018 tightened its stance in 26 or 37% of the communiqués using a combination of the policy rate, OMO sales, CRR and sometimes foreign exchange interventions and withdrawal of public sector funds from commercial banks when government institutions were still allowed to deposit with them. The easing stance was observed in 11 or 16% and neutral stance in 33 or 47% of the

communiqués. In terms of communication about inflation, the average MPCl of 0.135 for all the communiqués indicated that the CBN communicated more about upside risk to inflation between 2001 and 2018.

The correlation between the MPCl and the voting pattern of the members of CBN's monetary policy committee showed a positive but weak relationship between voting to increase the policy rate and the MPCl. This suggests that, apart from the policy rate, the CBN also uses other policy instruments like the OMO and CRR to manage liquidity and so inflation in the short-term.

Another inference from the graphical illustration is that a paradox was observed between the movement in the policy rate and the MPCl. This is because the upside risk sentiments coincided with decreasing or flattening policy rate and the following reasons were attributed for the contradiction:

- a) Given the multiple policy objectives and instruments, the CBN sometimes alter the other tools like the OMO and CRR, etc. to manage inflation in the short-term instead of raising the policy rate. Thus, in the periods where the policy rates were unchanged when the CBN expressed upside risk to inflation sentiments, the other instruments may have been adjusted to tighten liquidity.
- b) It could be that the CBN saw the inflationary threats as temporary in those periods that it expressed upside risk to inflation sentiments and decided to remain neutral on policy change on those occasions.
- c) The CBN implicitly targets inflation at between 6-9%. Thus, in some periods where upside risk to inflation sentiments were expressed, the bank may have decided to remain neutral if it sees inflation not crossing its upper target limit of 9%.
- d) The official policy rate is the most visible monetary policy tool to the politicians who see raising rates as undermining their preference for economic growth. As such, for some of the periods that the CBN expressed upside risk to inflation sentiments, it may have, for political reasons, adjusted other policy instruments like the OMO and CRR instead of raising the policy rate.

The summary of the empirical results are as follows:

- a) The ARDL/Bounds testing method confirmed cointegration in all the equations.

- b) The ECTs are negative and significant, implying the presence of long-run causality.
- c) The low values of the ECTs indicate that the speed of adjustment back to equilibrium is very slow in all the models, suggesting that communication did not improve the transmission of monetary policy in Nigeria in the period reviewed. Given that the fundamental goal of central bank communication is to manage expectations, the inference from the result is that it reinforces the findings of CBN's research department in 2010 that found weak existence of policy transmission through the inflation expectations channel.
- d) The models with MPCCI performed relatively better than the ones with MPS that considers the tightening, loosening or hold stance of the CBN in line with the multiple objectives and instruments. This strengthens the view by Hosny and Sullivan (2018) that the transmission of monetary policy in Nigeria is weak because of the multiple objectives and instruments that send conflicting signals to the markets.
- e) In the augmented baseline model, communication with MPS weakens the transmission process compared with MPCCI. This suggests that CBN's tightening or loosening with multiple tools sends mixed signals.
- f) In the credit channel, the model with MPS also reverts more sluggishly to equilibrium compared with the model without communication and with MPCCI. This also indicates that the multiplicity of tools impairs the transmission process.
- g) In the exchange rate channel, communication slightly improved transmission with BDC rate and MPCCI but weakened with MPS. This indicates that transmission is weaker when CBN's tightening and easing stance are considered compared with talk about inflation.
- h) In the asset channel, communication with MPCCI improved the transmission process compared with MPS that weakened transmission.
- i) In the interest rate channel, communication with MPS marginally improved transmission of policy when nominal rate is considered, and neutral with real interest rate.
- j) The ranking of all the models with both MPS and MPCCI showed that the effect of communication is relatively highest in the asset channel with MPCCI, followed by the credit channel with MPCCI and then the augmented model with MPCCI. The exchange rate channel with the BDC rate and MPCCI, and that with the official rate with MPCCI were next.

- k) Given that the top models are those with MPCl, it suggests that communication about inflation have relatively better effect on the transmission of monetary policy when compared with the overall policy communication of multiple objectives.
- l) The findings strengthen the hypothesis that because the CBN deals with multiple objectives and uses different policy instruments to achieve them, communicating the policy stance by way of tightening, neutral or easing, often results in mixed signals that impair the transmission of policy. However, because of the primacy of the inflation objective, communication about inflation as reflected in the MPCl is less confusing, hence its relatively better effect on the transmission process.

The results of the short-run causality are as follows:

- a) MS granger-causes GDP and Inflation; there is bi-directional causality between MPCl and inflation; and MPS granger-causes GDP.
- b) In the credit channel, CRD granger-causes GDP; INF granger-causes CRD; and CRD granger-causes MS.
- c) In the asset channel, MPS granger-causes ASI.
- d) Interest Rate Channel - bidirectional causality between GDP and RIBR; MPR and MS granger-cause GDP; MS and MPCl granger-cause RIBR and MPR granger-cause MPS.

Overall, the short-run causality results underpin the importance that the CBN attaches to monetary targeting given that money supply granger-causes GDP and inflation. Also, the CBN's tightening and easing postures as captured in the MPS is important for short-run macroeconomic management given that the MPS granger-causes GDP.

Residual diagnostic tests were conducted to ascertain the validity of the results in the different models. None of the models violated the serial correlation assumption while the CUSUM stability test showed that all the models are stable as the blue lines are in between the 5% significance lines.

CHAPTER SIX: Analyzing Communication about Fiscal Policy

'Central banks are often accused of being obsessed with inflation. This is untrue. If they are obsessed with anything, it is with fiscal policy.' **King (1995:71)**

6.1 Introduction

Fiscal policy is the use of government tax and expenditure tools to impact the level of economic activities. Like monetary policy, it is very crucial in the overall macroeconomic management in any country. In taking monetary policy decisions and projecting to the future, central banks consider wide ranging issues including domestic fiscal policy as well as those of other countries. For example, fiscal deficit as well as the financing mode(s) is often of interest to central banks due to the implications for monetary policy.

Allusions to fiscal policy by a central bank is not limited to domestic events, but also of other countries, especially those with huge trading and financial volumes with the country in question. Similarly, references to fiscal policy are made on the background of the execution of monetary policy, for example if bonds are bought or sold. Another reason why fiscal policy is vital as an input to central bank decision making is because it is the key macroeconomic policy that, together with monetary policy, determines the general economic policy in a country.

Measuring the intensity with which central banks communicate about fiscal policy is an emerging aspect of the literature. The objective of this chapter is therefore to contribute to this evolving area by quantifying the intensity with which the CBN discussed fiscal policy in its monetary policy communiqués between 2001 and 2018. To this end, a *Fiscal Policy Communication Indicator* (FPCI) is developed and how it is influenced by subjects in the broader economy ascertained. In other words, the main topic that emanates from this is to examine the magnitude with which the intensity of CBN's communication about fiscal policy is affected by changes in key macroeconomic variables.

The rest of the chapter is structured as follows: The evolving literature on central bank communication about fiscal policy is discussed, followed by an explanation of the data, method, and estimation techniques. The results are subsequently presented, while the last part summarizes and concludes the chapter.

6.2 Literature on central bank communication on fiscal policy

The literature on central bank communication is dominated by works that ascertain the predictability of monetary policy outcomes. The main attempt so far at quantifying fiscal policy communication by central banks is Allard *et al.* (2013) that evaluated the issue for five central banks (FED, ECB, BOE, BoJ, and Swedish Riksbank) over the period 1999-2011. The study developed a fiscal indicator gauging the fiscal-related communication in records or statements of the banks by categorizing fiscal statements as shown in figure 6.1 below:

Figure 6. 1: Classification of Fiscal Policy Statements

Source: Allard *et al.* (2013)

Allard *et al.* (2013) showed that the ECB communicated intensely about fiscal policy in both positive and normative terms, while the other central banks typically referred to fiscal policy when describing overseas developments, using fiscal policy as input to forecasts, or when referring to the use of government debt instruments in monetary policy operations.

Econometrically, the study estimated the multiple regression equation as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Fiscal Policy Index} = & \alpha_0 \cdot \text{Intercept} + \alpha_1 \cdot \text{Index}_{-4} + \alpha_2 \cdot \Delta \text{Budget} + \alpha_3 \cdot \Delta \text{Debt} + \alpha_4 \cdot D_{\text{crisis}} + \alpha_5 \cdot \\
 & \Delta \text{Budget} \cdot D_{\text{crisis}} + \alpha_6 \cdot \Delta \text{Debt} \cdot D_{\text{crisis}} + \alpha_7 \cdot \text{ABS} (\text{Inflation} - 2\%) + \alpha_8 \cdot \text{ABS} (\text{Output gap}) + \alpha_9 \cdot \text{ABS} \\
 & (\Delta R_{\text{off}}) + \alpha_{10} \cdot \Delta \cdot \text{Exchange rate}
 \end{aligned}$$

The regression was estimated using the OLS ‘general-to-specific’ approach and found amongst others, that the state of public finances (captured by change in the budget balance ratio and change in the debt ratio) played a role in setting the length of the fiscal part of central bank

minutes or introductory statements. In addition, the financial crisis also increased the intensity of fiscal policy communication by the central banks.

Some studies have also investigated fiscal policy discussions, though not directly in the context of central bank communication, but from other perspectives that explain that central banks are interested in fiscal policy matters. Exploring from an expectations point of view, Montes and Acar (2018) used market expectations conveyed by the Bank of Brazil to build a fiscal credibility index while scrutinizing the effect of the index on the disagreement in expectations about inflation. Their results suggested that fiscal credibility is important for reducing the disagreement in expectations about inflation, implying that since fiscal credibility reduces disagreement in expectations, it thus helps in the process of anchoring inflation expectations, providing better results for the inflation targeting central banks.

Montes *et al.* (2019) analyzed the effects of fiscal communication and clarity of announcements about fiscal policy on public debt uncertainty. Using different econometric techniques, the results showed that the provision of more information must be accompanied by improvements in the clarity of the announcements released. They concluded that as the clarity of fiscal announcements increases, the stronger is the effect of improvements in communication from fiscal authority in reducing public debt uncertainty; and this effect is stronger when public debt uncertainty is higher. The impact on monetary policy and central bank communication is positive.

An earlier study by Moser-Boehm (2006) argued that central bank communication on fiscal fluctuations is sometimes demand-driven. The central bank may be required by law or at the request of national parliament to comment either in their role as the country's monetary authority or as an independent adviser. Using survey data and quantitative statistical analysis, the results suggested that in cases where central banks in industrialized countries comment on government's budgets, they do so because they are obliged in 10% of all cases, in 80% they choose to comment and in 10% they choose not to comment. Furthermore, fiscal policy is one of the subjects of high-level meetings between the central bank and the government in more than 40% of the meetings amongst industrialized countries.

Because the literature on central bank communication about fiscal policy is still emerging as indicated in the short literature review, this study provides evidence for Nigeria. The next subsection explains the approach to measuring fiscal policy communication by the CBN.

6.3 Methodology and data

6.3.1 Quantifying fiscal policy communication.

As shown in figure 6.2, Allard *et al.* (2013) classified statements containing fiscal elements into *Positive statements*; *Normative statements*; *References to fiscal policy as an input or outcome of central bank forecast*; *References to government financing instruments*; *References to fiscal policies of other countries*; and *Remarks by government representatives on fiscal policy issues*. The definitions and examples of each of the categories are provided in Table 1 of Appendix 5. After categorizing the identified fiscal statements, the number of words in each category and for each month was counted. Outcomes were normalized to account for the overall size of the minutes/introductory statements and its evolution overtime, by dividing word counts by the total number of words contained in the relevant minutes/introductory statements.

Figure 6. 2: Framework for Developing Fiscal Policy Communication Indicator

Source: Allard *et al.* (2013)

In applying the approach by Allard *et al.* (2013) to quantify fiscal policy communication by the CBN, a template as shown in table 6.1 was designed. Sentences in each of the communiqués were extracted according to the subject matter being discussed and entered in Panel A of the template, and the different categories of fiscal statements identified. Any statement on fiscal policy in the highlighted sentences are entered as 'Yes' in Panels B - F as follows:

- a) If a comment is about *positive statement*, we reflect ‘Yes’ in Panel B and ‘No’ in Panels C-F.
- b) If a comment is about *normative*, we reflect ‘Yes’ in Panel C and ‘No’ in Panels B and D-F.
- c) If a comment makes *references to fiscal policy as an input of central bank forecasts*, we reflect ‘Yes’ in Panel D and ‘No’ in Panels B, C, E and F.
- d) If any comment is about *government financing instruments*, we reflect ‘Yes’ in Panel E and ‘No’ in Panels B, C, D and F.
- e) If any comment is about *fiscal policies in other countries*, we reflect ‘Yes’ in Panel F and ‘No’ in Panels B, C, D and E.

Panel G provides the summary of the categorization of the fiscal policy comments by stating the number of statements in each category, the number of words in that category and then the scale relative to the total word count of the communique. For example, if the number of comments on positive statements in a communique is three, and the number of words used in those three statements are 120, and assuming the total word count of the communique is 450, then the scale of positive statements relative to the total words is $120/450$ which is equal to 26.7%.

Table 6. 1: Template for Measuring CBN’s Discussions of Fiscal Policy

	A: Sentence	B: Does the highlighted statement(s) reflect positive statement on domestic fiscal policy as an element taken into account by the central bank when assessing the monetary policy stance?	C: Does the highlighted statement(s) reflect a normative statement calling on the government to take some defined action?	D: Does the highlighted statement(s) reflect a forecast or references to fiscal policy as an input to or outcome of central bank forecasts?	E: Does the highlighted statement(s) refer to monetary policy instrument: references to government financing instruments (government bonds, bills, deposits) in the context of the implementation of monetary policy?	F: Does the highlighted statement(s) make reference to fiscal policies in other countries : references to foreign fiscal policies in the macroeconomic and financial outlook?
1						
2						
3						
4						
5						
Total Number of Statements		0	0	0	0	0
G: Summary						
		Number of Statements in each category	Number of words in each category	Scale relative to total word count of communique		
1	Total number of statements that reveal positive statements on domestic fiscal policy as an element taken into account by the central bank when assessing the monetary policy stance	0	0	0	Total number of words capturing fiscal policy discussions relative to the total word count of the communique.	
2	Total number of statements that reveal normative element - calling on the government to take some defined action	0	0	0		
3	Total number of statements that reveal forecast or make references to fiscal policy as an input to or outcome of central bank forecasts.	0	0	0		
4	Total number of statements that reveal monetary policy instrument - references to government financing instruments (government bonds, bills, deposits) in the context of the implementation of monetary policy.	0	0	0		
5	Total number of statements that reveal fiscal policies in other countries: references to foreign fiscal policies in the macroeconomic and financial outlook	0	0	0		
FPCI Indicator				0		

Author

Tables 2 – 5 in Appendix 5 show how the designed template was used to quantify the communication of fiscal policy by the CBN. In table 2 using *Communique No. 1* the CBN only communicated about fiscal policy as an input to, or outcome of its forecasts in two statements using a total of 96 words. With the word count of the communique totaling 656, it means that the scale of fiscal policy communication relative to the whole communique is 14.6%.

For *Communique No. 68* as indicated in table 3, the CBN made one *normative statement* and used 59 words to explain it, made two *statements concerning government financing instruments (government bonds, bills, deposits)* and used 106 words, and then used two statements and 59 words to refer to the *fiscal policy of other countries*. In all, the CBN used a total of five statements and 224 words to explain fiscal policy issues in communique No. 68. When scaled relative to the total communique word count of 2,558, it means that the CBN used 8.7% of the contents of the communique to discuss fiscal policy.

Table 4 shows the extent to which the CBN discussed fiscal policy in *Communique No. 121*. With a total word count of 2,364, the CBN used one statement and 34 words to talk about positive issues where it commended the Government for taking certain measures. Furthermore, the bank used one statement and 117 words to make normative calls, advising the Government to embark on certain actions. References to fiscal policy as an input to or outcome of central bank forecasts was made in four statements using 328 words, while one statement and 35 words were used to talk about government financing instruments. Finally, one statement and 26 words were used to refer to the fiscal policy in other countries. In all, a total of eight statements and 540 words were used to discuss fiscal policy in *Communique No. 121*. When put in context of the total communique, the CBN used 22.8% of the contents of the communique to discuss fiscal policy.

Table 5 shows the overall pattern of fiscal policy discussions by the CBN between 2001 and 2018. A total of 51 statements and 2,812 words were used to discuss *positive statements*, resulting in an average of 1.8% of all total word count of the 113 communiqués in the period. The deliberations on *normative fiscal policy statements* saw the CBN using a total of 76 statements and 4,141 words, resulting in an average of 1.9% of the total word count of all the communiqués.

The reference to *fiscal policy as an input to or outcome of central bank forecasts* saw the CBN using 136 statements and 7,439 words to discuss the matter, implying that an average of 4.5% of

the total word count of all the communiqués was used to talk about it. In referring to *government financing instruments (bonds and treasury bills)*, the CBN used 99 statements and 3,425 words, or average 2.6% of total word count of all the communiqués to discuss the matter. Finally, the CBN used 47 statements and 2,376 words, or average 0.8% of total word count of the communiqués to refer to *fiscal policies in other countries*. Overall, the CBN used 409 statements and 20,193 words or average 11.8% of total word count to discuss different categories of fiscal policy statements.

Figures A – R in Appendix 5 show the pattern of CBN’s communication about the different aspects of fiscal policy between 2001 and 2018. However, figure 6.3 below illustrates that the CBN communicated more positively about fiscal policy between 2004 and 2005 when the oil-price based fiscal rule, meant to limit fiscal dominance and procyclicality, was introduced. The change towards the creation of the SWF in 2011 resulted in more normative fiscal policy statements as shown in figure 6.4 as the CBN’s posture changed from commendation to advisory.

Overall, communication about fiscal policy, especially in normative and positive terms, as reflected in the FPCI and depicted in figure 6.5, increased in the period of the oil-price based fiscal rule and the creation of the SWF. This aligns with the findings of Allard *et al.* (2013) that showed that the ECB communicated intensely about fiscal policy in both positive and normative terms.

Figure 6. 3: Positive Fiscal Policy Statements by the CBN

Source: Author's Plot

Figure 6. 4: Normative Fiscal Policy Statements by the CBN

Source: Author's Plot

Figure 6. 5: Overall Fiscal Policy Statements by the CBN

Source: Author's Plot

Having established the intensity with which the CBN discussed fiscal policy in its monetary policy communiqués between 2001 and 2018, the subsequent sub-section shows empirically, the extent to which changes in key macroeconomic variables, especially public financial indicators like fiscal deficit and public debt, while controlling for other effects, affect the intensity of CBN communicated about fiscal policy communication in the review period.

6.3.2 Data, Estimation Techniques and Results

Data

Table 6.2 shows the data and sources, as well as the justifications for including each of the variables in the empirical examination of CBN’s discussion of fiscal policy.

Table 6. 2: Data - Variables and Definitions

Variable	Description	Source	Rationale
FPCI	Fiscal Policy Communication Indicator	Developed by Author	Fiscal policy developments are important for the central bank and thus influences short-term decisions and long-term monetary policy expectations
DEF	Fiscal Deficit % of GDP	CBN 2018 Statistical Bulletin	Fiscal deficit arises when there is a gap between projected revenue and planned expenditures. How the deficit is financed is of concern to the central bank.
DEB	Total Public Debt (% of GDP)	CBN 2018 Statistical Bulletin	The Federal Government of Nigeria funds its deficit mainly through borrowing from non-bank. The Debt Management Office is saddled with this responsibility.
MSG	Broad Money Supply Growth (%)	CBN 2018 Statistical Bulletin	Expansionary fiscal policy could increase money supply with implications for monetary policy
INF	Inflation Rate (%)	CBN 2018 Statistical Bulletin	This is the ultimate concern of the central bank and fiscal issues could trigger inflationary pressures

Source: Author

Estimation techniques

Two estimation techniques were applied. First, following Allard *et al.* (2013), the OLS regression of the form stated below is estimated:

$$fpci_t = \alpha + \beta def_t + \lambda deb_t + \gamma msg_t + \phi inf_t + \varepsilon_t \dots\dots\dots 1$$

Where *fpci*, *def*, *deb*, *msg* and *inf* are as defined in table 5.2 and α is the intercept, while β , λ , γ and ϕ are the estimated parameters that explain the impact of the explanatory variables on CBN’s discussion of fiscal policy. The second technique is the VAR equation stated below:

$$x = (fpci, def, deb, msg, inf) \dots\dots\dots 2$$

The suitability of the VAR is hinged on the fact that the Impulse-Response Function (IRF) and Variance Decomposition (VD) provide perspectives that have practical policy implications. The sequence or ordering of the variables in the VAR model is based on the premise that the first signal for the central bank to talk about fiscal policy is the size of the fiscal deficit which in turn determines the level of borrowing.

Results- OLS

The results of the ADF test as indicated in table 6.3 shows that all the variables are I (0), meaning that they are stationary at level. In other words, they do not have unit roots, and this paves the way for the OLS regression and the IRF and VD estimations.

Table 6. 3: ADF Unit Root Test

	ADF Test at Level					Order of Integration
	1% Level	5% Level	10% Level	ADF test Statistic	Prob*	
FPCI	-3.5285	-2.9042	-2.5896	-4.8866	0.0001	I (0)
DEF	-3.5285	-2.9042	-2.5896	-3.4930	0.0110	I (0)
DEB	-3.5285	-2.9042	-2.5896	-2.6817	0.0824	I (0)
INF	-3.5300	-2.9048	-2.5896	-4.2279	0.0012	I (0)
MSG	-3.5316	-2.9055	-2.5903	-4.0303	0.0023	I (0)

Source: Author's Computations

The results of the OLS as presented in table 6.4 show that:

- a) Fiscal deficit has positive and significant impact on CBN's communication about fiscal policy. This is because fiscal deficit and especially the financing mode, could be inflationary and create challenges for monetary policy.
- b) The impact of inflation is also positive, but the magnitude is lower when compared with the deficit impact. This may be due to the fact that the inflationary effect of deficit financing is muted because the government finances the deficit mainly through non-bank borrowing. However, the CBN provides advances when government's projected revenues fall short of expectation and it manages any inflationary tendency using its OMO operations.
- c) The effect of public debt on communication about fiscal policy is insignificant because CBN is concerned about the aggregate demand impact of borrowing and not the monetary effect.
- d) The effect of money supply growth on CBN's communication about fiscal policy is expectedly insignificant because money supply growth is controlled through monetary policy instruments.

Overall, while the variables (deficit, inflation, debt, and money supply growth) explain approximately 15% of the variation in the dependent variable FPCI, they are jointly significant given the *F-statistic* of 2.7125 and its corresponding *p-value* of 0.0375.

Table 6. 4: OLS Results

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
c	10.8577	3.0652	3.5421	0.0007
DEF	3.3050	1.1070	2.9854	0.0040
INF	0.4516	0.2475	1.8242	0.0728
DEB	0.0862	0.0631	1.3645	0.1772
MSG	-0.1193	0.0759	-1.5706	0.1212
R-squared	0.1449	Mean dependent var	11.5152	
Adj.R-squared	0.0915	S.D. dependent var	8.37986	
S.E. of regression	7.9871	Akaike info criterion	7.06326	
Sum squared resid	4082.897	Schwarz criterion	7.2251	
Log likelihood	-238.6825	Hannan-Quinn criter.	7.1274	
F-statistic	2.7125	Durbin-Watson stat	1.4256	
Prob. (F-statistic)	0.0375			

Source: Author's Computations

The residual diagnostics tests are shown in table 6.5. The problem of serial correlation, using the Breusch-Godfrey test, is not present given the probability value of 0.0660 which is higher than the 0.05 threshold. Similarly, the Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey test for heteroskedasticity shows that the assumption is not violated as the probability value of 0.1695 is higher than the threshold of 0.05. Using the CUSUM stability test, figure 6.6 shows that the estimated OLS model is stable as the CUSUM line is in-between the two 5% significance lines.

Table 6. 5: Residual Diagnostic Tests

<i>Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test</i>			
F-statistic	2.8400	Prob. F(2,62)	0.0660
Obs*R-squared	5.7908	Prob. Chi-Square (2)	0.0553
<i>Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey</i>			
F-statistic	1.6629	Prob. F (4,64)	0.1695
Obs*R-squared	6.4963	Prob. Chi-Square (4)	0.1650
Scaled explained SS	14.5120	Prob. Chi-Square (4)	0.0058

Source: Author's Estimates

Figure 6. 6: Model Stability - CUSUM Stability Test

Impulse-Response Function

The impulse-response and variance decomposition techniques were used to provide further insight on how CBN’s communication about fiscal policy respond to key macroeconomic variables. Figure 6.7 presents the charts of the impulse-response functions as follows:

- a) Chart A shows that the response of FPCI to shocks to fiscal deficit dies out at the end of the period after the initial sharp and positive response. This is because the government funds its deficit mainly through borrowing from non-bank public, while the CBN provides temporary advances only when revenues fall short of projections during the fiscal period.
- b) Chart B depicts that the response of FPCI to shock to public debt is positive for the entire period, not because of the monetary impact, but because of how government uses the borrowings to implement projects that affect aggregate demand in the economy.
- c) Chart C indicates that the response of FPCI to money supply growth is significant in quarter 3 (the same single quarter in which the deficit variable is significant).
- d) Chart D illustrates that the response of FPCI to shock to inflation is positive for most of the period, but the effect gradually vanishes because ultimately, inflation in the long-term is considered a monetary phenomenon.

Figure 6. 7: Impulse-Response Charts

Variance Decomposition

The variance decomposition results in table 6.6 shows that the explanatory variables did not significantly explain the FEV of the FPCI as average 77% of the variation was due to own effect. While the effect of the explanatory variables increased over time, they remain largely small, with fiscal deficit, public debt, inflation, and money supply accounting for only average 7.7%, 1.3%, 6% and 8% of the FEV. This reinforces the OLS estimation where the explanatory variables accounted for only 15% of the variation in the FPCI.

Table 6. 6: Variance Decomposition

Period	S.E.	FPCI	DEF	DEB	MSG	INF
1	7.2819	100.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
2	7.6948	93.3971	4.2126	0.0041	1.4299	0.9564
3	8.4178	80.0472	8.0357	1.0088	7.0772	3.8311
4	8.7661	74.5782	9.0405	1.2480	8.8900	6.2433
5	8.9594	71.8784	9.3213	1.4064	9.8693	7.5246
6	9.0464	70.6902	9.3921	1.5686	10.3454	8.0037
7	9.0883	70.1197	9.3939	1.7537	10.5772	8.1556
8	9.1082	69.8315	9.3748	1.9193	10.6626	8.2119
9	9.1183	69.6765	9.3552	2.0480	10.6797	8.2407
10	9.1242	69.5904	9.3458	2.1379	10.6711	8.2548
Ave.	8.6605	76.9809	7.7472	1.3095	8.0202	5.9422

Source: Author's Computations

Granger Causality

In terms of the direction of causality, table 6.7 shows that apart from inflation, fiscal policy communication is granger-caused by fiscal deficit, public debt, and money supply, meaning that the previous values of these variables can help predict changes in the FPCI. The combined effect of all the indicators (deficit, debt, money supply and inflation) illustrates that they all granger-cause fiscal policy communication by the CBN.

Table 6. 7: VAR Granger Causality/Block Exogeneity Wald Tests

Dependent Variable: FPCI			
Excluded	Chi-sq.	df	Prob.
DEF	10.9639	2	0.0042
DEB	5.2791	2	0.0714
MSG	7.9532	2	0.0187
INF	4.2803	2	0.1176
All	15.0311	8	0.0585

Source: Author's Computations

Diagnostic tests

The VAR residual serial correlation test shown in table 6.8 indicates that serial correlation is not a problem given that the probability values at the different lag levels are higher than the 0.05 threshold. The residual plots depicted in figure 6.8 shows that the VAR system is stable given that the residuals are stationary or do not have unit roots.

Table 6. 8: VAR Residual Serial Correlation LM Tests

Lags	LM-Stat	Prob.
1	36.7959	0.0604
2	32.8994	0.1336
3	19.5895	0.7680

Source: Author's Computations

Figure 6. 8: Residual Plots

Source: Author's Plots

6.4 Summary

The chapter contributes to the emerging literature on central bank communication about fiscal policy by examining the intensity with which the CBN discusses fiscal policy matters. To measure CBN's fiscal policy communication, a template was designed and used to develop a *Fiscal Policy Communication Indicator* (FPCI) in line with the approach of Allard *et al.* (2013). The empirical analysis also followed Allard *et al.* (2013) that used the OLS regression to explore the connection between the intensity of fiscal policy deliberations and developments in the larger economy. This study also complemented the OLS technique with the IRF and VD in order to gain further insight.

The results from evaluating the fiscal policy communication in the policy communiqués issued between 2001 and 2018 showed that 51 statements and 2,812 words or average 1.8% of the total word count of all the communiqués were used to talk about *positive fiscal policy statements*. The discussions on *normative fiscal policy statements* saw the CBN using 76 statements and 4,141 words or average 1.9% of total word count. The reference to *fiscal policy as an input to or outcome of central bank forecasts* saw the CBN using 136 statements and 7,439 words or 4.5% to discuss the matter. In referring to *government financing instruments (bonds and treasury bills)*, the bank used 99 statements and 3,425 words or 2.6% of total word count while 47 statements and 2,376 words or 0.85% of total word count were used to refer to *fiscal policies in other countries*. Overall, 409 statements and 20,193 words or 11.8% of total word count of all the communiqués were used to discuss fiscal policy matters between 2001 and 2018.

Juxtaposing the FPCI with key policy developments, it was observed that the CBN communicated more positively about fiscal policy between 2004 and 2005 when the oil-price based fiscal rule, meant to limit fiscal dominance and procyclicality, was introduced. The creation of the SWF in 2011 resulted in more normative fiscal policy statements as the CBN's posture changed from commendation to advisory. Generally, communication about fiscal policy increased in the period of the oil-price based fiscal rule and the creation of the SWF.

The OLS estimation showed that fiscal deficit and inflation have significant effect on FPCI because the size and financing modes of deficit are important, and the likely inflationary effects are also crucial. Although the effect of public debt is positive, it is insignificant while the effect of

money supply growth is also insignificant because monetary expansion or contraction is principally a function of monetary decisions.

The IRF results showed that the response of FPCI to shocks to fiscal deficit dies out while its response to shock to public debt is positive for the entire period. This is because the CBN over time discusses how the accumulated debt is used to implement projects that affect aggregate demand in the economy. The response of FPCI to money supply growth is significant in quarter 3, the same single quarter in which the deficit variable is significant. Finally, the response of FPCI to shock to inflation is positive for most of the period but the effect vanishes because ultimately, inflation in the long-term is a monetary phenomenon. The variance decomposition results showed that about 77% of the FEV in the FPCI is due to own effect, meaning that the explanatory variables did not significantly explain the variance in the FPCI.

In terms of the direction of causality, apart from inflation, fiscal policy communication is granger-caused by fiscal deficit, public debt, and money supply, meaning that the previous values of these variables can help predict changes in the FPCI. The combined effect of all the indicators (deficit, debt, money supply and inflation) granger-cause fiscal policy communication by the CBN.

In conclusion, the space dedicated to discussing fiscal policy in the monetary policy communiqués issued by the CBN between 2001 and 2018 increased, with more emphasis on positive, normative and statements that see fiscal policy as a forecasting item in taking monetary policy decisions. Expectedly, issues like fiscal deficit and inflation are crucial and have significant effects on CBN's discussions of fiscal policy. The results of this analysis compare with those of Allard *et al.* (2013) who showed that the ECB communicated intensely about fiscal policies in both positive and normative terms, while fiscal deficit increases fiscal policy discussions.

CHAPTER SEVEN: The Public and Monetary Policy in Nigeria

‘Monetary and financial policies can be more effective if their objectives, rationale, and methods of implementation are communicated to the public in a clear and timely manner’ – IMF (1999)

7.1 Introduction

Central bank communication helps to manage public expectations and so enhances the predictability of monetary policy outcomes. Because the financial sector is the medium through which the pass-through effects of monetary policy on the economy are achieved, the literature is dominated by studies that treat the financial sector as synonymous with the public.

Blinder *et.al.* (2008) argued that there is need to investigate the whole public’s knowledge of monetary policy because the decisions of central banks and how they are communicated have implications for choices made by all stakeholders and not only financial markets. However, years after this observation, only a handful of studies have explored the nexus between central bank communication and the general public.

This chapter contributes to the literature by examining the extent to which the public in Nigeria, including financial sector players, understand monetary policy. Specifically, attempt is made to analyse whether the public is conversant with the monetary policy objectives and instruments of the CBN, while also probing how they source monetary policy information.

To achieve the objective, the following questions are scrutinized:

- a) Does age, educational qualifications, years of work experience and income influence knowledge of monetary policy?
- b) Does having the desire to learn improve knowledge of monetary policy?
- c) What are the predominant sources of getting information about monetary policy?
- d) To what extent do sources of getting information impact awareness of monetary policy?
- e) Do people use more of past information, current information, or a combination of to predict future monetary policy?

The rest of this chapter is structured as follows: The literature on central bank communication and the general public is discussed, followed by the methodology, data, and the estimation techniques for analyzing how the public understands monetary policy in Nigeria. The last part of the section details the results and implications of the findings.

7.2 Central bank communication and the public

Carvalho and Nechio (2014) as well as Cruijisen *et al.* (2015) are perhaps the two main studies that have explored central bank communication and the public in line with the observation of Blinder *et al.* (2008). There are however studies that have indirectly scrutinized this link by analyzing how the media handles monetary policy decisions and how these are disseminated to the public.

Cruijisen *et al.* (2015) surveyed Dutch households and studied whether they understood the monetary policy of the ECB. They postulated that there is an interdependencies between the knowledge of monetary policy (U), that is the extent to which the public are familiar about the objectives and instruments of the central bank's monetary policy, the desire to be conversant about monetary policy (D), the sources of monetary policy information (S), and quantity of monetary policy information (Q), that is the amount of monetary policy information available to the public.

Cruijisen *et al.* (2015) further opined that the desire of person i to be knowledgeable about monetary policy is a function of self-interest (SI), ideology (ID), education (ED), and a vector X that contains control variables like sex and age. Using the logit and probit techniques, they found that knowledge of the ECB's objectives was far from perfect. Also, both a weak desire to be informed and unawareness or insufficient knowledge are barriers for improving households understanding of ECB monetary policy. They also showed that more intensive use of information improves understanding, signifying that the media channel may play a vital and positive role in refining knowledge of monetary policy. Finally, the study depicted that knowledge of monetary policy objectives contributes to an individual's ability to form realistic inflation expectations.

Carvalho and Nechio (2014) examined if households in the US understood central bank talk, positing that improving the public's knowledge of the central bank's policy and strategy reduces economic and financial uncertainty, and helps households and firms make more-informed decisions. The study combined answers to questions about inflation, unemployment, and interest rates. Applying the Taylor rule and using probit technique for the analysis, they found that some households are aware of the principles underlying the Taylor rule when forming their expectations. The degree to which this occurs is however not even across income and education levels.

Also focusing on US households, Binder (2017) addressed the bases and efficiency of communication with households, adding it with new evidence from an assortment of consumer data. Using survey data and logistic technique, the findings showed that consumers' expectations

are imperfectly anchored and that the anchoring of more informed expectations increased more than the anchoring of less informed consumers' expectations following the FED's announcement of a 2% inflation target.

Başkaya *et al.* (2008) examined inflation expectations and central bank communication in Turkey by focusing on the heterogeneities in expectations formation in different sectors of the economy. The results showed that the financial sector and the real sector display significant heterogeneities in their expectations formation and their attentiveness to the economic news and central bank communication. The real sector is more backward looking, while the financial sector is sensitive to the short-term variations in financial data. They concluded that finding sectoral heterogeneities may be important for designing an effective communication strategy.

Another strand of studies is those that evaluate the role of the media in conveying central bank communication and how such transmissions affect expectations of the public. The relevance of the media is hinged on the fact that economic agents are flooded with macroeconomic news from different sources and may not have the time to directly monitor and evaluate central bank messages. Therefore, the role of the media in the public's understanding of central bank's objectives, strategies and decisions has been investigated empirically.

Carroll (2003) suggested that households get economic news using different media sources and because people absorb released information with some element of probability, it takes time for news of changed macroeconomic conditions such as central bank interest rate decisions to spread to the whole populace. One of the main outcomes is that the variances between household expectations and the opinions of experts thin when inflation is more significant, due partly to increased media coverage and higher household interest.

Given the role of the media in disseminating the decision of a central bank to the public, the ECB as part of its strategy holds a press conference as well as a question-and-answer session. In its monthly bulletin of November 2002, the ECB specified that the monthly press conference signifies one of its most vital communication channels that provides a complete summary of economic developments. Because the press conference includes question and answer session, there is the perception that the media is better placed to report the decisions of the bank as against reading policy communiqués and attempting to make inferences in the grey areas. This has contributed to

the growing empirical studies that have evaluated the impact of the ECB press conference on the public's understanding of the bank's monetary policy decisions.

Rosa and Verga (2005) verified the extent to which expectations respond to the information released by the ECB and found that the public not only understood but also believed the signals sent by the ECB through its press conference. Similarly, Musard-Gies (2006) tested whether the ECB's press conference move market short-term and long-term interest rates in the euro zone by coding statements according to whether they are neutral, hawkish, or dovish. Using a principal components analysis and non-parametric tests, the results showed that the impact of statements peak on interest rates with a maturity of six or twelve months and is smaller for the longer maturities. Likewise, Brand *et al.* (2006) investigated the effect of the ECB policy decisions with emphasis on the press conference influence. They found that communication during the press conference led to changes in expectations of the path of monetary policy.

Lamlay and Rupprecht (2006)) used the GARCH method to investigate the role of media as a transmitter and filter of news to the public. They posited that many models relax the assumption of perfectly informed fully rational consumers, but consumers are rather assumed to be occasionally informed and/or inattentive. The study found that the media plays active role in transmitting policy decisions, including those of the central bank to the public.

Using the Czech National Bank as a case study, Böhm *et al.* (2009) analyzed the extent of the media coverage on monetary policy decisions. Using articles published in the four most relevant Czech daily broadsheets immediately after monetary policy meetings and also taking account of parameters of monetary policy decisions and related communication, the findings showed that the Czech National Bank decisions that surprise financial markets and the public are not negatively apparent by the media and the media welcomes rate changes.

Hayo and Neuenkirch (2010) used the GARCH model to explore differences in reactions to newswire reports and original communications by the Bank of Canada and found that markets move in the intended direction after communications and do not require media filtering. Similarly, Hayo and Neuenkirch (2012) examined how Bank of Canada communicates and the media reporting of the decisions. They found that communication have a relatively larger influence on the bond market while media coverage is more applicable for the stock market.

Focusing on communication through newspapers, Reid and Plessis (2011) evaluated the role of the South African media in the expectations channel of monetary policy transmission. The results revealed limitations in the evaluation and reporting of monetary policy by the media and concluded that the press is not adequately fulfilling their role of digesting monetary policy information.

Neuenkirch (2013) explored the determinants of newswire coverage of FED's communications and the implications for the public. Sampling about 344 forward-looking communications made in the period May 1999–May 2004, they found a higher probability of coverage for reports and speeches by Greenspan than for testimony and speeches by other FED members. The results also showed that speeches by regional FED presidents are less reported while coverage of FED's president speeches is more likely if central bank communication is stale.

Lamlay and Sturm (2013) used media reports to examine how actions of the ECB are perceived by journalists and then provided to the public. Because it is costly to assess monetary policy decisions by themselves, the public is likely to update their expectations by reading newspapers. Thus, the assessment of journalists is likely to shape the perceptions and expectations of the public with respect to ECB policy. The results showed that both interest rate changes and communication form expectations as conveyed by the media. However, while the interest rate signal is significant in all conditions, the import of communication depends upon the type of indicator used.

Neuenkirch (2014) outlined two risks of the public relying on media reporting of monetary policy decisions. First, it is argued that the media might be discriminatory in their reporting, thereby overlooking events they consider non-newsworthy. Second is the risk of misinterpretation. The results showed that Reuters disregards most speeches by the lesser-known FED presidents while the media attempts to sell news to markets, as the probability of coverage is higher if there has not been any communication for a while or it occurs before the weekend.

Hayo and Neuenkirch (2014) examined if financial agents monitor central bank actions and communications directly or rely on the media. Focusing on the BOE, BOJ, ECB, and the FED, and using the ordered probit models, they showed that media reporting is important for financial markets understanding of central bank policy decisions.

7.3 Data and methodology

7.3.1 Questionnaire design, structure and contents

Generally, inquiries into the public's understanding of macroeconomic issues are conducted using surveys. For example, Jonung (1981) used a cross-section of Swedish households and showed how perceived and expected rates of inflation differ between numerous demographic groups. Bryan and Venkatu (2001) found variances between demographic groups for the United States, while Souleles (2004) used household data based on the Michigan Index of Consumer Sentiment and found that expectations are biased as well as inefficient.

To examine the public's knowledge of monetary policy in Nigeria, the questionnaire by Crujisen *et al.* (2015) was modified as shown in figure 7.1 and in Appendix 6. It was structured in five parts in line with the objective and the research questions. The first part is *Identification* aimed at getting contextual information, including sector of employment, work experience and income level. The second part is *Background Questions* about the macroeconomy, while the third part inquiries about *General Knowledge of the CBN*. The fourth part focused on *Monetary Policy Objectives and Instruments* while the last part was about getting *Information on Monetary Policy*.

Sectors of employment were grouped into *Financial, Government, Real and 'Other' Sectors*. Participants in the financial sector were drawn randomly from banks, stockbroking firms and pension fund administrators. The Government sector comprises public and civil servants selected randomly from different institutions of the federal government.

Figure 7. 1: Structure of the Questionnaire

Source: Modified version of Crujisen *et al.* (2015)

The real sector classification comprises participants drawn randomly from the agriculture, manufacturing, telecommunication, oil and gas, transportation, and *others*. Because the survey was conducted in Abuja, partakers in the agriculture, manufacturing and oil and gas were mainly those in administrative positions as core operational functions are carried out in Lagos, Port Harcourt, and other areas. Also, because policy decisions of the central bank affect investment and credit operations of the real sector, and because their workers make savings and investment decisions, it was important to add the real sector in the survey.

The last segment is '*Others*' comprising Entrepreneurs, Professional Economists, Consultants, Students and Politicians. The inclusion of entrepreneurs followed Montes and Thiago (2016) that examined how entrepreneurs comprehend monetary policy in Brazil, while adding economists, especially those that are involved in forecasting macroeconomic developments is prevalent in the literature. The choice of students is justified given efforts at improving financial literacy amongst them, including their understanding of monetary policy. For the purpose of this survey, student participants were randomly selected from final year undergraduate and first year postgraduate economics students at the University of Abuja. Politics is important in shaping public policies, including monetary policy, as such few politicians serving as members of the Nigeria National Assembly were involved in the survey.

Overall, while the sample surveyed was not representative of the Nigerian population given that the survey was limited to Abuja, it nevertheless provided an insight into the public's knowledge of monetary policy in Nigeria.

7.3.2 The pilot and main surveys

Prior to carrying out the pilot and main surveys, application for ethical approval was made and approval granted as indicated in Part B of Appendix 6. The pilot survey was conducted between October and November 2017 with 22 participants selected randomly from the Ministries, Departments and Agencies, all of whom were Directorate Level personnel. The choice of 22 participants was premised on the notion that the number of participants for pilot surveys should normally be between 10 and 30.⁹

⁹Isaac and Michael, 1995; and Hill, 1998 – Cited in Hashim (2010)

The rationale for the pilot was to test the validity of the proposed questions, as well as get feedback on how the structure and content of the questionnaire can be improved. Part C of Appendix 6 provides the responses that helped in modification of the draft questionnaire while the main field work was subsequently carried out and the details provided in table 7.1.

Table 7. 1: Summary of Main Survey Activities

<p><u>The Survey</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Conducted in Abuja, Nigeria ▪ Start Date: October 23rd, 2018. ▪ End Date: November 2nd, 2018 ▪ Six (6) field enumerators were engaged to cover a sample size of 2000 participants. ▪ Each field enumerator administered 333 questionnaires. ▪ 2 field enumerators handled the <i>Real Sector</i>. ▪ 2 field enumerators handled <i>Government sector</i>. ▪ 1 field enumerator handled the <i>Financial sector</i>. ▪ 1 field enumerator handled ‘<i>Other</i>’ sectors. ▪ A total of 1,959 questionnaires were returned which accounts for over 97% response rate 	<p><u>Editing</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Start Date: November 5th, 2018. ▪ End Date: November 8th, 2018. ▪ Questionnaires given unique identification numbers. ▪ Edited where some respondents selected all responses in the <i>Only One Response Questions</i>. ▪ A pre-coding was also done to aid data entry using both numeric and alpha numeric system of coding. ▪ Each question was given a value set variable. ▪ Don’t know response was given as 8 which is the standard for coding of Don’t Know Responses. Also, 9 was used for missing variables. ▪ Question 22 was coded alpha numeric, where X = Others; Y = Don’t Know and Z = Missing.
<p>Sector-specific Challenges</p>	
<p><u>Financial Sector</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Difficult access due to rigidity of some bank managers ▪ Some bank managers handpicked those that participated in their branches. ▪ With persuasion the field enumerator was able to meet the threshold. 	<p><u>Real Sector</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Telecommunication sub-sector totally refused to grant access to the enumerator to conduct the survey. ▪ Initial resistance but persuasion led to access to other sub-sectors - Hospitality, Bakery, Restaurants, Interior Decorator, Artists, Furniture Makers, Pharmacy
<p><u>Government</u></p> <p>The government sector which was sub divided into public and civil servants had relatively no notable challenges</p>	<p><u>Others</u></p> <p>The ‘<i>Other</i>’ sectors comprise Students, Economist, Entrepreneur and Politicians had few challenges, except that only a handful of the legislators participated.</p>
<p>Overall Challenges</p>	
<p>Two enumerators did not do a check list and follow up mechanism; meaning they got some sectors confused and didn’t know how to track the respondents, resulting in 41 questionnaires not collected</p>	
<p><u>Data Entry</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Start Date: December 12th, 2018. ▪ End Date: December 20th, 2018. ▪ Software - CSPRO (Census and Survey Pro) ▪ 4 data entry clerks were engaged. ▪ Data exported to SPSS and STATA. 	<p><u>Data Analysis</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Start Date: 10th January 2019. ▪ End Date: April 2019 ▪ SPSS and STATA were used for the Analysis.

Source: Author

7.3.3 Data presentation and estimation technique

The information gathered from the survey were presented graphically to put in perspective the relationship between responses to the knowledge questions and key attributes like gender, age, educational qualifications, sector of employment, income level, source(s) of information on monetary policy and how they form their outlook of monetary policy.

Formally, the relationship between the knowledge questions and attributes of the participants was scrutinized using the logistic regression technique. The method is generally used to obtain odds ratios and predict a categorical variable from a set of predictor variables.

A logistic regression models the chance of an outcome founded on separate features. Because chance is a ratio, what is modeled is the logarithm of the chance given by:

$$\log \left(\frac{\pi}{1-\pi} \right) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \dots + \beta_m X_m$$

where π shows the likelihood of an event and β is are the regression coefficients and the x_i explanatory variables.

7.4. Results

Table 7.2 shows the correctness of participants to each of the knowledge questions on monetary policy while the results of the logistic regressions are presented in table 7.3, with the detailed interpretations in Part D of Appendix 6. Each of the questions aimed at testing the knowledge of participants about monetary policy as indicated in *Section D* of the questionnaire, are regressed on gender, age, education, sector of employment, work experience, income level, sources of information on monetary policy, as well as how participants form their expectations of future monetary policy.

In analyzing the responses from the survey which used a Likert questionnaire format, this study assumed that participants who answered ‘*Neither Agree nor Disagree*’ to any question do not have the knowledge of that particular activity of the CBN. As such, it is either a participant answers a question correctly or does not, thereby informing the use of the binary logistic analysis instead of multinomial logistic regression. The summary of the results are as follows:

- a) Knowledge of monetary policy is not influenced by **gender**, implying that being male or female is not a determinant of how conversant the participant is about monetary policy.

- b) **Age** plays a key role as older participants are more knowledgeable about monetary policy.
- c) **Higher educational qualification** does not significantly increase the likelihood of being well-informed about monetary policy.
- d) Participants in the real sector tend to be more conversant about monetary policy compared with those in the financial sector, while those in government and ‘other’ sectors are less likely to understand monetary policy better than financial sector workers.
- e) In line with Cruijsen *et al.* (2015), those with **desire** to be well-informed appear to be more knowledgeable about monetary policy.
- f) **Work experience** raises the likelihood of being well-conversant about monetary policy.
- g) **Higher income** earners are more likely to be well-knowledgeable about monetary policy. This is logical given that propensity to save and invest is higher as incomes increases.
- h) Participants who rely more on Newspapers tend to be more conversant, followed by users of CBN’s website, Radio and Television. Those that depend more on magazines, social media, ‘contacts’ and ‘others’ are less likely to be well-informed.
- i) Using past information, current information, or current and past information, does not significantly affect knowledge of monetary policy.

Table 7. 2: Percentage of Correctness to each Monetary Policy Question

Question	Classification									
	Gender	Age	Education	Sector	Experience	Income	Desire	Source	Forecast	
1 Achieving monetary and price stability is the primary objective of the CBN	Male 89% Female 88%	Below 30 86% 31 – 40 89% 41 – 50 91% 51- above 97%	BSc 89.2% MSc 89.5% PhD 85.2% Others 80.0%	Financial 92.2% Real 95.8% Govt. 84.9% Others 81.5%	0– 5 yrs.87.0% 6– 10 yrs.91.8% 11 - above 93.9%	Less than N1m 86.8% N1m – N3m 91.3% N3m – N5m 94.3% N5m – above 92.6% Prefer not to say 88.5%	Desire 91.4% No Desire 73.7%	Television 87.9% Radio 97.6% Newspapers 92.3% Magazines 91.7% CBN Website 94.6% Social Media 84.5% Other websites91.4% Contacts 90.5% Others 51.7%	Past Information 89.9% Current Information 91.1% Past and Current 90.2%	
2 The CBN defines price stability as sustained low and single digit inflation rate	Male 83% Female 79%	Below 30 79% 31 – 40 80% 41 – 50 85% 51- above 97%	BSc 82.9% MSc 77.9% PhD 71.6% Others 60.0%	Financial 85.2% Real 91.5% Govt. 74.4% Others 75.0%	0– 5 yrs. 80.8% 6– 10 yrs. 83.4% 11 - above 84.1%	Less than N1m 80.3% N1m – N3m 81.6% N3m – N5m 81.4% N5m – above 85.2% Prefer not to say 82%	Desire 83.6% No Desire 67.0%	Television 81.8% Radio 87.3% Newspapers 82.1% Magazines 83.3% CBN Website 88.6% Social Media 70.4% Other websites 80.8% Contacts 66.7% Others 48.3%	Past Information 83.5% Current Information 79.7% Past and Current 83.0%	
3 Apart from pursuing monetary and price stability, the CBN also provides economic and financial advice to the Federal Government	Male 87% Female 82%	Below 30 83% 31 – 40 84% 41 – 50 90% 51- above 96%	BSc 85.7% MSc 84.7% PhD 81.5% Others 80.0%	Financial 92.4% Real 95.5% Govt. 76.7% Others 80.2%	0– 5 yrs. 81.8% 6– 10 yrs. 88.8% 11 - above 92.7%	Less than N1m 80.3% N1m – N3m 90.6% N3m – N5m 95.7% N5m – above 88.9% Prefer not to say 86%	Desire 87.2% No Desire 72.7%	Television 86.7% Radio 94.4% Newspapers 91.5% Magazines 91.7% CBN Website 91.8% Social Media 57.8% Other websites85.6% Contacts 80.9% Others 48.3%	Past Information 85.6% Current Information 88.9% Past and Current 85.4%	
4 The key monetary policy instruments of the CBN include but not limited to Monetary Policy Rate and Open Market Operations	Male 79% Female 72%	Below 30 76% 31 – 40 75% 41 – 50 81% 51- above 83%	BSc 76.7% MSc 77.9% PhD 72.8% Others 40.0%	Financial 85.9% Real 90.4% Govt. 68.0% Others 76.7%	0– 5 yrs. 74.2% 6– 10 yrs. 80.2% 11 - above 80.0%	Less than N1m 72.3% N1m – N3m 77.5% N3m – N5m 84.3% N5m – above 88.9% Prefer not to say 80%	Desire 78.2% No Desire 66.3%	Television 77.8% Radio 84.1% Newspapers 84.6% Magazines 75.0% CBN Website 85.9% Social Media 45.1% Other websites81.7% Contacts 76.2% Others 34.5%	Past Information 79.1% Current Information 75.2% Past and Current 77.8 %	
5 To adjust its monetary policy instruments, the CBN must obtain permission from the Federal Government	Male 87% Female 89%	Below 30 9.5% 31 – 40 12.2% 41 – 50 16.7% 51- above 16%	BSc 9.8% MSc 19.3% PhD 16.1% Others 0.0%	Financial 7.60% Real 10.0% Govt. 14.5% Others 13.4%	0– 5 yrs. 11.1% 6– 10 yrs. 10.8% 11 - above 17.5%	Less than N1m 10.1% N1m – N3m 11.3% N3m – N5m 14.3% N5m – above 33.3% Prefer not to say 14%	Desire 13.0% No Desire 6.0%	Television 11.6% Radio 15.1% Newspapers 15.4% Magazines 12.5% CBN Website 15.5% Social Media 4.2% Other websites 9.6% Contacts 19.1% Others 13.8%	Past Information 10.1% Current Information 17.1% Past and Current 11.6 %	

Source: Author

Table 7. 3: Logistic Results for each Monetary Policy Question and the Aggregate Knowledge

	Achieving monetary and price stability is the primary objective of the CBN				The CBN defines price stability as sustained low and single digit inflation rate				Apart from pursuing monetary and price stability, the CBN also provides economic and financial advice to the Federal Government				The key monetary policy instruments of the CBN include but not limited to Monetary Policy Rate and Open Market Operations				To adjust its monetary policy instruments, the CBN must obtain permission from the Federal Government				Aggregation of Monetary Policy Knowledge			
	Odds Ratio	Std. Err.	z	P > Z	Odds Ratio	Std. Err.	z	P > Z	Odds Ratio	Std. Err.	z	P > Z	Odds Ratio	Std. Err.	z	P > Z	Odds Ratio	Std. Err.	z	P > Z	Odds Ratio	Std. Err.	z	P > Z
Gender	0.8624	0.1457	-0.8800	0.3810	0.8893	0.1188	-0.8800	0.3800	0.6939	0.1069	-2.3700	0.0180	0.6988	0.0891	-2.8100	0.0050	0.8369	0.1336	-1.1200	0.2640	0.7739	0.0790	-2.5100	0.0120
Age																								
31-40	1.1596	0.2318	0.7400	0.4590	0.9940	0.1591	-0.0400	0.9700	0.8483	0.1552	-0.9000	0.3690	0.8335	0.1304	-1.1600	0.2440	1.1754	0.2264	0.8400	0.4020	1.0377	0.1262	0.3000	0.7610
41-50	1.6325	0.5097	1.5700	0.1160	2.1797	0.5469	3.1100	0.0020	1.6016	0.4682	1.6100	0.1070	1.6552	0.3898	2.1400	0.0320	1.3021	0.3503	0.9800	0.3270	2.0410	0.3857	3.7700	0.0000
51- above	4.9234	3.2815	2.3900	0.0170	3.9760	1.5896	3.4500	0.0010	4.4668	2.6173	2.5500	0.0110	2.6876	0.9446	2.8100	0.0050	0.9485	0.3630	-0.1400	0.8900	3.4983	0.9782	4.4800	0.0000
Education																								
MSc	0.7085	0.1568	-1.5600	0.1190	0.6057	0.1012	-3.0000	0.0030	0.5531	0.1100	-2.9800	0.0030	0.8532	0.1405	-0.9600	0.3350	2.0763	0.3763	4.0300	0.0000	0.9736	0.1329	-0.2000	0.8450
PhD	0.4629	0.1830	-1.9500	0.0510	0.4060	0.1225	-2.9900	0.0030	0.4105	0.1509	-2.4200	0.0150	0.6409	0.1940	-1.4700	0.1420	1.5249	0.5376	12.000	0.2310	0.6223	0.1579	-1.8700	0.0620
Others	0.1752	0.2183	-1.4000	0.1620	0.1308	0.1306	-2.0400	0.0420	0.3602	0.4381	-0.8400	0.4010	0.0915	0.0963	-2.2700	0.0230	10.000	empty	empty	empty	0.1909	0.1409	-2.2400	0.0250
Sector																								
Real	4.0849	1.4029	4.1000	0.0000	2.6706	0.6714	3.9100	0.0000	2.9356	0.9810	3.2200	0.0010	2.4201	0.6030	3.5500	0.0000	1.7075	0.5112	1.7900	0.0740	2.3665	0.4151	4.9100	0.0000
Government	0.5360	0.1488	-2.2500	0.0250	0.4843	0.1024	-3.4300	0.0010	0.2718	0.0735	-4.8200	0.0000	0.2885	0.0613	-5.8500	0.0000	3.0228	0.8446	3.9600	0.0000	0.5923	0.0964	-3.2200	0.0010
Others	0.5127	0.1804	-1.9000	0.0580	0.7690	0.2191	-0.9200	0.3570	0.5094	0.1792	-1.9200	0.0550	0.6849	0.2009	-1.2900	0.1970	2.0090	0.6904	2.0300	0.0420	0.9684	0.2191	-0.1400	0.8870
Experience																								
6-10 years	1.9978	0.4454	3.1000	0.0020	1.4317	0.2466	2.0800	0.0370	2.0154	0.4024	3.5100	0.0000	1.7508	0.2914	3.3700	0.0010	0.6673	0.1336	-2.0200	0.0430	1.2871	0.1660	1.9600	0.0500
11 years - above	2.3227	0.7991	2.4500	0.0140	1.2240	0.3019	0.8200	0.4130	2.3505	0.7413	2.7100	0.0070	1.3461	0.3198	1.2500	0.2110	0.9516	0.2484	-0.1900	0.8490	1.2661	0.2389	1.2500	0.2110
Income																								
N1-3m	1.1140	0.2647	0.4500	0.6500	0.9561	0.1754	-0.2400	0.8070	1.5877	0.3564	2.0600	0.0390	0.9717	0.1688	-0.1700	0.8690	0.8218	0.1815	-0.8900	0.3740	0.8729	0.1223	-0.9700	0.3320
N3-5m	2.0929	1.1998	1.2900	0.1980	1.1134	0.4060	0.2900	0.7680	4.8046	3.1062	2.4300	0.0150	1.8041	0.6992	1.5200	0.1280	0.8669	0.3502	-0.3500	0.7240	1.4182	0.4230	1.1700	0.2410
N5m - above	1.1842	0.9624	0.2100	0.8350	1.2190	0.7439	0.3200	0.7460	0.9574	0.6849	-0.0600	0.9510	1.6017	1.0867	0.6900	0.4870	2.9254	1.3896	2.2600	0.0240	3.2705	1.4756	2.6300	0.0090
Prefer not to say	1.5469	0.3574	1.8900	0.0590	1.1850	0.2117	0.9500	0.3420	1.2946	0.2676	1.2500	0.2120					1.6309	0.3125	2.5500	0.0110	1.4493	0.1900	2.8300	0.0050
Source of Info																								
Radio	6.1524	4.5141	2.4800	0.0130	1.4850	0.4930	1.1900	0.2340	3.0751	1.6464	2.1000	0.0360	1.1216	0.3321	0.3900	0.6980	1.5933	0.4564	1.6300	0.1040	1.3386	0.2801	1.3900	0.1630
Newspaper	3.0356	1.3533	2.4900	0.0130	1.4233	0.4040	1.2400	0.2140	2.0631	0.7840	1.9100	0.0570	2.0534	0.6056	2.4400	0.0150	1.3063	0.3813	0.9200	0.3600	1.5894	0.3464	2.1300	0.0340
Magazines	1.2197	0.9496	0.2600	0.7990	1.0273	0.5939	0.0500	0.9630	1.2788	0.9996	0.3100	0.7530	0.9036	0.4871	-0.1900	0.8510	0.7783	0.5064	-0.3900	0.7000	0.8042	0.3625	-0.4800	0.6290
CBN Website	2.6709	0.9357	2.8000	0.0050	1.9437	0.4891	2.6400	0.0080	1.6130	0.4811	1.6200	0.1060	1.8133	0.4302	2.5100	0.0120	1.5004	0.3666	1.6600	0.0970	1.8479	0.3383	3.3500	0.0010
Other Websites	2.0248	0.8064	1.7700	0.0760	1.0759	0.3075	0.2600	0.7980	1.4079	0.4896	0.9800	0.3250	1.4530	0.4183	1.3000	0.1940	0.8759	0.3189	-0.3600	0.7160	1.0696	0.2444	0.2900	0.7680
Social Media	1.7191	0.5085	1.8300	0.0670	0.9987	0.2321	-0.0100	0.9950	0.3577	0.0816	-4.5000	0.0000	0.3340	0.0730	-5.0200	0.0000	0.3517	0.1539	-2.3900	0.0170	0.4000	0.0694	-5.2800	0.0000
Contacts	2.3508	1.1984	1.0500	0.2950	0.4893	0.2581	-1.3500	0.1750	0.7807	0.5154	-0.3800	0.7080	0.8535	0.4896	0.2800	0.7820	2.0330	1.2145	1.1900	0.2350	0.6787	0.3077	-0.8600	0.3930
Others	0.2411	0.1273	-2.6900	0.0070	0.3191	0.1628	-2.2400	0.0250	0.2258	0.1247	-2.6900	0.0070	0.2151	0.1168	-2.8300	0.0050	1.1735	0.9252	0.2000	0.8390	0.2145	0.1016	-3.2500	0.0010
Expectation																								
Current data	0.8673	0.3468	-0.3600	0.7220	0.5774	0.1771	-1.7900	0.0730	1.0463	0.3840	0.1200	0.9020	0.5976	0.1741	-1.7700	0.0770	2.2437	0.7986	2.2700	0.0230	0.8613	0.1952	-0.6600	0.5100
Past and Current data	0.7472	0.2631	-0.8300	0.4080	0.6825	0.1904	-1.3700	0.1710	0.7907	0.2521	-0.7400	0.4620	0.7083	0.1870	-1.3100	0.1920	1.4495	0.4830	1.1100	0.2650	0.8591	0.1736	-0.7500	0.4520
Others	0.3217	0.1322	-2.7600	0.0060	0.3638	0.1199	-3.0700	0.0020	0.4337	0.1659	-2.1800	0.0290	0.4096	0.1303	-2.8100	0.0050	1.0878	0.4435	0.2100	0.8360	0.5172	0.1272	-2.6800	0.0070
Cons	7.4802	3.6914	4.0800	0.0000	7.5479	2.9973	5.0900	0.0000	15.2000	7.1601	5.7800	0.0000	10.1824	3.9309	6.9309	6.1000	0.0390	0.0195	-6.5000	0.0000	-3.0013	0.3074	empty	empty

Source: Author

7.5 Summary

This chapter contributes to the literature on central bank communication by investigating the public's understanding of monetary policy in Nigeria. It deviates from the dominant approach where the financial sector is treated as synonymous with the public. The questionnaire developed by Cruijssen *et al.* (2015) was modified and used for data gathering while a pilot was conducted prior to the main survey. The information gathered were presented graphically and further analyzed using the logistic regression techniques and the key results are as follows:

- a) Gender is not a determinant of how respondents are conversant about monetary policy.
- b) Age plays a key role as older respondents are more likely to be more conversant about monetary policy.
- c) Higher educational qualification does not increase the likelihood of being well-informed about monetary policy.
- d) Respondents in the real sector tend to be more conversant about monetary policy compared with those in the financial, government and in 'other' sectors.
- e) In line with Cruijssen *et al.* (2015), those with desire to be well-informed appear to be more knowledgeable about monetary policy.
- f) Work experience increases the likelihood of being well-conversant about monetary policy.
- g) Higher income earners are more likely to be well-knowledgeable about monetary policy.
- h) Users of Newspapers, CBN's website, Radio and Television tend to be more aware about monetary policy compared with those that depend on magazines, social media, and contacts.
- i) Using past information, current information, or both, does not influence the likelihood of being conversant about monetary policy.

In conclusion, the public's knowledge of monetary policy in Nigeria is influenced by age, work experience and income levels. Also, the CBN's press briefing which is usually held after the committee meeting, and where print and electronic media representatives are present, is yielding result as Newspapers, Radio and Television help improve awareness of monetary policy. In addition, the CBN should continue to improve the content and simplicity of its website as it is a key source of acquiring information and knowledge of monetary policy.

CHAPTER EIGHT: Summary, Conclusion and Recommendations

8.1 Summary

This thesis contributes to the literature on central bank communication from a developing economy perspective. It is mainly empirical and examined the communication of monetary policy by the CBN from the viewpoints of clarity of communication, quantifying communication and ascertaining the transmission effects, measuring the intensity with which the CBN communicated about fiscal policy, as well as gauging the public's knowledge of monetary policy in Nigeria.

The objectives of the study, the associated research questions, the methodologies and main results are as follows:

1) **Objective 1:** Examine the clarity of monetary policy communication by the CBN.

a) Research questions

- i. How clear is the CBN in its communication of monetary policy?
- ii. How sensitive is the clarity to changes in key macroeconomic indicators?

b) Methodology

- i. The Flesch Kincaid and the Gunning Fog Index were used to measure clarity while the OLS multiple regression technique was applied for the estimation in line with Mathur and Sengupta (2019).
- ii. To provide further insight into how clarity respond to changes in key macro variables, the OLS technique was complemented with the IRF and VD techniques of the VAR model.

c) Results

- i. The number of paragraphs, sentences and words of the communiqués issued by the CBN between 2001 and 2018 increased over time. This implies increased transparency by the CBN.
- ii. The communiqués were difficult to understand as the Flesch Kincaid and Gunning Fog Index scores were higher than the required minimum. The findings contrast Bulíř *et al.* (2008) and Jansen and Jakob de Haan (2010) that found the ECB's communication to be clear; Bulíř and Šmídková (2008) that showed that the Czech National Bank provided clear messages in about three

out of every four observations; and Omotosho (2019) that found that the press releases of the Bank of Ghana have become clearer. The outcomes are however similar to Mathur and Sengupta (2019), Tumala and Omotosho (2019) and Calixte *et. al.* (2020) that found that the statements of the Reserve Bank of India, the CBN and the Bank of Indonesia have become more complex due to the word and sentence structures.

- iii. The regression results showed that the explanatory variables described about 29% of the variation in the Flesch Kincaid. Their joint influence is significant given the F-statistics and the associated p-value. The residual diagnostic showed that the model did not violate the serial correlation and heteroskedasticity assumptions, while the residuals are normally distributed, and CUSUM stability plot indicate model stability.
- iv. The effects of credit and fiscal deficit are significant on clarity as the credit channel is important in policy transmission while the challenge of fiscal dominance has receded with measures such as the oil-price based fiscal rule introduced in 2003 and the ensuing the ECA, as well as the SWF.
- v. The IRF showed that the response of Flesch Kincaid to shocks to the explanatory variables was not significant and were not reported. However, the variance decomposition outcome showed that the variations in the clarity indicator was largely due to own effect, implying that the explanatory variables did not explain much of the variance.

2) **Objective 2:** Measure CBN's monetary policy communication by developing two indicators, the *Monetary Policy Stance* (MPS) that reflects the multiple aims and tools and the *Monetary Policy Communication on Inflation* (MPCI) that captures the statements on inflation. The two measures were used to study the role of communication in the transmission process.

a) Research questions

- i. What was CBN's pattern of tightening, loosening and neutral stance and how did it communicate about *Upside, Downside or Neutral* position on inflation?
- ii. To what extent does communication enhance monetary policy transmission in Nigeria?

b) Methodology

- i. Communication of the CBN was measured using the heuristic approach to design the MPS and MPCCI.
- ii. The MPS was developed in line with the conventional method of coding tightening (+1), hold (0) and loosening (-1) postures used by Ehrmann and Fratzscher (2007), Jansen and De Haan (2009) and Lehtimäki and Palmu (2019)
- iii. The MPCCI was designed based on the approach of the ECB KOF Monetary Policy Communicator.
- iv. The empirical analysis followed Neuenkirch (2013) that estimated the monetary policy transmission of the ECB by adding the ECB KOF Communicator in a VAR framework. Also, the study by CBN's research department in 2010 on monetary policy transmission in Nigeria provided guide in terms of the equations estimated, which were augmented with the MPS and MPCCI. Another study that provided direction for estimation is Hosny and Sullivan (2018) where the BDC exchange rate was incorporated in an exchange rate equation.
- v. The estimations were carried out using the ARDL/Bounds testing approach to cointegration and the Error Correction Model where the coefficients showed the speed of adjustment to equilibrium and long-run and short-run causality. The rationale for applying the ARDL/Bounds testing method was because the ADF test for unit root showed that the variables were a mixture of $I(0)$ and $I(1)$.
- vi. The estimated equations were: (1) a baseline model; (2) an augmented baseline model with MPS and MPCCI separately; (3) six equations in the interest rate channel - first, the nominal interest rate equation without communication, with MPS and then with MPCCI. Second, the real interest rate equation without communication, then with MPS and with MPCCI; (4) three equations in the credit channel - that without communication, with MPS and then with MPCCI; (5) six equations for the exchange rate channel - first, the official exchange rate without communication, with MPS and then with MPCCI. Second, the BDC exchange rate equation without communication, with MPS and with MPCCI; (6) three equations in the asset channel - the equation without communication, followed by that with MPS and then with MPCCI.

c) Results

- i. The findings from the descriptive analysis of the MPS showed that between 2001 and 2018 the CBN tightened its stance in 26 or 37% of the communiqués using a combination of the policy rate, OMO sales, CRR and sometimes foreign exchange interventions and withdrawal of public sector funds from commercial banks when government institutions were still allowed to deposit with them. The easing stance was observed in 11 or 16% of the communiqués while it maintained a neutral stance in 33 or 47%. In terms of communication about inflation, the estimated *MPCI* of 0.135 meant that the CBN communicated more about upside risk to inflation in the period.
- ii. The correlation coefficient between voting to increase the policy rate and the *MPCI* is positive but weak, suggesting that, apart from the policy rate, the CBN also uses other instruments like OMO and CRR to manage liquidity and inflation in the short-term.
- iii. The illustration between the *MPCI* and the CBN policy rate showed a paradox because the upside risk sentiments coincided with decreasing or flattening policy rate. The likely reasons for this are: (1) Given the multiple objectives and tools, the CBN sometimes alter other instruments like the OMO and CRR, etc. instead of raising the policy rate. Thus, in the periods where the policy rates were unchanged when the CBN expressed upside risk to inflation sentiments, the other instruments may have been adjusted; (2) It could be that the CBN saw the inflationary threats as temporary and won't exceed the implicit upper limit target of 9% in those periods that it expressed upside risk to inflation sentiments and decided to remain neutral; (3) The policy rate is the most visible tool to the politicians who see raising rates as undermining their preference for economic growth. As such, for some of the periods that the CBN expressed upside risk to inflation sentiments, it may have, for political reasons, adjusted other policy instruments like the OMO and CRR instead of raising the policy rate

iv. The summary of the empirical results are as follows:

- The ARDL/Bounds testing method confirmed cointegration in all the models while the ECTs in the estimated ECMs are negative and significant, implying the presence of long-run causality.
- The low values of the ECTs indicated that the speed of adjustment back to equilibrium was very slow in all the models, with or without communication. It thus suggested that communication did not improve the transmission of monetary policy in Nigeria in the period reviewed. Given that the fundamental goal of communication is to manage expectations, the inference is that the result reinforces the findings of CBN's research department in 2010 that found weak existence of policy transmission through the inflation expectations channel.
- The models with MPCCI performed relatively better than the ones with MPS that considers communication about general policy stance in line with the multiple objectives and instruments. This strengthens the view by Hosny and Sullivan (2018) that the transmission of monetary policy in Nigeria is weak because of the multiple objectives and instruments that send conflicting signals to the markets.
- In the augmented baseline model, communication with MPS weakens the transmission process compared with MPCCI. This suggests that CBN's tightening or loosening with multiple tools sends mixed signals.
- In the credit channel, the model with MPS also reverts more sluggishly to equilibrium compared with the model without communication and with MPCCI, also indicating that the multiplicity of tools impairs the transmission process.
- In the exchange rate channel, communication slightly improved transmission with BDC rate and MPCCI but weakened with MPS. This shows that transmission is weaker when CBN's tightening and easing stance are considered compared with talk about inflation.
- In the asset channel, communication with MPCCI improved the transmission process compared with MPS that weakened transmission.

- In the interest rate channel, communication with MPS marginally improved transmission of policy when nominal rate is considered, and neutral with real interest rate.
 - The ranking of all the models with both MPS and MPCCI showed that the effect of communication is relatively highest in the asset channel with MPCCI, followed by the credit channel with MPCCI and then the augmented model with MPCCI. The exchange rate channel with the BDC rate and MPCCI, and that with the official rate with MPCCI were next.
 - Given that the top models are those with MPCCI, it suggests that communication about inflation have relatively better effect on the transmission process when compared with communication about the general policy stance that considers the multiple objectives of the CBN.
 - Overall, the findings strengthen the hypothesis that because the CBN deals with multiple objectives and uses different policy instruments to achieve them, communicating the policy stance by using multiple tools for tightening or easing, often results in mixed signals that impair the transmission of policy. However, communication about inflation is less confusing, hence its relatively better effect on the transmission process.
- v. The results of the short-run causality are as follows:
- MS granger-causes GDP and Inflation; there is bi-directional causality between MPCCI and inflation; and MPS granger-causes GDP.
 - In the credit channel, CRD granger-causes GDP; INF granger-causes CRD; and CRD granger-causes MS.
 - In the asset channel, MPS granger-causes ASI.
 - Interest Rate Channel - bidirectional causality between GDP and RIBR; MPR and MS granger-cause GDP; MS and MPCCI granger-cause RIBR and MPR granger-cause MPS.
 - The short-run causality results underpin the importance that the CBN attaches to monetary targeting given that money supply granger-causes GDP and inflation. Also, the CBN's tightening and easing postures as

captured in the MPS is important for short-run macroeconomic management given that the MPS granger-causes GDP.

3) **Objective 3:** Quantify the intensity of CBN's communication about fiscal policy by developing a *Fiscal Policy Communication Indicator* (FPCI).

a) Research questions

- i. How strongly does the CBN communicate about fiscal policy?
- ii. To what degree is this intensity influenced by changes in key macroeconomic variables?

b) Methodology

- i. A template was designed and used to develop the FPCI in line with the approach of Allard *et al.* (2013) where communication about fiscal policy was grouped into the following categories: positive, normative, references to fiscal policy as an input to the central bank's forecast, references to government's financing instruments, and references to the fiscal policy in other countries.
- ii. The designed template was used to categorize the CBN's communication about these aspects of fiscal policy statements.
- iii. The empirical analysis also followed Allard *et al.* (2013) that used OLS regression to explore the connection between intensity of fiscal policy deliberations and events in the larger economy. This study complemented the OLS technique with the IRF and VD in order to gain further insight.

c) Results

- i. A total of 51 statements and 2,812 words or average 1.8% of the total word count of all the communiqués were used to talk about *positive fiscal policy statements*.
- ii. The discussions on *normative fiscal policy statements* saw the use of 76 statements and 4,141 words or average 1.95% of the total word count of all the communiqués.
- iii. The reference to *fiscal policy as an input to or outcome of central bank forecasts* saw the CBN using 136 statements and 7,439 words or 4.56% to discuss the matter.

- iv. In referring to *government financing instruments (bonds and treasury bills)*, the bank used 99 statements and 3,425 words or 2.65% of total word count.
 - v. A total of 47 statements and 2,376 words or 0.85% of total word count were used to refer to *fiscal policies in other countries*.
 - vi. Overall, 409 statements and 20,193 words or 11.82% of total word count of all the communiqués were used to discuss fiscal policy between 2001 and 2018.
- d) Juxtaposing the FPCI with key policy events, it was observed that the CBN communicated more positively about fiscal policy between 2004 and 2005 when the oil-price based fiscal rule was introduced. The creation of the SWF in 2011 resulted in more normative fiscal policy statements as the CBN's posture changed from commendation to advisory. Generally, communication about fiscal policy increased in the period of the oil-price based fiscal rule and the creation of the SWF.
- e) The OLS estimation showed that fiscal deficit and inflation have significant effect on FPCI because the size and financing modes of deficit are important, and the likely inflationary effects are also crucial. Although the effect of public debt is positive, it is insignificant while the effect of money supply growth is also insignificant.
- f) The IRF results showed that the response of FPCI to shocks to fiscal deficit dies out while its response to public debt is positive for the entire period. This is because the CBN over time discusses how the accumulated debt is used to implement projects that affect aggregate demand in the economy. The response of FPCI to money supply growth is significant in quarter 3, the same single quarter in which the deficit variable is significant. The response of FPCI to money supply growth is significant in quarter 3 (the same single quarter in which the deficit variable is significant). Finally, the response of FPCI to shock to inflation is positive for most of the period but the effect vanishes because ultimately, inflation in the long-term is a monetary phenomenon. The variance decomposition results showed that about 77% of the FEV in the FPCI is due to own effect. This means that the explanatory variables contributed little in terms of the variance in FPCI.
- g) In terms of the direction of causality, FPCI is granger-caused by fiscal deficit, public debt, and money supply, while it is not granger-caused by inflation. The combined effect of all the indicators showed that they all granger caused FPCI.

4) **Objective 4:** Investigate the extent to which the public in Nigeria understand the monetary policy objectives and instruments of the CBN.

a) Research questions

- i. What are the determinants of monetary policy knowledge in Nigeria?
- ii. What are the major sources of getting information on about monetary policy?
- iii. To what extent do the sources influence knowledge of monetary policy?

b) Methodology

- i. The questionnaire developed by Cruijsen *et al.* (2015) was modified and used for data gathering while a pilot was conducted prior to the main survey.
- ii. The information gathered were presented graphically and further analyzed using the logistic regression techniques.

c) Results

- i. Gender is not a factor in respondents' familiarity about monetary policy.
- ii. Age plays a key role as older respondents are more likely to be more conversant about monetary policy.
- iii. Higher educational qualification does not increase the likelihood of being well-informed about monetary policy.
- iv. Respondents in the real sector tend to be more conversant about monetary policy compared with those in the financial, government and in 'other' sectors.
- v. In line with Cruijsen *et al.* (2015), those with desire to be well-informed appear to be more knowledgeable about monetary policy.
- vi. Work experience increases the likelihood of being well-conversant about monetary policy.
- vii. Higher income earners are more likely to be conversant about monetary policy.
- viii. Users of Newspapers, CBN's website, Radio and Television tend to be more aware about monetary policy compared with those that depend on magazines, social media, and contacts.
- ix. Using current information, past information or both does not influence the likelihood of being conversant about monetary policy.

8.2 Conclusion

Based on the findings, the study concludes as follows:

- a) CBN's communication of monetary policy through the policy communiqué is complex.
- b) The transmission mechanism of monetary policy was not enhanced by communication in the review period. However, communication about inflation performed relatively better than communication about the general policy stance based on the multiple objectives and instruments of the CBN.
- c) The discussions about fiscal policy have expectedly increased over the years, with the CBN's positive communication increasing in periods of strategic fiscal policy initiatives.
- d) The public's knowledge of monetary policy is enhanced by age, income and the media reporting through Newspapers, Television and Radio. The CBN's website is also instrumental for improving the public's awareness of monetary policy.

8.3 Recommendations

The following recommendations are drawn from the conclusions:

- a) To improve clarity, CBN should devise means of explicitly conveying its multiple objectives and tools and also simplify its vocabularies and choice of words.
- b) The transmission process can also be enhanced if clarity improves with simplification of vocabularies and choice of words.
- c) Commending government when certain actions are taken and advising them to take firm measures in some instances will improve monetary-fiscal bond.
- d) The press briefing channel of communication is effective as those who get information through Newspapers and TV are conversant about the CBN's policy objectives and instruments.

8.4 Limitations of the study

- a) Comparative study with another oil-exporting country would have provided more insight.
- b) Subjectivity in classifying and coding inflation and fiscal policy related statements.
- c) The bi-directional causalities could have been addressed using the Structural VAR.
- d) Analysis of survey data using binary instead of multinomial logit.

References

- Afolabi, J. and Atolagbe, O. (2018).** ‘Empirical Analysis of Fiscal Dominance and the conduct of Monetary Policy in Nigeria’. [https://mpira.ub.uni-muenchen.de/88786/MPRA Paper No. 88786](https://mpira.ub.uni-muenchen.de/88786/MPRA_Paper_No.88786), Accessed December 14, 2020.
- Akinmade, B., Adedoyin, F., and Bekun, F. (2020).** ‘The Impact of Stock Market Manipulation on Nigeria’s Economic Performance’. *Economic Structures*, No. 9, 52.
- Allard, J., Catenaro, M., Vidal, J., and Wolswijk, G. (2013).** ‘Central Bank Communication on Fiscal Policy’. *European Journal of Political Economy*, vol. 30(C), pp. 1-14.
- Alper, C. (2006).** ‘U.S. Monetary Policy Surprises and Emerging Markets Sovereign Spreads’. *AEA Conference Papers*.
- Amato, J. and Shin, H. (2003).** ‘Public and Private Information in Monetary Policy Models’. *DNB Staff Report No. 117*.
- Amaya, D. and Filbien, J. (2015).** ‘The Similarity of ECB’s Communication’. *Finance Research Letters*, vol. 13, pp. 234-242.
- Andersson, M. (2007).** ‘Using Intraday Data to Gauge Financial Market responses to FED and ECB Monetary Policy Decisions’. *ECB Working Paper*, No 726.
- Apel, M. and Grimaldi, B. (2012).** ‘The Information Content of Central Bank Minutes’. *Sveriges Riksbank Working Paper Series*, No. 261.
- Armelius, H., Bertsch, C., Hull, I. and Zhang, X. (2018).** ‘Spread the Word: International Spillovers from Central Bank Communication’. *Working Paper Series 357*, Sveriges Riksbank.
- Arora, V. and Cerisola, M. (2001).** ‘How Does U.S. Monetary Policy Influence Sovereign Spreads in Emerging Markets?’. *IMF Staff Papers*, 48(3):3-3.
- Atoi, N. (2018).** ‘Non-performing Loan and its Effects on Banking Stability: Evidence from National and International Licensed Banks in Nigeria’. *CBN Journal of Applied Statistics*, vol. 9 No. 2, pp. 43-74.
- Baeriswyl, R. (2007).** ‘Central Bank’s Action and Communication’. *Munich Discussion Paper*, No. 10.
- Bailey, A., and Schonhardt-Bailey, C. (2008).** ‘Does Deliberation Matter in FOMC Monetary Policymaking? The Volcker Revolution of 1979’. *Political Analysis*, vol. 16, No. 4, Special Issue: The Statistical Analysis of Political Text (Autumn 2008), pp. 404-427.
- Baskaya, Y., Gulsen, E., and Kara, H. (2012).** ‘Inflation Expectations and Central Bank Communication in Turkey’. *Central Bank Review*, vol. 12, No. 2, pp. 1-10.

- Bennania, H., Fanta, N., Gertler, P., and Horvath, R. (2019).** ‘Does Central Bank Communication Signal Future Monetary Policy? The Case of the ECB’. *IES Working Paper*, 12/2019.
- Bennani, H. (2014).** ‘Does one word fit all? The Asymmetric Effects of Central Banks’ Communication Policy’. *MPRA Paper 57150*, University Library of Munich, Germany.
- Bennani, H. and Neuenkirch, M. (2014).** ‘The (Home) Bias of European Central Bankers: New Evidence Based on Speeches’. *Research Papers in Economics 2014-16*, University of Trier, Department of Economics.
- Bholat, D., Hansen, S., Santos, P., and Schonhardt-Bailey, C. (2015).** ‘Text Mining for Central Banks, *SSRN Electronic Journal*, No. 33, pp.1-19.
- Binder, C. (2017).** ‘FED Speak on Main Street: Central Bank Communication and Household Expectations’. *Journal of Macroeconomics*, vol.52, pp. 238-251.
- Blinder, A. Ehrmann, M. Fratzscher, M. Jakob, De Haan and David-Jan, J. (2008).** ‘Central Bank Communication and Monetary Policy - A Survey of Theory and Evidence’. *Journal of Economic Literature*, vol. 46(4), pp. 910-45.
- Blinder, A. Goodhart, C. Hildebrand, P Lipton, D. and Wyplosz, C. (2001).** *How Do Central Banks Talk?* Geneva Reports on the World Economy 3, Geneva/London: ICMB/CEPR.
- Böhm, J., Saxa, B., and Kral, P. (2012).** ‘The Czech National Bank's Monetary Policy in the Media’. *European Journal of Political Economy*, vol. 28(3), pp.341–357.
- Born, B. Ehrmann, M. and Fratzscher, M. (2011)** ‘Central Bank Communication on Financial Stability, *ECB Working Paper Series*, No. 1332.
- Brand, C., Buncic, D., and Turunen, J. (2006).** ‘The Impact of ECB Monetary Policy Decisions and Communication on the Yield Curve’. *Journal of the European Economic Association*, 8(657).
- Brière, M. (2009).** ‘Market Reactions to Central Bank Communication Policies: Reading Interest Rate Options Smiles, *CEB Working Paper*, No. 06/009.
- Bryan, M. and Venkatu, G. (2001).** ‘The Demographics of Inflation Opinion Surveys’. *Economic Commentary*, Federal Reserve Bank of Cleveland.
- Budget Office of the Federation, Nigeria –** Various Editions of the Medium-Term Expenditure Framework, <https://www.budgetoffice.gov.ng/index.php/resources/internal-resources/policy-documents/mtef>, Accessed on different dates.
- Bulíř, A. Martin, Č. and David-Jan, J. (2014).** ‘Does the Clarity of Inflation Reports Affect Volatility in Financial Markets? *IMF Working Paper*, WP/14/175.
- Bulíř, A. and Šmídková, K. (2008).** ‘Striving to be “Clearly Open” and “Crystal Clear”: Monetary Policy Communication of the CNB’. *IMF Working Paper*, WP/08/84.

Bulíř, A. Martin, C. and Katerina, S. (2012). ‘Writing Clearly: The ECB’s Monetary Policy Communication’ *German Economic Review*: 1–23.

Bulíř, A. Kateřina, Š. Viktor, K. and David, N. (2008). ‘Inflation Targeting and Communication: It Pays Off to Read Inflation Reports, *IMF Working Paper*, WP/08/234.

Bulíř, A. Martin, Č. and David-Jan, J. (2012). ‘Clarity of Central Bank Communication About Inflation, *IMF Working Paper*, WP/12/9.

Bulíř, A. Jaromír, H. and Kateřina, Š. (2014). ‘Inflation Reports and Models: How Well Do Central Banks Really Write? *IMF Working Paper*, WP/14/91.

Calixte, A., Isnawangsih, A., Shah, N. and Ting, Y. (2020). ‘The Impact of Monetary Policy Communication in an Emerging Economy: The Case of Indonesia’. *IMF Working Paper*, WP/20/109.

Cannon, S. (2015). ‘Sentiment of the FOMC: unscripted’. *Economic Review*, Fall 2015, p. 55.

Carroll, C. (2003). ‘Macroeconomic Expectations of Households and Professional Forecasters’. *Quarterly Journal of Economics*, vol. 118, No. 1.

Carvalho, C. and Nechio, F. (2014). ‘Do People Understand Monetary Policy? *Journal of Monetary Economics*, vol.66, pp. 108-123.

Carvalho, C. Cordeiro, F. and Vargas, J. (2014). ‘Just Words? A Quantitative Analysis of the Communication of the Central Bank of Brazil’. *Texto Para Discussão*, No. 617.

Central Bank of Nigeria Act 2007,

<https://www.cbn.gov.ng/OUT/CIRCULARS/CSD/2007/CBN%20ACT%202007.PDF>, Accessed July 2018.

Central Bank of Nigeria (2010). *Monetary Policy Transmission Mechanism in Nigeria*, Research Department Publication.

Chague, F. De-Losso, R. Giovannetti, B. and Manoel, P. (2015). ‘Central Bank Communication Affects the Term-Structure of Interest Rates’. *Revista Brasileira de Economia*, vol. 69, No. 2, pp. 147–162.

Connolly, E. and Kohler, M. (2004). ‘News and Interest Rate Expectations: A Study of Six Central Banks’. *Reserve Bank of Australia Research Discussion Paper 10*.

Conrad, C. and Lamla, M. (2010). ‘The High-Frequency Response of the EUR-US Dollar Exchange Rate to ECB Monetary Policy Announcements’. *KOF Working Papers No. 174*.

Coppel, C. and Connolly, E. (2003). ‘What Do Financial Market Data Tell Us About Monetary Policy Transparency? *Research Discussion Paper 2003-05*.

Crujisen, C. Jansen, D. and Jakob, D. (2015). ‘How Much Does the Public Know About the ECB’s Monetary Policy? Evidence from a Survey of Dutch Households’. *International Journal of Central Banking*, vol. 11, No. 4, pp. 169 – 218.

Cukierman, A. (2001). *Accountability, Credibility, Transparency and Stabilization Policy in the Eurosystem, in the Impact of EMU on Europe and the Developing Countries*, Wyplosz, C. (ed.), Oxford University Press, pp.40-75.

Cukierman, A. (2008). ‘The Limits of Transparency’. *Paolo Baffi Centre Research Paper No.31*

Dale, S. Orphanides, A., and Osterholm, P. (2008). ‘*Imperfect central bank communication: Information versus distraction*’. *IMF working paper*, No. 08/60.

Debt Management Office, Nigeria – 2018 Annual Report,
<https://www.dmo.gov.ng/publications/reports/dmo-annual-report-statement-of-accounts/3060-2018-annual-report>, Accessed December 2020.

Demertzis, M. and Hoerberichts, M. (2007). ‘The Costs of Increasing Transparency’. *Open Economies Review*, vol. 18(3), pp. 263-280.

Demiralp, S. (2001). ‘Monetary Policy in a Changing World: Rising Role of Expectations and the Anticipation Effect’, *Finance and Economics Discussion Series 2001-55*.

Demiralp, S. Kara, H. Pinar, Ö. (2011). ‘Monetary Policy Communication in Turkey’. *European Journal of Political Economy*, col. 28, No. 4, pp. 540–556.

Égert, B. and Kočenda, E. (2014). ‘The Impact of Macro News and Central Bank Communication on Emerging European Forex Markets’, *Economic Systems*, 38(1).

Ehrmann, M. and Fratzscher, M. (2009). ‘Explaining Monetary Policy in Press Conferences’, *International Journal of Central Banking*, vol. 5 No. 2, pp. 41 – 84.

Ehrmann, M. and Fratzscher, M. (2007). ‘Transparency, Disclosure and the Federal Reserve’ *International Journal of Central Banking*, vol. 3 No. 1, pp. 179-225.

Eijffinger, S. Hoerberichts, M. and Tesfaselassie, M. (2004). ‘Central Bank Communication and Output Stabilization’, *CEPR Discussion Paper No. 4408*.

Ekkehard, E. and Merola, R. (2018). ‘Central Bank communication: A quantitative assessment’, *ILO Research Department Working Paper No. 33*.

Ekor, M., Adeniyi, O. and Saka, J. (2015). ‘Central bank communication and Monetary Policy Effectiveness: Empirical Evidence from Nigeria’. *Journal of Monetary and Economic Integration*, vol. 13, No.1, pp. 118 – 152.

El-Shagi, M. and Jung, A. (2015). ‘Have Minutes Helped Markets to Predict the MPC's Monetary Policy Decisions?’, *European Journal of Political Economy*, vol. 39, pp. 222-234.

Eusepi, S. and Preston, B. (2010). ‘Central Bank Communication and Expectations Stabilization’, *American Economic Journal: Macroeconomics*, vol. 2, No. 3, pp. 235-271.

Eyup, K. and Odaba, A. (2016). ‘Central Banks Communication Strategy and Content Analysis of Monetary Policy Statements: The Case of FED, ECB and CBRT’ *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, Vol. 235, pp. 618-629.

Ezema, C. (2009). ‘Monetary Policy Framework in Nigeria: Formulation and Implementation Challenges’. *African Institute of Applied Economics (AIAE): Monthly Seminar*.

Farka, M. (2011). ‘The Asymmetric Impact Of “Informative” And “Uninformative” Federal Open Market Committee Statements on Asset Prices’. *Contemporary Economic Policy*, vol. 29, Issue 4, pp. 469 – 493.

Farka, M. and Fleissig, A. (2013). The Impact of FOMC Statements on the Volatility of Asset Prices’. *Journal of Applied Economics*, vol. 45, Issue 10, pp. 1287-1301.

Fiscal Responsibility Act – 2007, Nigeria,

<http://lawsfnigeria.placng.org/laws/fiscal%20responsibility.pdf>, Accessed July 15, 2018.

Fischer, A. and Ranaldo, A. (2011). ‘Does FOMC News Increase Global FX Trading? *Journal of Banking and Finance*, vol. 35, No. 11, pp. 2965-73.

Fligstein, N., Brundage, J. S., and Schultz, M. (2014). ‘Why the Federal Reserve Failed to See the Financial Crisis of 2008: The Role of “Macroeconomics” as a Sense Making and Cultural Frame. IRLE Working Paper, 111 -14. <http://irle.berkeley.edu/workingpapers/111-14.pdf>, Accessed Feb. 10, 2019.

Fracasso, A. Genberg, H. and Wyplosz, C. (2003). ‘How Do Central Banks Write? An Evaluation of Inflation Targeting Central Banks’. *Geneva Reports on the World Economy Special Report 2*.

Fukač, M. (2006). ‘New Keynesian Model Dynamics under Heterogenous Expectations and Adaptive Learning’. *Czech National Bank Working Paper No. 5*.

Gábel, P. and Pintér, K. (2006). ‘The Effect of the MNB’s Communication on Financial Markets’. *MNB Working Papers 2006/9*.

Garcia-Herrero, A. and Girardin, E. (2013). ‘China’s Monetary Policy Communication: Money Markets Not Only Listen, but they also Understand’. *HKIMR Working Paper No.02*.

Geraats, P. (2001). ‘Why Adopt Transparency? The Publication of Central Bank Forecasts’. *ECB Working Paper No 41*.

Geraats, P. (2007). ‘Political Pressures and Monetary Mystique’. *CESifo Working Paper Series, No. 1999*.

Gizatulina, A. (2012). ‘Interpreting How Others Interpret It: Social Value of Public Information’. *CESifo Working Paper Series 3787, CESifo Group Munich*.

Goyal, A., and Arora, S. (2010). ‘The Indian Exchange Rate and Central Bank Action: A GARCH analysis’.

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/46435390_The_Indian_exchange_rate_and_central_bank_action_A_GARCH_analysis/link/55f13f1e08ae0af8ee1d504b/download, Cited July 5, 2019

Grimaldi, M. (2011). ‘Up for count? Central bank words and financial stress’. *Sveriges Riksbank Working Paper Series No. 252*.

Gurkaynak, R. Sack, B. and Swanson, E. (2005). ‘Do Actions Speak Louder than Words? The Response of Asset Prices to Monetary Policy Actions and Statements’. *International Journal of Central Banking*, vol. 1 No. 1, pp. 55-93.

Hagen, J. and Bernoth, K. (2004). ‘The Euribor Futures Market: Efficiency and the Impact of ECB Policy Announcements’. *International Finance*, vol. 7(1), pp.1-24.

Hansen, S. and McMahon, M. (2016). ‘Shocking Language: Understanding the Macroeconomic Effects of Central Bank Communication’. *Journal of International Economics*, vol. 99, Supplement 1, pp. 114-133.

Hansen, S., McMahon, M., and Prat, A. (2018). ‘Transparency and Deliberation Within the FOMC: A Computational Linguistics Approach’. *Quarterly Journal of Economics*, vol. 133, No. 2, pp. 801-870.

..... **(2012)** ‘Bank of Canada Communication, Media Coverage, and Financial Market Reactions’, *Economics Letters*, vol. 115, Issue 3, pp. 369-372.

Hayo, B., Kutan, A. and Neuenkirch, M. (2012). ‘FOMC Communication and Emerging Equity Markets’. *Southern Economic Journal*, vol. 78, No. 3, pp. 1041-1056.

Heenan, G., Marcel, P. and Scott, R. (2006). ‘Implementing Inflation Targeting: Institutional Arrangements, Target Design, and Communications’, *IMF Working Paper WP/06/278*, Monetary and Capital Markets Department.

Heinemann, F. and Ullrich, K. (2007). ‘Does It Pay to Watch Central Bankers’ Lips? The Information Content of ECB Wording’. *Swiss Journal of Economics and Statistics*, vol. 143, Issue 2, pp. 155–185.

Helder, F. and Ivando, S. (2014). ‘Effects of the Brazilian Central Bank Communication on Financial Markets Expectations’. *Macroeconomics and Finance in Emerging Market Economies*, 8 (1-2).

Holmsen, A., Qvigstad, J., Røisland, Q., and Solberg, K. (2008). ‘Communicating Monetary Policy Intentions: The Case of Norges Bank’. *Monetary Policy Dept Working Paper No. 20*.

Horváth, R. and Fiser, R. (2009). ‘Central Bank Communication and Exchange Rate Volatility: A GARCH Analysis’. *William Davidson Institute Working Paper No. 962*.

Horváth, R. and Karas, P. (2013). ‘Central Bank Communication and Interest Rates: The Case of the Czech National Bank’. *Czech Journal of Economics and Finance*, vol. 63, No. 5 pp. 454 – 464.

Hosny and Sullivan (2018). ‘Understanding Monetary Policy in Nigeria’. *IMF Country Report No. 18/64*.

Hubert, P. and Labondance, F. (2019). ‘Central Bank Tone and the Dispersion of Views within Monetary Policy Committees, *Working Papers 2019-08, CRESE*.

International Monetary Fund (2019). ‘IMF Staff Proposal to Update the Monetary and Financial Policies Transparency Code’. *IMF Policy Paper*, Release No. 19/163.

International Monetary Fund (2018). *Credibility, Communication, and Monetary Policy Procyclicality in Latin America*, Chapter 3 in Regional Economic Outlook, April 2018, Western Hemisphere Department: Seizing the Momentum, April (Washington).

International Monetary Fund (1999) ‘Code of Good Practices on Transparency in Monetary and Financial Policies: Declaration of Principles’. <https://www.imf.org/external/np/mae/mft/code/index.htm>, Assessed March 10, 2019.

James, J., and Lawler, P. (2011). ‘Optimal Policy Intervention and the Social Value of Public Information’. *American Economic Review*, vol. 101, No. 4, pp. 1561-74.

Jansen, D., and Jakob de Haan (2003). ‘Statements of ECB officials and their Effect on the Level and Volatility of the Euro-Dollar Exchange Rate’ *Research Memorandum WO no 726*.

..... **(2005)** ‘Is a Word to the Wise Indeed Enough? ECB Statements and the Predictability of Interest Rate Decisions’. *DNB Working Papers 075*, Netherlands Central Bank, Research.

..... **(2005).** ‘Were Verbal Efforts to Support the Euro Effective? A High-Frequency Analysis of ECB Statements, *DNB Working Paper*, No. 033.

Jansen, D., and Jakob de Haan (2010). ‘An Assessment of the Consistency of ECB Communication using Wordscores’. *DNB Working Paper*, No. 259.

Jensen, H. (2002). ‘Optimal Degrees of Transparency in Monetary Policymaking’. *The Scandinavian Journal of Economics*, vol. 104, No. 3, pp. 399-422.

Jonung, L. (1981). ‘Perceived and Expected Rates of Inflation in Sweden’. *The American Economic Review*, vol. 71, No. 5, pp. 961-968.

Jubinski, D. and Tomljanovich, M. (2013). ‘Do FOMC Minutes Matter to Markets? An Intraday Analysis of FOMC Minutes Releases on Individual Equity Volatility and Returns, *Review of Financial Economics*, vol. 22, Issue 3, pp. 86-97.

Kawamura, K. Yohei, K. Masato, S. and Ueda, K. (2019). ‘Strategic Central Bank Communication: Discourse Analysis of the Bank of Japan’s Monthly Report’. *Journal of Economic Dynamics and Control*, vol. 100, pp. 230-250.

King, M. (1995). ‘Commentary: Monetary Policy Implications of Greater Fiscal Discipline’. *Federal Reserve Bank of Kansas City Proceedings*, pp. 71-183.

Kliesen, K., Levine, B., and Waller, C. (2019). ‘Gauging Market Responses to Monetary Policy Communication’. *Federal Reserve Bank of St. Louis Review*, Second Quarter, 101(2), pp. 69-91.

- Knütter, R. Mohr, B. and Wagner, H. (2011).** ‘The Effects of Central Bank Communication on Financial Stability: A Systematization of the Empirical Evidence’. *University of Hagen, Department of Economics Discussion Paper No. 463*.
- Kohn, D. and Sack, B. (2003).** ‘Central Bank Talk: Does It Matter and Why?’ <https://www.federalreserve.gov/pubs/feds/2003/200355/200355pap.pdf>, Accessed Feb 3, 2018.
- Lamlay, M., and Sturm, J. (2013).** ‘Interest Rate Expectations in the Media and Central Bank Communication’. *KOF Working Papers, No. 334*.
- Lamlay, M. and Rupprecht, S. (2006).** ‘The Impact of ECB Communication on Financial Market Expectations’. *Arbeitspapiere/Working Papers No. 135*.
- Lehtimäki, J., and Palmu, M. (2019).** ‘Central Bank Communication and Monetary Policy Predictability under Uncertain Economic Conditions’. *Journal of Central Banking Theory and Practice*, vol. 2, pp. 5-32.
- Lildholdt, P. and Vila, A. (2004).** ‘Anticipation of Monetary Policy in UK Financial Markets’. *Bank of England Working Paper No. 241*.
- Lindner, A. (2007).** ‘Does Too Much Transparency of Central Banks Prevent Agents from Using their Private Information Efficiently?’ *IWH Discussion Papers, No. 16/2007*.
- Lucca, D. and Trebbi, F. (2009).** ‘Measuring Central Bank Communication: An Automated Approach with Application to FOMC Statements’. *NBER Working Papers 15367*.
- Mathur, A. and Sengupta, R. (2019).** ‘Analyzing Monetary Policy Statements of the Reserve Bank of India’. *IHEID Working Papers 08-2019*.
- Meade, E., and Acosta, M. (2015).** ‘Hanging on Every Word: Semantic Analysis of the FOMC's post-meeting statement’. *FEDS Notes*.
- McCredie, B. Docherty, P. Easton, S. and Uylangco, K. (2014).** ‘The Differential Impact of Monetary Policy Announcements and Explanatory Minutes Releases on the Australian Interest Rate Futures Market’. *Pacific-Basin Finance Journal*, vol. 29, No. 10, pp. 261-271.
- McMahon, M., Schipke, A., and LI Xiang (2019).** *Monetary Policy Communication: Frameworks and Market Impact*, In Longmei, eds. 2019. *The Future of China's Bond Market*. Washington, DC: International Monetary Fund.
- Middeldorp, M. (2011).** ‘FOMC Communication Policy and the Accuracy of FED Funds Futures’. *Federal Reserve Bank of New York Staff Reports*, No. 491.
- Montes, G. and Acer, T. (2018).** ‘Fiscal credibility and disagreement in expectations about inflation: Evidence for Brazil’. *Economics Bulletin*, vol. 38(2), pp.826-843.
- Montes, G. Nicolay, R. and Acer, T. (2019).** ‘Do Fiscal Communication and Clarity of Fiscal Announcements Affect Public Debt Uncertainty? Evidence from Brazil’. *Journal of Economics and Business*, vol. 103, pp. 38-60.

- Morris, M. Shin, H. and Tong, H. (2006).** ‘Response to Social Value of Public Information: Morris and Shin (2002) Is Actually Pro Transparency, Not Con’. <https://www.nuffield.ox.ac.uk/users/Shin/PDF/svenssonresponse.pdf>, Accessed Feb 3, 2018.
- Morris, M. and Shin, H. (2007).** ‘Optimal Communication’ *Journal of the European Economic Association*, vol. 5, No.2, pp. 594–602.
- Morris, M. and Shin, H. (2002).** ‘Social Value of Public Information’. *The American Economic Review*, vol. 92, No. 5, pp. 1521-1534.
- Moser-Boehm, P. (2006).** ‘The Relationship between the Central Bank and the Government’. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/292155687_The_relationship_between_the_central_bank_and_the_government, Cited March 12, 2019.
- Muller, P. and Zelmer, M. (1999).** ‘Greater Transparency in Monetary Policy: Impact on Financial Markets’. *Technical Reports 86, Bank of Canada*.
- Musard-Gies, M. (2006).** ‘Do European Central Bank's Statements Steer Interest Rates in the Euro zone? *Manchester School*, 74(s1):116-139.
- Na’allah, N. (2012).** ‘Impact of Central Bank Communications on Exchange Rate Dynamics in Nigeria (2007-2011)’. *Unpublished MSc thesis submitted to the school of post graduate studies, Ahmadu bello University, Zaria, Nigeria*.
- Narayan, P. (2005).** ‘The Saving and Investment Nexus for China: Evidence from Cointegration Tests’. *Applied Economics*, vol. 37, No. 17, pp. 1979-1990.
- Neuenkirch, M. (2013).** ‘Monetary Policy Transmission in Vector Autoregressions: A New Approach Using Central Bank Communication, *Journal of Banking & Finance*, vol. 37, No. 11, pp. 4278-4285.
- Obafemi, N. and Ifere, E. (2015).** ‘Monetary Policy Transmission Mechanism in Nigeria: A Comparative Analysis’. *Research in World Economy*, vol. 6(4), pp. 93-103.
- Ogechi, A., and Ikpesu, F. (2017).** ‘Macroeconomic Determinants of Non-Performing Loans in Nigeria: An Empirical Analysis’. *Journal of Developing Areas*, Tennessee State University, College of Business, vol. 51(2), pages 31-43.
- Okonjo-Iweala, N. (2014).** ‘Responses to the 50 Questions on Nigeria’s Economy Posed by the House of Representatives Committee on Finance’. Federal Ministry of Finance, Nigeria.
- Omosho, B. (2019).** ‘Central Bank Communication in Ghana: Insights from a Text Mining Analysis’. *SSRN Electronic Journal*, December 2019.
- Orphanides, A. (2019).** ‘Monetary Policy Strategy and its Communication’, *Paper prepared for the Federal Reserve Bank of Kansas City 2019 Jackson Hole Economic Policy Symposium*, <https://www.kansascityfed.org/~media/files/publicat/sympos/2019/20190819orphanides.pdf?la=en>, Cited January 5, 2021

- Pesaran, M. (1997).** ‘The Role of Economic Theory in Modelling the Long Run’. *The Economic Journal*, vol. 107, pp. 178-191.
- Pesaran, M., Shin, Y. and Smith, R. (2001).** ‘Bounds Testing Approaches to the Analysis of Level Relationships’. *Journal of Applied Econometrics*, vol. 16, pp. 289-326.
- Pescatori, A. (2018).** ‘Central Bank Communication and Monetary Policy Surprises in Chile’. *IMF Working Paper*, No. 18/156.
- Picault, M. and Renault, T. (2017).** ‘Words Are Not all created Equal: A New Measure of ECB Communication’. *Journal of International Money and Finance*, vol. 79, pp. 136-156.
- Praet, P. (2014).** ‘Current Issues and Challenges for Central Bank Communication’. *ECB Conference on: “The ECB and Its Watchers XV”, Frankfurt, 12 March.*
<https://www.ecb.europa.eu/press/key/date/2014/html/sp140312.en.html>, Cited February 10, 2021
- Rafferty, M. and Tomljanovich, M. (2002).** ‘Central Bank Transparency and Market Efficiency: An Econometric Analysis’. *Journal of Economics and Finance*, vol. 26(2), pp. 150 - 161.
- Reeves, R. and Sawicki, M. (2005).** ‘Do Financial Markets React to Bank of England Communication? *External MPC Unit Discussion Paper No. 15.*
- Reid, M. and Plessis, S. (2009).** ‘Loud and Clear? Can We Hear When the SARB Speaks? *Department of Economics, University of Stellenbosch Working Paper No. 155.*
- Roca, M. (2010).** ‘Transparency and Monetary Policy with Imperfect Common Knowledge’. *IMF Working Paper 10/91.*
- Romer, C. and Romer, D. (2004).** ‘A New Measure of Monetary Shocks: Derivation and Implications’. *The American Economic Review*, vol.94 No.4, pp. 1055 – 1084.
- Rosa, C. and Verga, G. (2005).** ‘Is ECB Communication Effective? *CEP Discussion Paper No 682.*
- Rozkrut, M. Rybińska, K. Sztabaa, L. and Szwajaa, R. (2007).** ‘Quest for Central Bank Communication: Does It Pay to be “Talkative”? *European Journal of Political Economy*, vol. 23, No. 1, pp. 176–206.
- Rozkrut, M. (2008).** ‘It’s Not only WHAT is said, it’s also WHO the speaker is. Evaluating the Effectiveness of Central Bank Communication’. *National Bank of Poland Working Paper No. 47.*
- Sanusi, K., and Akinlo, E. (2016).** ‘Investigating Fiscal Dominance in Nigeria’. *Journal of Sustainable Development*, vol. 9, No. 1.
- Schmidt, S., and D. Nautz (2012).** ‘Central Bank Communication and the Perception of Monetary Policy by Financial Market Experts’. *Journal of Money, Credit and Banking*, 44(2-3), 323-340.
- Shrestha, M., and Bhatta, G. (2018).** ‘Selecting appropriate methodological framework for time series data analysis’, *The Journal of Finance and Data Science*, vol. xx, pp. 1 – 19.

- SHU, C., and B. Ng. (2010).** ‘Monetary Stance and Policy Objectives in China: A Narrative Approach’. *HKMA China Economic Issues*, vol. 1, No. 10, pp. 1–40.
- Sturm, J. and Jakob, D. (2011).** ‘Does Central Bank Communication Really Lead to Better Forecasts of Policy Decisions? New Evidence Based on a Taylor Rule Model for the ECB’. *Rev World Econ* 147:41–58.
- Siklos, P. (2019).** ‘US Monetary Policy since the 1950s and the Changing Content of FOMC Minutes’. https://cama.crawford.anu.edu.au/sites/default/files/publication/cama_crawford_anu_edu_au/2019-09/69_2019_siklos.pdf, Accessed December 15, 2020.
- SUN, R. (2013).** ‘Does Monetary Policy Matter in China? A Narrative Approach’. *China Economic Review*, vol. 26 (C), pp. 56–74.
- Svensson, L. (2006).** ‘Social Value of Public Information: Comment: Morris and Shin (2002) Is actually pro transparency, not con’. *American Economic Review*, vol. 96(1), pp. 448 – 452.
- Su, S., Ahmad, A.H. and Wood, J. (2020).** ‘How Effective is Central Bank Communication in Emerging Economies? An Empirical Analysis of the Chinese Money Markets Responses to the People’s Bank of China’s policy communications. *Rev Quant Finance Acc* **54**, 1195–1219.
- Tang, M. and Yu, X. (2011).** ‘Communication of Central Bank Thinking and Inflation Dynamics’. *IMF Working Papers*, No. 11/209, pp. 1-32.
- Tobback, E., Stefano, N. and Martens, D. (2017).** ‘Between Hawks and Doves: Measuring Central Bank Communication, *ECB Working Paper* 2085.
- Tobias, A., Laxton, D. and Obstfeld, M. (2018).** ‘An Overview of Inflation-Forecast Targeting’. Chapter 1 in *Advancing the Frontiers of Monetary Policy* (Washington: International Monetary Fund).
- Trabelsi, E. (2010).** ‘Central Bank Communication: Fragmentation as an Engine for Limiting the Publicity Degree of Information, <http://mpr.ub.uni-uenchen.de/26647/>Cited Feb. 10, 2018.
- Tumala, M., and Omotosho, B. (2019).** ‘A Text Mining Analysis of Central Bank Monetary Policy Communication in Nigeria’. *Central Bank of Nigeria Journal of Applied Statistics*, vol. 10(2):73-107.
- Ullrich, K. (2007).** ‘Inflation Expectations of Experts and ECB Communication’. *ZEW Discussion Papers*, No. 07-054.
- Umar, A. and Salisu, U. (2016).** ‘Monetary Policy Transparency: Evidence from Central Bank of Nigeria. *Modern Economy*, Vol. 7, pp. 1070-1085.
- Usman, S. (2012).** ‘Impact of Central Bank Communications on Stock Prices in Nigeria’. *Unpublished MSc Thesis submitted to the post graduate school, Ahmadu Bello university, Zaria, Nigeria.*

- Uribe, M. and Yue, V. (2006).** ‘Country Spreads and Emerging Countries: Who Drives Whom?’ *Journal of International Economics*, vol. 69, pp. 6 – 36.
- Vayid, I. (2013).** ‘Central Bank Communications Before, During and After the Crisis: From Open-Market Operations to Open-Mouth Policy’, *Working Paper/Document de travail 2013-41*
- Westelius, N. (2009).** ‘Imperfect Transparency and Shifts in the Central Bank’s Output Gap Target’. *Journal of Economic Dynamics and Control*, vol. 33, pp. 985-996.
- Wongswan, J. (2009).** ‘The Response of Global Equity Indexes to U.S. Monetary Policy Announcements’. *Journal of International Money and Finance*, vol. 28, No. 2, pp. 344-365.
- Wongswan, J. and Hausman, J. (2006).** ‘Global Asset Prices and FOMC Announcements’. *Journal of International Money and Finance*, vol. 30, No. 3, pp. 547-571.
- Yellen, J. (2012).** ‘Revolution and Evolution in Central Bank Communications’. <https://www.federalreserve.gov/newsevents/speech/yellen20121113a.htm>, Assessed March 12, 2019
- Young, J. Kim, S. and Park, Y. (2018).** ‘Deciphering Monetary Policy Committee Minutes with Text Mining Approach: A Case of South Korea’. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. 10.2139/ssrn.3237909.

Appendix 1: Templates for Analyzing Clarity of CBN's Monetary Policy communiqués

Table 1: Template for Extracting Information from Communiques

Communique Details	Readability Tools			
	Gunning Fog Index		Coh-Metrix 3.0	
Date of Meeting		Number of major punctuation marks		Descriptive
Meeting No.		Number of words		Paragraph count, number of paragraphs
Communique No.		Number of 3+ syllable words		Sentence count, number of sentences
Date of Release		Gunning Fog Index Value		Word count, number of words
Communique Signed By ..				Paragraph length, number of sentences in a paragraph, mean
Date Published on Website				Paragraph length, number of sentences in a paragraph, standard deviation
Governor				Sentence length, number of words, mean
				Sentence length, number of words, standard deviation
				Word length, number of syllables, mean
				Word length, number of syllables, standard deviation
				Word length, number of letters, mean
				Word length, number of letters, standard deviation
				Word Information
				Noun incidence
				Verb incidence
				Adjective incidence
				Adverb incidence
				Pronoun incidence
				Clarity Indicators
				Flesch Reading Ease
				Flesch-Kincaid Grade level
				Coh-Metrix L2 Readability

Source: Author

Table 2: Extracted Information for Communique No. 1

Communique Details		Readability Tools			
		Gunning Fog Index		Coh-Metrix 3.0	
Date of Meeting	June 26, 2001	Number of major punctuation marks	39	Descriptive	
Meeting No.	1	Number of words	648	Paragraph count, number of paragraphs	12
Communique No.	1	Number of 3+ syllable words	134	Sentence count, number of sentences	26
Date of Release of Communique	June 30, 2001	Gunning Fog Index Value	14.92	Word count, number of words	656
Communique Signed By ..	No Signatory			Paragraph length, number of sentences in a paragraph, mean	2.167
Date Published on Website	June 30, 2001			Paragraph length, number of sentences in a pragraph, standard deviation	1.03
Governor	Joseph Oladele Sanusi			Sentence length, number of words, mean	25.231
				Sentence length, number of words, standard deviation	15.379
				Word length, number of syllables, mean	1.753
				Word length, number of syllables, standard deviation	1.127
				Word length, number of letters, mean	5.149
				Word length, number of letters, standard deviation	2.872
				Word Information	
				Noun incidence	318.597
				Verb incidence	82.317
				Adjective incidence	97.561
				Adverb incidence	32.012
				Pronoun incidence	15.244
				Clarity Indicators	
				Flesch Reading Ease	32.922
				Flesch-Kincaid Grade level	14.935
				Coh-Metrix L2 Readability	2.264

Source: Author

Table 3: Extracted Information for Communique No. 68

Communique Details		Readability Tools			
		Gunning Fog Index		Coh-Metrix 3.0	
Date of Meeting	March 1-2, 2010	Number of major punctuation marks	155	Descriptive	
Meeting No.	213	Number of words	2541	Paragraph count, number of paragraphs	37
Communique No.	68	Number of 3+ syllable words	536	Sentence count, number of sentences	103
Date of Release of Communique	March 1-2, 2010	Gunning Fog Index Value	15	Word count, number of words	2558
Communique Signed By ..	Sanusi Lamido Sanusi			Paragraph length, number of sentences in a paragraph, mean	2.784
Date Published on Website	March 1-2, 2010			Paragraph length, number of sentences in a paragraph, standard deviation	1.828
Governor	Sanusi Lamido Sanusi			Sentence length, number of words, mean	24.835
				Sentence length, number of words, standard deviation	13.669
				Word length, number of syllables, mean	1.754
				Word length, number of syllables, standard deviation	1.078
				Word length, number of letters, mean	5.265
				Word length, number of letters, standard deviation	2.897
				Word Information	
				Noun incidence	319.39
				Verb incidence	101.251
				Adjective incidence	103.206
				Adverb incidence	29.32
				Pronoun incidence	9.773
				Clarity Indicators	
				Flesch Reading Ease	33.239
				Flesch-Kincaid Grade level	14.793
				Coh-Metrix L2 Readability	7.84

Source: Author

Table 4: Extracted Information for Communique No. 121

Communique Details		Readability Tools			
		Gunning Fog Index		Coh-Metrix 3.0	
Date of Meeting	November 21 and 22, 2018	Number of major punctuation marks	163	Descriptive	
Meeting No.	265	Number of words	2349	Paragraph count, number of paragraphs	47
Communique No.	121	Number of 3+ syllable words	520	Sentence count, number of sentences	104
Date of Release of Communique	22-Nov-18	Gunning Fog Index Value	14.62	Word count, number of words	2364
Communique Signed By ..	Godwin I. Emeziele			Paragraph length, number of sentences in a paragraph, mean	2.213
Date Published on Website	22-Nov-18			Paragraph length, number of sentences in a paragraph, standard deviation	1.444
Governor	Godwin I. Emeziele			Sentence length, number of words, mean	22.731
				Sentence length, number of words, standard deviation	14.514
				Word length, number of syllables, mean	1.768
				Word length, number of syllables, standard deviation	1.047
				Word length, number of letters, mean	5.353
				Word length, number of letters, standard deviation	2.941
				Word Information	
				Noun incidence	332.488
				Verb incidence	101.523
				Adjective incidence	99.408
				Adverb incidence	34.687
				Pronoun incidence	11.421
				Clarity Indicators	
				Flesch Reading Ease	34.19
				Flesch-Kincaid Grade level	14.137
				Coh-Metrix L2 Readability	6.026

Source: Author

Table 5: Extracted Information for Communiques No. 1 - 121

	No. of Paragraphs	No. of Sentences	No. of Words	No. of syllables	Noun incidence	Verb incidence	Adjective incidence	Adverb incidence	Pronoun incidence	Gunning Fog Index	Flesch-Kincaid level
Q2 2001	98.500	181.000	3172.000	1.753	318.597	82.317	97.561	32.012	15.244	14.920	14.935
Q3 2001	75.000	150.500	3057.500	1.726	332.631	79.915	93.039	20.551	8.929	13.423	14.313
Q4 2001	72.000	144.000	2931.500	1.810	344.779	90.913	77.694	27.114	11.931	15.495	16.011
Q1 2002	70.000	140.000	2834.000	1.838	351.241	92.565	84.406	23.343	13.224	15.635	14.919
Q2 2002	68.500	138.500	2807.500	1.787	344.377	98.541	96.352	26.982	7.594	15.140	14.201
Q3 2002	66.000	136.500	2797.000	1.742	316.283	104.089	87.540	26.832	8.521	15.740	14.445
Q4 2002	65.000	134.000	2791.000	1.783	331.010	89.067	101.195	29.486	7.689	16.280	14.402
Q1 2003	59.000	132.500	2678.000	1.760	332.464	93.935	90.753	25.598	5.283	15.340	14.810
Q2 2003	58.000	124.500	2660.000	1.681	341.971	87.124	94.319	35.334	7.346	13.223	13.379
Q3 2003	56.500	123.000	2632.000	1.681	341.971	87.124	94.319	35.334	7.346	12.075	13.379
Q4 2003	56.000	123.000	2606.000	1.681	341.971	87.124	94.319	35.334	7.346	12.075	13.379
Q1 2004	56.000	122.000	2606.000	1.753	323.282	88.816	97.588	36.550	10.691	14.235	13.776
Q2 2004	53.000	120.667	2547.500	1.690	324.544	95.893	95.791	38.107	11.271	11.420	14.707
Q3 2004	52.500	119.000	2545.000	1.650	316.331	106.394	111.694	22.680	14.303	13.913	13.348
Q4 2004	52.500	119.000	2364.000	1.621	298.206	99.960	94.957	28.904	12.183	11.263	12.037
Q1 2005	52.000	114.000	2338.000	1.627	300.000	109.090	97.728	22.727	6.818	10.390	11.780
Q2 2005	52.000	114.000	2294.000	1.692	301.483	97.198	95.551	32.949	3.295	12.620	12.266
Q3 2005	51.000	114.000	2221.000	1.692	301.483	97.198	95.551	32.949	3.295	12.620	12.266
Q4 2005	51.000	113.000	2215.000	1.688	309.205	97.562	100.708	39.339	11.802	14.260	12.323
Q1 2006	51.000	111.500	2205.500	1.766	322.076	87.315	117.793	38.715	9.885	15.290	12.422
Q2 2006	50.000	111.000	2159.500	1.621	315.789	89.374	97.319	24.826	10.924	11.290	11.090
Q3 2006	49.500	109.000	2126.500	1.690	319.270	85.520	98.061	33.068	13.683	11.870	10.460
Q4 2006	48.000	104.000	2086.500	1.771	348.838	102.991	96.345	21.595	6.645	18.610	15.090
Q1 2007	47.000	103.000	2059.000	1.719	319.753	93.827	106.173	20.988	4.938	13.440	11.415
Q2 2007	47.000	102.000	2058.500	1.622	321.731	85.607	80.903	29.162	6.585	11.520	11.087
Q3 2007	46.000	102.000	2058.000	1.610	327.664	85.033	99.774	26.077	5.669	11.770	11.226
Q4 2007	45.500	101.000	2027.500	1.646	322.156	92.216	92.215	26.347	5.988	12.175	11.070
Q1 2008	44.500	98.000	1966.000	1.703	295.973	81.611	130.576	34.820	9.793	13.810	12.297
Q2 2008	44.000	98.000	1928.000	1.730	318.346	89.927	127.698	25.180	9.592	12.650	12.504
Q3 2008	44.000	93.000	1906.500	1.656	302.074	89.204	120.704	34.024	9.919	13.845	12.001
Q4 2008	41.500	91.000	1881.000	1.710	278.409	106.061	130.682	35.985	7.576	15.080	11.689
Q1 2009	41.000	91.000	1862.000	1.722	315.773	106.222	104.910	27.717	10.201	14.055	12.857
Q2 2009	41.000	90.500	1853.000	1.748	325.591	95.391	120.001	28.644	5.243	12.935	12.060
Q3 2009	38.000	90.000	1816.000	1.606	321.338	98.710	101.383	34.322	9.795	14.500	11.009
Q4 2009	37.000	88.000	1812.000	1.689	308.937	90.214	109.787	38.298	5.957	14.950	11.978
Q1 2010	36.500	76.000	1724.000	1.724	314.798	94.073	109.411	31.631	9.848	14.885	13.749
Q2 2010	33.000	66.000	1271.000	1.728	312.664	100.228	105.006	27.151	9.412	13.235	14.132
Q3 2010	28.500	62.000	1214.000	1.683	304.895	101.195	104.883	27.996	8.725	12.300	12.510
Q4 2010	27.000	60.000	1175.000	1.725	320.701	102.611	102.968	24.312	10.726	13.100	13.610
Q1 2011	26.000	58.500	1114.000	1.744	323.538	100.465	107.287	26.245	11.011	14.440	12.915
Q2 2011	26.000	56.000	1063.000	1.736	323.666	93.967	109.629	27.262	6.381	14.670	12.535
Q3 2011	25.000	55.000	1056.500	1.653	321.193	89.956	113.135	28.698	5.519	13.200	13.214
Q4 2011	24.000	55.000	1048.000	1.753	314.791	98.771	110.978	31.868	10.032	15.160	12.764
Q1 2012	24.000	54.000	1007.000	1.667	304.370	89.756	100.327	34.754	10.212	12.990	12.290
Q2 2012	23.000	52.000	919.000	1.683	314.672	88.487	100.678	30.248	8.126	13.490	11.847
Q3 2012	23.000	47.000	882.000	1.673	316.148	94.826	107.512	26.490	10.552	12.915	12.398
Q4 2012	22.500	46.000	877.000	1.679	326.747	96.504	104.864	22.037	9.119	14.780	11.883
Q1 2013	22.000	45.000	835.000	1.729	317.753	92.645	107.463	30.443	9.201	14.355	14.396
Q2 2013	21.500	44.000	834.000	1.675	318.649	92.387	98.803	31.651	5.560	13.960	13.115
Q3 2013	20.500	42.500	810.000	1.707	338.654	92.791	97.866	29.905	8.106	12.790	12.592
Q4 2013	20.500	37.500	730.500	1.689	318.922	100.712	87.996	31.027	12.716	12.770	11.784
Q1 2014	19.000	30.000	656.000	1.678	306.935	97.831	90.539	32.521	15.415	12.830	11.814
Q2 2014	14.000	30.000	646.000	1.701	303.423	111.514	92.324	26.453	9.855	12.090	11.136
Q3 2014	14.000	29.000	607.000	1.721	314.554	104.400	105.399	27.299	9.176	13.685	12.299
Q4 2014	14.000	29.000	607.000	1.743	331.739	100.478	97.821	29.772	5.848	13.920	13.039
Q1 2015	12.000	26.000	602.000	1.756	318.943	102.366	105.786	31.166	7.692	14.165	12.721
Q2 2015	12.000	24.000	528.000	1.770	324.920	105.263	107.411	31.686	4.296	14.560	13.365
Q3 2015	11.000	21.000	520.333	1.756	312.214	100.180	115.023	27.174	8.299	14.370	13.043
Q4 2015	10.333	21.000	489.500	1.777	328.231	108.060	100.855	29.716	13.057	14.260	12.977
Q1 2016	8.800	20.667	480.333	1.799	321.087	99.079	109.888	31.228	8.546	14.445	13.564
Q2 2016	8.800	20.000	442.000	1.735	323.379	100.590	100.590	31.041	7.859	14.430	11.973
Q3 2016	8.800	18.000	440.000	1.732	326.052	103.693	102.405	31.296	11.281	13.160	12.878
Q4 2016	8.500	18.000	396.000	1.718	317.150	103.720	94.578	38.461	12.926	13.780	11.517
Q1 2017	7.667	18.000	396.000	1.775	318.228	99.357	106.491	31.815	11.945	15.055	11.296
Q2 2017	7.500	17.000	396.000	1.810	328.959	103.985	108.843	37.901	8.746	13.990	12.293
Q3 2017	7.000	16.500	375.000	1.789	327.993	99.222	101.353	34.621	5.529	14.895	13.440
Q4 2017	7.000	16.000	373.667	1.779	321.182	105.525	107.061	32.617	9.210	14.360	13.943
Q1 2018	6.667	15.333	335.000	1.779	321.182	105.525	107.061	32.617	9.210	14.360	13.943
Q2 2018	6.333	15.000	330.667	1.775	324.503	101.536	102.870	33.237	8.165	14.925	12.624
Q3 2018	5.000	13.000	313.333	1.737	323.670	103.354	97.226	33.143	6.347	14.005	13.634
Q4 2018	4.500	12.500	304.000	1.768	332.488	101.523	99.408	34.687	11.421	14.640	14.137

Appendix 2: Monetary Policy Decisions of the CBN and Coding of the Stance

s/n	Communique Details	Decisions	Reasons for the Decisions	Interpretation	Code
1	Communique No. 1 Date - June 26, 2001 Publication - June 30, 2001	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Minimum Rediscount Rate (MRR) increased by 200 basis points to 18.5% b) Cash Reserve Ratio (CRR) retained at 12.5% c) Liquidity Ratio (LR) retained at 40.0% d) Silent on Open Market Operations (OMO) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Expansionary fiscal operations of the three tiers of government led to a rapid acceleration in the rate of monetary expansion thereby putting intense pressure on domestic prices and the exchange rate b) Broad money supply (M2) increased rapidly during the first five months of 2001 c) Exchange rate of the naira depreciated in all the segments of the market. 	Tightening	1
2	Communique No. 2 Date - July 10 and 24, 2001 Publication - July 31, 2001	Retained the existing monetary policy measures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Movements in macroeconomic indicators pointed to relative stability in the money and foreign exchange markets due to tight monetary measures taken in June. b) Although inflation inched to 15.7 per cent in May, from 13.9 per cent in April, it is anticipated that the combination of tight monetary policy and the onset of the harvest of agricultural commodities, will have a moderating effect on domestic the price level. 	Neutral	0
3	Communique No. 3 Date - Aug 7 and 21, 2001 Publication - Aug 31, 2001	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) The Committee did not consider further tightening of monetary policy measures. b) To address the problem of liquidity over-hang, the Committee decided to re-issue the first tranche of CBN certificates of 180-day tenor maturing on August 24, 2001, at 19.5 per cent. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) The Committee noted the relative stability in both the money and foreign exchange markets in the first three weeks of August 2001. b) The weighted average inter-bank call rate fell from 21.7 per cent in July to 16.79 and 16.72 per cent in the first and second weeks of August. c) The exchange rate of the naira appreciated in all segments of the foreign exchange market. 	Tightening	1
4	Communique No. 4 Date - Sep 4 and 18, 2001 Publication - Sep 30, 2001	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) MRR raised by 200 basis points to 20.5% b) Silent on other instruments 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Developments in fiscal operations point to further growth in money supply b) Broad measure of money supply increased by 23.9 per cent by end-August as against the 12.2 per cent programmed for the entire year c) Increasing risk of demand pressure in the foreign exchange market and escalation of the inflation rate. 	Tightening	1
5	Communique No. 5 Date - Oct 2, 16 and 30, 2001 Publication - Oct 31, 2001	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) The Committee retained the existing policy measures in October. b) The Committee also decided to re-issue the fourth tranche of the CBN Certificates of 180-day tenor, maturing on November 23, 2001, at 20.5 per cent rate of interest, as the lingering problem of liquidity overhang remained. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Relative stability in macroeconomic conditions during the month, which was attributable largely to the tightening of monetary policy and enhanced surveillance of the financial markets. b) Although the growth rate of broad money stock (M2) rose from 21.2 per cent in August 2001 to 22.7 per cent in September, the rate was substantially lower than the 25.8 per cent recorded in May. 	Tightening	1

			c) The inflation rate (moving average), however, rose moderately to 18.5 per cent in September 2001, up from 18.1 per cent in the preceding month, representing an improvement, compared to the rapid acceleration observed since the beginning of the year.		
6	Not Available for Download				
7	Communique No. 7 Date - Dec 11, 2001 Publication - Dec, 2001	The Committee retained the existing policy measures in December.	a) Growth in monetary aggregates, which accelerated by 28.1 per cent in September, moderated to 26.1 per cent in October and was 26.8 per cent in November 2001, as against the growth target of 12.2 per cent for fiscal 2001 b) The inflation rate (moving average) rose moderately to 18.6 per cent in October 2001, from 18.4 per cent in the preceding month, representing an improvement, compared to the rapid acceleration observed since the beginning of the year. c) The exchange rate of the naira appreciated in all segments of the foreign exchange market.	Neutral	0
8	Not Available for Download				
9	Communique No. 9 Date - Feb 5, and 19, 2002 Publication - Feb 2002	a) In order to attenuate the recurrent problem of excess liquidity in the system, the Committee decided to sustain the policy of monetary tightening designed to encourage increased investment in the domestic money market securities. b) Consequently, the Committee approved the re-issuance of matured CBN Certificates on February 25, 2002.	a) The review of financial market developments revealed further growth in aggregate demand and persistence of pressure on the foreign exchange market. b) Between end-December 2001 and the second week of February 2002, the average naira exchange rate depreciated in all segments of the markets c) The Committee also noted the persistence of liquidity overhang in the banking system and its potential adverse impact on macroeconomic variables, especially on inflation, interest, and exchange rates.	Tightening	1
10	Communique No. 10 Date - Mar 12 and 26, 2002 Publication - Mar 27, 2002	The Committee decided to extinguish three maturing tranches of CBN certificate in March	a) Broad money (M2) increased by 2.1 per cent in the first two months of 2002, compared with the 16.3 per cent growth rate in the corresponding period of 2001. b) In January 2002, the rate of inflation remained stable at its December 2001 level of 18.9 per cent. c) Relative stability in the interest rate and the need to sustain stability in the financial markets d) Although, the exchange rate of the Naira vis-à-vis the U.S. dollar depreciated in the official window, the parallel market rate showed some appreciation.	Tightening	1
11	Communique No. 11 Date - Apr 9 and 23, 2002	a) Retained existing monetary policy measures. b) Decided not to roll-over the CBN Certificate of 360-day tenor that matured in April.	a) Implications of the approved huge budget deficits – especially its negative implications for domestic prices and the exchange rate b) Need to subdue inflation with a view to influencing a downward movement in lending rates.	Tightening	1

	Publication - Apr 26, 2002		<p>c) Acceleration of broad money (M2) to 8.8 per cent in the first quarter of 2002 compared with the permissible expansion rate of 15.3 per cent for the whole year.</p> <p>d) The exchange rate of the Naira vis-à-vis U.S. dollar remained relatively stable in the Inter-bank Foreign Exchange Market (IFEM) but depreciated in the parallel market and bureau de change.</p>		
12	Not Available for Download				
13	<p>Communique No. 13</p> <p>Date - June 4 and 18, 2002</p> <p>Publication - June 21, 2002</p>	<p>a) In order to attenuate the problem of high and persistent domestic demand pressure and ensure that the current downward trend in the inflation rate is sustained, the Committee retained the existing tight monetary policy measures.</p> <p>b) Developments in the money market will continue to be reviewed in order to guide the pricing of treasury securities and promote financial market stability.</p>	<p>a) The appraisal of macroeconomic conditions during the month revealed continued moderation of the inflation rate.</p> <p>b) Rapid growth of aggregate demand as broad money supply (M2) rose further by 1.3 per cent in May 2002, bringing the cumulative growth rate of broad money to 9.8 per cent in the first five months of the year.</p> <p>c) Reflecting the effect of increased demand pressure, the average Naira exchange rate against the US dollar depreciated from N116.80 = US\$1.00 on 3rd June to N119.55 = US\$1.00 on 14th June 2002.</p>	Tightening	1
14	<p>Communique No. 14</p> <p>Date - July 2, 16, 19 and 30, 2002</p> <p>Publication - July 31, 2002</p>	<p>a) Adjusted the MRR downward by 200 basis points to 18.5 per cent.</p> <p>b) Reduced the CRR by 300 basis points to 9.5 per cent for banks that increase their credit to the real sector by a minimum of 20 per cent over the level at the end of June 2002. It is hoped that both measures will help moderate banks' cost of fund and thereby influence a downward review of bank lending rates to the real sector.</p> <p>c) Re-introduced the Dutch Auction System (DAS) with effect from July 22, 2002. The DAS is aimed at enhancing the efficiency of the foreign exchange market through market-based determination of the Naira exchange rate.</p>	<p>a) Broad measure of money stock (M2) increased by 9.8 per cent in the first half of 2002. On an annualized basis, the growth translates to 19.6 per cent as of June 2002 compared with the 15.3 per cent target for fiscal 2002. However, the growth represented a deceleration relative to the rapid expansion of 21.2 per cent in the corresponding period of 2001.</p> <p>b) The rate of inflation (moving average) which accelerated in 2001 and peaked at 18.9 per cent between December 2001 and February 2002, declined consistently to 16.8 per cent by May 2000, while the month-on-month rate declined to 10.2 per cent from 18.0 per cent in February</p> <p>c) Sluggish growth in bank credit to the private sector and the need to increase the level of credit for productive activities and thereby stimulate investment growth.</p>	Loosening	-1
15	<p>Communique No. 15</p> <p>Date - Aug 13 and 27, 2002</p> <p>Publication - Aug 29, 2002</p>	<p>a) The Committee retained the existing policy measures.</p> <p>b) In August, the last tranche of the CBN Certificate matured and was retired. It would be recalled that the CBN Certificate was introduced in February 2001, when the problem of excess liquidity in the banking system became intractable. Following the improvement in liquidity conditions, however,</p>	<p>a) The appraisal of macroeconomic developments during the month revealed continued moderation in monetary conditions and inflationary pressure.</p> <p>b) The rate of inflation, on moving average basis, in June 2002 (for which actual data were available) was 16.4 per cent, reflecting further decline from the 16.8 per cent recorded in May 2002. The projections for July and</p>	Neutral	0

		maturing CBN Certificate has since March 2002, not been rolled over.	<p>August 2002 indicated further deceleration of the inflation rate.</p> <p>c) Also, there was considerable moderation of pressure in the money market, resulting in the general downward movement of short-term interest rates.</p> <p>d) Relative stability of the naira exchange rate, after the initial erratic movement witnessed at the introduction of the Dutch Auction System (DAS) on July 22, 2002.</p>		
16	Not Available for Download				
17	<p>Communique No. 17</p> <p>Date - Oct 8 and 22, 2002</p> <p>Publication - Oct 31, 2002</p>	<p>a) The Committee retained the existing policy measures</p> <p>b) Approved, in principle, the creation of "Special OMO Bills", to be issued strictly for liquidity management, as and when necessary</p>	<p>a) The assessment of macroeconomic developments during the month indicated the continued moderation of inflationary pressure</p> <p>b) Relative calm in the money market, particularly the downward movement in short-term interest rates.</p> <p>c) Surge in monetary expansion as broad money supply (M2) recorded a further increase due to the monetization of the external reserves draw down by US\$500 million, which was shared by the three tiers of government</p> <p>d) Relative stability in the naira exchange rate was maintained, reflecting the impact of increased supply of foreign currency by the CBN to the market</p> <p>e) Steady decline in CBN's holdings of Nigerian Treasury Bill (NTB) and the corresponding increase in the holdings by the public.</p>	Neutral	0
18	<p>Communique No. 18</p> <p>Date - Nov. 5 and 19, 2002</p> <p>Publication - Nov 20, 2002</p>	<p>a) The Committee retained the existing policy measures.</p> <p>b) Supported the decision of the deposit money banks to adjust their lending rate to not more than 4 percentage points above the prevailing Minimum Rediscount Rate (MRR).</p>	<p>a) The Committee reviewed noted with satisfaction the continued moderation of inflationary pressure.</p> <p>b) The observed deceleration in the domestic price level was attributable largely to the dampening effect of good agricultural harvests on food prices.</p> <p>c) The Committee, however, expressed concern about the high demand pressure in the economy, given the acceleration in the rate of monetary expansion, which has the potential of reversing the downward trend in the domestic price level and increasing the risk of macroeconomic stability.</p> <p>d) Developments in the foreign exchange market remained positive, as the gap between the official and parallel market exchange rates narrowed.</p>	Neutral	0
19	<p>Communique No. 19</p> <p>Date - Dec. 3, and 17, 2002</p>	Reduction of the MRR by 200 basis points to 16.5 per cent, with immediate effect.	<p>a) The Committee welcomed the continued moderation in inflationary pressure during review period</p> <p>b) The Committee also noted the calm in the money market, and the general downward movement in short-term rates in recent months.</p>	Loosening	-1

	Publication - Dec. 18, 2002		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> c) Moreover, the exchange rate of the Naira vis -à-vis the U.S. dollar appreciated in all segments of the foreign d) Need to encourage increased credit to the private sector to boost investment/output growth. 		
20	<p>Communique No. 20</p> <p>Date - Jan 14 and 28, 2003</p> <p>Publication - Jan 29, 2003</p>	Maintained the current monetary policy stance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Continued moderation of inflationary pressure and prevalence of relative stability in the financial market. b) Continued downward movement of money market interest rates. c) Renewed demand pressure in the foreign exchange markets was observed resulting in some depreciation of the naira in all segments of the foreign exchange market. 	Neutral	0
21	<p>Communique No. 21</p> <p>Date - Feb. 25, 2003</p> <p>Publication - Feb. 28, 2003</p>	No additional policy action was introduced during the month.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Relative price stability observed in most of 2002 was sustained during the month. b) The problem of excess liquidity in the system persisted, with the broad money stock (M2) rising by 2.55 per cent. c) Helped by the surfeit of funds in the financial market, the weighted average call rate in the inter-bank money market declined. d) Modest depreciation of the naira value in all segments of the foreign exchange market. 	Neutral	0
22	<p>Communique No. 22</p> <p>Date - Mar. 11 and 25, 2003</p> <p>Publication - Mar. 31, 2003</p>	The existing monetary policy measures were retained	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Continued downward movement in the inflation rate b) Growth in monetary aggregates moderated c) Money market rates showed further moderation. d) The Naira/US Dollar exchange rate appreciated marginally. e) Approval of the National Savings Certificate (NSC) by Government which will encourage financial savings and enhance the effectiveness of monetary policy. 	Neutral	0
23	<p>Communique No. 23</p> <p>Date - Apr x and y, 2003</p> <p>Publication - May 6, 2003</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) The Committee viewed the accelerated growth in money supply and the renewed pressure on domestic prices and the naira exchange rate with serious concern. b) It, however, decided to monitor developments in the macroeconomy further, with a view to taking appropriate steps to tighten monetary policy, should the pressure in aggregate demand persist. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Growth in monetary aggregates accelerated during the first four months of 2003, with the broad money stock (M2) rising by an estimated 22.7 percent over the end December 2002 levels, thus, exceeding the programme target of 15.0 per cent for fiscal 2003. b) Substantial growth in bank credit to the domestic economy, as well as increases in the foreign and other assets (net) of the banking system c) Induced largely by the surfeit of liquidity in the financial system, interest rates on bank deposits and lending moderated considerably. 	Neutral	0
24	<p>Communique No. 24</p> <p>Date - May x and y, 2003</p>	The Committee did not adopt any change in the stance of monetary policy.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Moderation in growth in the monetary aggregates. b) Inflation rate showed further deceleration. c) Pressure on the foreign exchange market intensified, resulting in the depreciation of the naira. 	Neutral	0

	Publication - June 13, 2003		d) Downward movement in interest rates, particularly bank deposit and lending rates.		
25	Communique No. 25 Date - June x and y, 2003 Publication - June 30, 2003	The Committee noted that a change in the stance of monetary policy was not considered as desirable	a) Slowdown of the accelerated growth in money supply b) Further moderation in the inflationary pressure. c) Exchange rate movement remained stable, as the naira depreciated only marginally. d) Interest rates on deposits and lending rates maintained a general downward trend.	Neutral	0
26	Communique No. 26 Date - July x and y, 2003 Publication - Aug 18, 2003	Reduction in the MRR by 150 basis points, from 16.5 per cent to 15.0 per cent.	a) Continued deceleration in the inflation rate. b) Further decline in the money market interest rates. c) Marginal depreciation of the naira exchange.	Loosening	-1
27	Communique No. 27 Date - Aug x and y, 2003 Publication - Aug 28, 2003	a) The Committee did not adopt any change in the stance of monetary policy. b) The frequency of the Committee's meetings has been changed from fortnightly to monthly.	a) Relative stability continued to be maintained through the review month. b) Risk of renewed demand pressure and a reversal of the persistent fall in the inflation rate had started to build up. c) Further moderation in the growth in monetary aggregates d) Marginal appreciation of the naira in the Dutch Auction System of the market.	Neutral	0
28	Not Available for Download				
29					
30					
31					
32	Communique No. 32 Date - Jan x and Feb x, 2004 Publication - Feb 18, 2004	The Committee decided to tighten the stance of monetary policy by approving a selective withdrawal of public sector funds from the banking system, targeting a total of N40 billion, as a strategy for reducing excess liquidity in the system	a) The problem of inflation resurgence was evident. b) Pressure on the foreign exchange market moderated with the naira exchange rate appreciating marginally. c) Level of gross external reserves increased marginally d) A sharp contraction in money supply was observed.	Tightening	1
33	Communique No. 33 Date - March x, 2004 Publication - March 10, 2004	The Committee decided to continue monitoring developments in the economy with a view to fine-tuning the existing policies, if necessary	a) Monetary aggregates showed further contraction b) The foreign exchange market remained generally stable with the naira recording a modest appreciation c) Gross external reserves improved significantly d) The level of interest rates showed further moderations. e) High prospects of bringing the rate of inflation down if fiscal prudence was sustained.	Neutral	0
34	Communique No. 34 Date - Apr x, 2004	The Committee decided not to introduce any monetary policy change.	a) Growth in monetary aggregates slowed as the banking system's credit to government contracted b) The foreign exchange market remained stable c) Gross external reserves showing further improvement	Neutral	0

	Publication - Apr 22, 2004		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> d) The level of the banks' interest rates increased, and the average inflation rate rose further. e) High prospects of containing inflation and stabilizing the interest rate if the current level of fiscal prudence was sustained. 		
35	<p>Communique No. 35</p> <p>Date - May x, 2004</p> <p>Publication - May 31, 2004</p>	The Committee decided to embark on partial withdrawal of public sector funds with the deposit money banks, as a strategy for mopping up excess liquidity in the system.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Growth in money supply (M2) was broadly on target. b) The rate of inflation continued to accelerate. c) The pressure on the naira moderated. d) Level of gross official external reserves increased. e) Money market remained relatively calm, with both deposit and lending rates rising only moderately. 	Tightening	1
36	<p>Communique No. 36</p> <p>Date - June x, 2004</p> <p>Publication - July 2, 2004</p>	The Committee decided to recall N74.5 billion of public sector funds lodged with deposit money banks, with effect from July 21, 2004	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) The inflation rate, on twelve-month moving average basis, exceeded the 17.5 per cent recorded in April 2004. b) The daily average demand for foreign exchange remained unsustainably high. c) The level of gross official external reserves recorded only a modest increase during the month, despite the substantial rise in net inflow. d) Widening of the spread between official and unofficial exchange rate. e) Growth in monetary aggregates remained broadly within the programme targets, helped mainly by the continued fall in bank credit to Federal Government. 	Tightening	1
37	<p>Communique No. 37</p> <p>Date - July x, 2004</p> <p>Publication - July 29, 2004</p>	The Committee decided to sustain the phased recall of public sector funds with the deposit money banks until further notice.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Inflationary pressure continued. b) The daily average demand for foreign exchange dropped but remained unsustainably high. c) The gross official external reserve increased, and the naira exchange rate appreciated owing to the increased supply of foreign exchange by the CBN. d) The exchange rate depreciated in the Bureaux de Change (BDC) market, thereby widening the spread between the DAS and the BDC exchange rates. e) Growth in monetary aggregates remained within the programme targets, as bank credit to the Federal Government continued to fall. f) Committee however recognized the threat to monetary stability posed by the anticipated bunched government spending on capital projects in the rest of the year. g) It also noted the risk of further pressure on prices if the monetary policy stance should be relaxed so soon. 	Tightening	1
38	<p>Communique No. 38</p> <p>Date - Sept x, 2004</p>	The Committee agreed to suspend the withdrawal of public sector deposits from the deposit money banks in order to enhance the stability of the financial system.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) The pressure on prices has moderated as both the moving average and point on point inflation rates fell. 	Loosening	-1

	Publication - Sept 20, 2004		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> b) The gross official reserves rose from US\$12.2 to US\$12.3 billion c) The arbitrage premium between the DAS exchange rate and the bureau de change stabilized d) Growth in monetary aggregates remained within the program targets. e) The Committee noted that the combined effect of the high international oil price and a continuation of current prudent macroeconomic policies would help to lower the inflation rate close to single digit. 		
39	<p>Communique No. 39</p> <p>Date - Oct 12, 2004</p> <p>Publication - Oct 18, 2004</p>	The Committee decided not to introduce any monetary policy change	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) The year-on-year inflation rate increased from 10.7 per cent in July 2004 to 13.0 per cent in August 2004. b) The 12-month moving average inflation rate remained unchanged at the July 2004 level of 19.10 per cent. c) The exchange rate of the naira was relatively stable d) Gross official reserves rose further from US \$12.48 billion to US \$13.27 at end-September 2004. e) Broad money stock (M2) rose by 9.9 per cent in the first nine months of 2004, representing an annualized growth rate of 13.2 per cent. This growth rate is within the 16.0 per cent target set for 2004. f) Credit (net) to government contracted further, reflecting the prudent fiscal operations of the federal government. 	Neutral	0
40	<p>Communique No. 40</p> <p>Date - Nov 22, 2004</p> <p>Publication - Nov 26, 2004</p>	The Committee decided not to introduce any monetary policy change	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Both the 12-month moving average and the year-on-year inflation rates moderated. b) The exchange rate of the naira remained relatively stable c) The gross official reserves increased further. d) Broad money stock (M2) increased by 12.9 per cent representing an annualised growth rate of 15.5 per cent, which compared with the 16.0 per cent target for 2004. e) Credit (net) to government declined further in the first ten months of 2004, while credit to the private sector rose by 25.8 per cent as against the 22.0 per cent target for 2004. 	Neutral	0
41	<p>Communique No. 41</p> <p>Date - Dec 14, 2004</p> <p>Publication - Dec 16, 2004</p>	The Committee decided not to introduce any monetary policy change	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Both the 12-month moving average and the year-on-year inflation rates moderated. b) The exchange rate of the naira remained relatively stable. c) The gross official reserves increased further. d) Credit (net) to government declined further. 	Neutral	0

42	<p>Communique No. 42</p> <p>Date - Jan 24 and 25, 2005</p> <p>Publication - Feb 2, 2005</p>	<p>a) Reduction of the MRR by 200 basis points, in order to reduce the cost of private sector borrowing for productive investment.</p> <p>b) Withdrawal/re-injection of public sector deposits to address the problem of excess liquidity in the banking system.</p> <p>c) Adoption of two weeks maintenance period for the CRR; and</p> <p>d) Adoption of an exchange rate band of plus/minus 3.0 per cent, to sustain exchange rate stability, anchor expectations and minimize transaction costs.</p>	<p>a) Deceleration in the rate of inflation</p> <p>b) For the first time in almost two decades, the CBN met the target on broad money supply (M2).</p> <p>c) Fiscal deficit /GDP ratio improved from the target of 3.0 per cent to about 2.1 (cash basis).</p> <p>d) The stock of external reserves for the year ended December 2004 was US\$16.9 billion, compared with the target of US\$7.68 billion.</p> <p>e) The naira exchange rate was N132.85=US\$1.00 at end-December 2004, representing a nominal appreciation of about 3.0 per cent when compared with the rate of N137.0 to US \$1.00 in January 2004.</p> <p>f) The Committee, however, noted with concern the amount of the proposed budget deficit for 2005, the bulk of which would be financed through the savings from the 2004 windfall crude oil receipts.</p>	Loosening	-1
43	<p>Communique No. 43</p> <p>Date - May 10, 11 and June 15, 2005</p> <p>Publication - June 20, 2005</p>	<p>a) Withdrawal of N60 billion public sector deposit from the banks to the CBN.</p> <p>b) Retain MRR at 13%.</p> <p>c) Upward revision of the CRR by 50 basis points from 9.5 to 10 per cent.</p> <p>d) Debiting of banks accounts with CBN to meet the stipulated CRR should be implemented immediately after the monthly Federal Account Allocation Committee (FAAC) meetings.</p> <p>e) Revision of the definition of liquid assets to include 3-year bonds.</p> <p>f) Pension Fund should not be invested in the Nigerian Treasury Bills instead they should be invested in long-term securities or sterilized.</p> <p>g) Sustainance of exchange rate band of \pm 3 per cent.</p>	<p>a) The month-on-month inflation rate was 16.3 per cent, higher than the 10.0 percent at end-December 2004 and substantially above the target of a single digit for end-2005.</p> <p>b) The broad money stock (M2) rose by 17.5 per cent, representing an annualized growth rate of 42.0 per cent. This was more than doubled the target of 15 per cent for fiscal 2005.</p> <p>c) The rise reflected the injection of liquidity by the tiers of government through the releases from the Federation Accounts Allocation Committee (FAAC).</p> <p>d) The Committee, however, observed with satisfaction, the steady build-up in external reserves, which stood at \$23 billion at end-May 2005 as against the target of \$20.75 billion for the year.</p>	Tightening	1
44	<p>Communique No. 44</p> <p>Date - Oct 25, 2005</p> <p>Publication - Nov 7, 2005</p>	<p>a) Complete the sale of N60 billion of CBN instrument and sell more if need be.</p> <p>b) Sale of Treasury Bills which will be sterilized for liquidity management</p> <p>c) Sale of additional foreign exchange to mop up liquidity.</p> <p>d) Move all NNPC deposits with commercial banks to the CBN and sterilize much of it with effect from October 31, 2005.</p> <p>e) All banks that collect revenues on behalf of the NNPC are expected to remit all such funds to the CBN within 48 hours of the collection.</p>	<p>a) Interest rates have crashed to an all-time lowest level</p> <p>b) Credit to the private sector has grown at unprecedented, annualized levels of about 39 percent (higher than the target of 30 percent under NEEDS) – thereby spurring rapid growth of the non-oil sector</p> <p>c) Inflationary pressures have been worrisome.</p> <p>d) Broad money supply (M2) has grown at about 22 percent at the end of September (as against the target 15 for end period 2005).</p> <p>e) The foreign exchange market remained stable, and the Naira has appreciated against all major currencies in all markets.</p>	Tightening	1

45	<p>Communique No. 45</p> <p>Date - Feb 14, 2006</p> <p>Publication - Feb 16, 2006</p>	<p>a) Mop-up of liquidity using the OMO, Treasury/CBN bills will be done in a more systematic manner to keep the liquidity trend stable throughout the year.</p> <p>b) Zero Ways and Means advances to Government but in the extreme circumstances however, the Bank could allow the Government to borrow up to 5% of last year's actual revenue (at the interest rate of MRR plus 1) and which must be retired in the quarter in which the advance is given.</p> <p>c) MRR maintained at 13% in line with the anti-inflation stance of the CBN.</p> <p>d) CRR left unchanged</p> <p>e) Liquidity ratio retained at 40%</p> <p>f) Wholesale-DAS will commence on 20th February 2006 to foster exchange rate convergence between the DAS and the inter-bank market rates. The CBN will issue revised guidelines for transactions in the foreign exchange market, to further liberalize the market.</p>	<p>a) The MPC carefully reviewed the key macroeconomic developments in 2005, and noted that despite the liquidity surfeit, a mix of external shocks (drought in neighboring countries, capital flows and rising prices of oil imports), and challenges arising from the banking sector consolidation, the overall macroeconomic performance was satisfactory</p> <p>b) The deceleration in inflation in the last quarter was very impressive, and the goal of monetary policy in 2006 is to sustain the anti-inflation stance.</p> <p>c) Exchange rate remained stable and within the announced band of plus or minus 3% around the central rate.</p> <p>d) Growth of Monetary aggregates declined in the 4th quarter as a direct consequence of the effective tightening of liquidity.</p> <p>e) Interest rates fell in 2005 relative to the previous years.</p>	Neutral	0
46	<p>Communique No. 46</p> <p>Date - June 8, 2006</p> <p>Publication - July 2006</p>	<p>a) Raised the MRR from 13% to 14%</p> <p>b) Maintained the CRR at 5%</p> <p>c) Sustain the liberalization of the forex market.</p> <p>d) The OMO shall continue to be the major instrument of monetary policy.</p>	<p>a) Both the end-April headline and core inflation rates increased to 12.6 and 16.6 per cent from 11.6 and 2.4 per cent in December 2005 respectively.</p> <p>b) The GDP growth was seasonally low in 2006, relative to the high growth in 2005.</p> <p>c) Relative stability of the naira</p> <p>d) Gross external reserves increased from US \$28.0 billion at end-December 2005 to US \$36 billion at end-March 2006.</p> <p>e) Broad money (M2) grew by 14.1% as at end-May 2006 over the December 2005, which represented an annualized growth rate of 33.8 percent compared with the target of 15 – 17 percent for 2006</p> <p>f) General decline in banks' deposit and lending rates following the excess liquidity in the system.</p>	Tightening	1
47	<p>Communique No. 47</p> <p>Date - Aug 9, 2006</p> <p>Publication - August 2006</p>	<p>a. Maintain the MRR at 14% with a proviso to review it should the threat to monetary policy continue</p> <p>b. Approve a new framework for monetary policy implementation. The IT and other logistics requirements are to be sorted out between now and October 2006. Pilot implementation is expected to commence on or before November 1st, 2006</p> <p>c. Sustain the CBN's zero tolerance to lending to government</p>	<p>a) Both the headline and core inflation rates decreased to 8.5 and 13.6 per cent from 12.0 and 16.3 per cent at end-March 2006 respectively. It, however, noted that core inflation at 13.6 per cent was still unacceptably high.</p> <p>b) GDP was low reflecting the decline in oil production and the seasonal slowdown in agricultural production. Economic activity, however, is projected to pick up in the months ahead.</p>	Neutral	0

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> d. Reaffirm that there is no control on interest rate or pegging of lending rate to the MRR. e. Approve operational guidelines on the CBN Discount Window f. Approve guidelines for discount window operations in FGN bonds and g. Sustain the on-going liberalization of the forex market. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> c) Sustained stability of the naira following the Bank's liberalization of the forex market since March 27, 2006 d) The stock of external reserves stood at US \$32 billion at end-April, and rose to US \$38 billion at end-July 2006 e) Broad money (M2) grew by 34.69% as at end-July 2006 over the December 2005, which represented an annualized growth rate of 59.46 per cent compared with the target of 15 – 17 per cent for 2006. f) Growth in aggregate domestic credit (net) was 15.2 per cent in the first six months. This increased to 16.9 per cent at end-July 2006 and 28.96 per cent on annualized basis. The credit development was driven largely by DMBs credit to government through investments in treasury securities. Credit to the private sector, however, fell short of the target for the year. g) General decline in banks' deposit and lending rates following the excess liquidity in the system. 		
48	<p>Communique No. 48</p> <p>Date - Nov 28, 2006</p> <p>Publication - Nov 28 2006</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Begin the implementation of the new monetary policy framework with effect from Monday, December 11, 2006. b) Adopt a Monetary Policy Rate (MPR) that will replace the MRR. The MPR, which is the main instrument of the new framework, will determine the lower and upper band of the CBN standing facility and is expected to have the capability of acting as the nominal anchor for other rates. c) Discontinue outright rediscounting of bills in the CBN to encourage trading among the market operators. d) Ensure the full deployment of IT infrastructure (RTGS, T24 and eFASS) for the effective implementation of the new framework. e) Convene meeting of the MPC every other month to review developments in the economy. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Relative stability in the overall macroeconomic environment during the review period b) Relative stability in the banking system since the banking consolidation 	Neutral	0
49	<p>Communique No. 49</p> <p>Date - Feb 7, 2007</p> <p>Publication - Feb 7, 2007</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Leave the MPR unchanged at 10 per cent b) Release the 8 per cent special CRR invested on behalf of the Banks by the CBN, to the DMBs on maturity. This would enable the banks utilize the amount of reserve money released for regular operations. c) Keep the CRR unchanged at 3 per cent d) Maintain the liquidity ratio at 40 per cent 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Headline and the food (year-on-year) inflation stayed within single digit. b) At end 2006, provisional data on real output showed a growth of 5.63 per cent compared with 6.51 percent growth in 2005. c) Stability of the naira following the Bank's liberalization of the forex market. 	Loosening	-1

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> d) Allow the collateralized placements among deposit money banks to count as liquid assets, for purposes of liquidity ratio e) That the domiciliary deposit accounts shall continue to be excluded from the definition of the broad money (M2) and the computation of a bank's CRR. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> d) Gross official reserves (at end-December 2006) amounted to \$41.96 billion compared with \$28.3 billion recorded at end-December 2005. e) Broad money (M2) grew by 28.23 per cent over the end-December 2005 level, compared with the target of 27.8 per cent for 2006. Money supply was influenced mainly by growth in bank's credit to the private sector. f) Growth in aggregate domestic credit (net) declined by about 88.84 per cent at end-December 2006 relative to its level at end-December 2005. The fall in aggregate credit was attributed to the decline in credit (net) to government. g) Interest rate volatility moderated and stayed within the lending and deposit standing facility rates of the CBN. 		
50	<p>Communique No. 50</p> <p>Date - June 7, 2007</p> <p>Publication - June 5, 2007</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Introduce tenured repo at MPR b) Reduce the MPR by 200 basis points, i.e., from 10.0 per cent to 8.0 per cent c) Reduce the width of the interest rate corridor from +/- 300 to +/- 250 basis points. d) The combined implication of (b) and (c) is that the deposit facility now stands at 5.5 per cent while the lending facility would be 10.5 per cent, both down from 7 and 13 per cent, respectively. e) Both facilities are expected to be used as a last resort, consequently the frequent usage of these facilities will attract penalty. f) Increase the issuance of primary market instruments to mop up about N100 billion 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Inflation rate stayed within single digit in the first four months of 2007. b) Stability of the naira exchange rate in the first five months of 2007 as the naira remained stable at both the wDAS and the BDCs during the period. c) Gross official reserves rose to \$43.48 billion as of 28th May 2007, which could finance 25 months of imports. The Committee, however, noted the risk to growth of reserves arising from the decline in the volume of crude oil production due to disturbances in the Niger Delta, but welcomed the initiatives of the government to resolve the crisis. d) Broad money grew by 8.80 per cent and moderated to 7.70 per cent at end April 2007, which when annualized showed a growth of 23.0 per cent compared with the target of 19.0 per cent for entire 2007. e) A significant proportion of credit went into import financing, which have low inflation risk for the domestic economy. The spending items included payments for Telecommunications and Information Technology imports and the payment for oil blocs in foreign currencies. f) Moderate the volatility in interbank rates in the first five months of 2007. 	Loosening	-1
51	Communique No. 51	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Retain the MPR at 8.0 per cent 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Inflation stayed within single digit. b) Continued stability of the naira exchange rate. 		

	Date - Aug 1, 2007 Publication - Aug 1, 2007	b) Approve increased sale of financial securities to mitigate the impact of increased fiscal injections pre-emptively and proactively on system liquidity.	c) Decline in gross official reserves from \$43.17 billion at end-May 2007 to \$42.74 at end-June. Reserves stood at \$42.9 billion at end-July 2007 owing to increased foreign exchange sales at the wDAS. The level of reserves, the Committee noted, would cover approximately 19 months of current foreign exchange disbursements or 25 months of imports. d) Broad money grew by 10.9 per cent. When annualized the growth in M2 translates to 21.7 per cent which was higher than the 2007 target of 19.0 per cent. The increase in M2 was driven largely by sustained increase in the foreign assets (net) of the banking system e) Growth in aggregate domestic credit (net) declined by about 9.12 per cent at end-May, and by 37.18 per cent in June 2007 relative to its level at end-December 2006. f) Volatility in the inter-bank rates continued to moderate.	Neutral	0
52	Communique No. 52 Date - Oct 3, 2007 Publication - Oct 3, 2007	a) Continue to deploy increased forex sales for purposes of liquidity management. b) Embark upon active open market operations. c) Move the MPR to 9.0 per cent, which would be the repo rate and the rate at which CBN lends to the banks. d) The deposit money banks' deposits with the CBN will no longer earn interest. e) These measures are intended, amongst others, to deepen inter-bank trading and encourage banks to free-up resources to enlarge the credit market.	a) Inflation stayed within single digit in the third quarter of 2007. b) Slight appreciation in the naira exchange rate at the wDAS in July through September 2007. c) Increase in gross official reserves which stood at about US\$47 billion in September 2007. d) Broad money grew by 13.3 per cent and further to 15.7 per cent in August. e) Growth in aggregate domestic credit (net) declined by 36.6 per cent in August compared to 56.11 per cent decline at the end of the second quarter of 2007, driven mainly by sustained decline in credit (net) to government. f) Volatility in the interbank rates continued to ameliorate as rates fluctuated around the MPR.	Tightening	1
53	Communique No. 53 Date - Dec 4, 2007 Publication - Dec 4, 2007	a) Issued new primary instruments to mop up a significant portion of the anticipated excess liquidity in the system. b) Continued with the regular open market operations (OMO)	a) Decline in year-on-year (headline) inflation from 6.4 per cent in June 2007 to 4.1 per cent in September 2007. b) Steady appreciation in the Naira exchange rate, particularly in the second half of 2007. c) Gross official reserve increased to about US\$50 billion in November 2007, could support approximately 23 months of current foreign exchange disbursements.	Tightening	1

			<p>d) Broad money (M2) grew by 21.3 and 25.31 percent in September and October 2007. When annualized the M2 grew by 28.44 and 30.25 percent, respectively in the two months, compared with 33.3 and 39.6 percent, respectively in the corresponding months of 2006.</p> <p>e) While the Committee expressed concern about the rapid growth of M2, it however, noted with relief that this did not translate to higher inflation during the year, partly on account of the sharp increase in non-oil output.</p> <p>f) Credit to the private sector maintained an upward trend in most of 2007.</p> <p>g) Volatility in the inter-bank short-term rates continued to ameliorate during the year, as rates fluctuated within the interest rate corridor up to October when it was reviewed. Although the average inter-bank rate trended slightly upwards thereafter, it has remained generally below the MPR</p> <p>h) The Federal budget for 2008 projected significant increases in expenditure on account of build-up of infrastructure, environmental protection, and social safety nets.</p>		
54	<p>Communique No. 54</p> <p>Date - Feb 5, 2008</p> <p>Publication - Feb 5, 2008</p>	<p>a) Left the MPR unchanged at 9.5 per cent</p> <p>b) Continued the use of OMO for liquidity management and appropriate exchange rate policies.</p>	<p>a) Improvement in inflation outcomes in 2007 compared with the previous year. It however, expressed concern that given the rise in food prices and the overall global and domestic outlook, it will be necessary to ensure that inflation in 2008 is within single digit.</p> <p>b) Steady appreciation in the Naira exchange rate, particularly in the second half of 2007</p> <p>c) Gross official reserves as of 31st January 2008 stood at US\$54.22 billion. This level of reserves would support about 28 months of current foreign exchange disbursements.</p> <p>d) Broad money (M2) grew by 30.68 per cent in 2007. The growth in M2 was driven by the increase in foreign assets (net) of the banking system as well as the rise in credit to the private sector. While the Committee expressed concern about the rapid growth of M2, it noted with relief that this did not translate to higher inflation during the year, partly on account of improved supply conditions.</p>	Neutral	0

			<p>e) Inter-bank call money market rate increased slightly in December 2007, and January 2008, following the upward review of the MPR at the 201 meeting of the MPC which held on 4th December 2007.</p> <p>f) Salutary effects of sharing the Paris Club debt refund to the states in dollars. The Federal budget for 2008 has projected significant increases in expenditure on account of government focus on infrastructure development, environmental protection, and social safety nets. As these expenditures take time to yield results, the initial impact would be on aggregate demand. The private sector's own investments in partnership with those of the public sector would also have lagged effects on output.</p> <p>g) The Committee welcomes the recent decision of the National Economic Council (NEC) to phase the distribution of the proceeds of the Excess Crude Account to be paid in US dollars.</p>		
55	<p>Communique No. 55</p> <p>Date - Apr 1, 2008</p> <p>Publication - Apr 1, 2008</p>	<p>a) Raised the MPR by 50 basis points from 9.5 per cent to 10.0 per cent.</p> <p>b) Issued treasury bills for liquidity management; and</p> <p>c) Increased the sale of foreign exchange as the need arises.</p>	<p>a) The year-on-year (headline) inflation rose from 6.6 per cent at end-December 2007 to 8.6 per cent in January but fell to 8.0 per cent in February 2008. The higher levels of the headline inflation in January and February relative to that of December 2007, were mainly attributable to the increase in food prices.</p> <p>b) The expected huge fiscal injections in the months ahead and the sustained rise in asset prices would constitute potential downside risks that need to be addressed by strengthening the current restrictive monetary policy.</p> <p>c) Naira appreciated in the first quarter of 2008, driven mainly by rising foreign exchange inflows reflecting the continued investor confidence in the economy. The foreign exchange market, however, continued to function in a stable manner.</p> <p>d) The Committee noted with satisfaction that the gross official reserves amounted to US\$59.70 billion as of March 31, 2008. This level of reserves would support 38 months of current foreign exchange disbursements.</p> <p>e) Provisional figures indicate that the M2 grew by 20.59 per cent in the first two months of 2008. The growth in M2 was driven mainly by the increase in foreign assets</p>	Tightening	1

			<p>(net) of the banking system as well as credit to the private sector.</p> <p>f) The money market exhibited stability as evidenced from the data on the volume and deals in the inter-bank market.</p> <p>g) Actual and potential impact on liquidity of the recent distribution of the Naira equivalent of US \$ 2.008 billion excess crude oil revenue and the second-round distribution of same amount scheduled for June 2008. In addition, it noted that the federal budget as proposed contained significant increases in expenditure which would lead to projected budget deficits in the next two quarters of the year.</p>		
56	<p>Communique No. 56</p> <p>Date - June 2, 2008</p> <p>Publication - June 2, 2008</p>	<p>a) Continue and even strengthen the use of instruments such as open market operations (OMO) and special sale of foreign exchange.</p> <p>b) Signal the tightening of the stance of monetary policy by a) raising the MPR by 25 basis points from 10.0 per cent to 10.25 per cent, and b) increasing the CRR by 100 basis points from 3.0 per cent to 4.0 per cent with effect from June 09, 2008.</p> <p>c) Set up a technical committee to work out other intervention securities that the CBN would issue to further strengthen the effectiveness of liquidity management.</p>	<p>a) Inflationary pressures intensified in April 2008 from a lower 7.8 per cent in March 2008 and 6.6 per cent in December 2007.</p> <p>b) Growth in real gross domestic product (GDP) is projected at 6.4 per cent for the first quarter, and 6.6 per cent for the second quarter of 2008, driven principally by the growth in non-oil GDP.</p> <p>c) Broad money grew by 34.8 per cent in the first three months of 2008. On a year-on-year basis, M2 has gone up by 62.2 per cent by end March 2008. The growth in M2 was driven by increases in net foreign assets of the banking system as well as credit to the private sector.</p> <p>d) Credit to the private sector maintained an upward trend during the first quarter of 2008.</p> <p>e) The exchange rate has been relatively stable in the first five months of 2008.</p> <p>f) Gross official reserves amounted to US \$59.16 billion as of May 28, 2008. It would support 27 months of current foreign exchange disbursements. The accretion to reserves is expected to be sustained during the remainder of the year.</p> <p>g) Inter-bank call rates rose in April in response to policy and market conditions. The rates continued to be relatively stable in May at the elevated level of April. With the inflation rate at 8.2 per cent in April 2008, all the interest rates excepting the saving deposit rate were positive in real terms.</p>	Tightening	1

			h) Federal government budget as approved, and the distribution of part of excess crude oil proceeds, would lead to high liquidity injection.		
57	<p>Communique No. 57</p> <p>Date - Aug 5, 2008</p> <p>Publication - Aug 5, 2008</p>	<p>a) The MPR left unchanged at 10.25 per cent since the core inflation is expected to remain at a relatively moderate level.</p> <p>b) After reviewing developments in the financial market and the misplaced perceptions that the interest rate trends are linked to the requirement of a common year-end, the MPC decided that the common year-end for banks would no longer be a requirement and therefore left the decision to the discretion of the banks.</p> <p>c) In order to ensure a transparent pricing regime in the money market and thereby foster healthier competition, banks are required to fully disclose to the public their deposit rates as well as their base lending rates and other charges for all the sectors of the economy. These should be published on their respective websites and updated daily. The banks are required to report these rates to the CBN to enable the Bank to publish a summary of the rates for each deposit money bank every month.</p>	<p>a) Sharp rise in the year-on-year inflation rate of 12.0 per cent compared with 7.8, 8.2 and 9.7 per cent recorded in March, April, and May 2008, respectively.</p> <p>b) The NBS projects a favourable outlook for output in 2008 on the assumption of projected strong growth in the non-oil sectors, particularly agriculture and services.</p> <p>c) Broad money (M2) growth over the end-December 2007 level continued to be excessive, driven largely by the growth in credit to the core private sector, complemented by growth in net foreign assets.</p> <p>d) The threat of sustained rapid growth in money and credit aggregates for the remainder of the year remains strong against the backdrop of the prospect of further liquidity injections.</p> <p>e) Continued increase in international reserves and is likely to remain high owing to the expectations that oil prices would remain at elevated levels and partly to private capital inflows.</p> <p>f) Exchange rate of the naira has generally been stable.</p> <p>g) Upward movement of most key interest rates in response to the prevailing market conditions.</p> <p>h) Huge liquidity injection from the fiscal arm which emanated from the sharing of part of the excess crude proceeds and the enhanced regular FAAC allocations.</p>	Neutral	0
58	<p>Communique No. 58</p> <p>Date - Sept 18, 2008</p> <p>Publication - Sept 18, 2008</p>	<p>a) Reduce MPR from 10.25 per cent to 9.75 per cent.</p> <p>b) Reduce CRR from 4 per cent to 2 per cent with immediate effect.</p> <p>c) Reduce liquidity ratio from 40 per cent to 30 per cent.</p> <p>d) Allow repo transactions against eligible securities for 90 days, 180 days and 360 day.</p> <p>e) Buy and sell securities through the two-way quotes.</p>	<p>a) Economic fundamentals remain very strong and therefore the impact of the global financial turmoil is expected to be limited.</p> <p>b) Foreign exchange reserves are high at US \$63.0 billion, representing about 16 months of total foreign exchange disbursements.</p> <p>c) Inflow of foreign investment remained strong at about US\$ 8.5 billion by the end of August 2008, compared to US\$ 5.8 billion for the corresponding period of 2007.</p> <p>d) Headline inflation and food prices have been on the increase, core inflation has been in single digit.</p>	Loosening	-1

			<p>e) The outlook on output for 2008 is strong, with non-oil GDP growing at over 8 per cent.</p> <p>f) Growth in M2 and credit to the private sector have been high. Credit to the core private sector grew at 70.6 per cent at annualized rate by end of August 2008.</p> <p>g) Increase in interest rates in August was mainly due to pressure of liquidity in the financial markets in general and in the inter-bank market in particular.</p>		
59	<p>Communique No. 59</p> <p>Date - Dec 11, 2008</p> <p>Publication - Dec 11, 2008</p>	<p>a) Leave the MPR unchanged at 9.75 per cent.</p> <p>b) Reduce banks' foreign exchange net open position from 20.0 to 10.0 per cent of shareholders' funds with effect from Monday December 15, 2008.</p> <p>c) CBN to participate actively in the daily inter-bank foreign exchange market by buying and selling through the two-way quotes.</p>	<p>a) The general expectation is that in 2009 highly developed economies would post negative growth rates while emerging market economies are likely to register sharp slowdown as a consequence.</p> <p>b) Other developing countries are also expected to decelerate. In the circumstance, the policy responses of most developed and emerging economies have tended to focus on growth and financial stability.</p> <p>c) Overall, the challenges facing the Nigerian economy are in respect of developments in the international oil market encompassing both slack demand from advanced economies and declining oil prices.</p> <p>d) If the current trend continues, Nigeria's fiscal and external payments positions are likely to be further weakened in 2009. It is, however, expected that the domestic non-oil sector will rise to the challenge to offset to some extent the slack from the external sector.</p> <p>e) The optimism stems from the expected buoyant agricultural output, improvement in infrastructure as financial resources flow to the sector, and other development-enhancing activities of the government.</p>	Neutral	0
60	<p>Communique No. 60</p> <p>Date - Jan 14, 2009</p> <p>Publication - Jan 14, 2009</p>	<p>a) Reintroduction of the Retail Dutch Auction System (RDAS), with effect from Monday, January 19, 2009.</p> <p>b) Bids for the purchase of foreign exchange under the RDAS must be cash-backed at the time of the bid.</p> <p>c) Funds purchased from CBN at the Auction shall be used for eligible transactions only, subject to stipulated documentation requirements.</p>	<p>a) Estimate of the GDP growth rate for the end of 2008 was an impressive 6.8% compared with 6.2% in 2007.</p> <p>b) Inflationary pressure remained high throughout the year and provisional figures indicate that the end December headline inflation was 14.6% while estimated core (non-food). Inflation rate was at 9.2%.</p> <p>c) Depreciation of the naira in the light of decreased supply of foreign exchange vis a vis increased demand.</p> <p>d) Uncertainties and the speculative pressures in the foreign exchange market.</p>	Neutral	0

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> d) Authorized Dealers shall return to the CBN any unutilized funds within five (5) business days after delivery, at the rate of purchase. e) Purchases by banks on behalf of their customers will be published in the dailies fortnightly. f) Interest earned on Letters of Credit established and for which settlement has not been implemented, shall be repatriated to the CBN for repurchase at the bid rate at the time the funds were purchased. g) The foreign exchange Net Open Position (NOP) of banks will be reduced from 10% to 5% with effect from Monday, January 19, 2009. 			
61	<p>Communique No. 61</p> <p>Date - Feb 9, 2009</p> <p>Publication - Feb 9, 2009</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) MPR kept unchanged at 9.75 per cent. b) OMO will be actively used for achieving effective liquidity management. c) To anchor expectations and stabilize the exchange rate, MPC remains committed to managing the exchange rate within a band of +/-3 per cent until further notice. d) The difference between the CBN buying and selling rates shall not be more than 1 per cent; while that of banks and BDCs will not be more than 1 per cent and 2 per cent, respectively around the CBN rate. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) The Bank's six month forecast horizon suggests gradual moderation of the year-on-year headline inflation. b) Aggregate output growth for 2008 was estimated at 6.41 per cent, close to the 6.45 per cent achieved in 2007. c) Staff estimates indicate that monetary expansion in 2009 is likely to moderate on account of the expected decline in net foreign assets, complemented by the anticipated deceleration in growth in credit to the domestic economy. d) Sharp depreciation in the naira exchange in all the segments of the foreign exchange market e) Improvement in the activities at the equities segment of the Nigeria Stock Exchange. 	Neutral	0
62	<p>Communique No. 62</p> <p>Date - Apr 8, 2009</p> <p>Publication - Apr 8, 2009</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Reduce MPR from 9.75 per cent to 8.0 per cent. b) Reduce the liquidity ratio from 30.0 per cent to 25.0 per cent with effect from April 14, 2009 c) Reduce the Cash Reserve Requirement (CRR) from 2.0 per cent to 1.0 per cent with effect from April 14, 2009. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Staff estimates indicate that inflation could decelerate to single digit in response to subdued aggregate demand, lower impact of imported inflation and the near completion of the passthrough effect of the depreciation of the Naira. b) Staff expects that in the near-term, interest rates are likely to moderate in response to expected subdued inflation an improvement in the liquidity conditions facilitated by the CBN initiatives in this regard. c) Positive outcomes of measures taken in stabilizing the exchange rates in all the segments of the market. d) The order of expansion in M2 on a year-on-year basis is in line with long term trends and could be sustained in the short to medium term. 	Loosening	-1

			e) Foreign exchange reserves position has continued to support external sustainability, facilitated by the downward movement in the overall world trade and financial flows.		
63	<p>Communique No. 63</p> <p>Date - May 21, 2009</p> <p>Publication - May 21, 2009</p>	<p>a) Issue short-term instruments to be synchronized with the Debt Management Office's (DMO) issuance of the FGN Bonds to mop-up excess liquidity in the system.</p> <p>b) Return to a regime of fully liberalized foreign exchange market over the next three months and increase the net foreign exchange open position for banks from 1.0 to 2.5 per cent with immediate effect, while keeping in view the possibility of raising it further at the end of June 2009.</p> <p>c) Removal of the requirement that banks transact foreign exchange at 1.0 per cent around the CBN rate. The CBN will now participate in the interbank foreign exchange market at the prevailing rate.</p> <p>d) Approval-in-Principle (AIP) granted to 50 non-bank Class 'A' BDCs. The list of the BDCs will be published from Saturday, May 23, 2009.</p>	<p>a) Need to address the problem of excess liquidity in the system without necessarily putting pressure on interest rates.</p> <p>b) Exchange rates remained stable at both the official and the parallel market rates. But there has remained a wide premium between the official and parallel market rates. The medium-term outlook for the forex market was stable.</p> <p>c) The Committee decided to review the series of controls instituted in the last few months, and over the next three months return to fully liberalized regime that we had before the recent controls.</p> <p>d) Government Agencies and Oil Companies will have discretion to sell foreign exchange at the interbank foreign exchange market or to the CBN with effect from May 25, 2009.</p>	Neutral	0
64	<p>Communique No. 64</p> <p>Date - July 7, 2009</p> <p>Publication - July 7, 2009</p>	<p>a) All interest rate caps and floors imposed by the Bankers' Committee removed.</p> <p>b) MPR reduced from 8.00 per cent to 6.00 per cent per annum. The corridor of interest rates would be +/- 200 basis points, with the rate on the standing lending facility at 8.00 per cent and the rate on the standing deposit facility at 4.00 per cent.</p> <p>c) CBN shall provide a guarantee on all interbank placements from July 2009 to March 31, 2010. This guarantee is also extended to placements with banks by pension funds.</p> <p>d) Liberalization of the Interbank Foreign Exchange Market by removing restrictions and increasing the net open position limit for banks to 5% of banks' capital base.</p>	<p>a) Headline inflation would slow down on account of slack demand and improvement in the supplies of agricultural produce.</p> <p>b) Broad money (M2) decelerated sharply by 4.9 per cent in the first five months of 2009.</p> <p>c) The weighted average rate on all categories of deposits rose from 5.98 per cent in April to 6.13 per cent in May 2009. Thus, the spread between the two rates is higher than the current inflation rate, which provides a unique opportunity to banks to improve efficiency and reduce lending rates.</p> <p>d) Naira exchange rate has stabilized at the rDAS while in the other segments, the rates have appreciated, thereby narrowing the arbitrage opportunities</p> <p>e) Foreign exchange reserves as of July 03, 2009 amounted to US\$43.19 billion compared with US\$53 billion at end December 2008. The decline in reserves mirrored mainly the relative downward drift in international crude oil prices.</p>	Loosening	-1

65	<p>Communique No. 65</p> <p>Date - Sept 1, 2009</p> <p>Publication - Sept 1, 2009</p>	<p>a) Retain the MPR unchanged at 6 per cent per annum</p> <p>b) Maintain the interest rate corridor at +/- 2 per cent around the MPR</p> <p>c) Approve in principle the establishment of an "Asset Purchase Facility Fund". The Central Bank of Nigeria and Federal Ministry of Finance to jointly consider the modalities for setting up the APF Fund for effective liquidity injection and credit easing targeted at specific areas of the economy.</p>	<p>a) Moderation in the rates of real GDP growth. The revised growth rate for 2008 is put at 5.99 per cent as against an earlier estimate of 6.41 per cent.</p> <p>b) The main risk to inflation comes from core inflation with higher oil prices and possible removal of subsidies combining with the usual growth of spending around the Christmas festive season.</p> <p>c) Broad money showed a growth of 10.2 per cent on a year-on-year basis, the lowest for any month since February 2006.</p> <p>d) With the reduction of the Monetary Policy Rate and the introduction of the interest rate corridor as well as Central Bank's guarantees of unsecured inter-bank market transactions which were firmly set, effective July 20, there has been considerable improvement in the risk perceptions of market participants.</p> <p>e) The foreign exchange market has in general been relatively stable with the re-introduction of the wholesale Dutch auction system and the measures taken to further liberalize the inter-bank market.</p> <p>f) The Committee noted that recent improvements in oil output and prices would help to improve the gross foreign exchange reserves of the economy.</p>	Neutral	0
66	<p>Communique No. 66</p> <p>Date - Nov 3, 2009</p> <p>Publication - Nov 3, 2009</p>	<p>a) The MPR remains unchanged at 6 per cent, but an asymmetric corridor of interest rates around the MPR is introduced. The rate on the standing lending facility will remain at 200 basis points above the MPR, while the rate on the standing deposit facility will be 400 basis points below the MPR.</p> <p>b) There will be quantitative easing to bridge the gap currently estimated at about N500 billion between the levels of the current monetary aggregates and the benchmark levels for 2009.</p> <p>c) The modalities for quantitative easing include investments in bonds to be issued by Asset Management Company (AMC). The setting up of AMC, however, is subject to the approval of the National Assembly. Other modalities include the redemption of promissory notes issued by the Federal Ministry of Finance as well as by the CBN</p>	<p>a) The Committee felt that on the basis of the output growth recorded thus far and other indicators, growth in 2009 would remain robust.</p> <p>b) The inflation rate as measured by the year-on-year increase in 'all items' consumer price index was 10.4 per cent in September 2009. This outcome is lower than the headline inflation of 15.1 per cent in December 2008 and lower than the average headline inflation of 12.6 per cent for the first 9 months of the year.</p> <p>c) Notwithstanding the low monetary growth, money market rates, reflected market realities. With the inter-bank money market guarantees in place and the measures to strengthen the banking sector, confidence in the money market improved.</p> <p>d) The foreign exchange market has been stable. There was a slight appreciation of the Naira during the month. The</p>	Loosening	-1

		<p>in connection with the retirement of debt and liabilities arising from purchase and assumption of failed banks.</p> <p>d) Purchase of loans by banks under the AMC will be based on terms aimed at strengthening the balance sheets with a focus on asset quality, improving liquidity and capital adequacy as well as on reducing debt overhang relating to the stock market in order to stimulate activity in the capital market.</p>	<p>spread between the rates has continued to be insignificant.</p> <p>e) Foreign exchange reserves stood at US\$43.34 billion as at end September 2009, an improvement of about US\$ 1.64 billion over August, mainly owing to the receipt of the SDR allocation.</p>		
67	<p>Communique No. 67</p> <p>Date - Jan 4-5, 2010</p> <p>Publication - Jan 5, 2010</p>	<p>a) Retain MPR at 6 per cent with the asymmetric corridor remaining at 200 basis points above the MPR and 400 basis points below the MPR.</p> <p>b) Extended the guarantee on all interbank transactions up till December 31, 2010.</p> <p>c) Approved the Monetary Programme for 2010/2011 and the Monetary, Credit, Foreign Trade and Exchange Guidelines for Fiscal years 2010/2011.</p>	<p>a) GDP growth for 2009 was projected at 6.90 per cent which is significantly higher than the 5.98 per cent recorded in 2008.</p> <p>b) The headline inflation rate, as measured by the year-on-year increase in all item consumer price index, was 12.4 per cent in November 2009, up from 11.6 and 10.4 per cent recorded in October and September, respectively. The outcome was, however, lower than the headline inflation of 15.1 per cent recorded in December 2008.</p> <p>c) Broad money (M2) grew by 12.80 per cent (on annualized basis) in November 2009, which was significantly below the indicative benchmark of 20.8 per cent growth for 2009.</p> <p>d) Annualized growth rate of aggregate domestic credit (net) as of November 2009 was 56.10 per cent, compared with the provisional benchmark growth rate of 86.97 per cent for 2009.</p> <p>e) The Committee observed that despite the falling interbank rates, the retail lending rates of deposit money banks (DMBs) were still high. The average maximum lending rate had risen to 23.1 per cent in November from 22.97 and 22.64 per cent in September and June 2009, respectively.</p> <p>f) The foreign exchange market remained relatively stable for the most part of 2009, after the initial turbulence recorded in the first quarter, following measures taken by the CBN.</p> <p>g) External reserves stood at US\$42.47 billion on 29th December 2009, down from the level of US\$53.00 billion recorded at end-December 2008.</p>	Loosening	0

68	<p>Communique No. 68</p> <p>Date - Mar 1-2, 2010</p> <p>Publication - Mar 1-2, 2010</p>	<p>a) MPR remains unchanged at 6.0 per cent.</p> <p>b) Standing Lending Facility interest rate remains unchanged at 8.00 per cent, while the Standing Deposit Facility rate is lowered from 2.0 per cent to 1.0 per cent</p> <p>c) Granted liquidity status to bonds issued by state governments, subject to their meeting the specified eligibility criteria.</p> <p>d) Continue with the quantitative easing policy by providing N500 billion facility for investment in debentures issued by the Bank of Industry (BOI) in accordance with Section 31 of the CBN Act 2007, for investment in emergency power projects dedicated to industrial clusters.</p>	<p>a) GDP growth for 2010 was projected at 7.53 per cent which is higher than the 6.90 per cent recorded in 2009.</p> <p>b) The headline inflation rate, as measured by the year-on-year increase in the all-item CPI, was 12.3 per cent in January 2010, up from 12.0 per cent in December 2009, but lower than the 12.4 per cent recorded in November 2009 and the 14.0 per cent recorded in January 2009.</p> <p>c) Confidence in the money market continued to improve following the inter-bank money market guarantee and other measures to strengthen the banking sector. This is reflected in the downward movement of the daily interbank call rates.</p> <p>d) The foreign exchange market remained relatively stable in the first two months of 2010 and external reserves stood at US\$41.54 billion on 24th February 2010, down by US\$0.51 billion or 1.21 per cent from the level of US\$42.05 billion recorded.</p>	Neutral	0
69	<p>Communique No. 69</p> <p>Date - Apr 15, 2010</p> <p>Publication - Apr 15, 2010</p>	<p>a) Retained the MPR at 6 per cent and existing asymmetric corridor at +2.0 per cent and -5.0 per cent.</p> <p>b) Endorsed complementary policies being put in place by the Board of the CBN, especially the revised guidelines for loan loss provisioning for preferred sectors, the N200 billion guarantee for real sector credit and regulations governing margin lending</p>	<p>a) Persisting tight credit conditions and the continuing under-performance of key monetary aggregates</p> <p>b) The Committee commended the co-operation of key stakeholders in preparing the modalities for the injection of the N500 billion financing facility for the emergency power projects dedicated to industrial clusters and restructuring/refinancing of DMBs' exposures to the manufacturing sector and SMEs.</p> <p>c) Rebound in global economic activity which started in the second half of 2009, has been sustained.</p> <p>d) Real Gross Domestic Product (GDP) grew by 6.68 percent in the first quarter of 2010, down from 7.44 per cent in the fourth quarter of 2009, but up from the 4.50 per cent recorded in the first quarter of 2009.</p> <p>e) The stability in the domestic price level could be attributed to a number of factors, namely, the continuing monetary contraction, the delay in the passage of the 2010 federal budget and the improvement in the supply of petroleum products, amongst others.</p> <p>f) Broad money (M2) declined by 0.23 per cent at end-February 2010, which, when annualized represented a decline of 1.38 per cent, compared to the indicative growth target of 29.26 per cent for 2010 and the</p>	Loosening	0

			<p>annualized M2 decline of 5.16 per cent in the corresponding February of 2009.</p> <p>g) The Committee observed that the naira exchange rate has remained stable in all segments of the market during the first quarter.</p> <p>h) Gross external reserves were sufficient to finance 17 months of imports, which were well above the internationally recommended 3-months import cover.</p>		
70	<p>Communique No. 70</p> <p>Date - May 10-11, 2010</p> <p>Publication - May 11, 2010</p>	<p>a) Leave the MPR unchanged at 6.0 per cent.</p> <p>b) Retain the asymmetric corridor of interest rates at 200 basis points above the MPR and 500 basis points below the MPR for the Standing Lending Facility and Standing Deposit Facility, respectively</p> <p>c) Extend the CBN guarantee for all interbank transactions and foreign credit lines as well as pension funds' placements with banks from December 31, 2010 to June 30, 2011. This is to provide ample time for the conclusion of the banking sector resolution and the publication of audited accounts for the period up to December 2010. It is expected that by June 2011 all creditors and investors will have sufficient information to take an independent view of the risk of individual counterparties.</p>	<p>a) Real Gross Domestic Product (GDP) grew by 6.68 per cent in the first quarter of 2010, down from 7.44 per cent in the fourth quarter of 2009, but up from the 4.50 per cent recorded in the first quarter of 2009.</p> <p>b) The downward trend in the domestic price level could be attributed to a number of factors, including the continuing underperformance of monetary aggregates, with the associated constrained demand, availability of food stuff, and improvement in the supply of petroleum products, amongst others.</p> <p>c) Notwithstanding these developments, the Committee restated its earlier position that the threat of inflationary pressure in the near-to-medium term remains real given the expansionary stance of the 2010 Federal Government budget and the anticipated increase in spending usually associated with the run-up to election across the country.</p> <p>d) The Committee observed that the naira exchange rate has remained stable in all segments of the market during the review period, reflecting increased confidence in the Naira and the efficacy of the current exchange rate policy stance of liberalizing the foreign exchange market which has enhanced</p> <p>f) foreign exchange supply from autonomous sources.</p> <p>g) The Committee noted that the level of external reserves was sufficient to finance 17 months of current imports, which is well above the internationally recommended benchmark of 3-months import cover.</p> <p>h) It believed that with the rising price of crude oil in the international market in recent months, coupled with the improvement in output with peace in the Niger Delta,</p>	Loosening	0

			there is likely to be an accretion in the level of foreign exchange reserves in the near term.		
71	<p>Communique No. 71</p> <p>Date - July 5, 2010</p> <p>Publication - July 5, 2010</p>	<p>a) No changes are made to the current policy stance viz: the MPR should remain unchanged at 6.0 per cent; and</p> <p>b) The asymmetric corridor of 200 basis points above and 500 basis points below the MPR, respectively, are to be retained.</p>	<p>a) GDP growth for 2010 is projected at 7.74 per cent which is higher than the revised figure of 6.66 per cent recorded in 2009.</p> <p>b) Threat of inflationary pressure arising from several factors including the announcement effect of salary increase in the civil service and the rising food prices against the backdrop of the famine in neighboring Niger Republic.</p> <p>c) Broad money (M2) declined by 0.2 per cent in May 2010, which, when annualized represented a contraction of 0.48 per cent, compared with the indicative growth target of 29.26 per cent for 2010.</p> <p>d) The substantial growth of credit to government (net) against the backdrop of declining private sector credit reflected the risk aversion of the DMBs to lending to non-government borrowers.</p> <p>e) The Committee believes that in order to provide the private sector with the necessary credit to grow the economy, further efforts are needed to unlock the credit market in order to enhance the flow of credit to the real economy.</p> <p>f) The foreign exchange market remained relatively stable in the first half the year while external reserves level is still adequate as it would finance 16 months of import, compared to the internationally recommended benchmark of 3 months of import cover for a country's external reserves.</p>	Neutral	0
72	<p>Communique No. 72</p> <p>Date - Sept 21, 2010</p> <p>Publication - Sept 21, 2010</p>	<p>a) Resumption of active Open Market Operations for the purpose of targeted liquidity management.</p> <p>b) An increase in MPR by 25 basis points from 6.0 to 6.25 per cent.</p> <p>c) Adjustment of asymmetric corridor to 200 basis points above and 300 basis points below the MPR for the Standing Lending Facility and Standing Deposit, respectively. This effectively increases</p>	<p>a) GDP growth for 2010 is projected at 7.78 per cent which is higher than the 6.96 per cent recorded in 2009.</p> <p>b) The MPC welcomes the recent revision and rebasing of the Consumer Price Index (CPI) by the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) to reflect the current structure of consumption in the economy.</p>	Tightening	1

		interest payable on standing deposits with the CBN by 225 basis points forthwith.	<p>c) The MPC reiterated its earlier position on the threat of inflationary pressure arising from several other factors including implementation of the new salary structure in the civil service, expected fiscal injections arising from electioneering expenses and the injections relating to AMCON purchase of non-performing loans of DMBs, spillover effects of the rising food prices from famine in neighboring Niger Republic and floods in Asia, deregulation of energy prices as well as the expected increase in household-spending toward year-end festivities.</p> <p>d) The Committee believes that in order to provide the private sector with the necessary credit to grow the economy, further efforts were needed to restore confidence to the credit market and to unlock the flow of credit to the real economy.</p> <p>e) The foreign exchange market remained relatively stable over the review period as the naira exchange rate had remained stable in all segments of the market.</p> <p>f) The Committee noted that the current external reserves level is still adequate and is expected to remain robust in view of the favorable outlook for oil price and output. Consequently, there is no compelling reason to alter the existing exchange rate regime stability will remain a priority.</p>		
73	<p>Communique No. 73</p> <p>Date - Nov 22-23, 2010</p> <p>Publication - Nov 23, 2010</p>	<p>a) Retain the MPR at 6.25 per cent.</p> <p>b) Adjust the corridor to +/- 200 basis points, implying Standing Lending Facility (SLF) rate of 8.25 per cent, and Standing Deposit Facility (SDF) rate of 4.25 per cent.</p> <p>c) Maintain the policy stance of a stable exchange rate.</p> <p>d) Continue to monitor inflationary trends with a view to taking appropriate steps as and when necessary.</p> <p>e) On the stance of monetary policy in the year ahead, the Committee reaffirmed that monetary policy would seek to exert pressure on aggregate demand, thereby helping to lower inflation expectations. In addition, monetary policy would stand ready to provide adequate and timely liquidity to support</p>	<p>a) GDP growth for 2010 is projected at 7.85 per cent compared with 6.96 per cent recorded in 2009. The non-oil sector remained the main driver of overall growth.</p> <p>b) The persistence of high inflation remains a major challenge, when viewed against the relatively good harvests, improved supply of petroleum products and weak expansion of credit to the private sector.</p> <p>c) The interest rates at the interbank segment of the money market responded to the increase in the Monetary Policy Rate (MPR) effected at the last meeting of the MPC in September in line with policy expectation.</p> <p>d) The foreign exchange market remained relatively stable. The total foreign exchange inflow in October was US\$2.38 billion, representing a decrease of US\$0.32</p>	Neutral	0

		credit dynamics that would sustain fiscal mechanisms to bolster growth.	billion or 11.85 per cent below the US\$2.70 billion recorded in the preceding month.		
			e) The gross external reserves stood at US\$34.27 billion on 15th November 2010 compared with US\$33.597 billion as at end-October and US\$34.59 billion as at end-September.		
74	<p>Communique No. 74</p> <p>Date - Jan 24-25, 2011</p> <p>Publication - Jan 25, 2011</p>	<p>a) Raise the MPR by 25 basis points from 6.25 per cent to 6.50 per cent.</p> <p>b) Maintain the symmetric corridor of +/- 200 basis points.</p> <p>c) Raise the CRR by 100 basis points from 1.00 per cent to 2.00 per cent.</p> <p>d) Raise the LR by 500 basis points from 25.00 per cent to 30.00 per cent.</p>	<p>a) While the general outlook on growth is highly favourable, it is important to be vigilant on prices and financial market developments.</p> <p>b) The Committee noted that the risk of inflation is on the upward side as a result of the liquidity injections from the likely increase in government spending in the run up to the April 2011 elections, and AMCON purchases, as well as rising global energy and food prices and the expected pass-through to the domestic economy.</p> <p>c) The MPC also noted with serious concern the existing low rates of about 1.0 percent paid on savings deposits and its implications for financial intermediation and the mobilization of long-term funds which is critical for enhancing investment in real sector economic activities, and economic growth.</p> <p>d) With regard to external reserves, the Committee observed that the fundamental structural problem of the country as an import-dependent economy was largely responsible for the continuing depletion of the external reserves.</p> <p>e) The MPC identified the greatest challenge facing the economy as the lack of flow of credit to the critical sectors, and the consequent need to unlock the flow of credit for critical investments in agriculture, SMEs, and manufacturing sectors.</p> <p>f) To achieve this, government would need to create the right policy and regulatory environment, including the sustained fight against corruption, strengthening of transparency and institutions, as well as implementing critical reforms.</p> <p>g) On its part, the CBN will continue to engage banks and take the lead in programmes and interventions to channel credit to the real economy. To this end, the</p>	Tightening	1

			<p>Committee noted the initiatives being pursued by the Bankers' Committee and urged speedy implementation.</p> <p>h) The Committee further stated that the economy is affected not only by monetary and fiscal policy measures but also by political risk and concerns about national security which affect investors' confidence in the economy.</p>		
75	Not Available for Download				
76	<p>Communique No. 76</p> <p>Date - May 23-24, 2011</p> <p>Publication - May 24, 2011</p>	<p>a) Increase in CRR from 2 per cent to 4 per cent</p> <p>b) Increase in MPR from 7.5 per cent to 8.0 per cent</p> <p>c) Maintain the symmetric corridor of +/- 200 basis points around the MPR.</p>	<p>a) The Committee noted that the impressive output growth in 2010 was sustained in Q1 2011.</p> <p>b) Notwithstanding the decline in the inflation rate in April, inflation expectations remain high owing to the subsisting high fiscal spending, the increases in public sector wages, the possible removal of subsidy on petroleum products, and further liquidity injection due to AMCON activity.</p> <p>c) Growth in broad money (M2) during the first four months of 2011 was 3.24 per cent, or 9.72 per cent when annualized.</p> <p>d) The huge growth in credit to government against the backdrop of continuing decline in private sector credit indicates that government borrowing is crowding-out private sector credit.</p> <p>e) The interbank market rates fluctuated at the various segments since the beginning of the year. Key interbank rates moved in tandem with the upward revision of the monetary policy rate.</p> <p>f) The foreign exchange market remained relatively stable owing to a deliberate policy on the part of the CBN to increase supply to the market to maintain the exchange rate within a band of ± 3 percentage points, complemented by funding from autonomous sources.</p> <p>g) The Committee noted the modest accretion to the external reserves in recent months. It, however, noted that inflow into the CBN is not consistent with the high oil prices and, this underscores the need for tighter fiscal controls around oil revenues as well as first line charges including JVC deductions and subsidies.</p> <p>h) A higher rate of retention of oil revenues should facilitate the efforts at maintaining exchange rate stability as an antidote to imported inflation without excessive reliance on monetary tightening measures.</p>	Tightening	1
77	Communique No. 77	<p>a) Raise the MPR by 75 basis points from 8.0 per cent to 8.75 per cent</p>	<p>a) Inflationary pressures moderated but the outlook appears uncertain owing to the expected implementation</p>		

	<p>Date - July 25-26, 2011</p> <p>Publication - July 26, 2011</p>	<p>b) Maintain the corridor at +/- 200 basis points around the MPR.</p>	<p>of the new national minimum wage policy and the imminent deregulation of petroleum prices.</p> <p>b) The Committee welcomed the favorable growth projections but cautioned that the current security challenges, infrastructural bottlenecks, and the uncertainty in the international economy as well as fiscal developments could undermine investors' confidence and output growth in the near term.</p> <p>c) The Committee expressed serious concerns about the continued sluggish growth of credit to the private sector.</p> <p>d) Broad money (M2) grew by 5.66 per cent in June 2011 over the end-December 2010 level, which when annualized, translated to a growth rate of 11.32 per cent.</p> <p>e) Interest rates in all segments of the interbank money market moved up in response to the upward review of the MPR for most part of the period since the last meeting of the MPC.</p> <p>f) The premium between the rates at the wDAS and the interbank rate narrowed while that between the wDAS and the BDCs widened which is not unconnected with the measures taken to limit sales to BDCs.</p> <p>g) However, while strengthening of currency is an important factor in mitigating inflationary pressures, the spread may lead to arbitrage by players and fuel unhealthy speculation.</p> <p>h) The Committee noted the modest accretion to external reserves but remained concerned about the sustained low level of accretion in the face of higher oil output, higher oil exports volume and higher oil prices.</p>	<p>Tightening</p>	<p>1</p>
78	<p>Communique No. 78</p> <p>Date - Sept 19, 2011</p> <p>Publication - Sept 19, 2011</p>	<p>a) Increase MPR from 8.75 to 9.25 per cent.</p> <p>b) Maintain the symmetric corridor of +/-200 basis points around the MPR</p> <p>c) Retain the current CRR of 4.0 per cent</p>	<p>a) GDP growth for 2011 is projected at 7.85 per cent which is slightly lower than the 7.87 recorded in 2010.</p> <p>b) Moderation in inflationary pressures continued into the third quarter but under threat because of anticipated fiscal injections.</p> <p>c) Broad money (M2) grew by 8.55 per cent in the eight months to August 2011, which annualized to a growth rate of 12.82 per cent.</p> <p>d) Interest rates in all segments of the interbank money market rose in response to the upward review of the MPR at the previous MPC meeting.</p>	<p>Tightening</p>	<p>1</p>

			<p>e) The Committee noted that the premium between the rates at the WDAS and the interbank stabilized, while that of the BDCs narrowed significantly, suggesting the need to sustain existing measures to improve the efficiency of the market.</p> <p>f) The Committee also noted the modest accretion of external reserves to US\$34.85 billion, representing an increase of 3.32 per cent above the level of US\$33.73 billion attained on July 21, 2011.</p>		
79	<p>Communique No. 79</p> <p>Date - Oct 10, 2011</p> <p>Publication - Oct 10, 2011</p>	<p>a) The MPR is raised by 275 basis points from 9.25 per cent to 12.0 per cent</p> <p>b) Maintain the current symmetric corridor of +/-200 basis points around the MPR</p> <p>c) The cash reserve ratio(CRR) is increased from 4.0 per cent to 8.0 per cent</p> <p>d) The net open position (NOP) is reduced from 5.0 per cent to 1.0 per cent of share-holders funds</p> <p>e) It was further agreed that the reserve averaging method of computation be suspended in favour of daily maintenance until further notice.</p>	<p>a) Inflation had come down to 9.3 per cent in August but, a combination of monetary, fiscal, and structural factors continues to advise against complacency.</p> <p>b) The naira has come under increasing pressure and traded outside the band of N150 +/- 3.0 per cent.</p> <p>c) The fiscal authorities have signaled a commitment to medium-term consolidation and the projected deficit in 2012 is lower than the deficit in the 2011 budget. This notwithstanding, the projected increase in spending, particularly the high levels of recurrent expenditure, would suggest increasing pressure on prices in general.</p> <p>d) In the face of the spectre of declining oil prices, declining foreign reserves, increased demand for foreign exchange, fiscal dominance and capital flow reversals, monetary policy must bear a larger burden of economic adjustment. The MPC had to make difficult choices, each of which has clear costs and benefits.</p>	Tightening	1
80	Not Available for Download				
81					
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83	<p>Communique No. 83</p> <p>Date - May 21-22, 2012</p> <p>Publication - May 22, 2012</p>	<p>a) Retained at 12.0 per cent with the symmetric band at +/- 200 basis points.</p> <p>b) Cash Reserve Requirement (CRR) and Liquidity Ratio (LR) also remain unchanged.</p>	<p>a) Real GDP growth for fiscal 2012 is projected at 6.50 per cent, down from 7.45 per cent in 2011.</p> <p>b) Inflationary threats reemerged in Q1 2012, having moderated in Q4 2011 but remain within forecast range.</p> <p>c) Broad money supply (M2) grew by 0.01 per cent in April 2012 when compared with the level at end-December 2011.</p> <p>d) Relative to the level at end-December 2011, aggregate domestic credit (net) declined by 2.04 per cent in April 2012,</p> <p>e) translating to a decline of 6.12 per cent on annualized basis. The decline in aggregate credit during the period</p>	Neutral	0

			<p>was mainly due to the decline in credit to the core private sector.</p> <p>f) Money market interest rates remained anchored around the upper band of the interest rate corridor.</p> <p>g) Increase in foreign exchange reserves reflected generally favourable commodity prices and inflows of capital in response to the removal of restrictions on repatriation and high domestic interest rates, as well as stable exchange rates.</p> <p>h) The Committee expressed satisfaction over the orderliness in the foreign exchange market and the stability of the exchange rate.</p>		
84	Not Available for Download				
85	<p>Communique No. 85</p> <p>Date - May 21-22, 2012</p> <p>Publication - May 22, 2012</p>	<p>a) Retain the MPR at 12 per cent with +/- 200 basis points corridor.</p> <p>b) Retain the CRR at 12.0 per cent.</p> <p>c) Retain the Net Open Position at 1.0 per cent.</p>	<p>a) Economy is performing better than forecasts although growth in the first two quarters of 2012 has remained consistently below the corresponding growth rates in 2011.</p> <p>b) Inflationary pressures experienced during the first half of 2012 appear to be moderating</p> <p>c) Broad money supply (M2) grew by 3.50 per cent in August 2012 over the level at end-December 2011, which annualized to 5.25 per cent. The annualized growth rate is significantly lower than the growth rate of 15.43 per cent recorded in 2011.</p> <p>d) Interest rates trended downwards toward the end of the review period.</p> <p>e) The inter-bank call and OBB rates, which opened at 17.85 and 14.99 per cent, closed at 14.19 and 13.56 per cent, respectively</p> <p>f) The exchange rate appreciated due to the combined effects of the increase in CRR, reduction in the Net open position and the policy barring DMBs/Discount Houses from accessing Lending.</p> <p>g) The Committee expressed satisfaction with the significant accretion to external reserves during the period.</p>	Neutral	0
86	Communique No. 86	a) Retain the MPR at 12 per cent with a corridor of +/- 200 basis points around the midpoint	a) Developments in the global economy characterized by general uncertainty on the back of the deceleration in global growth.		

	<p>Date - Nov 19-20, 2012</p> <p>Publication - Nov 20, 2012</p>	<p>b) Retain the CRR at 12.0 per cent</p> <p>c) Liquidity Ratio at 30 per cent.</p>	<p>b) Events in the domestic economy highlight some new pressure points to macroeconomic stability.</p> <p>c) Despite the high interest rates, additional shocks to the economy emanating from the devastating floods, imported inflation and the upward adjustment in electricity tariffs continue to stoke inflationary pressure.</p> <p>d) Conflicting price signals with headline and food inflation trending upwards, while core inflation rate continued to moderate for the fourth consecutive month. This according to the Committee has created uncertainty as to the appropriate policy stance at this time.</p> <p>e) Since the factors underpinning the inflationary pressures were mainly structural, a monetary response may not be appropriate at this time.</p>	Neutral	0
87	<p>Communique No. 87</p> <p>Date - Jan 21, 2013</p> <p>Publication - Jan 21, 2013</p>	<p>a) Retain the MPR at 12.0 per cent with a corridor of +/- 200 basis points around the midpoint.</p> <p>b) Retain the CRR at 12.0 per cent</p> <p>c) Retain the Liquidity Ratio at 30.0 per cent.</p>	<p>a) Performance of the global economy largely subdued and was characterized by uncertainty and contraction.</p> <p>b) Committee cautioned against complacency over government revenues, despite high level of oil prices.</p> <p>c) Efforts the Government at keeping deficits within the threshold prescribed by the Fiscal Responsibility Act and advocated sustenance of the effort.</p> <p>d) Need to continue to drive down recurrent expenditure in favor of capital expenditure in view of the infrastructure deficit that continued to constrain growth performance.</p> <p>e) The Committee noted that the oil price benchmark for the 2013 budget which was increased from US\$75 to US\$79 may pose downside risk to the inflation objective and, therefore, constituted a pressure point for the low inflation objective and effective monetary policy in 2013.</p>	Neutral	0
88	<p>Communique No. 88</p> <p>Date - March 18-19, 2013</p> <p>Publication - March 19, 2013</p>	<p>a) Retain the MPR at 12 per cent with a corridor of +/- 200 basis points around the midpoint</p> <p>b) Retain the CRR at 12 per cent</p> <p>c) Retain the Liquidity Ratio at 30 per cent with the Net Open Position at 1 per cent.</p>	<p>a) The Committee was pleased with the prevailing macroeconomic stability despite shocks from both external and domestic environments.</p> <p>b) Having achieved a reasonable degree of moderation in the rate of inflation, there were compelling arguments to consider easing monetary policy, at least from the perspective of stimulating growth in the real sector.</p> <p>c) The Committee carefully weighed the option of relaxing monetary policy against the likely risks in the near-to-</p>	Neutral	0

			<p>medium term, noting that reversing the current stance of monetary policy was not likely to produce a neutral outcome, as it may signal the preference for a higher inflation rate on the part of the CBN.</p> <p>d) Widespread between deposits and lending rates, which it attributed to the inefficiencies in the market requiring institutional and structural reforms that would enforce behavioral change on the market, consistent with the long-term needs of the economy.</p> <p>e) The Committee was of the view that sustainable low lending rates, could be achieved if the necessary infrastructure such as stable power and good roads, amongst others, were put in place.</p>		
89	<p>Communique No. 89</p> <p>Date - May 20-21, 2013</p> <p>Publication - May 21, 2013</p>	<p>a) Retain the MPR at 12 per cent with a corridor of +/- 200 basis points</p> <p>b) Retain the CRR at 12 per cent</p> <p>c) Retain Liquidity Ratio at 30 per cent with the Net Open Position at 1.0 per cent.</p>	<p>a) The Committee was pleased with the prevailing macroeconomic stability-moderation in all measures of inflation on month-on-month basis, stable banking system and exchange rate and robust external reserves.</p> <p>b) The Committee was concerned about the threat posed by developments in the oil sector arising from uncertain oil market environment, high output leakages arising from oil theft which has negatively affected the oil sector's contribution to GDP and the prospects for declining output if the state of affairs continues.</p> <p>c) The Committee observed that the accretion to reserves resulted principally from increased portfolio capital inflows. The Committee noted the potential effect of this development on exchange rates, reserves, and the capital account in the event of capital flow reversal and stressed the need to maintain stability and retain confidence of investors in the consistency of monetary policy.</p> <p>d) The Committee also expressed concern over the low level of credit growth to the private sector and traced this to the crowding out effect of high growth in credit to the public sector.</p> <p>e) The Committee was of the view that the principal risks to long-term stability can be addressed through diligent implementation of sound policies of fiscal consolidation and efficient sectoral policies underpinned by structural reforms.</p>	Neutral	0
90	Communique No. 90	a) Retain the MPR at 12 per cent and the symmetric corridor +/-2 per cent.	a) The Committee was satisfied with the prevailing macroeconomic stability achieved during the period,		

	<p>Date - July 22-23, 2013</p> <p>Publication - July 23, 2013</p>	<p>b) Retain the CRR at 12 per cent; and</p> <p>c) Introduce a 50 per cent CRR on public sector deposits. This will be applied on Federal, State and Local Government deposits and all MDAs. For other deposits CRR will remain at 12 per cent.</p>	<p>including the single digit inflation, stable banking system, exchange rate stability, favourable output growth, capital market recovery and growth in external reserves, thus sustaining internal balance and external viability.</p> <p>b) The Committee also noted the recent volatility in the foreign exchange market and also recognized that the commitment of the Bank to defend the currency in the face of capital flow reversal and significant revenue attrition has stemmed the depreciation of the naira.</p> <p>c) The Committee expressed strong concerns about the risks posed to government revenues from oil theft, less than expected production, new discoveries of shale oil, the fast-increasing number of African oil exporters, the dwindling market for Nigerian crude as well as the inevitability of a fall in global oil prices as well as capital flow reversal, which may impact the current global (dollar) carry trade, for which Nigeria has been a major beneficiary.</p> <p>d) The Committee considered the inflationary outlook for the rest of the year as benign. However, principal risks remain largely due to the loose fiscal stance and rising deficit, excess liquidity in the banking system and risks to the exchange rate due to a combination of revenue shocks and external developments.</p>	Tightening	1
91	<p>Communique No. 91</p> <p>Date - Sept 23-24, 2013</p> <p>Publication - Sept 24, 2013</p>	<p>a) Retain the MPR at 12.0 per cent and the symmetric corridor of 200 basis points.</p> <p>b) Retain the 50.0 per cent CRR on public sector funds.</p> <p>c) Retain 12.0 per cent CRR on private sector deposits.</p>	<p>a) Positive developments in the economy, especially, the moderation in inflation, stability in the financial system and currency markets.</p> <p>b) Strong growth forecast by the National Bureau of Statistics for Q3 and Q4 on the back of relatively slow growth in Q2.</p> <p>c) Committee observed that the actions taken since the last MPC yielded their intended effect on stabilizing the exchange rate while maintaining inflation within its target range.</p> <p>d) However, the Committee noted the existence of strong foreign exchange demand pressures coming domestically, and which are not necessarily linked to an increase in the import of goods. This non import related demand was attributed to the buildup in political</p>	Neutral	0

			<p>activities in the country and increasing resort to dollarization of the economy by the political class.</p> <p>e) The Committee charged the Bank to ensure the stability of the currency in the face of these challenges, and to fast-track plans for adopting new regulations aimed at combating money laundering in the BDC segment.</p>		
92	<p>Communique No. 92</p> <p>Date - Nov 18-19, 2013</p> <p>Publication - Nov 19, 2013</p>	<p>a) Retain MPR at 12% +/- 2%</p> <p>b) Retain private sector CRR at 12%</p> <p>c) Retain public sector CRR at 50%</p> <p>d) Retain Liquidity Ratio at 30%</p>	<p>a) Decline in inflation and the benign outlook going into the first half of 2014.</p> <p>b) Positive impact of monetary policy in engendering a stable exchange rate regime and attracting portfolio investment</p> <p>c) AMCON expected to reduce its debt by N1 trillion in December 2013.</p> <p>d) The outlook for 2014 portends some potential headwinds that may lead to further tightening in monetary conditions.</p> <p>e) The Committee noted that, while Federal Government spending overall in 2013 has not been significantly higher than in 2012, oil revenues have continued to decline in spite of the relative stability in oil price and output when compared with preceding years.</p> <p>f) Excess Crude savings have fallen from about \$11.5b at year-end 2012 to less than \$5b on November 14. The MPC calls on the Fiscal Authorities to rebuild buffers in the excess crude account, and this can be done by blocking fiscal leakages in the oil sector and increasing oil revenues.</p> <p>g) External Reserves have remained in excess of \$45billion only because of a massive inflow in portfolio funds. The implication of this is that financial markets are extremely fragile and susceptible to external shocks.</p>	Neutral	0
93	Not Available for Download				
94	<p>Communique No. 94</p> <p>Date - March 24-25, 2014</p> <p>Publication - March 25, 2014</p>	<p>a) Retain the MPR and its corridor at current levels</p> <p>b) Raise the CRR on private sector deposits by 300 basis points to 15 per cent.</p>	<p>a) The Committee unanimously agreed that a continuation of a tight monetary policy was needed to consolidate recent gains.</p> <p>b) Resurgence of core inflation in spite of the downward trend in headline inflation reinforces this position.</p> <p>c) Prudent monetary stance would facilitate better reserve and exchange rate management.</p>	Tightening	1

			<p>d) The Committee welcomed the growth expectations but expressed concern that the industrial sector has continued to lag behind.</p> <p>e) Recent pressure in the foreign exchange market was in response to key developments in the US over the Fed's unwinding of its assets purchase programme.</p> <p>f) The pressure on external reserves was deemed to be consistent with the seasonal annual payment of dividends to foreign investors.</p>		
95	<p>Communique No. 95</p> <p>Date - May 19-20, 2014</p> <p>Publication - May 20, 2014</p>	<p>a) Retain the MPR at 12%.</p> <p>b) Retain the CRR on public sector deposits at 75%.</p> <p>c) Retain the CRR on private sector deposits at 15%.</p> <p>d) Retain the MPR corridor at +/-200 basis points.</p>	<p>a) Mixed signals over the global growth prospects in the advanced, emerging markets and developing economies.</p> <p>b) The Committee noted with satisfaction Nigeria's overall domestic economic environment which has remained stable with inflation contained within the target range, the recent stability in the foreign exchange market, stable interbank rates, and strong growth outlook.</p> <p>c) It noted, also, that over the medium term, the major risks to price stability appeared to be emanating from both external and internal sources.</p> <p>d) From the external environment, risks to the domestic economy include the prospects for increased yields and interest rates in the US and the rather low level of economic activity in the emerging markets; both of which could have repercussions for foreign exchange inflows (private and official) and stability of the naira exchange rate.</p> <p>e) Internally, the key risk factors include the high systemic banking system liquidity, elevated security concerns and anticipated high election-related spending in the run-up to the 2015 general elections.</p> <p>f) The key challenge for policy, in the Committee's view, was that of sustaining and deepening the outcomes of existing policies.</p>	Neutral	0
96	<p>Communique No. 96</p> <p>Date - July 21-22, 2014</p> <p>Publication - July 22, 2014</p>	<p>a) Retain the MPR at 12 per cent with a corridor of +/- 200 basis points around the midpoint.</p> <p>b) Retain the Liquidity Ratio at 30 per cent.</p> <p>c) Retain the public sector Cash Reserve Requirement at 75.0 per cent.</p>	<p>a) Satisfied with the relative stability in the macroeconomy as reflected in the impressive growth rates, stable consumer prices and exchange rate as well as increased external reserves.</p>	Neutral	0

		<p>d) Retain the private sector Cash Reserve Requirement at 15.0 per cent.</p>	<p>b) Concerned about the weak translation of stability to microeconomic gains in employment and access to finance especially by small and medium scale businesses.</p> <p>c) Potential of the power sector to stimulate output growth through enhanced investment and the spill-over effect in employment generation if the challenges confronting the sector are effectively and appropriately addressed.</p> <p>d) Necessity of sustaining a stable naira exchange even as it has to deal with the delicate balancing of the need for a low interest rate regime. The Committee noted that portfolio flows were not employment generating but were essential in the absence of adequate fiscal buffers.</p> <p>e) Moderation in the rate of depletion in external reserves in recent months, noting that reserves accretion needed to improve much faster to provide a strong and more resilient buffer to fiscal operations.</p> <p>f) Gradual reduction in the country's import bills through domestic production of some of the major food imports should be a key element in the overall reserves' accretion strategy.</p> <p>g) Concerned about the liquidity level and the uptick in inflation due to the poor harvest in some agricultural producing areas, particularly in the north eastern and central states of the country. It however, noted that other reform measures could dampen food prices in the short to medium term and restore inflation to a sustainable long-run path.</p> <p>h) Overall, the Committee noted that the policy direction of inflation, exchange rate and interest rate must be seen not only in the context of price and financial stability but also in enhancing the quality of life of Nigerians and promoting employment generation.</p>		
97	<p>Communique No. 97</p> <p>Date - Sept 18-19, 2014</p> <p>Publication - Sept 18-19, 2014</p>	<p>a) Retain the MPR at 12 per cent with a corridor of +/- 200 basis points around the midpoint.</p> <p>b) Retain the public sector Cash Reserve Requirement at 75.0 per cent</p> <p>c) Retain the private sector Cash Reserve Requirement at 15.0 per cent.</p>	<p>a) Relative stability in the economy while also noting the risks that lie ahead. The key risks include: the possibility of capital reversals as the Fed's Quantitative Easing in the US finally ends in October, amidst dwindling oil output and declining oil prices, domestic security challenges and upward trending headline inflation.</p>	Neutral	0

			<p>b) The policy challenges include sustaining the stability of the naira exchange rate, managing the vulnerability to capital flow reversal, building fiscal buffers to insure against global shocks, managing inflation and exchange rate expectations and safeguarding the financial system stability as well as a buildup in election related spending.</p> <p>c) The Committee welcomed the efforts by government to address some of the constraints and risks to economic activity like the insurgency in the North-East and the Ebola Virus Disease epidemic.</p> <p>d) It noted that as progress is made in these areas and in respect of other constraints like power and improving SME financing, the outlook for growth appears bright and prospects for upward price pressure would be moderated.</p> <p>e) In light of the foregoing and consideration of other key risk factors, the Committee was of the view that the direction for policy in the short- to medium term would be to retain the current stance of monetary policy.</p>		
98	Not Available for Download				
99					
100	<p>Communique No. 100</p> <p>Date - March 23-24, 2015</p> <p>Publication - March 24, 2015</p>	<p>a) Retain the MPR at 13 per cent</p> <p>b) Retain the CRR on Private Sector deposits at 20 per cent</p> <p>c) Retain CRR on Public Sector deposits at 75 per cent</p> <p>d) Retain the liquidity ratio at 30 per cent.</p>	<p>a) The Committee expressed satisfaction with the impact of the decisions taken to harmonize the foreign exchange market.</p> <p>b) Concern about the wide divergence between the interbank and the bureau-de-change exchange rates, which provides an avenue for arbitrage and speculative activities in the market.</p> <p>c) Concern about the phenomenon of currency substitution and partial dollarization in the economy, a development which may have significantly fueled the high demand for foreign exchange.</p> <p>d) Concern about the outlook for growth, which had moderated partly due to the effects of low oil prices, naira exchange rate depreciation, and election related concerns.</p>	Neutral	0

			<p>e) The Committee was, however, optimistic that the situation would improve once elections were successfully conducted with the expected improvement in business confidence.</p> <p>f) Gradual rise in headline inflation, driven mainly by exchange rate-induced high prices of imported (processed) food and output supply shocks. However, the Committee was of the view that the prevailing tight monetary policy stance and some of the recent administrative measures would among others help to lock-in inflation expectations and further stabilize the naira exchange rate.</p>		
101	Not Available for Download				
102					
103	<p>Communique No. 103</p> <p>Date - Sept 21-22, 2015</p> <p>Publication - March 24, 2015</p>	<p>a) Reduce the CRR from 31 to 25 per cent.</p> <p>b) Retain the MPR at 13 per cent.</p> <p>c) Retain the symmetric corridor of 200 basis points around the MPR</p> <p>d) Retain the Liquidity Ratio at 30 per cent.</p>	<p>a) Overall macroeconomic environment remained fragile with the economy further slowing in the second quarter of the year, making it the second consecutive quarterly less-than expected performance.</p> <p>b) Year-on-year headline inflation continued to trend upwards, although the month-on-month measure moderated.</p> <p>c) Demand pressure in the foreign exchange market remained significant as oil prices continued to decline.</p> <p>d) Arising from these developments, there were indications that some of the banking sector performance indicators could be stressed if conditions worsen further.</p> <p>e) In the face of prevailing circumstances, the Committee acknowledged that synergy between monetary and fiscal policies remained the most potent option to sustainable growth.</p> <p>f) The impact of the persistent decline in global crude oil prices on the fiscal position of Government continues to reflect in rising credit to government.</p> <p>g) On inflation, the Committee was optimistic that as harvests progress in the coming months, pressure on food prices would gradually recede, while growth enhancing measures would over the medium term have some moderating effect on food prices.</p>	Loosening	-1
104	Communique No. 104	<p>a) Reduce the CRR from 25.0 per cent to 20.0 per cent.</p> <p>b) Reduce the MPR from 13.0 per cent to 11.0 per cent.</p>	<p>a) Continued fragile global economic environment, including the possibility of monetary policy</p>		

	Date - Nov 23-24, 2015 Publication - Nov 24, 2015	c) Change the symmetric corridor of 200 basis points around the MPR to an asymmetric corridor of +200 basis points and -700 basis points, around the MPR.	<p>normalization in the United States; poor outlook for commodity prices and further slowdown in the Emerging Markets and Developing Economies.</p> <p>b) Fragility of the domestic macroeconomic environment; reflected partly in low output growth, soft oil prices, low credit to the high elasticity sectors of the economy and sustained inflationary pressure, which however, softened moderately in October.</p> <p>c) The MPC was, particularly, concerned that the previous liquidity injections embarked upon through lowering of the CRR, in the last MPC, has not transmitted significantly to improved credit delivery to key growth and employment in sensitive sectors of the economy. Rather, credit went to sectors with low employment elasticity.</p>	Loosening	-1
105	Communique No. 105 Date - Jan 25-26, 2016 Publication - Jan 26, 2016	<p>a) Retain the CRR at 20.0 per cent.</p> <p>b) Retain MPR at 11.0 per cent.</p> <p>c) Retain Liquidity Ratio at 30 per cent.</p> <p>d) Retain the asymmetric corridor at +200 basis points and -700 basis points.</p>	<p>a) Need to brace up for a longer period of low government revenues due to declining oil prices.</p> <p>b) CBN finetuning the framework for foreign exchange management with a view to ensuring a more effective and liquid foreign exchange market.</p> <p>c) The sound and well-coordinated monetary, fiscal, and external sector policies provide room for optimism about the medium to long term macroeconomic prospects</p> <p>d) Effects of the softer monetary policy stance adopted at the last MPC, should start crystalizing through expansion of credit to critical sectors of the economy.</p> <p>e) The unveiling of the Federal budget oriented towards socio-economic and infrastructural development is expected to provide the necessary impetus for growth.</p>	Neutral	0
106	Communique No. 106 Date - March 21-22, 2016 Publication - March 22, 2016	<p>a) Raise MPR by 100 basis points from 11.00 per cent to 12.00 per cent.</p> <p>b) Raise CRR by 250 basis points from 20.00 to 22.50 per cent.</p> <p>c) Retain Liquidity Ratio at 30.00 per cent.</p> <p>d) Narrow the asymmetric corridor from +200 and -700 basis points to +200 and -500 basis points.</p>	<p>a) Weakening macroeconomic environment, reflected particularly in foreign exchange shortages, slowing GDP growth rate and rising inflation.</p> <p>b) Contrary to the notion of liquidity overhang in the financial system, the wider economy appears starved of the needed liquidity to spur growth and employment.</p> <p>c) The conflicting signals from slowing growth and rising inflation present a difficult policy challenge.</p>	Tightening	1

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> d) Excess liquidity in the banking system contributing to the pressure in the foreign exchange market with a strong pass-through to consumer prices. e) Need to sustain, deepen, and speed up reforms designed to ensure focused coordination of monetary and fiscal policies. 		
107	<p>Communique No. 107</p> <p>Date - May 23-24, 2016</p> <p>Publication - May 24, 2016</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Retain the MPR at 12.00 per cent. b) Retain the CRR at 22.50 per cent. c) Retain the Liquidity Ratio at 30.00 per cent. d) Retain the Asymmetric Window at +200 and -500 basis points around the MPR 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Increased inflationary pressure b) Contraction in real output c) Rising unemployment. d) Delay in passage of the 2016 budget constrained the much-desired fiscal stimulus e) Underlying conditions necessitates tight monetary policy, but the Committee favors some sundry administrative measures. 	Neutral	0
108	<p>Communique No. 108</p> <p>Date - July 25-26, 2016</p> <p>Publication - July 26, 2016</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) MPR increased by 200 basis points from 12.00 to 14 per cent. b) Retained the CRR at 22.50 per cent. c) Retained the Liquidity Ratio at 30.00 per cent. d) Retained the Asymmetric Window at +200 and -500 basis points around the MPR e) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Inflation had risen significantly, eroding real purchasing power of fixed income earners, and dragging growth b) Need to fast-track the implementation of the 2016 budget in order to stimulate economic activity to bridge the output gap and create employment. c) Non-payment of salaries in some states and urged express action in that direction to help stimulate aggregate demand. d) Economy passing through a difficult phase and need to deal with critical supply gaps. 	Tightening	1
109	<p>Communique No. 109</p> <p>Date - Sept 19-20, 2016</p> <p>Publication - Sept 20, 2016</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Retained the MPR at 14.0 per cent. b) Retained the CRR at 22.5 per cent. c) Retained the Liquidity Ratio at 30.0 per cent. d) Retained the Asymmetric corridor at +200 and -500 basis points around the MPR. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) The Committee acknowledged the weak macroeconomic performance and the challenges confronting the economy but noted that the MPC had consistently called attention to the implications of the absence of robust fiscal policy to complement monetary policy in the past. b) The Committee recognized that monetary policy had been substantially burdened since 2009 and had been stretched. c) The Committee noted that new capital flows into the economy, approximately US\$1 billion, had come in since July d) Month-on-month inflation has declined continuously since May 2016 e) Against this background, members reemphasized the need to prioritize the use of monetary policy instruments 	Neutral	0

			in dealing essentially with stability issues around key prices (consumer prices and exchange rate) as prerequisites for growth.		
110	<p>Communique No. 110</p> <p>Date - Nov 21-22, 2016</p> <p>Publication - Nov 22, 2016</p>	<p>a) Retain the MPR at 14.0 per cent.</p> <p>b) Retain the CRR at 22.5 per cent.</p> <p>c) Retain the Liquidity Ratio at 30.0 per cent.</p> <p>d) Retain the Asymmetric corridor at +200 and -500 basis points around the MPR.</p>	<p>a) Committee considered the implications of the twin deficits of current account and budget deficits, the rise of nationalist sentiments across the West and implications for national elections in France and Germany as well as the forthcoming referendum in Italy.</p> <p>b) Foreign exchange inflows into the economy improved significantly in July and August but it declined after the September MPC meeting, leading to rising inflation and increasing negative real interest rates.</p> <p>c) Limitations of monetary policy in reversing the current stagflationary condition in the economy, which it traced to supply and demand shocks.</p> <p>d) Members stressed the need for a robust and more keenly coordinated macroeconomic policy framework that would restart output growth, stimulate aggregate demand and rein in inflation expectations.</p> <p>e) The MPC urged the Federal Government to urgently assess the extent of its indebtedness to domestic economic agents and develop a framework for securitizing the debts in order to settle its outstanding domestic contractual obligations which cuts across all sectors of the economy.</p>	Neutral	0
111	<p>Communique No. 111</p> <p>Date - Jan 23-24, 2017</p> <p>Publication - Jan 24, 2017</p>	<p>a) Retain the MPR at 14.0 per cent.</p> <p>b) Retain the CRR at 22.5 per cent.</p> <p>c) Retain the Liquidity Ratio at 30.0 per cent.</p> <p>d) Retain the Asymmetric corridor at +200 and -500 basis points around the MPR.</p>	<p>a) Rising wave of nationalistic ideologues across the West, the re-evaluation of trade agreements and the possibility of rapid</p> <p>b) monetary policy normalization in the United States, with adverse consequences for other countries, including Nigeria.</p> <p>c) Imperative of sectoral policies and greater coordination of monetary and fiscal policy.</p> <p>d) Pressures on consumer prices were yet to abate and even as the economy continued to be in recession despite the intervention support by the Central Bank, the Committee stressed that it was not oblivious of the full ramifications of the economic challenges facing the country.</p>	Neutral	0

			e) Need for an early finalization of the 2017 Federal Budget by the authorities concerned, and the resolve to pursue a non-oil driven economy, as these will go a long way in stimulating aggregate demand and restoring confidence in the economy.		
112	<p>Communique No. 112</p> <p>Date - March 20-21, 2017</p> <p>Publication - March 21, 2017</p>	<p>a) Retain the MPR at 14.0 per cent.</p> <p>b) Retain the CRR at 22.5 per cent.</p> <p>c) Retain the Liquidity Ratio at 30.0 per cent.</p> <p>d) Retain the Asymmetric corridor at +200 and -500 basis points around the MPR.</p>	<p>a) Continuing global uncertainties as reflected in the unfolding protectionist posture of the United States and some European countries.</p> <p>b) Sustenance of the OPEC-Russian agreement to cut oil production beyond July 2017, sluggish global recovery, and the strengthening U.S. dollar.</p> <p>c) Persisting inflationary pressures; continuing output contraction; high unemployment rate; elevated demand pressure in the foreign exchange market; low credit to the real sector and weakening financial system indicators.</p> <p>d) Improved implementation of the foreign exchange policy that resulted in naira's appreciation.</p> <p>e) Release of the Economic Recovery and Growth Plan and urged its speedy implementation with clear timelines and deliverables.</p>	Neutral	0
113	<p>Communique No. 113</p> <p>Date - May 22-23, 2017</p> <p>Publication - May 23, 2017</p>	<p>a) Retain the MPR at 14.0 per cent.</p> <p>b) Retain the CRR at 22.5 per cent.</p> <p>c) Retain the Liquidity Ratio at 30.0 per cent.</p> <p>d) Retain the Asymmetric corridor at +200 and -500 basis points around the MPR.</p>	<p>a) Continuing global uncertainties arising from the dwindling commitment to global cooperation, the strengthening of the U.S. dollar, and the unsteady commodity prices.</p> <p>b) The downward trend in inflation in April 2017 is a welcomed development but the rate was still significantly above the policy reference band.</p> <p>c) Relative stability in the Naira exchange rate across all segments of the foreign exchange market and the improved prospects of foreign investment inflow.</p> <p>d) Welcomed the passage of the 2017 Budget and called on the relevant authorities to ensure its judicious implementation, especially, the capital budget in line with the Economic Recovery and Growth Plan.</p>	Neutral	0
114	<p>Communique No. 114</p> <p>Date - July 24-25, 2017</p>	<p>a) Retain the MPR at 14.0 per cent.</p> <p>b) Retain the CRR at 22.5 per cent.</p> <p>c) Retain the Liquidity Ratio at 30.0 per cent.</p>	<p>a) Gradual but consistent decline in inflationary pressures in the domestic economy, noting its base effect,</p>	Neutral	0

	Publication - July 25, 2017	d) Retain the Asymmetric corridor at +200 and -500 basis points around the MPR.	<p>b) Continuous improvements in the naira exchange rate across all segments of the foreign exchange market, and considerable signs of improved investments inflows.</p> <p>c) The Committee welcomed the move by the fiscal authorities to engage the services of asset-tracing experts to investigate the tax payment status of 150 firms and individuals in an effort to close some of the loopholes in tax collection, towards improving government revenue.</p> <p>d) The Committee expressed concern about the slow implementation of the 2017 Budget and called on the relevant authorities to ensure timely implementation, especially, of the capital portion in order to realize the objectives of the Economic Recovery and Growth Plan.</p>		
115	<p>Communique No. 115</p> <p>Date - Sept 25-26, 2017</p> <p>Publication - Sept 26, 2017</p>	<p>a) Retain the MPR at 14.0 per cent.</p> <p>b) Retain the CRR at 22.5 per cent.</p> <p>c) Retain the Liquidity Ratio at 30.0 per cent.</p> <p>d) Retain the Asymmetric corridor at +200 and -500 basis points around the MPR.</p>	<p>a) The Committee applauded the exit of the Nigerian economy from recession but observed that the growth remains fragile and, therefore, hopes that complementary fiscal and monetary policies would sustain the growth momentum.</p> <p>b) Gradual, but consistent decline in inflation, noting, however, the substantial base effect</p> <p>c) Continuous improvement in the naira exchange rate across all segments of the foreign exchange market</p> <p>d) Considerable improvement in foreign capital inflow.</p> <p>e) Steady implementation of the 2017 Budget, especially, the capital component of the budget</p> <p>f) The Committee, however, expressed concern on the sustained pressure on food prices, noting risks posed by floods, strikes and insurgencies in various parts of the country to food production and distribution.</p> <p>g) The Committee commended the Federal Government for issuing the Executive Order aimed at improving the ease of doing business in the country.</p>	Neutral	0
116	<p>Communique No. 116</p> <p>Date - Nov 20-21, 2017</p> <p>Publication - Nov 21, 2017</p>	<p>a) Retain the MPR at 14.0 per cent.</p> <p>b) Retain the CRR at 22.5 per cent.</p> <p>c) Retain the Liquidity Ratio at 30.0 per cent.</p> <p>d) Retain the Asymmetric corridor at +200 and -500 basis points around the MPR.</p>	<p>a) The Committee noted with satisfaction the second consecutive quarterly growth in real GDP following five quarters of contraction.</p> <p>b) Relative stability in the exchange rate, particularly the narrowing premia</p>	Neutral	0

			<p>c) Slow deceleration in consumer price inflation, largely attributable to base effects.</p> <p>d) Public investment has picked up with increased housing construction at the Federal and state levels, as well as shipping activities at the ports.</p>		
117	<p>Communique No. 117</p> <p>Date - Apr 3-4, 2018</p> <p>Publication - Apr 4, 2018</p>	<p>a) Retain MPR at 14.0 per cent.</p> <p>b) Retain CRR at 22.5 per cent.</p> <p>c) Retain Liquidity Ratio at 30.0 per cent.</p> <p>d) Maintain Asymmetric corridor at +200 and -500 basis points around the MPR.</p>	<p>a) Gradual return to macroeconomic stability as reflected in the third consecutive quarterly growth in real GDP</p> <p>b) Continued moderation in all measures of inflation</p> <p>c) Sustained stability in the naira exchange rate</p> <p>d) Committee welcomed the narrowing of the exchange rate premium between the BDC segment and the Investors' and Exporters' (I&E) window of the foreign exchange market.</p> <p>e) Overall, the Committee noted that the recovery of the economy was strengthening, in view of the return to growth of the Services Sector.</p> <p>f) The fiscal sector continues to settle its outstanding liabilities and it reduces its domestic debt profile, thus increasing the liquidity of the banking system.</p> <p>g) Committee noted with satisfaction the gradual implementation of the Economic Recovery and Growth Plan, in an effort to stimulate economic recovery.</p> <p>h) Committee urged quick passage of the 2018 Appropriation Bill by the National Assembly, so as to keep fiscal policy on track and deliver the urgently needed reliefs in terms of employment and growth for the citizenry.</p>	Neutral	0
118	<p>Communique No. 118</p> <p>Date - May 21-22, 2018</p> <p>Publication - May 22, 2018</p>	<p>a) Retain MPR at 14.0 per cent.</p> <p>b) Retain CRR at 22.5 per cent.</p> <p>c) Retain Liquidity Ratio at 30.0 per cent.</p> <p>d) Maintain Asymmetric corridor at +200 and -500 basis points around the MPR.</p>	<p>a) Real GDP grew for the fourth consecutive quarter</p> <p>b) Continued deceleration in headline inflation</p> <p>c) Stability in the foreign exchange market</p> <p>d) Satisfactory the level of activities in the Investors' and Exporters' (I&E) window of the foreign exchange market.</p> <p>e) Committee satisfied with the progress made with the implementation of the Economic Recovery and Growth Plan, but were concerned on the effect of delay in the passage of the 2018 Appropriation Bill</p>	Neutral	0

			g) Encouraged the Government to sustain current efforts at boosting tax revenue generation notwithstanding the increase in crude oil and other commodity prices.		
119	<p>Communique No. 119</p> <p>Date - July 23-24, 2018</p> <p>Publication - July 24, 2018</p>	<p>a) Retain MPR at 14.0 per cent.</p> <p>b) Retain CRR at 22.5 per cent.</p> <p>c) Retain Liquidity Ratio at 30.0 per cent.</p> <p>d) Maintain Asymmetric corridor at +200 and -500 basis points around the MPR.</p>	<p>a) Fourth consecutive quarters of growth in real GDP and the positive growth outlook in the domestic economy.</p> <p>b) Sustained moderation in inflationary pressures, especially headline inflation</p> <p>c) Stability in the foreign exchange market,</p> <p>d) Threat posed by incessant herdsmen-farmers crisis in some key food producing states and the negative impact on food supply chains which would continue to exert upward pressure on food prices.</p> <p>e) High level of activities in the Investors' and Exporters' (I&E) window of the foreign exchange market which continued to supply liquidity in foreign exchange market, narrow exchange rate premium, and reduce speculative activities in the market.</p> <p>f) Moderation in the levels of non-performing loans.</p>	Neutral	0
120	<p>Communique No. 120</p> <p>Date - Sept 24-25, 2018</p> <p>Publication - Sept 25, 2018</p>	<p>a) Retain the MPR at 14 per cent.</p> <p>b) Retain the asymmetric corridor of +200/-500 basis points around the MPR.</p> <p>c) Retain the CRR at 22.5 per cent.</p> <p>d) Retain the Liquidity Ratio at 30 per cent.</p>	<p>a) Modest stability achieved in key indicators, including inflation, exchange rate and external reserves.</p> <p>b) Relative stability returned to the foreign exchange market, buoyed by a robust level of external reserves</p> <p>c) The gains appear to be under threat of reversal, following new data which provides evidence of weakening fundamentals.</p> <p>d) The Committee identified rising inflation and pressure on external reserves created by capital flow reversal as the current challenges to growth.</p> <p>e) The Committee was concerned that the exit from recession may be under threat as the economy slowed to 1.95 and 1.50 per cent in Q1 and Q2 2018, respectively.</p> <p>f) Disruptions to the food supply chain in major food producing states due to the combined effects of poor infrastructure, flooding and the on-going security challenges resulted in a rise in food prices, contributing to the uptick in headline inflation.</p> <p>g) The Committee was, however, optimistic that as harvests progress in the coming months, pressure on food prices would gradually recede, while growth enhancing measures would over the medium term have some moderating impact on food prices.</p> <p>h) Potential impact of liquidity injections from election related spending and increase in FAAC distributions which is rising in tandem with increase in oil receipts.</p>	Neutral	0

			i) Rising level of non-performing loans in the banking system.		
121	<p>Communique No. 121</p> <p>Date - Nov 21-22, 2018</p> <p>Publication - Nov 22, 2018</p>	<p>a) Retain the MPR at 14 per cent.</p> <p>b) Retain the asymmetric corridor of +200/-500 basis points around the MPR.</p> <p>c) Retain the CRR at 22.5 per cent; and</p> <p>d) Retain the Liquidity Ratio at 30 per cent.</p>	<p>a) Modest stability in domestic prices, output growth and the financial system.</p> <p>b) Tepid growth expectations and growing uncertainty in the global financial markets.</p> <p>c) Moderation in inflation in October, reflecting declining food prices.</p> <p>d) Proposed increase in the national minimum wage would stimulate output growth due to prolonged weak aggregate demand arising from salary arrears and contractor debt.</p> <p>e) Improvements in the financial stability indicators,</p> <p>f) including non-performing loans, capital adequacy and liquidity ratios of the Deposit Money Banks (DMBs).</p>	Neutral	0

Appendix 3: Measuring Inflation Communication by the CBN

Table 1 – Example of Upside Risk Posture - Communiqué No. 1

	A: Sentence	B: Does the highlighted statement(s) in the sentence reveal upside risks to price stability?	C: Does the highlighted statement(s) in the sentence reveal downside risks to price stability?	D: Does the highlighted statement(s) in the sentence reveal neutral position on price stability?
1	Consistent with the global acceptance of the principles of the Code of Good Practices on Transparency on Monetary and Financial Policies, the Monetary Policy Committee (MPC) of the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), at its Meeting held on June 26, 2001, resolved to embark on the monthly publication of key monetary and exchange rate policy decisions. The essence of the release is to inform the public (stakeholders and operators) about the policy objectives of the CBN, including the rationale for its decisions. It is expected that this initiative will minimize the problem of information asymmetry and thus foster market confidence, which is essential for macroeconomic stability. This maiden communiqué of the Committee reports on the discussions of the Committee held on June 26, 2001, which reviewed recent developments in financial and macroeconomic conditions	No	No	No
2	Members recalled that the CBN had responded to the relative price and exchange rate stability and the need to enhance domestic output growth in fiscal 2000 by a policy of monetary ease. Specifically, the CBN's minimum rediscount rate (MRR), the nominal anchor of the Bank's interest rate policy, was reviewed downward from 18.0 per cent in the first quarter to 14.0 per cent in November, 2000. Similarly, the cash reserve requirement (CRR), was reduced from 12.0 per cent to 10.0 per cent, while the liquidity ratio (LR) was lowered to 35.0 per cent from 40.0 per cent.	No	No	No
3	The emergence of inflationary pressures and the need to sustain macroeconomic and price stability in fiscal 2001 have necessitated a review of the Bank's policy stance. In this regard, the MRR was raised by 250 basis points to 18.5 per cent, while the CRR and LR were raised to 12.5 per cent and 40.0 per cent, respectively, between January and April 2001. Despite the increases, the pressure intensified.	Yes	No	No
4	The expansionary fiscal operations of the three tiers of government, particularly the monetization of the proceeds of excess crude oil earnings, which exacerbated the problem of excess liquidity in the banking system, led to a rapid acceleration in the rate of monetary expansion, thereby putting intense pressure on domestic prices and the naira exchange rate. Broad money supply (M2) increased rapidly during the first five months of 2001, by 27.0 per cent, well above the 12.2 per cent target increase for the whole year. Inflation increased sharply from 6.9 per cent at end-December, 2000 to 13.9 per cent by end-April, 2001. These negative developments clearly needed prompt, corrective measures	No	No	Yes
5	In the Inter-bank Foreign Exchange Market (FEM), the liquidity pressure was reflected in the sharp increase in the demand for foreign exchange. For example, aggregate demand rose from US\$733.06 million in March to US\$962.56 million in April. Equivalent to an average daily demand of US\$33.8 million in March, vis-à-vis US\$53.8 million in April. Given the magnitude of the demand pressure, the exchange rate of the naira depreciated in all the segments of the market, with the spread between the FEM and parallel market rates hovering at 20.8 per cent as at end-June 2001	No	No	No
6	The Committee duly recognized that structural rigidities and market distortions also contributed to the macroeconomic imbalance, it nevertheless agreed that an accommodating monetary policy stance would only compound the problem. It was against this background, and in anticipation of subsequent injections of excess liquidity via fiscal operations, that the Committee, at its meeting held on June 26, 2001, decided to further raise the MRR by 200 basis points to 18.5 percent. The action was borne out of the need to avoid an accommodating monetary policy that would exacerbate inflationary pressures and precipitate exchange rate and macroeconomic instability, which are not only inimical to investment and sustainable output growth, but would also erode the economic gains made in the recent past.	Yes	No	No
7	The Monetary Policy Committee will continue to monitor developments in the leading macroeconomic indicators and will take appropriate measures for the interest of the economy	No	No	No
Total Statements on Upside, Downside and Neutral Position		2	0	1
E: Summary				
A	Total number of statements that reveal upside risks to price stability	2	Total number of statements that reveal upside risks to price stability minus total number of statements that reveal downside risks to price stability, divided by total number of statements about price stability, including neutral	
B	Total number of statements that reveal downside risks to price stability	0		
C	Total number of statements that reveal neutral position on price stability	1		
D	Total number of statements about price stability (A + B)	2		
E	Total number of statements about price stability (including neutral) (A + B + C)	3		
MPC		0.667		

Table 4 – Estimated MPCI for all the Communiqués

Quarter	Communiqué No.	Total number of statements that reveal upside risks to price stability	Total number of statements that reveal downside risks to price stability	Total number of statements that reveal neutral position on price stability	Total number of statements about price stability	Total number of statements about price stability, excluding forward	Necessary Policy Communication (MPC)
Q2 2001	1	0	0	1	1	1	0.667
Q3 2001	3	0	0	1	1	1	0.500
Q4 2001	4	0	0	1	1	1	0.667
Q1 2002	5	0	0	1	1	1	0.667
Q2 2002	7	1	0	0	1	1	0.333
Q3 2002	10	1	0	0	1	1	1.000
Q4 2002	13	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q1 2003	14	2	0	1	2	1	0.667
Q2 2003	17	1	0	0	1	1	0.333
Q3 2003	18	0	0	1	0	1	0.000
Q4 2003	19	0	0	1	0	1	0.000
Q1 2004	20	0	1	1	2	2	0.500
Q2 2004	21	1	1	1	3	3	0.667
Q3 2004	22	1	1	1	3	3	0.667
Q4 2004	23	1	1	1	3	3	0.667
Q1 2005	24	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q2 2005	25	0	1	1	2	2	0.500
Q3 2005	26	0	1	1	2	2	0.500
Q4 2005	27	1	0	1	2	2	0.500
Q1 2006	28	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q2 2006	29	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q3 2006	30	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q4 2006	31	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q1 2007	32	1	0	2	3	1	0.333
Q2 2007	33	0	0	0	0	1	0.000
Q3 2007	34	0	1	1	2	1	0.500
Q4 2007	35	1	1	1	3	2	0.667
Q1 2008	36	1	1	1	3	2	0.667
Q2 2008	37	2	1	1	4	3	0.750
Q3 2008	38	0	1	1	2	1	0.500
Q4 2008	39	1	0	1	2	1	0.500
Q1 2009	40	1	0	1	2	1	0.500
Q2 2009	41	0	0	1	1	1	0.333
Q3 2009	42	0	0	1	1	1	0.333
Q4 2009	43	1	0	1	2	1	0.500
Q1 2010	44	1	0	0	1	1	0.333
Q2 2010	45	1	0	0	1	1	0.333
Q3 2010	46	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q4 2010	47	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q1 2011	48	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q2 2011	49	1	0	0	1	1	0.333
Q3 2011	50	1	0	0	1	1	0.333
Q4 2011	51	1	0	0	1	1	0.333
Q1 2012	52	1	0	0	1	1	0.333
Q2 2012	53	1	0	0	1	1	0.333
Q3 2012	54	1	0	0	1	1	0.333
Q4 2012	55	1	0	0	1	1	0.333
Q1 2013	56	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q2 2013	57	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q3 2013	58	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q4 2013	59	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q1 2014	60	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q2 2014	61	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q3 2014	62	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q4 2014	63	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q1 2015	64	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q2 2015	65	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q3 2015	66	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q4 2015	67	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q1 2016	68	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q2 2016	69	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q3 2016	70	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q4 2016	71	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q1 2017	72	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q2 2017	73	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q3 2017	74	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q4 2017	75	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q1 2018	76	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q2 2018	77	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q3 2018	78	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q4 2018	79	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q1 2019	80	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q2 2019	81	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q3 2019	82	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q4 2019	83	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q1 2020	84	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q2 2020	85	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q3 2020	86	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q4 2020	87	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q1 2021	88	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q2 2021	89	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q3 2021	90	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q4 2021	91	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q1 2022	92	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q2 2022	93	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q3 2022	94	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q4 2022	95	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q1 2023	96	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q2 2023	97	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q3 2023	98	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q4 2023	99	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q1 2024	100	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q2 2024	101	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q3 2024	102	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q4 2024	103	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q1 2025	104	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q2 2025	105	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q3 2025	106	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q4 2025	107	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q1 2026	108	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q2 2026	109	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q3 2026	110	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q4 2026	111	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q1 2027	112	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q2 2027	113	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q3 2027	114	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q4 2027	115	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q1 2028	116	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q2 2028	117	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q3 2028	118	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q4 2028	119	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q1 2029	120	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q2 2029	121	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q3 2029	122	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Q4 2029	123	0	0	0	0	0	0.000

Appendix 4: Assessing the Transmission Effects of Communication by the CBN

Part A
Baseline Model

Table 1: Lag Length Selection

	Akaike Info Criterion	Akaike Rank	Schwarz Criterion	Schwarz Rank
Lag 4	-4.0091	2	-3.4738	4
Lag 3	-4.1004	1	-3.6691	1
Lag 2	-3.9686	3	-3.6396	2
Lag 1	-3.7165	4	-3.4880	3

Table 2: ARDL/Bounds Testing for the existence of long run cointegration

Model	F-Statistic
$X_t = (GDP_t, INF_t, MS_t)$	9.278
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Null Hypothesis: No Long-run Relationship ▪ Alternative Hypothesis: There is Long-run Relationship ▪ Decision Rules: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ If the F-statistic is below the lower bound, we do not reject the null hypothesis ○ If the F-statistic is higher than the upper bound, we reject the null hypothesis ○ If the F-statistic is between the lower and upper bounds, the result is inconclusive ▪ Decision: The F-statistic of 9.278 is higher than the upper bound of 5.020 at 5% critical level, we thus reject the null hypothesis of no cointegration and accept the alternative hypothesis of long-run cointegration. 	
k=2, n=70	
Nayaran (2005) Critical Value	Lower Bound Upper Bound
1%	5.487 6.880
5%	3.947 5.020
10%	3.250 4.237

Note: Critical values are obtained from Narayan (2005) (Table Case III: Unrestricted Intercept and No Trend)

Table 3: Error Correction and Long-run Causality

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.0439	0.0077	5.6505	0.0000
D(GDP(-1))	0.7794	0.1142	6.8215	0.0000
D(GDP(-2))	0.0077	0.1534	0.0507	0.9597
D(GD(-3))	-0.1831	0.1070	-1.7108	0.0927
D(INF(-1))	-0.0013	0.0168	-0.0778	0.9383
D(INF(-2))	-0.0078	0.0170	-0.4603	0.6471
D(INF(-3))	-0.0087	0.0163	-0.5349	0.5948
D(MS(-1))	-0.1521	0.0691	-2.1991	0.0321
D(MS(-2))	-0.2138	0.0778	-2.7450	0.0082
D(MS(-3))	-0.2114	0.0816	-2.5909	0.0122
ECT (-1)	-0.1132	0.0245	-4.6082	0.0000
R-squared	0.8038	Mean dependent var	0.0414	
Adjusted R-squared	0.7681	S.D. dependent var	0.0610	
S.E. of regression	0.0293	Akaike info criterion	-4.0653	
Sum squared resid	0.0475	Schwarz criterion	-3.7004	
Log likelihood	145.1581	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-3.9211	
F-statistic	22.5370	Durbin-Watson stat	1.9369	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.0000			

Table 4: Granger Causality Tests

Null Hypothesis	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.	Interpretation
INF does not Granger Cause GDP	68	0.6956	0.5025	Inflation does not Granger-Cause GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause INF		0.4390	0.6466	GDP does not Granger-Cause Inflation
MS does not Granger Cause GDP	68	7.8687	0.0009	Money Supply Granger-Causes GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause MS		0.4896	0.6152	GDP does not Granger-Cause MS
MS does not Granger Cause INF	68	3.3808	0.0403	Money Supply Granger-Causes Inflation
INF does not Granger Cause MS		1.9304	0.1536	Inflation does not Granger-Cause MS

Table 5: Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test

Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test			
F-statistic	0.1295	Prob. F (2,51)	0.8788
Obs*R-squared	0.3210	Prob. Chi-Square (2)	0.8517

Figure 1: CUSUM Model Stability Plot

Figure 2: Residual Plot

Part B

Augmented Baseline Model with Monetary Policy Communication (MPS)

Table 1: Lag Length Selection

	Akaike Info Criterion	Akaike Rank	Schwarz Criterion	Schwarz Rank
Lag 4	-3.9139	3	-3.2114	4
Lag 3	-4.0267	1	-3.4627	2
Lag 2	-3.9286	2	-3.5008	1
Lag 1	-3.7227	4	-3.4289	3

Table 2: ARDL/Bounds Testing for the existence of long run cointegration

Model	F-Statistic	
$X_t = (GDP_t, INF_t, MS_t, MPS_t)$	5.609	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Null Hypothesis: No Long-run Relationship ▪ Alternative Hypothesis: There is Long-run Relationship ▪ Decision Rules: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ If the F-statistic is below the lower bound, we do not reject the null hypothesis ○ If the F-statistic is higher than the upper bound, we reject the null hypothesis ○ If the F-statistic is between the lower and upper bounds, the result is inconclusive ▪ Decision: The F-statistic of 5.609 is higher than the upper bound of 4.545 at 5% critical level, we thus reject the null hypothesis of no cointegration and accept the alternative hypothesis of long-run cointegration. 		
k=3, n=70		
Nayaran (2005) Critical Value	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1%	4.635	6.055
5%	3.370	4.545
10%	2.818	3.880

Note: Critical values are obtained from Narayan (2005) (Table Case III: Unrestricted Intercept and No Trend)

Table 3: Error Correction and Long-run Causality

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.0413	0.0083	4.9602	0.0000
D (GDP (-1))	0.7945	0.1213	6.5455	0.0000
D (GDP (-2))	0.0235	0.1648	0.1428	0.8870
D (GDP (-3))	-0.1923	0.1135	-1.6942	0.0962
D (INF (-1))	-0.0004	0.0176	-0.0227	0.9819
D (INF (-2))	-0.0041	0.0179	-0.2308	0.8184
D (INF (-3))	-0.0007	0.0177	-0.0412	0.9673
D (MS (-1))	-0.1520	0.0764	-1.9885	0.0520
D (MS (-2))	-0.1910	0.0864	-2.2090	0.0316
D (MS (-3))	-0.2024	0.0875	-2.3125	0.0247
D (MPS (-1))	-0.0068	0.0054	-1.2526	0.2159
D (MPS (-2))	-0.0093	0.0058	-1.5864	0.1187
D (MPS (-3))	-0.0044	0.0052	-0.8474	0.4006
ECT (-1)	-0.1023	0.0276	-3.7016	0.0005
R-squared	0.8038	Mean dependent var	0.0414	
Adjusted R-squared	0.7548	S.D. dependent var	0.0610	
S.E. of regression	0.0302	Akaike info criterion	-3.9745	
Sum squared resid	0.0474	Schwarz criterion	-3.5101	
Log likelihood	145.1609	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-3.7910	
F-statistic	16.3923	Durbin-Watson stat	1.9752	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.0000			

Table 4: Short-run Granger Causality

Null Hypothesis	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.	Interpretation
INF does not Granger Cause GDP	68	0.6956	0.5025	Inflation does not Granger Cause GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause INF		0.4390	0.6466	GDP does not Granger Cause Inflation
MS does not Granger Cause GDP	68	7.8687	0.0009	MS Granger-Causes GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause MS		0.4896	0.6152	GDP does not Granger Cause MS
MPC does not Granger Cause GDP		3.7942	0.0278	MPC Granger-Causes GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause MPC		0.1365	0.8726	GDP does not Granger Cause MPC
MS does not Granger Cause INF	68	3.3808	0.0403	MS Granger-Causes Inflation
INF does not Granger Cause MS		1.9304	0.1536	Inflation does not Granger Cause MS
MPC does not Granger Cause INF	68	0.8496	0.4324	MPC does not Granger-Cause Inflation
INF does not Granger Cause MPC		0.9976	0.3745	Inflation does not Granger-Cause MPC
MPC does not Granger Cause MS	68	1.0913	0.3420	MPC does not Granger-Cause MS
MS does not Granger Cause MPC		0.1343	0.8745	MS does not Granger Cause MPC

Table 5: Serial Correlation LM Test

Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test			
F-statistic	0.3040	Prob. F(2,51)	0.7392
Obs*R-squared	0.7930	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.6726

Figure 1: Model Stability Plot

Figure 2: Residual Plot

Augmented Baseline Model with Monetary Policy Communication about Inflation (MPCI)

Table 1: Lag Length Selection

	Akaike Info Criterion	Akaike Rank	Schwarz Criterion	Schwarz Rank
Lag 4	-3.8922	2	-3.1897	4
Lag 3	-4.0086	1	-3.4447	2
Lag 2	-3.8873	3	-3.4595	1
Lag 1	-3.6665	4	-3.3729	3

Table 2: ARDL/Bounds Testing for the existence of long run cointegration

Model	F-Statistic
$X_t = (GDP_t, INF_t, MS_t, MPCI_t)$	6.440
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Null Hypothesis: No Long-run Relationship ▪ Alternative Hypothesis: There is Long-run Relationship ▪ Decision Rules: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ If the F-statistic is below the lower bound, we do not reject the null hypothesis ○ If the F-statistic is higher than the upper bound, we reject the null hypothesis ○ If the F-statistic is between the lower and upper bounds, the result is inconclusive ▪ Decision: The F-statistic of 6.440 is higher than the upper bound of 4.545 at 5% critical level, we thus reject the null hypothesis of no cointegration and accept the alternative hypothesis of long-run cointegration. 	
k=3, n=70	
Nayaran (2005) Critical Value	Lower Bound Upper Bound
1%	4.635 6.055
5%	3.370 4.545
10%	2.818 3.880

Note: Critical values are obtained from Narayan (2005) (Table Case III: Unrestricted Intercept and No Trend)

Table 3: Error Correction and Long-run Causality

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.0429	0.0078	5.4521	0.0000
D(GDP(-1))	0.7821	0.1169	6.6861	0.0000
D(GDP(-2))	0.0192	0.1604	0.1197	0.9051
D(GDP(-3))	-0.1860	0.1123	-1.6559	0.1037
D(INF(-1))	-0.0041	0.0178	-0.2339	0.8159
D(INF(-2))	-0.0066	0.0181	-0.3678	0.7145
D(INF(-3))	-0.0158	0.0175	-0.9016	0.3714
D(MS(-1))	-0.1537	0.0714	-2.1530	0.0360
D(MS(-2))	-0.2146	0.0797	-2.6932	0.0095
D(MS(-3))	-0.1979	0.0832	-2.3768	0.0212
D(MPCI(-1))	-0.0120	0.0101	-1.1903	0.2393
D(MPCI(-2))	-0.0124	0.0117	-1.0596	0.2942
D(MPCI(-3))	-0.0145	0.0100	-1.4491	0.1533
ECT(-1)	-0.1138	0.0254	-4.4705	0.0000
R-squared	0.8092	Mean dependent var	0.0414	
Adjusted R-squared	0.7615	S.D. dependent var	0.0610	
S.E. of regression	0.0298	Akaike info criterion	-4.0023	
Sum squared resid	0.0461	Schwarz criterion	-3.5378	
Log likelihood	146.0780	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-3.8188	
F-statistic	16.9669	Durbin-Watson stat	1.9584	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.0000			

Table 4: Short-run Granger Causality

Null Hypothesis	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.	Interpretation
INF does not Granger Cause GDP	68	0.69569	0.5025	No causal relationship between INF and GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause INF		0.43903	0.6466	
MS does not Granger Cause GDP	68	7.86874	0.0009	MS Granger-causes GDP GDP does not Granger-cause MS
GDP does not Granger Cause MS		0.48964	0.6152	
MPCI does not Granger Cause GDP	68	0.72025	0.4906	No causal relationship between MPCPI and GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause MPCPI		0.33697	0.7152	
MS does not Granger Cause INF	68	3.38084	0.0403	MS Granger-causes INF INF does not Granger-cause MS
INF does not Granger Cause MS		1.93049	0.1536	
MPCI does not Granger Cause INF	68	3.38960	0.0400	Bi-directional causality between MPCPI and INF
INF does not Granger Cause MPCPI		2.43972	0.0954	
MPCI does not Granger Cause MS	68	0.68541	0.5076	No causal relationship between MPCPI and MS
MS does not Granger Cause MPCPI		0.01873	0.9815	

Table 5: Serial Correlation LM Test

Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test			
F-statistic	0.1229	Prob. F(2,51)	0.8845
Obs*R-squared	0.3230	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.8508

Figure 1: Model Stability Plot

Figure 2: Residual Plot

Part C
Interest Rate Channel

Nominal Interest Rate without MPS and MPC

Table 1: Lag Length Selection

	Akaike Info Criterion	Akaike Rank	Schwarz Criterion	Schwarz Rank
Lag 4	-4.1217	1	-3.2520	4
Lag 3	-4.1081	2	-3.4114	1
Lag 2	-3.9270	3	-3.4005	2
Lag 1	-3.6189	4	-3.2599	3

Table 2: ARDL/Bounds Testing for the existence of long run cointegration

Model	F-Statistic
$X_t = (GDP_t, INF_t, MS_t, IBR_t, MPR_t)$	5.562
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Null Hypothesis: No Long-run Relationship ▪ Alternative Hypothesis: There is Long-run Relationship ▪ Decision Rules: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ If the F-statistic is below the lower bound, we do not reject the null hypothesis ○ If the F-statistic is higher than the upper bound, we reject the null hypothesis ○ If the F-statistic is between the lower and upper bounds, the result is inconclusive ▪ Decision: The F-statistic of 5.562 is higher than the upper bound of 4.256 at 5% critical level, we thus reject the null hypothesis of no cointegration and accept the alternative hypothesis of long-run cointegration. 	
k=4, n=70	
Nayaran (2005) Critical Value	Lower Bound Upper Bound
1%	4.098 5.570
5%	3.022 4.256
10%	2.552 3.648

Note: Critical values are obtained from Nayaran (2005) (Table Case III: Unrestricted Intercept and No Trend)

Table 3: Error Correction and Long-run Causality

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.0332	0.0116	2.8479	0.0067
D(GDP(-1))	0.8560	0.1508	5.6752	0.0000
D(GDP(-2))	-0.0272	0.1945	-0.1398	0.8894
D(GDP(-3))	-0.2379	0.1865	-1.2753	0.2090
D(GDP(-4))	0.0898	0.1341	0.6695	0.5067
D(INF(-1))	0.0080	0.0205	0.3904	0.6982
D(INF(-2))	-0.0120	0.0195	-0.6150	0.5418
D(INF(-3))	-0.0060	0.0196	-0.3095	0.7584
D(INF(-4))	-0.0061	0.0190	-0.3223	0.7488
D(MS(-1))	-0.1056	0.0926	-1.1396	0.2608
D(MS(-2))	-0.1818	0.0966	-1.8818	0.0666
D(MS(-3))	-0.2091	0.1049	-1.9929	0.0526
D(MS(-4))	0.0600	0.1040	0.5767	0.5671
D(IBR(-1))	-0.0833	0.1372	-0.6071	0.5469
D(IBR(-2))	0.2269	0.1424	1.5930	0.1185
D(IBR(-3))	-0.0158	0.1450	-0.1094	0.9133
D(IBR(-4))	0.0093	0.1405	0.0662	0.9475
D(MPR(-1))	-0.0086	0.0665	-0.1294	0.8976
D(MPR(-2))	-0.0960	0.0675	-1.4212	0.1625

D(MPR(-3))	0.0458	0.0656	0.6986	0.4885
D(MPR(-4))	-0.0356	0.0666	-0.5352	0.5952
ECT(-1)	-0.0838	0.0432	-1.9386	0.0591
R-squared	0.8190	Mean dependent var	0.0410	
Adjusted R-squared	0.7306	S.D. dependent var	0.0614	
S.E. of regression	0.0318	Akaike info criterion	-3.7903	
Sum squared resid	0.0436	Schwarz criterion	-3.0544	
Log likelihood	145.1865	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-3.4999	
F-statistic	9.2681	Durbin-Watson stat	2.0095	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.0000			

Table 4: Short-run Granger Causality

Null Hypothesis	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.	Interpretation
INF does not Granger Cause GDP	68	0.6956	0.5025	Inflation does not Granger Cause GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause INF		0.4390	0.6466	GDP does not Granger Cause Inflation
MS does not Granger Cause GDP	68	7.8687	0.0009	MS Granger-Causes GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause MS		0.4896	0.6152	GDP does not Granger Cause MS
IBR does not Granger Cause GDP	68	0.2062	0.8142	IBR does not Granger Cause GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause IBR		6.9028	0.0019	GDP Granger-Causes IBR
MPR does not Granger Cause GDP	68	3.9726	0.0237	MPR Granger-Causes GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause MPR		1.4325	0.2464	GDP does not Granger Cause MPR
MS does not Granger Cause INF	68	3.3808	0.0403	MS Granger-Causes INF
INF does not Granger Cause MS		1.9304	0.1536	INF does not Granger Cause MS
IBR does not Granger Cause INF	68	0.3528	0.7041	IBR does not Granger Cause INF
INF does not Granger Cause IBR		0.0026	0.9974	INF does not Granger Cause IBR
MPR does not Granger Cause INF	68	0.5659	0.5707	MPR does not Granger Cause INF
INF does not Granger Cause MPR		0.0988	0.9060	INF does not Granger Cause MPR
IBR does not Granger Cause MS	68	1.9112	0.1564	IBR does not Granger Cause MS
MS does not Granger Cause IBR		8.6511	0.0005	MS Granger-Causes IBR
MPR does not Granger Cause MS	68	0.8586	0.4287	MPR does not Granger Cause MS
MS does not Granger Cause MPR		0.6719	0.5144	MS does not Granger Cause MPR
MPR does not Granger Cause IBR	68	2.3258	0.1060	MPR does not Granger Cause IBR
IBR does not Granger Cause MPR		1.8684	0.1628	IBR does not Granger Cause MPR

Table 5: Serial Correlation LM Test

Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test			
F-statistic	1.7058	Prob. F(2,51)	0.1942
Obs*R-squared	4.9933	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.0824

Figure 1: Model Stability Plot

Figure 2: Residual Plot

Nominal Interest Rate with MPS

Table 1: Lag Length Selection

	Akaike Info Criterion	Akaike Rank	Schwarz Criterion	Schwarz Rank
Lag 4	-4.2308	1	-3.1937	3
Lag 3	-4.1396	2	-3.3102	1
Lag 2	-3.8760	3	-3.2508	2
Lag 1	-3.6073	4	-3.1830	4

Table 2: ARDL/Bounds Testing for the existence of long run cointegration

Model	F-Statistic
$X_t = (GDP_t, INF_t, MS_t, IBR_t, MPR_t, MPS_t)$	5.285
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Null Hypothesis: No Long-run Relationship ▪ Alternative Hypothesis: There is Long-run Relationship ▪ Decision Rules: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ If the F-statistic is below the lower bound, we do not reject the null hypothesis ○ If the F-statistic is higher than the upper bound, we reject the null hypothesis ○ If the F-statistic is between the lower and upper bounds, the result is inconclusive ▪ Decision: The F-statistic of 5.285 is higher than the upper bound of 4.073 at 5% critical level, we thus reject the null hypothesis of no cointegration and accept the alternative hypothesis of long-run cointegration. 	
k=5, n=70	
Nayaran (2005) Critical Value	Lower Bound Upper Bound
1%	3.747 5.285
5%	2.788 4.073
10%	2.363 3.510

Note: Critical values are obtained from Nayaran (2005) (Table Case III: Unrestricted Intercept and No Trend)

Table 3: Error Correction and Long-run Causality

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.0408	0.0086	4.7041	0.0000
D(GDP(-1))	0.7465	0.1410	5.2932	0.0000
D(GDP(-2))	0.0491	0.1784	0.2750	0.7845
D(GDP(-3))	-0.1824	0.1212	-1.5039	0.1394
D(INF(-1))	0.0096	0.0184	0.5252	0.6019
D(INF(-2))	-0.0126	0.0188	-0.6686	0.5070
D(INF(-3))	-0.0011	0.0187	-0.0610	0.9516
D(MS(-1))	-0.1170	0.0833	-1.4045	0.1669
D(MS(-2))	-0.1742	0.0911	-1.9121	0.0621
D(MS(-3))	-0.2310	0.0927	-2.4898	0.0165
D(IBR(-1))	-0.1277	0.1282	-0.9962	0.3243
D(IBR(-2))	0.2309	0.1365	1.6913	0.0975
D(IBR(-3))	-0.0673	0.1345	-0.5007	0.6189
D(MPR(-1))	-0.0272	0.0614	-0.4426	0.6601
D(MPR(-2))	-0.1046	0.0670	-1.5623	0.1251
D(MPR(-3))	0.0626	0.0622	1.0060	0.3196
D(MPS(-1))	0.0018	0.0067	0.2772	0.7828
D(MPS(-2))	-0.0045	0.0073	-0.6141	0.5421
D(MPS(-3))	-0.0026	0.0059	-0.4367	0.6644
ECT(-1)	-0.0942	0.0314	-2.9950	0.0044
R-squared	0.823162	Mean dependent var	0.041429	
Adjusted R-squared	0.7501	S.D. dependent var	0.0610	

S.E. of regression	0.0305	Akaike info criterion	-3.8964	
Sum squared resid	0.0428	Schwarz criterion	-3.2328	
Log likelihood	148.5816	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-3.6342	
F-statistic	11.2697	Durbin-Watson stat	1.8589	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.0000			

Table 4: Short-run Granger Causality

Null Hypothesis	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.	Interpretation
INF does not Granger Cause GDP	68	0.6956	0.5025	INF does not Granger Cause GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause INF		0.4390	0.6466	GDP does not Granger Cause INF
MS does not Granger Cause GDP	68	7.8687	0.0009	MS Granger-Causes GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause MS		0.4896	0.6152	GDP does not Granger Cause MS
IBR does not Granger Cause GDP	68	0.2062	0.8142	IBR does not Granger Cause GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause IBR		6.9028	0.0019	GDP Granger-Causes IBR
MPC does not Granger Cause GDP	68	3.7942	0.0278	MPC Granger-Causes GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause MPC		0.1365	0.8726	GDP does not Granger Cause MPC
MS does not Granger Cause INF	68	3.3808	0.0403	MS Granger-Causes INF
INF does not Granger Cause MS		1.9304	0.1536	INF does not Granger Cause MS
IBR does not Granger Cause INF	68	0.3528	0.7041	IBR does not Granger Cause INF
INF does not Granger Cause IBR		0.0026	0.9974	INF does not Granger Cause IBR
MPC does not Granger Cause INF	68	0.8496	0.4324	MPC does not Granger Cause INF
INF does not Granger Cause MPC		0.9976	0.3745	INF does not Granger Cause MPC
IBR does not Granger Cause MS	68	1.9112	0.1564	IBR does not Granger Cause MS
MS does not Granger Cause IBR		8.6511	0.0005	MS Granger-Causes IBR
MPC does not Granger Cause MS	68	1.0913	0.3420	MPC does not Granger Cause MS
MS does not Granger Cause MPC		0.1343	0.8745	MS does not Granger Cause MPC
MPC does not Granger Cause IBR	68	0.5893	0.5577	MPC does not Granger Cause IBR
IBR does not Granger Cause MPC		1.0088	0.3705	IBR does not Granger Cause MPC

Table 5: Serial Correlation LM Test

Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test			
F-statistic	0.9427	Prob. F(2,51)	0.3973
Obs*R-squared	2.7119	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.2577

Figure 1: Model Stability Plot

Figure 2: Residual Plot

Nominal Interest Rate with MPCl

Table 1: Lag Length Selection

	Akaike Info Criterion	Akaike Rank	Schwarz Criterion	Schwarz Rank
Lag 4	-4.1132	1	-3.0762	4
Lag 3	-3.9968	2	-3.1674	2
Lag 2	-3.8465	3	-3.2212	1
Lag 1	-3.5634	4	-3.1391	3

Table 2: ARDL/Bounds Testing for the existence of long run cointegration

Model	F-Statistic
$X_t = (GDP_t, INF_t, MS_t, IBR_t, MPR_t, MPCl_t)$	5.269
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Null Hypothesis: No Long-run Relationship ▪ Alternative Hypothesis: There is Long-run Relationship ▪ Decision Rules: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ If the F-statistic is below the lower bound, we do not reject the null hypothesis ○ If the F-statistic is higher than the upper bound, we reject the null hypothesis ○ If the F-statistic is between the lower and upper bounds, the result is inconclusive ▪ Decision: The F-statistic of 5.269 is higher than the upper bound of 4.073 at 5% critical level, we reject the null hypothesis of no cointegration and accept the alternative hypothesis of long-run cointegration. 	
k=5, n=70	
Nayaran (2005) Critical Value	Lower Bound Upper Bound
1%	3.747 5.285
5%	2.788 4.073
10%	2.363 3.510

Note: Critical values are obtained from Nayaran (2005) (Table Case III: Unrestricted Intercept and No Trend)

Table 3: Error Correction and Long-run Causality

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.0332	0.0120	2.7526	0.0089
D(GDP(-1))	0.8604	0.1577	5.4548	0.0000
D(GDP(-2))	-0.0383	0.2141	-0.1790	0.8588
D(GDP(-3))	-0.2109	0.2122	-0.9937	0.3265
D(GDP(-4))	0.0680	0.1536	0.4432	0.6600
D(INF(-1))	0.0038	0.0226	0.1693	0.8664
D(INF(-2))	-0.0131	0.0227	-0.5775	0.5669
D(INF(-3))	-0.0093	0.0222	-0.4217	0.6756
D(INF(-4))	-0.0088	0.0225	-0.3919	0.6972
D(MS(-1))	-0.1283	0.1029	-1.2469	0.2198
D(MS(-2))	-0.1867	0.1015	-1.8382	0.0736
D(MS(-3))	-0.1975	0.1160	-1.7029	0.0965
D(MS(-4))	0.0741	0.1110	0.6677	0.5082
D(IBR(-1))	-0.0572	0.1485	-0.3852	0.7021
D(IBR(-2))	0.2056	0.1532	1.3422	0.1873
D(IBR(-3))	-0.0158	0.1559	-0.1016	0.9196
D(IBR(-4))	0.0006	0.1523	0.0040	0.9968
D(MPR(-1))	-0.0110	0.0729	-0.1517	0.8802
D(MPR(-2))	-0.0861	0.0756	-1.1382	0.2620
D(MPR(-3))	0.0585	0.0768	0.7627	0.4502
D(MPR(-4))	-0.0626	0.0840	-0.7451	0.4606
D(MPCl(-1))	-0.0060	0.0145	-0.4166	0.6792
D(MPCl(-2))	-0.0099	0.0173	-0.5757	0.5681
D(MPCl(-3))	-0.0151	0.0164	-0.9216	0.3624

D(MPCI(-4))	-0.0070	0.0126	-0.5581	0.5799
ECT(-1)	-0.0842	0.0471	-1.7849	0.0820
R-squared	0.8227	Mean dependent var	0.0410	
Adjusted R-squared	0.7092	S.D. dependent var	0.0614	
S.E. of regression	0.0331	Akaike info criterion	-3.6882	
Sum squared resid	0.0427	Schwarz criterion	-2.8184	
Log likelihood	145.8668	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-3.3450	
F-statistic	7.2433	Durbin-Watson stat	2.0266	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.0000			

Table 4: Short-run Granger Causality

Null Hypothesis	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.	Interpretation
INF does not Granger Cause GDP	68	0.6956	0.5025	INF does not Granger Cause GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause INF		0.4390	0.6466	GDP does not Granger Cause INF
MS does not Granger Cause GDP	68	7.8687	0.0009	MS Granger-Causes GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause MS		0.4896	0.6152	GDP does not Granger Cause MS
IBR does not Granger Cause GDP	68	0.2062	0.8142	IBR does not Granger Cause GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause IBR		6.9028	0.0019	GDP Granger-Causes IBR
MPR does not Granger Cause GDP	68	3.9726	0.0237	MPR Granger-Causes GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause MPR		1.4325	0.2464	GDP does not Granger Cause MPR
MPCI does not Granger Cause GDP	68	0.7202	0.4906	MPCI does not Granger Cause GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause MPCI		0.3369	0.7152	GDP does not Granger Cause MPCI
MS does not Granger Cause INF	68	3.3808	0.0403	MS Granger-Causes INF
INF does not Granger Cause MS		1.9304	0.1536	INF does not Granger Cause MS
IBR does not Granger Cause INF	68	0.3528	0.7041	IBR does not Granger Cause INF
INF does not Granger Cause IBR		0.0026	0.9974	INF does not Granger Cause IBR
MPR does not Granger Cause INF	68	0.5659	0.5707	MPR does not Granger Cause INF
INF does not Granger Cause MPR		0.0988	0.9060	INF does not Granger Cause MPR
MPCI does not Granger Cause INF	68	3.3896	0.0400	MPCI Granger-Causes INF
INF does not Granger Cause MPCI		2.4397	0.0954	INF Granger-Causes MPCI
IBR does not Granger Cause MS	68	1.9112	0.1564	IBR does not Granger Cause MS
MS does not Granger Cause IBR		8.6511	0.0005	MS Granger-Cause IBR
MPR does not Granger Cause MS	68	0.8586	0.4287	MPR does not Granger Cause MS
MS does not Granger Cause MPR		0.6719	0.5144	MS does not Granger Cause MPR
MPCI does not Granger Cause MS	68	0.6854	0.5076	MPCI does not Granger Cause MS
MS does not Granger Cause MPCI		0.0187	0.9815	MS does not Granger Cause MPCI
MPR does not Granger Cause IBR	68	2.3258	0.1060	MPR does not Granger Cause IBR
IBR does not Granger Cause MPR		1.8684	0.1628	IBR does not Granger Cause MPR
MPCI does not Granger Cause IBR	68	0.4478	0.6410	MPCI does not Granger Cause IBR
IBR does not Granger Cause MPCI		0.4361	0.6485	IBR does not Granger Cause MPCI
MPCI does not Granger Cause MPR	68	0.2974	0.7437	MPCI does not Granger Cause MPR
MPR does not Granger Cause MPCI		0.3725	0.6905	MPR does not Granger Cause MPCI

Table 5: Serial Correlation LM Test

Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test			
F-statistic	1.2662	Prob. F(2,51)	0.2938
Obs*R-squared	4.1640	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.1247

Figure 1: Model Stability Plot

Figure 2: Residual Plot

Real Interest Rate without MPS and MPC1

Table 1: Lag Length Selection

	Akaike Info Criterion	Akaike Rank	Schwarz Criterion	Schwarz Rank
Lag 4	-4.4644	1	-3.5067	2
Lag 3	-4.4115	2	-3.6588	1
Lag 2	-4.0093	3	-3.4508	3
Lag 1	-3.6537	4	-3.2795	4

Table 2: ARDL/Bounds Testing for the existence of long run cointegration

Model	F-Statistic
$X_t = (GDP_t, INF_t, MS_t, RIBR_t, MPR_t)$	5.164
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Null Hypothesis: No Long-run Relationship ▪ Alternative Hypothesis: There is Long-run Relationship ▪ Decision Rules: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ If the F-statistic is below the lower bound, we do not reject the null hypothesis ○ If the F-statistic is higher than the upper bound, we reject the null hypothesis ○ If the F-statistic is between the lower and upper bounds, the result is inconclusive ▪ Decision: The F-statistic of 5.1643 is higher than the upper bound of 4.256 at 5% critical level, we thus reject the null hypothesis of no cointegration and accept the alternative hypothesis of long-run cointegration. 	
k=4, n=70	
Nayaran (2005) Critical Value	Lower Bound Upper Bound
1%	4.098 5.570
5%	3.022 4.256
10%	2.552 3.648

Note: Critical values are obtained from Narayan (2005) (Table Case III: Unrestricted Intercept and No Trend)

Table 3: Error Correction and Long-run Causality

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.0304	0.0074	4.1140	0.0002
D(GDP(-1))	0.9046	0.1467	6.1656	0.0000
D(GDP(-2))	-0.1015	0.2000	-0.5075	0.6146
D(GDP(-3))	-0.0620	0.1261	-0.4920	0.6254
D(INF(-1))	-0.0239	0.0276	-0.8645	0.3924
D(INF(-2))	0.1022	0.0374	2.7325	0.0093
D(INF(-3))	-0.0306	0.0308	-0.9957	0.3253
D(MS(-1))	-0.0651	0.0727	-0.8952	0.3760
D(MS(-2))	-0.1333	0.0830	-1.6068	0.1160
D(MS(-3))	-0.2621	0.0808	-3.2400	0.0024
D(RIBR(-1))	-0.0233	0.0216	-1.0804	0.2864
D(RIBR(-2))	0.1733	0.0496	3.4883	0.0012
D(RIBR(-3))	-0.0482	0.0349	-1.3799	0.1753
D(MPR(-1))	-0.0208	0.0509	-0.4085	0.6850
D(MPR(-2))	-0.1111	0.0526	-2.1129	0.0409
D(MPR(-3))	0.0776	0.0515	1.5053	0.1401
ECT(-1)	-0.0926	0.0319	-2.8991	0.0060
R-squared	0.8854	Mean dependent var	0.0398	
Adjusted R-squared	0.8396	S.D. dependent var	0.0654	
S.E. of regression	0.0262	Akaike info criterion	-4.2019	
Sum squared resid	0.0275	Schwarz criterion	-3.5926	
Log likelihood	136.7551	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-3.9651	

F-statistic	19.3286	Durbin-Watson stat	1.6473	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.0000			

Table 4: Short-run Granger Causality

Null Hypothesis	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.	Interpretation
INF does not Granger Cause GDP	68	0.6956	0.5025	INF does not Granger Cause GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause INF		0.4390	0.6466	GDP does not Granger Cause INF
MS does not Granger Cause GDP	68	7.8687	0.0009	MS Granger-Causes GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause MS		0.4896	0.6152	GDP does not Granger Cause MS
RIBR does not Granger Cause GDP	61	2.6255	0.0813	RIBR Granger-Causes GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause RIBR		2.8840	0.0642	GDP Granger-Causes RIBR
MPR does not Granger Cause GDP	68	3.9726	0.0237	MPR Granger-Causes GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause MPR		1.4325	0.2464	GDP does not Granger Cause MPR
MS does not Granger Cause INF	68	3.3808	0.0403	MS Granger-Causes INF
INF does not Granger Cause MS		1.9304	0.1536	INF does not Granger Cause MS
RIBR does not Granger Cause INF	61	0.6284	0.5371	RIBR does not Granger Cause INF
INF does not Granger Cause RIBR		1.4913	0.2339	INF does not Granger Cause RIBR
MPR does not Granger Cause INF	68	0.5659	0.5707	MPR does not Granger Cause INF
INF does not Granger Cause MPR		0.0988	0.9060	INF does not Granger Cause MPR
RIBR does not Granger Cause MS	61	0.5685	0.5696	RIBR does not Granger Cause MS
MS does not Granger Cause RIBR		4.1791	0.0203	MS Granger-Causes RIBR
MPR does not Granger Cause MS	68	0.8586	0.4287	MPR does not Granger Cause MS
MS does not Granger Cause MPR		0.6719	0.5144	MS does not Granger Cause MPR
MPR does not Granger Cause RIBR	61	0.4481	0.6411	MPR does not Granger Cause RIBR
RIBR does not Granger Cause MPR		0.9879	0.3787	RIBR does not Granger Cause MPR

Table 5: Serial Correlation LM Test

Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test			
F-statistic	2.0709	Prob. F(2,51)	0.1401
Obs*R-squared	5.6023	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.0607

Figure 1: Model Stability Plot

Figure 2: Residual Plot

Real Interest Rate with MPS

Table 1: Lag Length Selection

	Akaike Info Criterion	Akaike Rank	Schwarz Criterion	Schwarz Rank
Lag 4	-5.0634	1	-3.9216	1
Lag 3	-4.5976	2	-3.7015	2
Lag 2	-3.9425	3	-3.2792	3
Lag 1	-3.6354	4	-3.1932	4

Table 2: ARDL/Bounds Testing for the existence of long run cointegration

Model	F-Statistic
$X_t = (GDP_t, INF_t, MS_t, RIBR_t, MPR_t, MPS_t)$	7.049
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Null Hypothesis: No Long-run Relationship ▪ Alternative Hypothesis: There is Long-run Relationship ▪ Decision Rules: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ If the F-statistic is below the lower bound, we do not reject the null hypothesis ○ If the F-statistic is higher than the upper bound, we reject the null hypothesis ○ If the F-statistic is between the lower and upper bounds, the result is inconclusive ▪ Decision: The F-statistic of 7.049 is higher than the upper bound of 4.073 at 5% critical level, we thus reject the null hypothesis of no cointegration and accept the alternative hypothesis of long-run cointegration. 	
k=5, n=70	
Nayaran (2005) Critical Value	Lower Bound Upper Bound
1%	3.747 5.285
5%	2.788 4.073
10%	2.363 3.510

Note: Critical values are obtained from Nayaran (2005) (Table Case III: Unrestricted Intercept and No Trend)

Table 3: Error Correction and Long-run Causality

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.0310	0.0081	3.8099	0.0005
D(GDP(-1))	0.8542	0.1694	5.0407	0.0000
D(GDP(-2))	-0.0108	0.2293	-0.0474	0.9624
D(GDP(-3))	-0.1034	0.1370	-0.7550	0.4550
D(INF(-1))	-0.0234	0.0291	-0.8032	0.4270
D(INF(-2))	0.1105	0.0408	2.7086	0.0102
D(INF(-3))	-0.0344	0.0320	-1.0748	0.2894
D(MS(-1))	-0.0789	0.0779	-1.0127	0.3178
D(MS(-2))	-0.1375	0.0905	-1.5185	0.1374
D(MS(-3))	-0.2569	0.0878	-2.9240	0.0059
D(RIBR(-1))	-0.0256	0.0239	-1.0725	0.2904
D(RIBR(-2))	0.1861	0.0556	3.3449	0.0019
D(RIBR(-3))	-0.0572	0.0370	-1.5471	0.1303
D(MPR(-1))	-0.0251	0.0555	-0.4521	0.6538
D(MPR(-2))	-0.1149	0.0592	-1.9397	0.0601
D(MPR(-3))	0.0904	0.0560	1.6135	0.1151
D(MPS(-1))	0.0018	0.0067	0.2773	0.7830
D(MPS(-2))	-0.0036	0.0073	-0.5041	0.6171
D(MPS(-3))	-0.0042	0.0062	-0.6863	0.4968
ECT(-1)	-0.0925	0.0334	-2.7621	0.0089
R-squared	0.8879	Mean dependent var	0.0398	
Adjusted R-squared	0.8303	S.D. dependent var	0.0654	

S.E. of regression	0.0269	Akaike info criterion	-4.1182
Sum squared resid	0.0269	Schwarz criterion	-3.4013
Log likelihood	137.3690	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-3.8396
F-statistic	15.4262	Durbin-Watson stat	1.6468
Prob(F-statistic)	0.0000		

Table 4: Short-run Granger Causality

Null Hypothesis	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.	Interpretation
INF does not Granger Cause GDP	68	0.6956	0.5025	INF does not Granger Cause GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause INF		0.4390	0.6466	GDP does not Granger Cause INF
MS does not Granger Cause GDP	68	7.8687	0.0009	MS Granger-Causes GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause MS		0.4896	0.6152	GDP does not Granger Cause MS
RIBR does not Granger Cause GDP	61	2.6255	0.0813	RIBR Granger-Causes GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause RIBR		2.8840	0.0642	GDP Granger-Causes RIBR
MPR does not Granger Cause GDP	68	3.9726	0.0237	MPR Granger-Causes GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause MPR		1.4325	0.2464	GDP does not Granger Cause MPR
MPC does not Granger Cause GDP	68	3.7942	0.0278	MPC Granger-Causes GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause MPC		0.1365	0.8726	GDP does not Granger Cause MPC
MS does not Granger Cause INF	68	3.3808	0.0403	MS Granger-Causes INF
INF does not Granger Cause MS		1.9304	0.1536	INF does not Granger Cause MS
RIBR does not Granger Cause INF	61	0.6284	0.5371	RIBR does not Granger Cause INF
INF does not Granger Cause RIBR		1.4913	0.2339	INF does not Granger Cause RIBR
MPR does not Granger Cause INF	68	0.5659	0.5707	MPR does not Granger Cause INF
INF does not Granger Cause MPR		0.0988	0.9060	INF does not Granger Cause MPR
MPC does not Granger Cause INF	68	0.8496	0.4324	MPC does not Granger Cause INF
INF does not Granger Cause MPC		0.9976	0.3745	INF does not Granger Cause MPC
RIBR does not Granger Cause MS	61	0.5685	0.5696	RIBR does not Granger Cause MS
MS does not Granger Cause RIBR		4.1791	0.0203	MS Granger-Causes RIBR
MPR does not Granger Cause MS	68	0.8586	0.4287	MPR does not Granger Cause MS
MS does not Granger Cause MPR		0.6719	0.5144	MS does not Granger Cause MPR
MPS does not Granger Cause MS	68	1.0913	0.3420	MPS does not Granger Cause MS
MS does not Granger Cause MPC		0.1343	0.8745	MS does not Granger Cause MPC
MPR does not Granger Cause RIBR	61	0.4481	0.6411	MPR does not Granger Cause RIBR
RIBR does not Granger Cause MPR		0.9879	0.3787	RIBR does not Granger Cause MPR
MPC does not Granger Cause RIBR	61	0.6540	0.5238	MPC does not Granger Cause RIBR
RIBR does not Granger Cause MPC		0.8598	0.4287	RIBR does not Granger Cause MPC
MPC does not Granger Cause MPR	68	0.3531	0.7039	MPC does not Granger Cause MPR
MPR does not Granger Cause MPC		12.6745	0.0000	MPR Granger-Causes MPC

Table 5: Serial Correlation LM Test

Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test			
F-statistic	1.8569	Prob. F(2,51)	0.1712
Obs*R-squared	5.4680	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.0650

Figure 1: Model Stability Plot

Figure 2: Residual Plot

Real Interest Rate with MPCl

Table 1: Lag Length Selection

	Akaike Info Criterion	Akaike Rank	Schwarz Criterion	Schwarz Rank
Lag 4	-4.6797	1	-3.5379	1
Lag 3	-4.2798	2	-3.3837	2
Lag 2	-3.9194	3	-3.2562	3
Lag 1	-3.5967	4	-3.1545	4

Table 2: ARDL/Bounds Testing for the existence of long run cointegration

Model	F-Statistic
$X_t = (GDP_t, INF_t, MS_t, RIBR_t, MPR_t, MPCl_t)$	3.866
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Null Hypothesis: No Long-run Relationship ▪ Alternative Hypothesis: There is Long-run Relationship ▪ Decision Rules: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ If the F-statistic is below the lower bound, we do not reject the null hypothesis ○ If the F-statistic is higher than the upper bound, we reject the null hypothesis ○ If the F-statistic is between the lower and upper bounds, the result is inconclusive ▪ Decision: The F-statistic of 3.866 is higher than the upper bound of 3.510 at 10% critical level, we thus reject the null hypothesis of no cointegration and accept the alternative hypothesis of long-run cointegration. 	
k=5, n=70	
Nayaran (2005) Critical Value	Lower Bound Upper Bound
1%	3.747 5.285
5%	2.788 4.073
10%	2.363 3.510

Note: Critical values are obtained from Narayan (2005) (Table Case III: Unrestricted Intercept and No Trend)

Table 3: Error Correction and Long-run Causality

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.0303	0.0075	3.9972	0.0003
D(GDP(-1))	0.9175	0.1531	5.9927	0.0000
D(GDP(-2))	-0.1155	0.2072	-0.5576	0.5804
D(GDP(-3))	-0.0495	0.1314	-0.3768	0.7084
D(INF(-1))	-0.0253	0.0287	-0.8834	0.3827
D(INF(-2))	0.1039	0.0389	2.6663	0.0113
D(INF(-3))	-0.0362	0.0333	-1.0872	0.2840
D(MS(-1))	-0.0554	0.0757	-0.7308	0.4695
D(MS(-2))	-0.1411	0.0869	-1.6227	0.1131
D(MS(-3))	-0.2678	0.0846	-3.1652	0.0031
D(RIBR(-1))	-0.0221	0.0227	-0.9761	0.3353
D(RIBR(-2))	0.1728	0.0527	3.2757	0.0023
D(RIBR(-3))	-0.0549	0.0386	-1.4193	0.1642
D(MPR(-1))	-0.0367	0.0583	-0.6299	0.5326
D(MPR(-2))	-0.1129	0.0574	-1.9674	0.0567
D(MPR(-3))	0.0905	0.0588	1.5388	0.1324
D(MPCl(-1))	-0.0011	0.0119	-0.0932	0.9262
D(MPCl(-2))	0.0034	0.0130	0.2608	0.7957
D(MPCl(-3))	-0.0014	0.0105	-0.1418	0.8880
ECT(-1)	-0.0949	0.0327	-2.8939	0.0063
R-squared	0.8874	Mean dependent var	0.03982	
Adjusted R-squared	0.8296	S.D. dependent var	0.0654	

S.E. of regression	0.0270	Akaike info criterion	-4.1141
Sum squared resid	0.0270	Schwarz criterion	-3.3972
Log likelihood	137.2532	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-3.8355
F-statistic	15.3557	Durbin-Watson stat	1.6532
Prob(F-statistic)	0.0000		

Table 4: Short-run Granger Causality

Null Hypothesis	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.	Interpretation
INF does not Granger Cause GDP	68	0.6956	0.5025	INF does not Granger Cause GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause INF		0.4390	0.6466	GDP does not Granger Cause INF
MS does not Granger Cause GDP	68	7.8687	0.0009	MS Granger-Causes GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause MS		0.4896	0.6152	GDP does not Granger Cause MS
RIBR does not Granger Cause GDP	61	2.6255	0.0813	RIBR Granger-Causes GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause RIBR		2.8840	0.0642	GDP Granger-Causes RIBR
MPR does not Granger Cause GDP	68	3.9726	0.0237	MPR Granger-Causes GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause MPR		1.4325	0.2464	GDP does not Granger Cause MPR
MPCI does not Granger Cause GDP	68	0.7202	0.4906	MPCI does not Granger Cause GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause MPCI		0.3369	0.7152	GDP does not Granger Cause MPCI
MS does not Granger Cause INF	68	3.3808	0.0403	MS Granger-Causes INF
INF does not Granger Cause MS		1.9304	0.1536	INF does not Granger Cause MS
RIBR does not Granger Cause INF	61	0.6284	0.5371	RIBR does not Granger Cause INF
INF does not Granger Cause RIBR		1.4913	0.2339	INF does not Granger Cause RIBR
MPR does not Granger Cause INF	68	0.5659	0.5707	MPR does not Granger Cause INF
INF does not Granger Cause MPR		0.0988	0.9060	INF does not Granger Cause MPR
MPCI does not Granger Cause INF	68	3.3896	0.0400	MPCI Granger-Causes INF
INF does not Granger Cause MPCI		2.4397	0.0954	INF Granger-Causes MPCI
RIBR does not Granger Cause MS	61	0.5685	0.5696	RIBR does not Granger Cause MS
MS does not Granger Cause RIBR		4.1791	0.0203	MS Granger-Causes RIBR
MPR does not Granger Cause MS	68	0.8586	0.4287	MPR does not Granger Cause MS
MS does not Granger Cause MPR		0.6719	0.5144	MS does not Granger Cause MPR
MPCI does not Granger Cause MS	68	0.6854	0.5076	MPCI does not Granger Cause MS
MS does not Granger Cause MPCI		0.0187	0.9815	MS does not Granger Cause MPCI
MPR does not Granger Cause RIBR	61	0.4481	0.6411	MPR does not Granger Cause RIBR
RIBR does not Granger Cause MPR		0.9879	0.3787	RIBR does not Granger Cause MPR
MPCI does not Granger Cause RIBR	61	3.1110	0.0523	MPCI Granger-Causes RIBR
RIBR does not Granger Cause MPCI		1.9464	0.1523	RIBR does not Granger Cause MPCI
MPCI does not Granger Cause MPR	68	0.2974	0.7437	MPCI does not Granger Cause MPR
MPR does not Granger Cause MPCI		0.3725	0.6905	MPR does not Granger Cause MPCI

Table 5: Serial Correlation LM Test

Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test			
F-statistic	1.8625	Prob. F(2,51)	0.1703
Obs*R-squared	5.4829	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.0645

Figure 1: Model Stability Plot

Figure 2: Residual Plot

Part D

Credit Channel without MPS and MPC1

Table 1: Lag Selection

	Akaike Info Criterion	Akaike Rank	Schwarz Criterion	Schwarz Rank
Lag 4	-4.0506	2	-3.3481	4
Lag 3	-4.1386	1	-3.5746	1
Lag 2	-3.9454	3	-3.5177	2
Lag 1	-3.6769	4	-3.3832	3

Table 2: ARDL/Bounds Testing for the existence of long run cointegration

Model	F-Statistic	
$X_t = (GDP_t, INF_t, MS_t, CRD_t)$	9.4	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Null Hypothesis: No Long-run Relationship ▪ Alternative Hypothesis: There is Long-run Relationship ▪ Decision Rules: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ If the F-statistic is below the lower bound, we do not reject the null hypothesis ○ If the F-statistic is higher than the upper bound, we reject the null hypothesis ○ If the F-statistic is between the lower and upper bounds, the result is inconclusive ▪ Decision: The F-statistic of 9.409 is higher than the upper bound of 4.545 at 5% critical level, we thus reject the null hypothesis of no cointegration and accept the alternative hypothesis of long-run cointegration. 		
k=3, n=70		
Nayaran (2005) Critical Value	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1%	4.635	6.055
5%	3.370	4.545
10%	2.818	3.880

Note: Critical values are obtained from Narayan (2005) (Table Case III: Unrestricted Intercept and No Trend)

Table 3: Error Correction and Long-run Causality

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.0431	0.0082	5.2551	0.0000
D(GDP(-1))	0.7645	0.1165	6.5608	0.0000
D(GDP(-2))	0.0143	0.1548	0.0923	0.9267
D(GDP(-3))	-0.1608	0.1103	-1.4578	0.1509
D(INF(-1))	-0.0002	0.0170	-0.0166	0.9868
D(INF(-2))	-0.0102	0.0173	-0.5869	0.5598
D(INF(-3))	-0.0062	0.0170	-0.3665	0.7154
D(MS(-1))	-0.1553	0.0759	-2.0458	0.0458
D(MS(-2))	-0.2085	0.0817	-2.5505	0.0137
D(MS(-3))	-0.2163	0.0830	-2.6046	0.0120
D(CRDP(-1))	0.0842	0.0852	0.9882	0.3276
D(CRDP(-2))	0.0041	0.0969	0.0432	0.9656
D(CRDP(-3))	-0.0801	0.0893	-0.8962	0.3743
ECT(-1)	-0.1185	0.0250	-4.7391	0.0000
R-squared	0.8123	Mean dependent var	0.0414	
Adjusted R-squared	0.7653	S.D. dependent var	0.0610	
S.E. of regression	0.0295	Akaike info criterion	-4.0187	
Sum squared resid	0.0454	Schwarz criterion	-3.5542	
Log likelihood	146.6172	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-3.8351	
F-statistic	17.3123	Durbin-Watson stat	1.9034	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Table 4: Granger Causality Tests

Null Hypothesis	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.	Interpretation
INF does not Granger Cause GDP	68	0.6956	0.5025	INF does not Granger Cause GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause INF		0.4390	0.6466	GDP does not Granger Cause INF
MS does not Granger Cause GDP	68	7.8687	0.0009	MS Granger-Causes GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause MS		0.4896	0.6152	GDP does not Granger Cause MS
CRD does not Granger Cause GDP	68	6.1485	0.0036	CRD Granger-Causes GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause CRD		0.4855	0.6176	GDP does not Granger Cause CRD
MS does not Granger Cause INF	68	3.3808	0.0403	MS Granger-Causes INF
INF does not Granger Cause MS		1.9304	0.1536	INF does not Granger Cause MS
CRD does not Granger Cause INF	68	0.0135	0.9866	CRD does not Granger Cause INF
INF does not Granger Cause CRD		5.9266	0.0044	INF Granger-Causes CRD
CRD does not Granger Cause MS	68	5.9458	0.0043	CRD Granger-Causes MS
MS does not Granger Cause CRD		0.0721	0.9304	MS does not Granger Cause CRD

Table 5: Serial Correlation LM Test

Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test			
F-statistic	0.3717	Prob. F(2,51)	0.6914
Obs*R-squared	0.9669	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.6166

Figure 1: Model Stability Plot

Figure 2: Residual Plot

Credit Channel with MPS

Table 1: Lag Selection

	Akaike Info Criterion	Akaike Rank	Schwarz Criterion	Schwarz Rank
Lag 4	-4.0800	2	-3.2102	4
Lag 3	-4.0854	1	-3.3887	2
Lag 2	-3.9443	3	-3.4178	1
Lag 1	-3.7109	4	-3.3518	3

Table 2: ARDL/Bounds Testing for the existence of long run cointegration

Model	F-Statistic	
$X_t = (GDP_t, INF_t, MS_t, CRD_t, MPS_t)$	6.508	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Null Hypothesis: No Long-run Relationship ▪ Alternative Hypothesis: There is Long-run Relationship ▪ Decision Rules: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ If the F-statistic is below the lower bound, we do not reject the null hypothesis ○ If the F-statistic is higher than the upper bound, we reject the null hypothesis ○ If the F-statistic is between the lower and upper bounds, the result is inconclusive ▪ Decision: The F-statistic of 6.5080 is higher than the upper bound of 4.256 at 5% critical level, we thus reject the null hypothesis of no cointegration and accept the alternative hypothesis of long-run cointegration. 		
k=4, n=70		
Nayaran (2005) Critical Value	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1%	4.098	5.570
5%	3.022	4.256
10%	2.552	3.648

Note: Critical values are obtained from Narayan (2005) (Table Case III: Unrestricted Intercept and No Trend)

Table 3: Error Correction and Long-run Causality

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.0407	0.0088	4.6029	0.0000
D(GDP(-1))	0.7839	0.1240	6.3202	0.0000
D(GDP(-2))	0.0256	0.1666	0.1536	0.8785
D(GDP(-3))	-0.1675	0.1169	-1.4321	0.1584
D(INF(-1))	0.0013	0.0180	0.0741	0.9412
D(INF(-2))	-0.0061	0.0184	-0.3347	0.7392
D(INF(-3))	0.0008	0.0184	0.0440	0.9651
D(MS(-1))	-0.1591	0.0838	-1.8986	0.0635
D(MS(-2))	-0.1908	0.0894	-2.1328	0.0380
D(MS(-3))	-0.2150	0.0899	-2.3905	0.0207
D(CRDP(-1))	0.0843	0.0916	0.9203	0.3619
D(CRDP(-2))	0.0085	0.1037	0.0821	0.9348
D(CRDP(-3))	-0.0747	0.0959	-0.7792	0.4396
D(MPS(-1))	-0.0068	0.0055	-1.2283	0.2252
D(MPS(-2))	-0.0084	0.0060	-1.3938	0.1697
D(MPS(-3))	-0.0029	0.0055	-0.5357	0.5946
ECT(-1)	-0.1092	0.0287	-3.8047	0.0004
R-squared	0.8111	Mean dependent var	0.0414	
Adjusted R-squared	0.7494	S.D. dependent var	0.0610	
S.E. of regression	0.0305	Akaike info criterion	-3.9213	
Sum squared resid	0.0457	Schwarz criterion	-3.3573	

Log likelihood	146.4054	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-3.6985
F-statistic	13.1504	Durbin-Watson stat	1.9421
Prob(F-statistic)	0.0000		

Table 4: Granger Causality Tests

Null Hypothesis	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.	Interpretation
INF does not Granger Cause GDP	68	0.6956	0.5025	INF does not Granger Cause GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause INF		0.4390	0.6466	GDP does not Granger Cause INF
MS does not Granger Cause GDP	68	7.8687	0.0009	MS Granger-Causes GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause MS		0.4896	0.6152	GDP does not Granger Cause MS
CRD does not Granger Cause GDP	68	6.1485	0.0036	CRD Granger-Causes GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause CRD		0.4855	0.6176	GDP does not Granger Cause CRD
MPC does not Granger Cause GDP	68	3.7942	0.0278	MPC Granger-Causes GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause MPC		0.1365	0.8726	GDP does not Granger Cause MPC
MS does not Granger Cause INF	68	3.3808	0.0403	MS Granger-Causes INF
INF does not Granger Cause MS		1.9304	0.1536	INF does not Granger Cause MS
CRD does not Granger Cause INF	68	0.0135	0.9866	CRD does not Granger Cause INF
INF does not Granger Cause CRD		5.9266	0.0044	INF Granger-Causes CRD
MPC does not Granger Cause INF	68	0.8496	0.4324	MPC does not Granger Cause INF
INF does not Granger Cause MPC		0.9976	0.3745	INF does not Granger Cause MPC
CRD does not Granger Cause MS	68	5.9458	0.0043	CRD Granger-Causes MS
MS does not Granger Cause CRD		0.0721	0.9304	MS does not Granger Cause CRD
MPC does not Granger Cause MS	68	1.0913	0.3420	MPC does not Granger Cause MS
MS does not Granger Cause MPC		0.1343	0.8745	MS does not Granger Cause MPC
MPC does not Granger Cause CRD	68	0.3277	0.7218	MPC does not Granger Cause CRD
CRD does not Granger Cause MPC		1.9426	0.1518	CRD does not Granger Cause MPC

Table 5: Serial Correlation LM Test

Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test			
F-statistic	0.7187	Prob. F(2,51)	0.4926
Obs*R-squared	1.9588	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.3755

Figure 1: Model Stability Plot

Figure 2: Residual Plot

Credit Channel with MPC1

Table 1: Lag Selection

	Akaike Info Criterion	Akaike Rank	Schwarz Criterion	Schwarz Rank
Lag 4	-3.9517	2	-3.0819	4
Lag 3	-4.0440	1	-3.3473	2
Lag 2	-3.8736	3	-3.3471	1
Lag 1	-3.6344	4	-3.2753	3

Table 2: ARDL/Bounds Testing for the existence of long run cointegration

Model	F-Statistic	
$X_t = (GDP_t, INF_t, MS_t, CRD_t, MPC1_t)$	6.908	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Null Hypothesis: No Long-run Relationship ▪ Alternative Hypothesis: There is Long-run Relationship ▪ Decision Rules: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ If the F-statistic is below the lower bound, we do not reject the null hypothesis ○ If the F-statistic is higher than the upper bound, we reject the null hypothesis ○ If the F-statistic is between the lower and upper bounds, the result is inconclusive ▪ Decision: The F-statistic of 6.908 is higher than the upper bound of 4.256 at 5% critical level, we thus reject the null hypothesis of no cointegration and accept the alternative hypothesis of long-run cointegration. 		
k=4, n=70		
Nayaran (2005) Critical Value	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1%	4.098	5.570
5%	3.022	4.256
10%	2.552	3.648

Note: Critical values are obtained from Nayaran (2005) (Table Case III: Unrestricted Intercept and No Trend)

Table 3: Error Correction and Long-run Causality

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.0422	0.0083	5.0650	0.0000
D(GDP(-1))	0.7721	0.1193	6.4713	0.0000
D(GDP(-2))	0.0252	0.1626	0.1554	0.8771
D(GDP(-3))	-0.1684	0.1167	-1.4432	0.1553
D(INF(-1))	-0.0022	0.0182	-0.1224	0.9031
D(INF(-2))	-0.0097	0.0186	-0.5231	0.6032
D(INF(-3))	-0.0122	0.0184	-0.6647	0.5093
D(MS(-1))	-0.1544	0.0795	-1.9407	0.0581
D(MS(-2))	-0.2038	0.0847	-2.4058	0.0200
D(MS(-3))	-0.2011	0.0853	-2.3574	0.0224
D(CRDP(-1))	0.0714	0.0880	0.8111	0.4212
D(CRDP(-2))	0.0098	0.1028	0.0960	0.9239
D(CRDP(-3))	-0.0848	0.0952	-0.8910	0.3773
D(MPCI(-1))	-0.0130	0.0105	-1.2393	0.2211
D(MPCI(-2))	-0.0144	0.0122	-1.1772	0.2448
D(MPCI(-3))	-0.0135	0.0102	-1.3166	0.1941
ECT(-1)	-0.1182	0.0260	-4.5467	0.0000
R-squared	0.816003	Mean dependent var	0.0414	
Adjusted R-squared	0.755923	S.D. dependent var	0.0610	
S.E. of regression	0.030155	Akaike info criterion	-3.9476	
Sum squared resid	0.044556	Schwarz criterion	-3.3836	
Log likelihood	147.2720	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-3.7247	
F-statistic	13.5818	Durbin-Watson stat	1.9323	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.0000			

Table 4: Short-run Granger Causality

Null Hypothesis	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.	Interpretation
INF does not Granger Cause GDP	68	0.6956	0.5025	INF does not Granger Cause GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause INF		0.4390	0.6466	GDP does not Granger Cause INF
MS does not Granger Cause GDP	68	7.8687	0.0009	MS Granger-Causes GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause MS		0.4896	0.6152	GDP does not Granger Cause MS
CRDP does not Granger Cause GDP	68	6.1485	0.0036	CRD Granger-Causes GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause CRDP		0.4855	0.6176	GDP does not Granger Cause CRD
MPCI does not Granger Cause GDP	68	0.7202	0.4906	MPCI does not Granger Cause GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause MPCI		0.3369	0.7152	GDP does not Granger Cause MPCI
MS does not Granger Cause INF	68	3.3808	0.0403	MS Granger-Causes INF
INF does not Granger Cause MS		1.9304	0.1536	INF does not Granger Cause MS
CRDP does not Granger Cause INF	68	0.0135	0.9866	CRDP does not Granger Cause INF
INF does not Granger Cause CRD		5.9266	0.0044	INF Granger-Causes CRD
MPCI does not Granger Cause INF	68	3.3896	0.0400	MPCI Granger-Causes INF
INF does not Granger Cause MPCI		2.4397	0.0954	INF Granger-Causes MPCI
CRD does not Granger Cause MS	68	5.9458	0.0043	CRD Granger-Causes MS
MS does not Granger Cause CRD		0.0721	0.9304	MS does not Granger Cause CRDP
MPCI does not Granger Cause MS	68	0.6854	0.5076	MPCI does not Granger Cause MS
MS does not Granger Cause MPCI		0.0187	0.9815	MS does not Granger Cause MPCI
MPCI does not Granger Cause CRD	68	0.5629	0.5724	MPCI does not Granger Cause CRD
CRD does not Granger Cause MPCI		0.1086	0.8972	CRD does not Granger Cause MPCI

Table 5: Serial Correlation LM Test

Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test			
F-statistic	0.2561	Prob. F(2,51)	0.7751
Obs*R-squared	0.7117	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.7006

Figure 1: Model Stability Plot

Figure 2: Residual Plot

Part E

Official Exchange Rate without MPS and MPC

Table 1: Lag Selection

	Akaike Info Criterion	Akaike Rank	Schwarz Criterion	Schwarz Rank
Lag 4	-4.0654	2	-3.3629	4
Lag 3	-4.0956	1	-3.5316	1
Lag 2	-3.9341	3	-3.5063	2
Lag 1	-3.6720	4	-3.3782	3

Table 2: ARDL/Bounds Testing for the existence of long run cointegration

Model	F-Statistic
$X_t = (GDP_t, INF_t, MS_t, EXC_t)$	7.722
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Null Hypothesis: No Long-run Relationship ▪ Alternative Hypothesis: There is Long-run Relationship ▪ Decision Rules: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ If the F-statistic is below the lower bound, we do not reject the null hypothesis ○ If the F-statistic is higher than the upper bound, we reject the null hypothesis ○ If the F-statistic is between the lower and upper bounds, the result is inconclusive ▪ Decision: The F-statistic of 7.722 is higher than the upper bound of 4.545 at 5% critical level, we reject the null hypothesis of no cointegration and accept the alternative hypothesis of long-run cointegration. 	
k=3, n=70	
Nayaran (2005) Critical Value	Lower Bound Upper Bound
1%	4.635 6.055
5%	3.370 4.545
10%	2.818 3.880

Note: Critical values are obtained from Narayan (2005) (Table Case III: Unrestricted Intercept and No Trend)

Table 3: Error Correction and Long-run Causality

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.0409	0.0085	4.7685	0.0000
D(GDP(-1))	0.7537	0.1191	6.3257	0.0000
D(GDP(-2))	0.0493	0.1570	0.3139	0.7548
D(GDP(-3))	-0.1788	0.1089	-1.6412	0.1068
D(INF(-1))	0.0007	0.0174	0.0434	0.9655
D(INF(-2))	-0.0101	0.0176	-0.5748	0.5678
D(INF(-3))	-0.0118	0.0168	-0.7059	0.4834
D(MS(-1))	-0.1495	0.0704	-2.1228	0.0385
D(MS(-2))	-0.2127	0.0791	-2.6877	0.0096
D(MS(-3))	-0.2054	0.0834	-2.4619	0.0172
D(EXC(-1))	-0.0351	0.0744	-0.4725	0.6385
D(EXC(-2))	0.0992	0.0745	1.3320	0.1886
D(EXC(-3))	0.0464	0.0749	0.6201	0.5378
ECT(-1)	-0.1121	0.0254	-4.4118	0.0001
R-squared	0.8117	Mean dependent var	0.0414	
Adjusted R-squared	0.7646	S.D. dependent var	0.0610	
S.E. of regression	0.0296	Akaike info criterion	-4.0156	
Sum squared resid	0.0455	Schwarz criterion	-3.5512	
Log likelihood	146.5172	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-3.8321	
F-statistic	17.2479	Durbin-Watson stat	1.9256	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.0000			

Table 4: Short-run Granger Causality

Null Hypothesis	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.	Interpretation
INF does not Granger Cause GDP	68	0.6956	0.5025	INF does not Granger Cause GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause INF		0.4390	0.6466	GDP does not Granger Cause INF
MS does not Granger Cause GDP	68	7.8687	0.0009	MS Granger-Causes GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause MS		0.4896	0.6152	GDP does not Granger Cause MS
EXC does not Granger Cause GDP	68	0.6014	0.5511	EXC does not Granger Cause GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause EXC		1.2107	0.3048	GDP does not Granger Cause EXC
MS does not Granger Cause INF	68	3.3808	0.0403	MS Granger-Causes INF
INF does not Granger Cause MS		1.9304	0.1536	INF does not Granger Cause MS
EXC does not Granger Cause INF	68	0.4087	0.6662	EXC does not Granger Cause INF
INF does not Granger Cause EXC		0.5977	0.5531	INF does not Granger Cause EXC
EXC does not Granger Cause MS	68	0.0418	0.9590	EXC does not Granger Cause MS
MS does not Granger Cause EXC		1.1283	0.3300	MS does not Granger Cause EXC

Table 5: Serial Correlation LM Test

Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test			
F-statistic	0.0374	Prob. F(2,51)	0.9632
Obs*R-squared	0.0987	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.9518

Figure 1: Model Stability Plot

Figure 2: Residual Plot

Official Exchange Rate with MPS

Table 1: Lag Selection

	Akaike Info Criterion	Akaike Rank	Schwarz Criterion	Schwarz Rank
Lag 4	-4.1420	1	-3.2723	4
Lag 3	-4.0968	2	-3.4001	1
Lag 2	-3.9078	3	-3.3813	2
Lag 1	-3.6660	4	-3.3070	3

Table 2: ARDL/Bounds Testing for the existence of long run cointegration

Model	F-Statistic
$X_t = (GDP_t, INF_t, MS_t, EXC_t, MPS_t)$	6.179
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Null Hypothesis: No Long-run Relationship ▪ Alternative Hypothesis: There is Long-run Relationship ▪ Decision Rules: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ If the F-statistic is below the lower bound, we do not reject the null hypothesis ○ If the F-statistic is higher than the upper bound, we reject the null hypothesis ○ If the F-statistic is between the lower and upper bounds, the result is inconclusive ▪ Decision: The F-statistic of 6.179 is higher than the upper bound of 4.256 at 5% critical level, we thus reject the null hypothesis of no cointegration and accept the alternative hypothesis of long-run cointegration. 	
k=4, n=70	
Nayaran (2005) Critical Value	Lower Bound Upper Bound
1%	4.098 5.570
5%	3.022 4.256
10%	2.552 3.648

Note: Critical values are obtained from Narayan (2005) (Table Case III: Unrestricted Intercept and No Trend)

Table 3: Error Correction and Long-run Causality

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.0324	0.0128	2.5325	0.0151
D(GDP(-1))	0.7834	0.1426	5.4934	0.0000
D(GDP(-2))	0.0501	0.1781	0.2816	0.7796
D(GDP(-3))	-0.2355	0.1747	-1.3483	0.1846
D(GDP(-4))	0.0645	0.1232	0.5235	0.6033
D(INF(-1))	0.0035	0.0196	0.1779	0.8596
D(INF(-2))	-0.0051	0.0200	-0.2569	0.7984
D(INF(-3))	-0.0049	0.0203	-0.2446	0.8079
D(INF(-4))	-0.0100	0.0194	-0.5174	0.6075
D(MS(-1))	-0.1117	0.0912	-1.2250	0.2272
D(MS(-2))	-0.1782	0.0916	-1.9456	0.0583
D(MS(-3))	-0.2247	0.0996	-2.2565	0.0292
D(MS(-4))	0.0671	0.1036	0.6475	0.5207
D(EXC(-1))	-0.0504	0.0845	-0.5968	0.5538
D(EXC(-2))	0.1197	0.0833	1.4374	0.1578
D(EXC(-3))	0.0390	0.0834	0.4684	0.6418
D(EXC(-4))	0.0331	0.0833	0.3973	0.6931
D(MPS(-1))	-0.0090	0.0063	-1.4359	0.1583
D(MPS(-2))	-0.0108	0.0067	-1.6253	0.1114
D(MPS(-3))	-0.0049	0.0067	-0.7353	0.4661
D(MPS(-4))	-0.0080	0.0060	-1.339205	0.1875
ECT(-1)	-0.0926	0.0366	-2.5306	0.0151

R-squared	0.8244	Mean dependent var	0.0410	
Adjusted R-squared	0.7386	S.D. dependent var	0.0614	
S.E. of regression	0.0313	Akaike info criterion	-3.8204	
Sum squared resid	0.0423	Schwarz criterion	-3.0845	
Log likelihood	146.1661	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-3.5301	
F-statistic	9.6144	Durbin-Watson stat	2.0183	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.0000			

Table 4: Short-run Granger Causality

Null Hypothesis	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.	Interpretation
INF does not Granger Cause GDP	68	0.6956	0.5025	INF does not Granger Cause GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause INF		0.4390	0.6466	GDP does not Granger Cause INF
MS does not Granger Cause GDP	68	7.8687	0.0009	MS Granger-Causes GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause MS		0.4896	0.6152	GDP does not Granger Cause MS
EXC does not Granger Cause GDP	68	0.6014	0.5511	EXC does not Granger Cause GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause EXC		1.2107	0.3048	GDP does not Granger Cause EXC
MPC does not Granger Cause GDP	68	3.7942	0.0278	MPC Granger-Causes GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause MPC		0.1365	0.8726	GDP does not Granger Cause MPC
MS does not Granger Cause INF	68	3.3808	0.0403	MS Granger-Causes INF
INF does not Granger Cause MS		1.9304	0.1536	INF does not Granger Cause MS
EXC does not Granger Cause INF	68	0.4087	0.6662	EXC does not Granger Cause INF
INF does not Granger Cause EXC		0.5977	0.5531	INF does not Granger Cause EXC
MPC does not Granger Cause INF	68	0.8496	0.4324	MPC does not Granger Cause INF
INF does not Granger Cause MPC		0.9976	0.3745	INF does not Granger Cause MPC
EXC does not Granger Cause MS	68	0.0418	0.9590	EXC does not Granger Cause MS
MS does not Granger Cause EXC		1.1283	0.3300	MS does not Granger Cause EXC
MPC does not Granger Cause MS	68	1.0913	0.3420	MPC does not Granger Cause MS
MS does not Granger Cause MPC		0.1343	0.8745	MS does not Granger Cause MPC
MPC does not Granger Cause EXC	68	0.8670	0.4252	MPC does not Granger Cause EXC
EXC does not Granger Cause MPC		0.4634	0.6312	EXC does not Granger Cause MPC

Table 5: Serial Correlation LM Test

Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test			
F-statistic	0.2115	Prob. F(2,51)	0.8102
Obs*R-squared	0.6637	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.7176

Figure 1: Model Stability Plot

Figure 2: Residual Plot

Official Exchange Rate with MPCl

Table 1: Lag Selection

	Akaike Info Criterion	Akaike Rank	Schwarz Criterion	Schwarz Rank
Lag 4	-3.9796	2	-3.1099	4
Lag 3	-4.0371	1	-3.3404	2
Lag 2	-3.8695	3	-3.3430	1
Lag 1	-3.6180	4	-3.2590	3

Table 2: ARDL/Bounds Testing for the existence of long run cointegration

Model	F-Statistic	
$X_t = (GDP_t, INF_t, MS_t, EXC_t, MPCl_t)$	5.926	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Null Hypothesis: No Long-run Relationship ▪ Alternative Hypothesis: There is Long-run Relationship ▪ Decision Rules: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ If the F-statistic is below the lower bound, we do not reject the null hypothesis ○ If the F-statistic is higher than the upper bound, we reject the null hypothesis ○ If the F-statistic is between the lower and upper bounds, the result is inconclusive ▪ Decision: The F-statistic of 5.926 is higher than the upper bound of 4.256 at 5% critical level, we thus reject the null hypothesis of no cointegration and accept the alternative hypothesis of long-run cointegration. 		
k=4, n=70		
Nayaran (2005) Critical Value	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1%	4.098	5.570
5%	3.022	4.256
10%	2.552	3.648

Note: Critical values are obtained from Nayaran (2005) (Table Case III: Unrestricted Intercept and No Trend)

Table 3: Error Correction and Long-run Causality

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.0395	0.0087	4.5338	0.0000
D(GDP(-1))	0.7607	0.1211	6.2787	0.0000
D(GDP(-2))	0.0540	0.1625	0.3325	0.7409
D(GDP(-3))	-0.1722	0.1142	-1.5076	0.1381
D(INF(-1))	-0.0004	0.0183	-0.0226	0.9820
D(INF(-2))	-0.0093	0.0188	-0.4973	0.6212
D(INF(-3))	-0.0192	0.0180	-1.0633	0.2928
D(MS(-1))	-0.1567	0.0727	-2.1553	0.0361
D(MS(-2))	-0.2128	0.0812	-2.6191	0.0117
D(MS(-3))	-0.1867	0.0850	-2.1958	0.0329
D(EXC(-1))	-0.0440	0.0766	-0.5741	0.5685
D(EXC(-2))	0.1129	0.0774	1.4580	0.1512
D(EXC(-3))	0.0467	0.0782	0.5982	0.5524
D(MPCl(-1))	-0.0103	0.0104	-0.9845	0.3297
D(MPCl(-2))	-0.0137	0.0122	-1.1300	0.2640
D(MPCl(-3))	-0.0176	0.0102	-1.7196	0.0918
ECT(-1)	-0.1122	0.0266	-4.2179	0.0001
R-squared	0.8186	Mean dependent var	0.0414	
Adjusted R-squared	0.7594	S.D. dependent var	0.0610	
S.E. of regression	0.0299	Akaike info criterion	-3.9622	
Sum squared resid	0.0439	Schwarz criterion	-3.3982	
Log likelihood	147.7530	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-3.7393	
F-statistic	13.82618	Durbin-Watson stat	1.946499	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Table 4: Short-run Granger Causality

Null Hypothesis	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.	Interpretation
INF does not Granger Cause GDP	68	0.6956	0.5025	INF does not Granger Cause GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause INF		0.4390	0.6466	GDP does not Granger Cause INF
MS does not Granger Cause GDP	68	7.8687	0.0009	MS Granger-Causes GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause MS		0.4896	0.6152	GDP does not Granger Cause MS
EXC does not Granger Cause GDP	68	0.6014	0.5511	EXC does not Granger Cause GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause EXC		1.2107	0.3048	GDP does not Granger Cause EXC
MPCI does not Granger Cause GDP	68	0.7202	0.4906	MPCI does not Granger Cause GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause MPCI		0.3369	0.7152	GDP does not Granger Cause MPCI
MS does not Granger Cause INF	68	3.3808	0.0403	MS Granger-Causes INF
INF does not Granger Cause MS		1.9304	0.1536	INF does not Granger Cause MS
EXC does not Granger Cause INF	68	0.4087	0.6662	EXC does not Granger Cause INF
INF does not Granger Cause EXC		0.5977	0.5531	INF does not Granger Cause EXC
MPCI does not Granger Cause INF	68	3.3896	0.0400	MPCI Granger-Causes INF
INF does not Granger Cause MPCI		2.4397	0.0954	INF Granger-Causes MPCI
EXC does not Granger Cause MS	68	0.0418	0.9590	EXC does not Granger Cause MS
MS does not Granger Cause EXC		1.1283	0.3300	MS does not Granger Cause EXC
MPCI does not Granger Cause MS	68	0.6854	0.5076	MPCI does not Granger Cause MS
MS does not Granger Cause MPCI		0.0187	0.9815	MS does not Granger Cause MPCI
MPCI does not Granger Cause EXC	68	0.1323	0.8762	MPCI does not Granger Cause EXC
EXC does not Granger Cause MPCI		0.6344	0.5336	EXC does not Granger Cause MPCI

Table 5: Serial Correlation LM Test

Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test			
F-statistic	0.0014	Prob. F(2,51)	0.9986
Obs*R-squared	0.0040	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.9980

Figure 1: Model Stability Plot

Figure 2: Residual Plot

BDC Exchange Rate without MPS and MPC I

Table 1: Lag Selection

	Akaike Info Criterion	Akaike Rank	Schwarz Criterion	Schwarz Rank
Lag 4	-4.1466	1	-3.4441	3
Lag 3	-4.1180	2	-3.5540	1
Lag 2	-3.9531	3	-3.5253	2
Lag 1	-3.7371	4	-3.4433	4

Table 2: ARDL/Bounds Testing for the existence of long run cointegration

Model	F-Statistic
$X_t = (GDP_t, INF_t, MS_t, BDC_t)$	6.678
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Null Hypothesis: No Long-run Relationship ▪ Alternative Hypothesis: There is Long-run Relationship ▪ Decision Rules: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ If the F-statistic is below the lower bound, we do not reject the null hypothesis ○ If the F-statistic is higher than the upper bound, we reject the null hypothesis ○ If the F-statistic is between the lower and upper bounds, the result is inconclusive ▪ Decision: The F-statistic of 6.678 is higher than the upper bound of 4.545 at 5% critical level, we reject the null hypothesis of no cointegration and accept the alternative hypothesis of long-run cointegration. 	
k=3, n=70	
Nayaran (2005) Critical Value	Lower Bound Upper Bound
1%	4.635 6.055
5%	3.370 4.545
10%	2.818 3.880

Note: Critical values are obtained from Narayan (2005) (Table Case III: Unrestricted Intercept and No Trend)

Table 3: Error Correction and Long-run Causality

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.0308	0.0126	2.4412	0.0185
D(GDP(-1))	0.7621	0.1411	5.3995	0.0000
D(GDP(-2))	0.0379	0.1682	0.2256	0.8224
D(GDP(-3))	-0.1467	0.1706	-0.8598	0.3942
D(GDP(-4))	0.0207	0.1247	0.1666	0.8683
D(INF(-1))	-0.0101	0.0194	-0.5194	0.6059
D(INF(-2))	-0.0167	0.0192	-0.8673	0.3902
D(INF(-3))	-0.0220	0.0188	-1.1740	0.2463
D(INF(-4))	-0.0236	0.0181	-1.3025	0.1991
D(MS(-1))	-0.1629	0.0764	-2.1302	0.0384
D(MS(-2))	-0.1875	0.0875	-2.1415	0.0374
D(MS(-3))	-0.1845	0.0952	-1.9389	0.0585
D(MS(-4))	0.0794	0.0966	0.8222	0.4151
D(BDC(-1))	0.0533	0.0724	0.7359	0.4654
D(BDC(-2))	0.0468	0.0742	0.6317	0.5306
D(BDC(-3))	0.1011	0.0732	1.3806	0.1739
D(BDC(-4))	0.0564	0.0687	0.8200	0.4163
ECT(-1)	-0.1079	0.0332	-3.2428	0.0022
R-squared	0.8283	Mean dependent var	0.0410	
Adjusted R-squared	0.7663	S.D. dependent var	0.0614	
S.E. of regression	0.0296	Akaike info criterion	-3.9663	
Sum squared resid	0.0414	Schwarz criterion	-3.3642	

Log likelihood	146.9072	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-3.7287
F-statistic	13.3445	Durbin-Watson stat	1.9015
Prob(F-statistic)	0.0000		

Table 4: Short-run Granger Causality

Null Hypothesis	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.	Interpretation
INF does not Granger Cause GDP	68	0.6956	0.5025	INF does not Granger Cause GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause INF		0.4390	0.6466	GDP does not Granger Cause INF
MS does not Granger Cause GDP	68	7.8687	0.0009	MS Granger-Causes GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause MS		0.4896	0.6152	GDP does not Granger Cause MS
BDC does not Granger Cause GDP	68	1.6725	0.1960	BDC does not Granger Cause GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause BDC		2.0811	0.1333	GDP does not Granger Cause BDC
MS does not Granger Cause INF	68	3.3808	0.0403	MS Granger-Causes INF
INF does not Granger Cause MS		1.9304	0.1536	INF does not Granger Cause MS
BDC does not Granger Cause INF	68	0.4695	0.6275	BDC does not Granger Cause INF
INF does not Granger Cause BDC		0.4661	0.6296	INF does not Granger Cause BDC
BDC does not Granger Cause MS	68	0.0207	0.9795	BDC does not Granger Cause MS
MS does not Granger Cause BDC		2.3653	0.1022	MS does not Granger Cause BDC

Table 5: Serial Correlation LM Test

Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test			
F-statistic	0.4361	Prob. F(2,51)	0.6492
Obs*R-squared	1.2360	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.5390

Figure 1: Model Stability Plot

Figure 2: Residual Plot

BDC Exchange Rate with MPS

Table 1: Lag Selection

	Akaike Info Criterion	Akaike Rank	Schwarz Criterion	Schwarz Rank
Lag 4	-4.1392	1	-3.2695	4
Lag 3	-4.0476	2	-3.3509	3
Lag 2	-3.8961	3	-3.3696	1
Lag 1	-3.7154	4	-3.3564	2

Table 2: ARDL/Bounds Testing for the existence of long run cointegration

Model	F-Statistic	
$X_t = (GDP_t, INF_t, MS_t, BDC_t, MPS_t)$	5.549	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Null Hypothesis: No Long-run Relationship ▪ Alternative Hypothesis: There is Long-run Relationship ▪ Decision Rules: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ If the F-statistic is below the lower bound, we do not reject the null hypothesis ○ If the F-statistic is higher than the upper bound, we reject the null hypothesis ○ If the F-statistic is between the lower and upper bounds, the result is inconclusive ▪ Decision: The F-statistic of 5.549 is higher than the upper bound of 4.256 at 5% critical level, we reject the null hypothesis of no cointegration and accept the alternative hypothesis of long-run cointegration. 		
k=4, n=70		
Nayaran (2005) Critical Value	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1%	4.098	5.570
5%	3.022	4.256
10%	2.552	3.648

Note: Critical values are obtained from Nayaran (2005) (Table Case III: Unrestricted Intercept and No Trend)

Table 3: Error Correction and Long-run Causality

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.0272	0.0130	2.0816	0.0434
D(GDP(-1))	0.7502	0.1499	5.002	0.0000
D(GDP(-2))	0.0526	0.1813	0.2902	0.7730
D(GDP(-3))	-0.1454	0.1881	-0.7727	0.4439
D(GDP(-4))	0.0357	0.1354	0.2637	0.7932
D(INF(-1))	-0.0052	0.0208	-0.2502	0.8036
D(INF(-2))	-0.0135	0.0212	-0.6378	0.5269
D(INF(-3))	-0.0176	0.0210	-0.8399	0.4056
D(INF(-4))	-0.0168	0.0198	-0.8489	0.4006
D(MS(-1))	-0.1275	0.0887	-1.4380	0.1576
D(MS(-2))	-0.1867	0.1008	-1.8517	0.0709
D(MS(-3))	-0.1952	0.1058	-1.8454	0.0719
D(MS(-4))	0.1106	0.1060	1.0430	0.3028
D(BDC(-1))	0.0301	0.0816	0.3689	0.7140
D(BDC(-2))	0.0565	0.0803	0.7036	0.4854
D(BDC(-3))	0.1068	0.0775	1.3775	0.1755
D(BDC(-4))	0.0519	0.0718	0.7232	0.4734
D(MPS(-1))	-0.0065	0.0061	-1.0551	0.2972
D(MPS(-2))	-0.0085	0.0064	-1.3304	0.1904
D(MPS(-3))	-0.0058	0.0064	-0.9151	0.3652
D(MPS(-4))	-0.0085	0.0062	-1.3623	0.1802
ECT(-1)	-0.0981	0.0371	-2.6399	0.0115

R-squared	0.8337	Mean dependent var	0.0410	
Adjusted R-squared	0.7525	S.D. dependent var	0.0614	
S.E. of regression	0.0305	Akaike info criterion	-3.8752	
Sum squared resid	0.0401	Schwarz criterion	-3.1393	
Log likelihood	147.9456	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-3.5848	
F-statistic	10.2707	Durbin-Watson stat	1.9407	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.0000			

Table 4: Granger Causality Tests

Null Hypothesis	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.	Interpretation
INF does not Granger Cause GDP	68	0.69569	0.5025	INF does not Granger Cause GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause INF		0.43903	0.6466	GDP does not Granger Cause INF
MS does not Granger Cause GDP	68	7.86874	0.0009	MS Granger-Causes GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause MS		0.48964	0.6152	GDP does not Granger Cause MS
BDC does not Granger Cause GDP	68	1.67257	0.1960	BDC does not Granger Cause GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause BDC		2.08117	0.1333	GDP does not Granger Cause BDC
MPC does not Granger Cause GDP	68	3.79424	0.0278	MPC Granger-Causes GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause MPC		0.13656	0.8726	GDP does not Granger Cause MPC
MS does not Granger Cause INF	68	3.38084	0.0403	MS Granger-Causes INF
INF does not Granger Cause MS		1.93049	0.1536	INF does not Granger Cause MS
BDC does not Granger Cause INF	68	0.46954	0.6275	BDC does not Granger Cause INF
INF does not Granger Cause BDC		0.46613	0.6296	INF does not Granger Cause BDC
MPC does not Granger Cause INF	68	0.84961	0.4324	MPC does not Granger Cause INF
INF does not Granger Cause MPC		0.99765	0.3745	INF does not Granger Cause MPC
BDC does not Granger Cause MS	68	0.02074	0.9795	BDC does not Granger Cause MS
MS does not Granger Cause BDC		2.36534	0.1022	MS does not Granger Cause BDC
MPC does not Granger Cause MS	68	1.09133	0.3420	MPC does not Granger Cause MS
MS does not Granger Cause MPC		0.13439	0.8745	MS does not Granger Cause MPC
MPC does not Granger Cause BDC	68	0.15203	0.8593	MPS does not Granger Cause BDC
BDC does not Granger Cause MPC		0.31309	0.7323	BDC does not Granger Cause MPS

Table 5: Serial Correlation LM Test

Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test			
F-statistic	0.1263	Prob. F(2,51)	0.8816
Obs*R-squared	0.3982	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.8194

Figure 1: Model Stability Plot

Figure 2: Residual Plot

BDC Exchange Rate with MPCl

Table 1: Lag Selection

	Akaike Info Criterion	Akaike Rank	Schwarz Criterion	Schwarz Rank
Lag 4	-4.0151	2	-3.1454	4
Lag 3	-4.0199	1	-3.3232	3
Lag 2	-3.8944	3	-3.3679	1
Lag 1	-3.6906	4	-3.3316	2

Table 2: ARDL/Bounds Testing for the existence of long run cointegration

Model	F-Statistic	
$X_t = (GDP_t, INF_t, MS_t, BDC_t, MPCl_t)$	5.347	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Null Hypothesis: No Long-run Relationship ▪ Alternative Hypothesis: There is Long-run Relationship ▪ Decision Rules: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ If the F-statistic is below the lower bound, we do not reject the null hypothesis ○ If the F-statistic is higher than the upper bound, we reject the null hypothesis ○ If the F-statistic is between the lower and upper bounds, the result is inconclusive ▪ Decision: The F-statistic of 5.3479 is higher than the upper bound of 4.256 at 5% critical level, we reject the null hypothesis of no cointegration and accept the alternative hypothesis of long-run cointegration. 		
k=4, n=70		
Nayaran (2005) Critical Value	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1%	4.098	5.570
5%	3.022	4.256
10%	2.552	3.648

Note: Critical values are obtained from Narayan (2005) (Table Case III: Unrestricted Intercept and No Trend)

Table 3: Error Correction and Long-run Causality

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.0358	0.0094	3.7794	0.0004
D(GDP(-1))	0.7743	0.1304	5.9339	0.0000
D(GDP(-2))	0.0506	0.1717	0.2946	0.7695
D(GDP(-3))	-0.1507	0.1239	-1.2164	0.2296
D(INF(-1))	-0.0079	0.0192	-0.4130	0.6814
D(INF(-2))	-0.0130	0.0193	-0.6730	0.5041
D(INF(-3))	-0.0213	0.0182	-1.1690	0.2480
D(MS(-1))	-0.1618	0.0722	-2.2395	0.0297
D(MS(-2))	-0.1967	0.0896	-2.1954	0.0329
D(MS(-3))	-0.1629	0.0920	-1.7698	0.0830
D(BDC(-1))	0.0427	0.0734	0.5816	0.5635
D(BDC(-2))	0.0474	0.0769	0.6173	0.5398
D(BDC(-3))	0.0701	0.0710	0.9878	0.3281
D(MPCl(-1))	-0.0092	0.0105	-0.8759	0.3853
D(MPCl(-2))	-0.0080	0.0126	-0.6349	0.5284
D(MPCl(-3))	-0.0124	0.0106	-1.1694	0.2479
ECT(-1)	-0.1134	0.0280	-4.0516	0.0002
R-squared	0.8189	Mean dependent var	0.0414	
Adjusted R-squared	0.7598	S.D. dependent var	0.0610	
S.E. of regression	0.0299	Akaike info criterion	-3.9637	
Sum squared resid	0.0438	Schwarz criterion	-3.3997	
Log likelihood	147.8026	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-3.7408	

F-statistic	13.8516	Durbin-Watson stat	1.9660	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.0000			

Table 4: Granger Causality Tests

Null Hypothesis	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.	Interpretation
INF does not Granger Cause GDP	68	0.6956	0.5025	INF does not Granger Cause GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause INF		0.4390	0.6466	GDP does not Granger Cause INF
MS does not Granger Cause GDP	68	7.8687	0.0009	MS Granger-Causes GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause MS		0.4896	0.6152	GDP does not Granger Cause MS
BDC does not Granger Cause GDP	68	1.6725	0.1960	BDC does not Granger Cause GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause BDC		2.0811	0.1333	GDP does not Granger Cause BDC
MPCI does not Granger Cause GDP	68	0.7202	0.4906	MPCI does not Granger Cause GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause MPCI		0.3369	0.7152	GDP does not Granger Cause MPCI
MS does not Granger Cause INF	68	3.3808	0.0403	MS Granger-Causes INF
INF does not Granger Cause MS		1.9304	0.1536	INF does not Granger Cause MS
BDC does not Granger Cause INF	68	0.4695	0.6275	BDC does not Granger Cause INF
INF does not Granger Cause BDC		0.4661	0.6296	INF does not Granger Cause BDC
MPCI does not Granger Cause INF	68	3.3896	0.0400	MPCI Granger-Causes INF
INF does not Granger Cause MPCI		2.4397	0.0954	INF Granger-Causes MPCI
BDC does not Granger Cause MS	68	0.0207	0.9795	BDC does not Granger Cause MS
MS does not Granger Cause BDC		2.3653	0.1022	MS does not Granger Cause BDC
MPCI does not Granger Cause MS	68	0.6854	0.5076	MPCI does not Granger Cause MS
MS does not Granger Cause MPCI		0.0187	0.9815	MS does not Granger Cause MPCI
MPCI does not Granger Cause BDC	68	2.3192	0.1067	MPCI does not Granger Cause BDC
BDC does not Granger Cause MPCI		2.0288	0.1400	BDC does not Granger Cause MPCI

Table 5: Serial Correlation LM Test

Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test			
F-statistic	0.0288	Prob. F(2,51)	0.9716
Obs*R-squared	0.0807	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.9604

Figure 1: Model Stability Plot

Figure 2: Residual Plot

Part F

Asset Channel without MPS and MPC1

Table 1: Lag Selection

	Akaike Info Criterion	Akaike Rank	Schwarz Criterion	Schwarz Rank
Lag 4	-4.1535	1	-3.4510	1
Lag 3	-4.0023	2	-3.4383	2
Lag 2	-3.8617	3	-3.4340	3
Lag 1	-3.6380	4	-3.3442	4

Table 2: ARDL/Bounds Testing for the existence of long run cointegration

Model	F-Statistic
$X_t = (GDP_t, INF_t, MS_t, ASI_t)$	4.932
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Null Hypothesis: No Long-run Relationship ▪ Alternative Hypothesis: There is Long-run Relationship ▪ Decision Rules: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ If the F-statistic is below the lower bound, we do not reject the null hypothesis ○ If the F-statistic is higher than the upper bound, we reject the null hypothesis ○ If the F-statistic is between the lower and upper bounds, the result is inconclusive ▪ Decision: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The F-statistic of 4.932 is higher than the upper bound of 4.545 at 5% critical level, we reject the null hypothesis of no cointegration and accept the alternative hypothesis of long-run cointegration. 	
k=3, n=70	
Nayaran (2005) Critical Value	Lower Bound Upper Bound
1%	4.635 6.055
5%	3.370 4.545
10%	2.818 3.880

Note: Critical values are obtained from Narayan (2005) (Table Case III: Unrestricted Intercept and No Trend)

Table 3: Error Correction and Long-run Causality

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.0410	0.0102	4.0031	0.0002
D(GDP(-1))	0.6747	0.1293	5.2152	0.0000
D(GDP(-2))	0.0344	0.1544	0.2228	0.8246
D(GDP(-3))	-0.1242	0.1532	-0.8105	0.4217
D(GDP(-4))	-0.0308	0.1110	-0.2774	0.7826
D(INF(-1))	0.0070	0.0173	0.4074	0.6855
D(INF(-2))	-0.0190	0.0173	-1.0963	0.2785
D(INF(-3))	-0.0163	0.0170	-0.9597	0.3421
D(INF(-4))	-0.0031	0.0167	-0.1859	0.8533
D(MS(-1))	-0.1104	0.0730	-1.5119	0.1372
D(MS(-2))	-0.2386	0.0783	-3.0460	0.0038
D(MS(-3))	-0.1974	0.0835	-2.3647	0.0222
D(MS(-4))	0.0985	0.0864	1.1403	0.2599
D(ASI(-1))	0.0491	0.0274	1.7891	0.0800
D(ASI(-2))	0.0075	0.0277	0.2734	0.7857
D(ASI(-3))	-0.0195	0.0269	-0.7264	0.4712
D(ASI(-4))	-0.0917	0.0264	-3.4662	0.0011
ECT(-1)	-0.0968	0.0331	-2.9226	0.0053

R-squared	0.8538	Mean dependent var	0.0410
Adjusted R-squared	0.8010	S.D. dependent var	0.0614
S.E. of regression	0.0273	Akaike info criterion	-4.1271
Sum squared resid	0.0352	Schwarz criterion	-3.5250
Log likelihood	152.1337	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-3.8896
F-statistic	16.1557	Durbin-Watson stat	1.9245
Prob(F-statistic)	0.0000		

Table 4: Short-run Granger Causality

Null Hypothesis	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.	Interpretation
INF does not Granger Cause GDP	68	0.6956	0.5025	INF does not Granger Cause GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause INF		0.4390	0.6466	GDP does not Granger Cause INF
MS does not Granger Cause GDP	68	7.8687	0.0009	MS Granger-Causes GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause MS		0.4896	0.6152	GDP does not Granger Cause MS
ASI does not Granger Cause GDP	68	0.4248	0.6557	ASI does not Granger Cause GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause ASI		0.1148	0.8917	GDP does not Granger Cause ASI
MS does not Granger Cause INF	68	3.3808	0.0403	MS Granger-Causes INF
INF does not Granger Cause MS		1.9304	0.1536	INF does not Granger Cause MS
ASI does not Granger Cause INF	68	1.0781	0.3464	ASI does not Granger Cause INF
INF does not Granger Cause ASI		1.8251	0.1696	INF does not Granger Cause ASI
ASI does not Granger Cause MS	68	2.2270	0.1163	ASI does not Granger Cause MS
MS does not Granger Cause ASI		0.0066	0.9934	MS does not Granger Cause ASI

Table 5: Serial Correlation LM Test

Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test			
F-statistic	0.0820	Prob. F(2,51)	0.9214
Obs*R-squared	0.2361	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.8886

Figure 1: Model Stability Plot

Figure 2: Residual Plot

Asset Channel with MPS

Table 1: Lag Selection

	Akaike Info Criterion	Akaike Rank	Schwarz Criterion	Schwarz Rank
Lag 4	-4.1438	1	-3.2740	4
Lag 3	-3.9839	2	-3.2872	3
Lag 2	-3.8937	3	-3.3672	2
Lag 1	-3.7464	4	-3.3874	1

Table 2: ARDL/Bounds Testing for the existence of long run cointegration

Model	F-Statistic
$X_t = (GDP_t, INF_t, MS_t, ASI_t, MPS_t)$	3.793
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Null Hypothesis: No Long-run Relationship ▪ Alternative Hypothesis: There is Long-run Relationship ▪ Decision Rules: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ If the F-statistic is below the lower bound, we do not reject the null hypothesis ○ If the F-statistic is higher than the upper bound, we reject the null hypothesis ○ If the F-statistic is between the lower and upper bounds, the result is inconclusive ▪ Decision: The F-statistic of 3.793 is higher than the upper bound of 3.648 at 10% critical level, we thus reject the null hypothesis of no cointegration and accept the alternative hypothesis of long-run cointegration. 	
k=4, n=70	
Nayaran (2005) Critical Value	Lower Bound Upper Bound
1%	4.098 5.570
5%	3.022 4.256
10%	2.552 3.648

Note: Critical values are obtained from Nayaran (2005) (Table Case III: Unrestricted Intercept and No Trend)

Table 3: Error Correction and Long-run Causality

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.0388	0.0112	3.4639	0.0012
D(GDP(-1))	0.6885	0.1376	5.0021	0.0000
D(GDP(-2))	0.0259	0.1662	0.1558	0.8769
D(GDP(-3))	-0.1196	0.1684	-0.7104	0.4813
D(GDP(-4))	-0.0205	0.1203	-0.1704	0.8654
D(INF(-1))	0.0102	0.0192	0.5336	0.5963
D(INF(-2))	-0.0183	0.0195	-0.9391	0.3529
D(INF(-3))	-0.0174	0.0193	-0.9015	0.3723
D(INF(-4))	-0.0017	0.0178	-0.0960	0.9239
D(MS(-1))	-0.0928	0.0832	-1.1158	0.2707
D(MS(-2))	-0.2457	0.0907	-2.7090	0.0096
D(MS(-3))	-0.2089	0.0939	-2.2226	0.0315
D(MS(-4))	0.1280	0.0962	1.3294	0.1907
D(ASI(-1))	0.0543	0.0327	1.6586	0.1045
D(ASI(-2))	0.0085	0.0327	0.2599	0.7961
D(ASI(-3))	-0.0282	0.0314	-0.8962	0.3751
D(ASI(-4))	-0.0915	0.0301	-3.0328	0.0041
D(MPS(-1))	-0.0038	0.0059	-0.6507	0.5187
D(MPS(-2))	-0.0012	0.0066	-0.1827	0.8558
D(MPS(-3))	0.0003	0.0066	0.0459	0.9636
D(MPS(-4))	-0.0044	0.0059	-0.7433	0.4613
ECT(-1)	-0.0932	0.0389	-2.3938	0.0211

R-squared	0.8526	Mean dependent var	0.0410
Adjusted R-squared	0.7806	S.D. dependent var	0.0614
S.E. of regression	0.0287	Akaike info criterion	-3.9956
Sum squared resid	0.0355	Schwarz criterion	-3.2597
Log likelihood	151.8593	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-3.7052
F-statistic	11.8471	Durbin-Watson stat	1.9590
Prob(F-statistic)	0.0000		

Table 4: Short-run Granger Causality

Null Hypothesis	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.	Interpretation
INF does not Granger Cause GDP	68	0.6956	0.5025	INF does not Granger Cause GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause INF		0.4390	0.6466	GDP does not Granger Cause INF
MS does not Granger Cause GDP	68	7.8687	0.0009	MS Granger-Causes GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause MS		0.4896	0.6152	GDP does not Granger Cause MS
ASI does not Granger Cause GDP	68	0.4248	0.6557	ASI does not Granger Cause GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause ASI		0.1148	0.8917	GDP does not Granger Cause ASI
MPC does not Granger Cause GDP	68	3.7942	0.0278	MPC Granger-Causes GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause MPC		0.1365	0.8726	GDP does not Granger Cause MPC
MS does not Granger Cause INF	68	3.3808	0.0403	MS Granger-Causes INF
INF does not Granger Cause MS		1.9304	0.1536	INF does not Granger Cause MS
ASI does not Granger Cause INF	68	1.0781	0.3464	ASI does not Granger Cause INF
INF does not Granger Cause ASI		1.8251	0.1696	INF does not Granger Cause ASI
MPC does not Granger Cause INF	68	0.8496	0.4324	MPC does not Granger Cause INF
INF does not Granger Cause MPC		0.9976	0.3745	INF does not Granger Cause MPC
ASI does not Granger Cause MS	68	2.2270	0.1163	ASI does not Granger Cause MS
MS does not Granger Cause ASI		0.0066	0.9934	MS does not Granger Cause ASI
MPC does not Granger Cause MS	68	1.0913	0.3420	MPC does not Granger Cause MS
MS does not Granger Cause MPC		0.1343	0.8745	MS does not Granger Cause MPC
MPC does not Granger Cause ASI	68	5.0953	0.0089	MPC Granger-Causes ASI
ASI does not Granger Cause MPC		0.3080	0.7360	ASI does not Granger Cause MPC

Table 5: Serial Correlation LM Test

Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test			
F-statistic	0.0299	Prob. F(2,51)	0.9705
Obs*R-squared	0.0949	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.9536

Figure 1: Model Stability Plot

Figure 2: Residual Plot

Asset Channel with MPC1

Table 1: Lag Selection

	Akaike Info Criterion	Akaike Rank	Schwarz Criterion	Schwarz Rank
Lag 4	-4.1113	1	-3.2416	4
Lag 3	-3.9527	2	-3.2560	3
Lag 2	-3.8498	3	-3.3233	2
Lag 1	-3.6957	4	-3.3366	1

Table 2: ARDL/Bounds Testing for the existence of long run cointegration

Model	F-Statistic	
$X_t = (GDP_t, INF_t, MS_t, ASI_t, MPC1_t)$	4.557	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Null Hypothesis: No Long-run Relationship ▪ Alternative Hypothesis: There is Long-run Relationship ▪ Decision Rules: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ If the F-statistic is below the lower bound, we do not reject the null hypothesis ○ If the F-statistic is higher than the upper bound, we reject the null hypothesis ○ If the F-statistic is between the lower and upper bounds, the result is inconclusive ▪ Decision: The F-statistic of 4.557 is higher than the upper bound of 4.256 at 5% critical level, we reject the null hypothesis of no cointegration and accept the alternative hypothesis of long-run cointegration. 		
k=4, n=70		
Nayaran (2005) Critical Value	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1%	4.098	5.570
5%	3.022	4.256
10%	2.552	3.648

Note: Critical values are obtained from Nayaran (2005) (Table Case III: Unrestricted Intercept and No Trend)

Table 3: Error Correction and Long-run Causality

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.0442	0.0080	5.4792	0.0000
D(GDP(-1))	0.7178	0.1253	5.7270	0.0000
D(GDP(-2))	0.0873	0.1697	0.5145	0.6092
D(GDP(-3))	-0.2094	0.1176	-1.7801	0.0813
D(INF(-1))	-0.0011	0.0187	-0.0588	0.9533
D(INF(-2))	-0.0074	0.0190	-0.3931	0.6959
D(INF(-3))	-0.0091	0.0179	-0.5088	0.6132
D(MS(-1))	-0.1711	0.0732	-2.3359	0.0236
D(MS(-2))	-0.2111	0.0836	-2.5232	0.0149
D(MS(-3))	-0.2042	0.0868	-2.3511	0.0228
D(ASI(-1))	0.0433	0.0283	1.5297	0.1325
D(ASI(-2))	0.0010	0.0292	0.0367	0.9708
D(ASI(-3))	0.0022	0.0279	0.0816	0.9353
D(MPCI(-1))	-0.0141	0.0105	-1.3471	0.1841
D(MPCI(-2))	-0.0127	0.0119	-1.0677	0.2908
D(MPCI(-3))	-0.0132	0.0102	-1.2935	0.2019
ECT(-1)	-0.1287	0.0308	-4.1726	0.0001
R-squared	0.8197	Mean dependent var	0.0414	
Adjusted R-squared	0.7609	S.D. dependent var	0.0610	
S.E. of regression	0.0298	Akaike info criterion	-3.9682	
Sum squared resid	0.0436	Schwarz criterion	-3.4042	
Log likelihood	147.95	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-3.7454	

F-statistic	13.9288	Durbin-Watson stat	1.9609	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.0000			

Table 4: Granger Causality Tests

Null Hypothesis	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.	Interpretation
INF does not Granger Cause GDP	68	0.6956	0.5025	INF does not Granger Cause GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause INF		0.4390	0.6466	GDP does not Granger Cause INF
MS does not Granger Cause GDP	68	7.8687	0.0009	MS Granger-Causes GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause MS		0.4896	0.6152	GDP does not Granger Cause MS
ASI does not Granger Cause GDP	68	0.4248	0.6557	ASI does not Granger Cause GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause ASI		0.1148	0.8917	GDP does not Granger Cause ASI
MPCI does not Granger Cause GDP	68	0.7202	0.4906	MPCI does not Granger Cause GDP
GDP does not Granger Cause MPCI		0.3369	0.7152	GDP does not Granger Cause MPCI
MS does not Granger Cause INF	68	3.3808	0.0403	MS Granger-Causes INF
INF does not Granger Cause MS		1.9304	0.1536	INF does not Granger Cause MS
ASI does not Granger Cause INF	68	1.0781	0.3464	ASI does not Granger Cause INF
INF does not Granger Cause ASI		1.8251	0.1696	INF does not Granger Cause ASI
MPCI does not Granger Cause INF	68	3.3896	0.0400	MPCI Granger-Causes INF
INF does not Granger Cause MPCI		2.4397	0.0954	INF Granger-Causes MPCI
ASI does not Granger Cause MS	68	2.2270	0.1163	ASI does not Granger Cause MS
MS does not Granger Cause ASI		0.0066	0.9934	MS does not Granger Cause ASI
MPCI does not Granger Cause MS	68	0.6854	0.5076	MPCI does not Granger Cause MS
MS does not Granger Cause MPCI		0.0187	0.9815	MS does not Granger Cause MPCI
MPCI does not Granger Cause ASI	68	0.2765	0.7593	MPCI does not Granger Cause ASI
ASI does not Granger Cause MPCI		0.7674	0.4685	ASI does not Granger Cause MPCI

Table 5: Serial Correlation LM Test

Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test			
F-statistic	0.0824	Prob. F(2,51)	0.9210
Obs*R-squared	0.2308	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.8910

Figure 1: Model Stability Plot

Figure 2: Residual Plot

Appendix 5: Measuring Fiscal Policy Communication by the Central Bank of Nigeria

Table 1: Categorization of fiscal statements

Statement Category	Example
Monetary policy stance: (positive) statements on domestic fiscal policy as an element considered by the central bank when assessing the monetary policy stance	“In connection with the question of monetary policy’s possible limitations, she emphasised that fiscal policy also provides stimulation to the economy and therefore aids monetary policy. Ms Ekholm agreed with Mr. Nyberg that fiscal policy is more expansionary in Sweden than in many other countries thanks to larger automatic stabilisers and pointed out that a better initial public finance situation could also contribute to fiscal policy having a greater effect.” (Minutes of the Executive Board’s monetary policy meeting, April 2009, Swedish Riksbank)
Normative element: a statement calling on the government(s) in its jurisdiction to take some defined action	“As regards fiscal policy, the Governing Council notes with concern the pressures emerging in a number of countries to relax previous fiscal consolidation targets. In the current overall benign economic environment, it is imperative that all governments comply with the provisions of the Stability and Growth Pact on fiscal consolidation in economic “good times” and that all the countries concerned honour the commitments they made at the Eurogroup meeting in Berlin on 20 April 2007.” (ECB Introductory Statement of the Press Conference, July 2007)
Forecast: references to fiscal policy as an input to or outcome of central bank forecasts.	“The staff forecast prepared for this meeting suggested that the economy would continue to expand briskly for the rest of 2004 before decelerating somewhat in 2005 as fiscal policy shifted to a slightly restrictive stance. The considerable monetary and fiscal stimulus this year and still-strong advances in structural productivity were expected to cause businesses to shed still more of the caution they had been exhibiting in investing and hiring.” (Minutes of the Federal Open Market Committee, May 2004)
Monetary policy instrument: references to government financing instruments (government bonds, bills, deposits) in the context of the implementation of monetary policy.	“Also, some participants were concerned that Federal Reserve purchases of longer-term Treasury securities might be seen as an indication that the Federal Reserve was responding to a fiscal objective rather than its statutory mandate, thus reducing the Federal Reserve’s credibility regarding long-run price stability.” (Minutes the Federal Open Market Committee, March 2009)
Fiscal policies in other countries: references to foreign fiscal policies in the macroeconomic and financial outlook.	“Looking further ahead, however, there remained some downside risks to growth: in Germany, fiscal consolidation was due to be implemented in 2007; in Italy, there were concerns about competitiveness; and uncertainty over future reforms to pension and welfare benefit schemes in a number of euro-area countries might hold back growth in consumption.” (Minutes of the monetary policy committee decisions, January 2006, Bank of England)
Government representative: statements by a government representative on fiscal policy issues.	“The representatives from the Ministry of Finance made the following remarks. (...) In these circumstances, the Government would continue to implement fiscal measures so that a smooth shift in the driving force for an economic recovery from public to private demand would be realized and a full-scale recovery led by private demand could be achieved. Based on this understanding, the Government would promptly implement the second supplementary budget for fiscal 1999. The budget for fiscal 2000 was being deliberated in the Diet.” (Minutes of the monetary policy meetings, February 2000, Bank of Japan)

Source: Allard et. al. (2013)

Table 2 - CBN Discussions of Fiscal Policy in Communique No. 1

Sentence	Does the highlighted statement(s) reflect <i>positive statement</i> on domestic fiscal policy as an element taken into account by the central bank when assessing the monetary policy stance?	Does the highlighted statement(s) reflect a <i>normative statement</i> calling on the government to take some defined action?	Does the highlighted statement(s) reflect a <i>forecast</i> or references to fiscal policy as an input to or outcome of central bank forecasts?	Does the highlighted statement(s) refer to monetary policy instrument: <i>references to government financing instruments</i> (government bonds, bills, deposits) in the context of the implementation of monetary policy?	Does the highlighted statement(s) make <i>reference to fiscal policies in other countries</i> : references to foreign fiscal policies in the macroeconomic and financial outlook?
1 Consistent with the global acceptance of the principles of the Code of Good Practices on Transparency on Monetary and Financial Policies, the Monetary Policy Committee (MPC) of the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), at its Meeting held on June 26, 2001, resolved to embark on the monthly publication of key monetary and exchange rate policy decisions. The essence of the release is to inform the public stakeholders and operators about the policy objectives of the CBN, including the rationale for its decisions. It is expected that this initiative will minimize the problem of information asymmetry and thus foster market confidence, which is essential for macroeconomic stability. This makes communique of the Committee reports on the discussions of the Committee held on June 26, 2001, which reviewed recent developments in financial and macroeconomic conditions	No	No	No	No	No
2 Members recalled that the CBN had responded to the relative price and exchange rate stability and the need to enhance domestic output growth in fiscal 2000 by a policy of monetary ease. Specifically, the CBN's minimum rediscount rate (MRR), the nominal anchor of the Bank's interest rate policy, was reviewed downward from 18.0 per cent in the first quarter to 14.0 per cent in November, 2000. Similarly, the cash reserve requirement (CRR), was reduced from 12.0 per cent to 10.0 per cent, while the liquidity ratio (LR) was lowered to 35.0 per cent from 40.0 per cent.	No	No	No	No	No
3 However, the emergence of inflationary pressures and the need to sustain macroeconomic and price stability in fiscal 2001 have necessitated a review of the Bank's policy stance. In this regard, the MRR was raised by 250 basis points to 16.5 per cent, while the CRR and LR were raised to 12.5 per cent and 40.0 per cent, respectively, between January and April 2001. Despite the increases, the pressure intensified.	No	No	No	No	No
4 The expansionary fiscal operations of the three tiers of government, particularly the monetization of the proceeds of excess crude oil earnings, which exacerbated the problem of excess liquidity in the banking system, led to a rapid acceleration in the rate of monetary expansion, thereby putting intense pressure on domestic prices and the naira exchange rate. Broad money supply (M0) increased rapidly during the first five months of 2001, by 27.0 per cent, well above the 12.2 per cent target increase for the whole year. Inflation increased sharply from 6.9 per cent at end-December, 2000 to 13.9 percent, by end-April, 2001. These negative developments clearly needed prompt corrective measures.	No	No	Yes	No	No
5 In the inter-bank Foreign Exchange Market (IFEM), the liquidity pressure was reflected in the sharp increase in the demand for foreign exchange. For example, aggregate demand rose from US\$733.06 million in March to US\$926.56 million in April. Equivalent to an average daily demand of US\$33.8 million in March, it rose to US\$33.8 million in April. Given the magnitude of the demand pressure, the exchange rate of the naira depreciated in all the segments of the market, with the spread between the IFEM and parallel market rates hovering at 20.9 per cent as at end-June 2001.	No	No	No	No	No
6 The Committee duly recognized that structural rigidities and market distortions also contributed to the macroeconomic imbalance, it nevertheless agreed that an accommodating monetary policy stance would only compound the problem. It was against this background, and in anticipation of subsequent injections of excess liquidity via fiscal operations, that the Committee, at its meeting held on June 26, 2001, decided to further raise the MRR by 200 basis points to 18.5 percent. The action was borne out of the need to avoid an accommodating monetary policy that would exacerbate inflationary pressures and precipitate exchange rate and macroeconomic instability, which are not only inimical to investment and sustainable output growth, but would also erode the economic gains made in the recent past.	No	No	Yes	No	No
7 The Monetary Policy Committee will continue to monitor developments in the leading macroeconomic indicators and will take appropriate measures for the interest of the economy.	No	No	No	No	No
Total Number of Statements	0	0	2	0	0
Summary	Number of statements in each sentence category	Number of words in the statement(s) of the sentence category	Scale of the number of words in the statement(s) relative to total word count of communique		
A	Total number of statements that reveal positive statements on domestic fiscal policy as an element taken into account by the central bank when assessing the monetary policy stance	0	0.00		
B	Total number of statements that reveal normative element - calling on the government to take some defined action	0	0.00		
C	Total number of statements that reveal forecast or make references to fiscal policy as an input to or outcome of central bank forecasts.	2	14.63		
D	Total number of statements that reveal monetary policy instrument - references to government financing instruments (government bonds, bills, deposits) in the context of the implementation of monetary policy.	0	0.00		
E	Total number of statements that reveal fiscal policies in other countries: references to foreign fiscal policies in the macroeconomic and financial outlook	0	0.00		
F	MPC Indicator		14.63		

Total number of words capturing fiscal policy discussions relative to the total word count of the communique.

Table 3 - CBN's Discussions of Fiscal Policy in Communique No. 68

Paragraph	Does the highlighted statement(s) reflect a <i>positive statement</i> in discussion of fiscal policy as an avenue to address the demand for the central bank's role in setting the monetary policy stance?	Does the highlighted statement(s) reflect a <i>negative statement</i> calling on the government to take some defined action?	Does the highlighted statement(s) reflect a <i>forecast</i> or reference to fiscal policy as an input to or outcome of central bank forecasts?	Does the highlighted statement(s) refer to monetary policy in <i>reference</i> to government or policy decisions for the purpose of the implementation of monetary policy?	Does the highlighted statement(s) make <i>reference</i> to fiscal policies in other countries, reference to foreign fiscal policies in the macroeconomic and financial outlook?
1	no	no	no	no	no
2	no	no	no	no	no
3	no	no	no	no	no
4	no	no	no	no	no
5	no	no	no	no	no
6	no	no	no	no	no
7	no	no	no	no	no
8	no	no	no	no	no
9	no	no	no	no	no
10	no	no	no	no	no
11	no	no	no	no	no
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13	no	no	no	no	no
14	no	no	no	no	no
15	no	no	no	no	no
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17	no	no	no	no	no
18	no	no	no	no	no
19	no	no	no	no	no
20	no	no	no	no	no
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23	no	no	no	no	no
24	no	no	no	no	no
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34	no	no	no	no	no
35	no	no	no	no	no
36	no	no	no	no	no
37	no	no	no	no	no
38	no	no	no	no	no
39	no	no	no	no	no
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41	no	no	no	no	no
42	no	no	no	no	no
43	no	no	no	no	no
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48	no	no	no	no	no
49	no	no	no	no	no
50	no	no	no	no	no
51	no	no	no	no	no
52	no	no	no	no	no
53	no	no	no	no	no
54	no	no	no	no	no
55	no	no	no	no	no
56	no	no	no	no	no
57	no	no	no	no	no
58	no	no	no	no	no
59	no	no	no	no	no
60	no	no	no	no	no
61	no	no	no	no	no
62	no	no	no	no	no
63	no	no	no	no	no
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65	no	no	no	no	no
66	no	no	no	no	no
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69	no	no	no	no	no
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74	no	no	no	no	no
75	no	no	no	no	no
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78	no	no	no	no	no
79	no	no	no	no	no
80	no	no	no	no	no
81	no	no	no	no	no
82	no	no	no	no	no
83	no	no	no	no	no
84	no	no	no	no	no
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94	no	no	no	no	no
95	no	no	no	no	no
96	no	no	no	no	no
97	no	no	no	no	no
98	no	no	no	no	no
99	no	no	no	no	no
100	no	no	no	no	no
Total Number of Statements	0	0	0	0	0
Summary	number of Statements in each category	number of words in each category	Words refers to total word count of communiqué		
1	0	0	0.00		
2	0	0	0.00		
3	1	98	0.01		
4	0	0	0.00		
5	0	0	0.00		
6	0	0	0.00		
7	0	0	0.00		
8	0	0	0.00		
9	0	0	0.00		
10	0	0	0.00		
11	0	0	0.00		
12	0	0	0.00		
13	0	0	0.00		
14	0	0	0.00		
15	0	0	0.00		
16	0	0	0.00		
17	0	0	0.00		
18	0	0	0.00		
19	0	0	0.00		
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21	0	0	0.00		
22	0	0	0.00		
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24	0	0	0.00		
25	0	0	0.00		
26	0	0	0.00		
27	0	0	0.00		
28	0	0	0.00		
29	0	0	0.00		
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31	0	0	0.00		
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36	0	0	0.00		
37	0	0	0.00		
38	0	0	0.00		
39	0	0	0.00		
40	0	0	0.00		
41	0	0	0.00		
42	0	0	0.00		
43	0	0	0.00		
44	0	0	0.00		
45	0	0	0.00		
46	0	0	0.00		
47	0	0	0.00		
48	0	0	0.00		
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95	0	0	0.00		
96	0	0	0.00		
97	0	0	0.00		
98	0	0	0.00		
99	0	0	0.00		
100	0	0	0.00		
Total number of words regarding fiscal policy discussions relative to total word count of the communiqué.					

Table 4 - CBN's Discussions of Fiscal Policy in Communique No. 121

Statement	Does the highlighted statement(s) reflect a positive statement on domestic fiscal policy as an element taken into account by the central bank when assessing the monetary policy stance?	Does the highlighted statement(s) reflect a negative statement relating to the government's tax policy?	Does the highlighted statement(s) reflect a forecast or reference to fiscal policy's influence on or outcome of monetary policy?	Does the highlighted statement(s) refer to monetary policy instruments referenced to government financing instruments (government bonds, etc. deposits) in the context of the implementation of monetary policy?	Does the highlighted statement(s) make reference to fiscal policies in the macroeconomic and/or on the financial markets?
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Table 5 - Consolidated Data on CBN's Communication of Fiscal Policy

Quarter	Total number of statements that reveal fiscal policy statements on domestic fiscal policy as an element taken into account by the central bank when assessing the monetary policy stance			Total number of statements that reveal fiscal policy statements on the government to take some debt not on			Total number of statements that reveal fiscal or make reference to fiscal policy as an input or outcome of central bank for ex-ante			Total number of statements that reveal monetary policy instrument - reference to government's main instruments (government bonds, bills, deposits) in the context of the implementation of monetary policy			Total number of statements that reveal fiscal policy as 'other' - references to foreign fiscal policy as in the macroeconomic context and forecast			Aggregate of all communication on fiscal policy		
	No. of Statements	No. of Words	Scale relative to total word count of common que (%)	No. of Statements	No. of Words	Scale relative to total word count of common que (%)	No. of Statements	No. of Words	Scale relative to total word count of common que (%)	No. of Statements	No. of Words	Scale relative to total word count of common que (%)	No. of Statements	No. of Words	Scale relative to total word count of common que (%)	Total No. of Statements on F scal	Total No. of Words on F scal Pol cy	Total No. of Words on F scal Pol cy relative to total word count of common que (%)
Q1-2001	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	2	96	14.70	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	2	96	14.70
Q2-2001	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00
Q3-2001	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00
Q4-2001	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00
Q1-2002	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	2	94	14.14	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	2	94	14.14
Q2-2002	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00
Q3-2002	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00
Q4-2002	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00
Q1-2003	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00
Q2-2003	0	0	0.00	1	22	5.08	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	1	22	5.08
Q3-2003	0	0	0.00	1	36	6.78	1	29	5.22	1	27	5.08	0	0	0.00	3	91	17.14
Q4-2003	0	0	0.00	2	104	19.24	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	2	104	19.24
Q1-2004	0	0	0.00	1	35	6.13	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	1	35	6.13
Q2-2004	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00
Q3-2004	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00
Q4-2004	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00
Q1-2005	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00
Q2-2005	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00
Q3-2005	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00
Q4-2005	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00
Q1-2006	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	1	21	4.50	0	0	0.00	1	21	4.50
Q2-2006	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00
Q3-2006	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00
Q4-2006	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00
Q1-2007	1	21	4.50	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	2	69	10.07	0	0	0.00	2	69	10.07
Q2-2007	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00
Q3-2007	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00
Q4-2007	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00
Q1-2008	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00
Q2-2008	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00
Q3-2008	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00
Q4-2008	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00
Q1-2009	1	79	13.72	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	1	25	4.72	0	0	0.00	2	118	21.91
Q2-2009	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00
Q3-2009	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00
Q4-2009	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00
Q1-2010	1	32	5.91	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	1	32	5.91
Q2-2010	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00
Q3-2010	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00
Q4-2010	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00
Q1-2011	0	0	0.00	1	41	7.04	0	0	0.00	1	80	14.04	0	0	0.00	2	131	24.35
Q2-2011	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00
Q3-2011	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00
Q4-2011	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00
Q1-2012	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00
Q2-2012	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00
Q3-2012	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00
Q4-2012	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00
Q1-2013	1	29	5.22	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	1	29	5.22
Q2-2013	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00
Q3-2013	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00
Q4-2013	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00
Q1-2014	1	43	7.74	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	1	43	7.74
Q2-2014	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00
Q3-2014	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00
Q4-2014	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00
Q1-2015	1	32	5.91	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	1	32	5.91
Q2-2015	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00
Q3-2015	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00
Q4-2015	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00
Q1-2016	1	34	6.13	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	1	34	6.13
Q2-2016	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00
Q3-2016	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00
Q4-2016	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00
Q1-2017	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00
Q2-2017	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00
Q3-2017	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00
Q4-2017	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00
Q1-2018	1	43	7.74	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	1	43	7.74
Q2-2018	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00
Q3-2018	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00
Q4-2018	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00
Q1-2019	1	48	8.68	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	1	48	8.68
Q2-2019	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00
Q3-2019	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00
Q4-2019	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00
Q1-2020	1	38	6.78	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	1	38	6.78
Q2-2020	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00
Q3-2020	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00
Q4-2020	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00
Q1-2021	1	38	6.78	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	1	38	6.78

Charts for Fiscal Policy Discussions

Figure A

Figure B

Figure C

Figure D

Figure E

Figure F

Figure G

Figure H

Figure I

Figure J

Figure K

Figure L

Figure M

Figure N

Figure O

Figure P

Figure Q

Figure R

Appendix 6: The Public's Understanding of Monetary Policy in Nigeria

Part A: The Questionnaire

Do People Understand Monetary Policy in Nigeria?

Maxwell Ekor

BSc (Ife), MSc (Ibadan), MSc (Glasgow)

PhD Candidate

University of the West of Scotland

United Kingdom

2018

Purpose and Consent

Dear participant,

As part of a wider investigation into the issue of *Central Bank Communication in a Resource-rich Developing Economy*, this survey aims to examine the extent to which the public is knowledgeable about the monetary policy of the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN). The public in the context of this survey is not synonymous with only financial market players as widely used in the literature but includes stakeholders in the real sector and the public sector, as well as professional economists, entrepreneurs, private consultants, students and politicians.

The CBN publishes *Inflation Attitudes Survey Report* which looks at households' understanding of inflation dynamics and the inflation-interest rate nexus. The survey also investigates households' opinions about the Monetary Policy Committee (MPC) that set Nigeria's monetary policy rate, the level of independence of the MPC, and the overall satisfaction or dissatisfaction with the operations of the CBN. This survey departs from the CBN's study as it probes the public's understanding of monetary policy objectives and instruments, as well as how they obtain information about the monetary policy of the apex bank.

Your participation in this survey is voluntary and information derived herein will be used for academic purpose only. In line with the ethical requirements of the University of the West of Scotland, this survey guarantees maximum confidentiality as you are not expected to provide any personal or sensitive information. Therefore, your completion and return of this questionnaire implies that you gave your consent to participate in the research.

The estimated time for completing the questionnaire is 10 minutes. Should you have any concern about this survey kindly contact the under-listed.

Maxwell EKOR – Principal Investigator

University of the West of Scotland, UK

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

Professor John Struthers – Director of Studies

Centre for African Research on Enterprise and Economic Development (CAREED)

University of the West of Scotland, UK

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

Section A: Identification

Your completion of this introductory section will aid the analysis of the information you will provide

1. Gender
 - Male
 - Female
2. Age
 - Below 30
 - 31- 40
 - 41- 50
 - 51 and above
3. Highest level of education
 - BSc
 - MSc
 - PhD
 - Others – *Please state*
4. Sector of employment
 - *Financial sector*
 - Bank
 - Stockbroking
 - Pension Fund Administration
 - Others – *Please state*
 - *Real sector*
 - Agriculture
 - Manufacturing
 - Telecommunications
 - Oil & Gas
 - Transportation
 - Others – *Please state*
 - *Government*
 - Public Servant
 - Civil Servant
 - Others – *Please state*
 - *Others*
 - Entrepreneur
 - Economist
 - Consultant
 - Student
 - Politician
5. How long have you been in employment? (Do not respond here if you are a student)
 - 0 - 5 years
 - 6 - 10 years
 - 11 years – above
6. Income Band (Do not respond here if you are a student)
 - Less than N1 million per annum
 - N1 million – N3 million per annum
 - N3 million – N5 million per annum
 - N5 million – above per annum
 - Prefer not to say

Section B: Background Questions

Please kindly choose only one of the options

7. Recent economic policies of the federal government have had negative consequences on me

- No
- Barely
- Yes, slightly
- Yes, very much
- I don't know

8. My work relates to economic, monetary, and financial issues

- Yes, almost every day
- Often, but not on a daily basis
- Sometimes
- Hardly
- Never

9. I monitor and follow domestic political developments because politics and economics are connected

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree
- I don't know

10. I track global developments because international issues affect the Nigerian economy

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree
- I don't know

11. Which of the following global and regional central banks do you monitor the most

	Please select for all the options			
	Regularly	Occasionally	Never	I don't know
US Federal Reserve System				
Bank of England				
European Central Bank				
Bank of Japan				
Reserve Bank of New Zealand				
Reserve Bank of South Africa				
Central Bank of Ghana				
I monitor other central banks not listed here				

Section C: General knowledge about the Central Bank of Nigeria

Please kindly choose only one of the options

12. How do you judge your own knowledge about the Central Bank Nigeria (CBN)?
- Very good
 - Good
 - Fair
 - Poor
 - Very poor
 - I don't know
13. How do you judge your own knowledge about economic development subjects including *economic growth, inflation, and unemployment*?
- Very good
 - Good
 - Fair
 - Poor
 - Very poor
 - I don't know
14. How important is it to you to be well informed about the policies of the CBN?
- Extremely important
 - Very important
 - Somewhat important
 - Not very important
 - Not important at all
 - I don't know

Note: Please go to Section D if you choose 'Not important at all' in Question 14

15. Please explain more about your reasons to be informed about the policies of the CBN?

	Extremely important	Very important	Somewhat important	Not very important	Not important at all	I don't Know
CBN policies affect my personal or family income						
CBN policies influence how much my money can buy						
CBN policies affect my business/job/profession						
CBN policies affect the value of my stocks or other investments						
CBN policies are important for the economy						
I just like to keep informed well						
Other, namely _____						

Section D: Your knowledge of Monetary Policy Objectives and Instruments

16. Achieving monetary and price stability is the primary objective of the CBN.

- Strongly agree.
- Agree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree.
- I don't know.

17. The CBN defines price stability as sustained low and single digit inflation rate.

- Strongly agree.
- Agree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree.
- I don't know.

18. Apart from pursuing monetary and price stability, the CBN also provides economic and financial advice to the Federal Government

- Strongly agree.
- Agree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree.
- I don't know.

19. The key monetary policy instruments of the CBN include but not limited to *Monetary Policy Rate and Open Market Operations*

- Strongly agree.
- Agree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree.
- I don't know.

20. To adjust its monetary policy instruments, the CBN must obtain permission from the Federal Government

- Strongly agree.
- Agree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree.
- I don't know.

Section E: Obtaining Information on Monetary Policy

21. Through which source(s) of information do you hear or read about the policy of the CBN?

	Please select for all the options			
	Regularly	Occasionally	Never	I don't know
Television				
Radio				
Newspapers				
Magazines				
Internet – <i>CBN website</i>				
Internet – <i>Other websites</i>				
Internet – <i>Social media</i>				
Friends/relatives/colleagues/ business contacts				
Other, namely:				

22. Which of the following is your most important source of information about the monetary policy of the CBN?

	Please select only one option
Television	
Radio	
Newspapers	
Magazines	
Internet – <i>CBN website</i>	
Internet – <i>Other websites</i>	
Internet – <i>Social media</i>	
Friends/relatives/colleagues/ business contacts	
Other, namely	
I don't know	

23. Please indicate how you form your expectations about future monetary policy of the CBN

	Please select only one option
I use past information to forecast CBN's future monetary policy	
I use current information to forecast CBN's future monetary policy	
I use both past and current information to forecast CBN's future monetary policy	
I don't know	

Part B: Ethical Approval for Survey

UWS UNIVERSITY OF THE
WEST of SCOTLAND

Maxwell Ekor
B00217913

School of Business
and Enterprise
Paisley Campus
Paisley PA1 2BE
Scotland

Tel 0141 848 3932

21 September 2017

Dear Maxwell

Ethics Application Number: B&E217

Title of Study: Monetary Policy Communication in Oil-Exporting Countries

The School of Business & Enterprise Ethics Committee has considered your application and we are pleased to inform you that your application has been successful. Therefore approval to conduct the research as outlined in your application has been given.

We wish you well in your PhD research.

Yours sincerely

Dr A Kourouklis
Chair
School of Business & Enterprise Ethics Committee

Professor Malcolm Foley
Dean of the School

University of the West of Scotland is a registered Scottish charity. Charity number SC002520.

Part C: Outcome of Pilot Survey

Respondent	Suggestion
8	More questions should be added to make respondents acquainted with the policies of the CBN
12	The questionnaire is very objective, realistic, and educative. However, in future it should be more simplified and understandable
17	Generally, it is Okay. However, more monetary policy instruments could have been mentioned to test the understanding of those quite familiar with it
21	The questions are relevant but however you can reduce the number due to time constraint on the part of respondents especially the busy type

Part D: Interpretation of Logistic Regression Results

Table 1 - Responses to price stability as key objective of CBN

<p>Achieving price stability is the primary objective of the CBN</p>	<p>Gender: There is no significant difference between male and female respondents in their knowledge of price stability as the key objective of the CBN (odds ratio: 0.8624; p-value: 0.3810)</p>
	<p>Age: Older respondents (those aged 51 years and above) are five times more likely to have the correct knowledge of price stability as the key objective of the CBN relative to respondents below age 30 (odds ratio: 4.9234; p-value: 0.0170). Although the odds ratios of 1.1596 and 1.6325 for respondents between ages 31-40 and 41-50 respectively are also higher than 1, their p-values of 0.4590 and 0.1160 respectively are higher than threshold of 0.10, implying that the respondents in these age brackets are not differentially knowledgeable on the centrality of price stability to CBN objectives than respondents under age 30.</p>
	<p>Education: Holders of master's degrees are not more knowledgeable about CBN objectives than holders of bachelor's degrees, but PhD holders are, given odds ratios and p-values of (0.7085, 0.1190) for master's and (0.4629, 0.0510) for PhD with bachelor's degree as the reference category.</p>
	<p>Sector of employment: When compared with respondents in the financial sector, respondents employed in the real sector are four times more likely to understand that price stability is the key objective of the CBN (odds ratio: 4.0849; p-value: 0.000). On the other hand, respondents employed in Government and Other sectors are about fifty percent less likely to understand the primary mandate of the CBN compared to employees in the financial sector based on odds ratios and p-values of (0.5360, 0.0250) for government employees and (0.5127, 0.0580) for those in the 'Other' sectors.</p>
	<p>Experience: Respondents that have worked 6-10 years and those with 11 years and above are each about two times more likely to understand that achieving price stability is the primary objective of the CBN, compared to those with experience within 5 years, based on odds ratios and p-values of (1.9978, 0.0027) for 6-10 years of experience and (2.3227, 0.0140) for those with 11 years or more.</p>
	<p>Income: Income level is not a predictor of accurate knowledge about the primary objective of the CBN. Compared with respondents with income of less than one million naira, those with higher income levels are not more likely to understand that price stability is the primary mandate of CBN. Although odds ratios for all income levels above N1 million are higher than 1, the p-values are all above the threshold of 0.10.</p>
	<p>Source of Information on Monetary Policy: With the exception of magazines and personal contacts, respondents who depend on other named sources of information to learn about monetary policy are more likely to understand that price stability is the primary objective of the CBN compared to those that depend on television broadcasts (the reference category). For example, respondents who get most of their information on monetary policy through radio are six times more likely to understand that price stability is the primary objective of the CBN relative to the reference category. However, those who depend on other unnamed sources (listed as 'Others') are significantly, about 24% less likely to know that the primary goal of the CBN is achieving price stability.</p>
	<p>Expectation formation: Respondents who use current information and those who use both current and past information to form their expectations of future monetary policy of the CBN are likely to understand that the primary objective of the CBN is primary stability as respondents who use only past information (odds ratios are lower than 1 but the p-values are higher than 0.10). However, those who rely on "Other" methods are significantly less likely to understand that the primary objective of the CBN is price stability</p>

Table 2: Responses on how CBN Defines Price Stability

<p>The CBN defines price stability as sustained low and single digit inflation rate</p>	<p>Gender: There is no significant difference between male and female respondents in their knowledge of CBN’s definition of price stability as a sustained low and single digit inflation rate (odds ratio: 0.8893; p-value: 0.3800)</p>
	<p>Age: Older respondents (those aged 51 years and above) are four times more likely to have the correct knowledge of CBN’s definition of price stability as a sustained low and single digit inflation rate relative to respondents below age 30 (odds ratio:3.9760; p-value:0.0010). Similarly, older respondents (those aged 41 – 50 years) are two times more likely to have the correct knowledge relative to respondents below age 30 (odds ratio:2.1797; p-value:0.0020). Respondents in the age bracket 31 – 40 years are however less likely to have the correct knowledge relative to respondents below age 30 (odds ratio:0.9940; p-value:0.9700).</p>
	<p>Education: Holders of master’s and PhD degrees are more knowledgeable about CBN definition of price stability than holders of bachelor’s degrees, given odds ratios and p-values of (0.6057, 0.0030) for master’s and (0.4060, 0.0030) for PhD with bachelor’s degree as the reference category.</p>
	<p>Sector of employment: When compared with respondents in the financial sector, respondents employed in the real sector are almost three times more likely to understand CBN’s definition of price stability (odds ratio: 2.6706; p-value: 0.000). Respondents in Government sector are more likely to know the meaning of price stability compared to employees in the financial sector (odd ratio: 0.4843; p-value 0.0010) while those in ‘Other’ sectors are about seventy-six percent less likely to understand CBN’s definition of price stability relative to those in the financial sector (0.7690, 0.3570).</p>
	<p>Experience: Respondents that have worked 6-10 years are more likely to understand CBN’s definition of price stability, compared to those with experience within 5 years based on odds ratios and p-values of (1.4317, 0.0370). However, respondents that have worked 11 years and above are less likely to understand the issue given the odds ratio and p-value of 1.2240 and 0.4130.</p>
	<p>Income: Income level is not a predictor of accurate knowledge about CBN’s definition of price stability. Compared with respondents with income of less than one million naira, those with higher income levels are not more likely to understand that the CBN defines price stability as sustained low and single digit inflation rate. Although odds ratios for all income levels above N1 million (except for those earning between N1 and N3 million) are higher than 1, the p-values are all above the threshold of 0.10.</p>
	<p>Source of Information on Monetary Policy: With the exception of respondents that rely on CBN’s website, respondents who depend on other named sources of information to learn about monetary policy are not more likely to understand CBN’s definition of price stability compared to those that depend on television broadcasts (the reference category). Particularly, those who depend on other unnamed sources (listed as ‘Others’) are significantly, about 32% less likely to know CBN’s definition of price stability.</p>
	<p>Expectation formation: Respondents who use current and past information to form their expectations of future monetary policy of the CBN are likely to understand CBN’s definition of price stability as respondents who use only past information (odds ratio is lower than 1 but the p-value is higher than 0.10). However, those who rely on current information and those that use “Other” methods are significantly less likely to understand that the CBN defines price stability as sustained low and single digit inflation rate.</p>

Table 3: Responses on whether the CBN provides advice to Government.

<p>Apart from pursuing monetary and price stability, the CBN also provides economic and financial advice to the Federal Government</p>	<p>Gender: There is no significant difference between male and female respondents in their knowledge of CBN’s provision of economic and financial advice to the Government.</p>
	<p>Age: Older respondents (those aged 51 years and above) are four times more likely to have the correct knowledge of CBN’s provision of economic and financial advice to Government relative to respondents below age 30 (odds ratio:4.4668; p-value:0.0100). Although the odds ratio of 1.6015 for respondents between ages 31-40 is also higher than 1, the p-value of 0.1070 is higher than threshold of 0.10, implying that they are not differentially knowledgeable on the matter than respondents under age 30. For those between 31 – 40, the odds ratio of 0.8483 and p-value of 0.3690 means that they are not more knowledgeable compared with those below age 30 as the reference category.</p>
	<p>Education: Holders of master’s and PhD degrees are more knowledgeable about CBN’s provision of economic and financial advice to Government than holders of bachelor’s degrees, given odds ratios and p-values of (0.5531, 0.0030) for master’s and (0.4105, 0.0150) for PhD with bachelor’s degree as the reference category.</p>
	<p>Sector of employment: When compared with respondents in the financial sector, respondents employed in the real sector are almost three times more likely to understand that the CBN provides economic and financial advice to Government (odds ratio: 2.9356; p-value: 0.010). Respondents in Government and ‘Other’ sectors are more likely to know the issue compared to employees in the financial sector (odd ratio: 0.2718; p-value 0.0010) for Government and (odds ratio: 0.5094; p-value: 0.0550) for ‘Others’.</p>
	<p>Experience: Respondents that have worked 6-10 years and 11 years and above are two times more likely to understand that the CBN provides economic and financial advice to Government, compared to those with experience within 5 years based on odds ratios and p-values of (2.0154, 0.0000) and (2.3505, 0.0070) respectively.</p>
	<p>Income: Compared with respondents with income of less than one million naira, those with higher income between N1m-N3m and N3m-N5m almost two and five times more likely to know that the CBN provides the Government with economic and financial advice given the odds ratios and p-values of (1.5877, 0.0390) and (4.8046, 0.0150) respectively. However, respondents earning above N5m are not more knowledgeable on the matter when compared with those earning less than one million with odds ratio of 0.9574 and p-value of 0.9510.</p>
	<p>Source of Information on Monetary Policy: When compared with respondents that rely more on television (the reference category), those that depend on Radio and Newspapers are three and two times more likely to know that the CBN provides Government with economic and financial advice. Respondents that rely more on social media and ‘Others’ are thirty-six and twenty-three percent less likely to know the issue while those that depend on the other known sources are not differentially knowledgeable when compared with users of television given that the odds ratios are higher than 1 but the corresponding p-values are above the 0.10 threshold.</p>
	<p>Expectation formation: Respondents who use current data are not differentially knowledgeable compared with those that use past information given that the odds ratio is above 1 but the p-value is higher than the 0.10 threshold. Users of current and past data are not more knowledgeable than those who use only past information because the odds ratio is less than one, but the p-value is higher than 0.10. However, those who rely on “Other” methods are significantly less likely to know that the CBN provides economic and financial advice to Government.</p>

Table 4: Responses on Policy Instruments of the CBN

<p>The key monetary policy instruments of the CBN include but not limited to Monetary Policy Rate and Open Market Operations</p>	<p>Gender: There is no significant difference between male and female respondents in their knowledge that the key monetary policy instruments of the CBN include but not limited to Monetary Policy Rate and Open Market Operations.</p>
	<p>Age: Compared to respondents below age 30, the older ones, those aged 51 years and above and those between 41 – 50 years are almost three and two times more likely to have the correct knowledge that the key monetary policy instruments of the CBN include but not limited to Monetary Policy Rate and Open Market Operations relative to respondents below age 30 (odds ratio:2.6876; p-value:0.0050 for 51-above) and (1.6552; p-value:0.0320) for 41-50) while those between 31 – 40 years are not more knowledgeable on the matter given odds ratio of 0.8835 and p-value of 0.2440.</p>
	<p>Education: Holders of master’s and PhD degrees are not more knowledgeable about the monetary policy instruments of the CBN than holders of bachelor’s degrees given the odds ratios and p-values of (0.8532, 0.3350) for master’s and (0.6409, 0.1420) for PhD with bachelor’s degree as the reference category.</p>
	<p>Sector of employment: When compared with respondents in the financial sector, respondents employed in the real sector are two times more likely to know that the key policy instruments of the CBN include but not limited to Monetary Policy Rate and Open Market Operations (odds ratio: 2.4201; p-value: 0.000). Respondents in Government sector are more likely to know the issue (odd ratio: 0.2718; p-value 0.0010) while those in ‘Other’ sectors are not (odds ratio: 0.5094; p-value: 0.0550), when compared with respondents in the financial sector.</p>
	<p>Experience: Respondents that have worked 6-10 years are more likely to understand the policy instruments of the CBN, compared to those with experience within 5 years based on odds ratios and p-values of (1.7508, 0.0010). However, while the odds ratio of 1.1361 for respondents between ages 31-40 is also higher than 1, the p-value of 0.2110 is higher than threshold of 0.10, implying that they are not differentially knowledgeable on the matter than respondents under age 30.</p>
	<p>Income: Compared with respondents with income of less than one million naira, the odds ratio of 1.8041and 1.6017 for those earning between N3m-N5m and N5m and above is higher than 1, but the p-values of 0.1280 and 0.4870 are higher than threshold of 0.10, implying that they are not differentially knowledgeable on the matter than respondents earning less than N1m.</p>
	<p>Source of Information on Monetary Policy: When compared with respondents that rely more on television, those that depend on CBN website are more likely to know that the CBN does not need permission from Government to adjust its policy instruments. Users of the other known sources are less likely to know the issue compared with respondents that depend on television.</p>
	<p>Expectation formation: Respondents who use current data and those who use ‘Other’ methods are significantly less likely to understand the policy instruments of the CBN when compared with those that use only past information. Those who use both current and past information are also less likely to understand the issue but not significantly.</p>

Table 5: Responses on whether CBN Needs Permission from Govt.

<p>To adjust its monetary policy instruments, the CBN must obtain permission from the Federal Government</p>	<p>Gender: There is no significant difference between male and female respondents in their knowledge that the CBN does not obtain permission from Government before it can adjust its policy instruments (odds ratio: 0.8369; p-value: 0.2640).</p>
	<p>Age: Compared to respondents below age 30, the older ones, those aged 51 years and above are not more knowledgeable about the CBN not obtaining permission from Government before it can adjust its policy instruments given the odds ratio of 0.9485 and p-value of 0.8900. However, the odds ratios for those between 41 – 50 years and 31 – 40 years are above 1, but the p-values are higher than the threshold of 0.10, implying that they are not differentially knowledgeable on the matter compared with respondents under age 30.</p>
	<p>Education: When compared with bachelor’s degree holders, those with master’s degrees are two times more likely to understand that the CBN does not take permission from Government given the odds ratio of 2.0763 and p-value of 0.0000. However, the odds ratio for PhD holders is above 1, but the p-value is higher than the threshold of 0.10, implying that they are not differentially knowledgeable on the matter compared with respondents with bachelor’s degree.</p>
	<p>Sector of employment: When compared with respondents in the financial sector, respondents employed in the real sector, Government and the ‘Other’ sectors are more likely to understand that the CBN does not take permission from the Government before its policy instruments can be adjusted given the odds ratios that are above 1 and p-values that are less than the threshold 0.10.</p>
	<p>Experience: Respondents that have worked 6-10 years are less likely to understand that the CBN does to need to obtain permission from Government when compared with those within five years of employment based on odds ratios and p-values of (0.6603, 0.0430). Those with 11 years and above experience also less likely, but not significantly, to know the issue compared with less than five years’ experience.</p>
	<p>Income: Compared with respondents with income of less than one million naira, the odds ratio of 2.9254 and p-value of 0.024 for those earning N5m and above means that they are three times more likely to understand that the CBN does not require Government’s consent before adjusting its policy instruments. Respondents earning between N1m-N3m and N3m-N5m are not more knowledgeable than those earning less than a million naira given odds ratios that are less than one and p-values higher than the threshold of 0.10.</p>
	<p>Source of Information on Monetary Policy: When compared with respondents that rely on television, those that depend on CBN website are two times more likely to know that the CBN does not require Government’s permission to adjust its policy instruments. The odds ratios for users of radio, magazines, contacts and ‘Other’ methods are above 1, but the p-values are higher than 0.10, meaning that they are not differentially knowledgeable on the issue when compared with those that rely more on television. Respondents who rely more on magazines and ‘Other’ websites are not more knowledgeable given odds ratios that are less than one and p-values higher than the threshold of 0.10</p>
	<p>Expectation formation: Respondents who use current data are two times more likely to know that the CBN does not need Government’s permission before it can adjust its policy tools when compared with those that rely only on past information. Those that use more of current and past information as well as those that use ‘Other’ methods are not more knowledgeable than those using past information given odds ratios that are less than one and p-values higher than the threshold of 0.10.</p>

Table 6: Aggregation of Monetary Policy Knowledge

<p align="center">Aggregate Knowledge of Monetary Policy</p>	<p>Gender: There is no significant difference between male and female respondents in their overall knowledge of monetary policy in Nigeria (odds ratio: 0.7739; p-value: 0.0120).</p>
	<p>Age: Older respondents, those aged 51 years and above are three times more likely to be knowledgeable about monetary policy in Nigeria relative to respondents below age 30 given the odds ratio of 3.4938 and p-value of 0.000. Similarly, those between 41 – 50 years are two times more likely to be knowledgeable about monetary policy in Nigeria relative to respondents below age 30 given the odds ratio of 2.0410 and p-value of 0.0000. Although the odds ratio of 1.0377 for respondents between ages 31-40 is higher than 1, the p-value of 0.7610 is higher than the threshold of 0.10, implying that the respondents in this age bracket are not differentially knowledgeable about monetary policy in Nigeria than respondents under age 30.</p>
	<p>Education: Holders of master’s degrees are not more knowledgeable about monetary policy in Nigeria than holders of bachelor’s degrees, but PhD holders are, given odds ratios and p-values of (0.9736, 0.8450) for master’s and (0.6223, 0.0620) for PhD with bachelor’s degree as the reference category.</p>
	<p>Sector of employment: When compared with respondents in the financial sector, respondents employed in the real sector are two times more likely to understand monetary policy in Nigeria (odds ratio: 2.3665; p-value: 0.000). Respondents employed in Government sector are about sixty percent less likely to be conversant with monetary policy in Nigeria when compared with those in financial sector (odds ratio: 0.5923; p-value: 0.0010). Those employed in ‘Other’ sectors are not more knowledgeable about monetary policy in Nigeria compared to those in the financial sector given odds ratio that is less than one and p-value higher than 0.10.</p>
	<p>Experience: Respondents with 6-10 years’ experience are more likely to understand monetary policy compared with those that have worked within five years (odds ratio: 1.1271; p-value: 0.0500). Although the odds ratio for those with 11 years and above work experience is above 1, they are not more knowledgeable about monetary policy compared to those in the financial sector due to p-value that is higher than 0.10</p>
	<p>Income: When compared with respondents earning less than N1m, those that are receiving N5m and above are three times more likely to understand monetary policy in Nigeria (odds ratio: 3.2705; p-value: 0.0090). Those earning between N3m and N5m are not more knowledgeable about monetary policy compared to those receiving below N1m given odds ratio that is less than one and p-value higher than 0.10. Those earning between N1m-N3m are less likely, but not significantly, to understand monetary policy in Nigeria compared with those receiving less than N1m (odds ratio: 0.8729; p-value: 0.3320).</p>
	<p>Source of Information on Monetary Policy: Respondents who rely mostly on Newspapers and CBN website are more likely to be knowledgeable about monetary policy in Nigeria when compared with those that depend on television given the odds ratio of 1.5894 and p-value of 0.0340 for Newspaper and odds ratio of 1.8479 and p-value: 0.0100) for CBN website. Users of radio and ‘Other’ websites are not more knowledgeable about monetary policy given odds ratio above 1 but p-value that is higher than 0.10. Respondents that rely on other known sources are less likely to understand monetary policy compared with those that rely mostly on television</p>
	<p>Expectation formation: Respondents who use current information and those who use both current and past information to form their expectations of future monetary policy of the CBN are likely to understand monetary policy in Nigeria as respondents who use only past information (odds ratios are lower than 1 but the p-values are higher than 0.10). However, those who rely on “Other” methods are significantly less likely to understand monetary policy in Nigeria compared with those that rely mostly on past information.</p>